

CLIMATE ACTION PLAN AND ENVIRONMENTAL JUSTICE: A STUDY OF UTTAR PRADESH

NAAC A++

A THESIS
SUBMITTED TO C.C.S. UNIVERSITY, MEERUT
FOR THE DEGREE OF
DOCTOR OF PHILOSOPHY
IN
POLITICAL SCIENCE

Supervisor:

Dr. MAMATA UPADHYAY

Professor & Head

Dept. of Political Science

Km. Mayawati Govt. Girls (P.G.)

College, Badalpur (G.B. Nagar)

Submitted by:

PRADEEP KUMAR

DEPARTMENT OF POLITICAL SCIENCE
KM. MAYAWATI GOVT. GIRLS (P.G.) COLLEGE
BADALPUR, (G.B. NAGAR) U.P.
2025

CANDIDATE'S DECLARATION

I hereby declare that the thesis entitled “*Climate Action Plan and Environmental Justice: A Study of Uttar Pradesh*” which I submitted for the fulfillment of the Degree of Doctor of Philosophy in the Department of Political Science, Ch. Charan Singh University, Meerut is an original work. I have carried out the present research under the able guidance and supervision of **Prof. Mamata Upadhyay**, Professor, Km. Mayawati Govt. Girls (P.G.) College, Badalpur, (G.B. Nagar), U.P. The sources of material used and all assistance received during the course of research have been duly acknowledged.

Date:

(Pradeep Kumar)

Place:

**KM. MAYAWATI GOVT. GIRLS (P.G.) COLLEGE
BADALPUR, (G.B. NAGAR) U.P.**

Dr. MAMATA UPADHYAY

Professor & Head
Dept. of Political Science

Dated.....

CERTIFICATE OF SUPERVISOR

This is to certify that the thesis entitled ***“Climate Action Plan and Environmental Justice: A Study of Uttar Pradesh”*** is submitted for the fulfillment of the Degree of Doctor of Philosophy in the Department of Political Science, Ch. Charan Singh University, Meerut by **Mr. Pradeep Kumar**. He has carried out the work under my supervision and guidance. I am satisfied that this thesis is worthy of consideration for the award of **Doctor of Philosophy (Ph.D.) in Political Science**. To the best of my knowledge, this is an original piece of work.

The Candidate has put in required attendance as per ordinance of the university and the thesis is based on the candidate's own original work.

Date:

Place:

(Prof. Mamata Upadhyay)
Supervisor

RAJA MAHENDRA PRATAP LIBRARY

CHAUDHARY CHARAN SINGH UNIVERSITY, MEERUT - 250 004 INDIA

(0121) 2772694
(0121) 762021, 22, 24
Extn. 17

Ref No. *Lib/Y25/155*

Dated *29-05-2025*

Certificate of Plagiarism

Title of Thesis : Climate Action Plan and Environmental Justice : A Study of Uttar Pradesh

Research Scholar : Mr. Pradeep Kumar

Registration No : Res-2/B/21250010/14027

Subject : Political Science

Name of the Supervisor : Dr. Mamta Upadhayay

Name of Research Centre : Department of Political Science, Km. Mayawati Govt. Girls (P.G.) College, Badalpur (G.B.Nagar)

Form of Document : Soft Copy (DVD) as Submitted by the Research Scholar

Name of software : TURNITIN

Date of check : 28/05/2025

Similarity : 0%

I hereby certify that this thesis has been evaluated using TURNITIN software. I have analyzed the report produced by the system and based on it, I certify that the report is acceptable as per UGC/UNIVERSITY norms.

Checked By

Ojpal

Incharge

Digital Library

[University Librarian]

This certificate is valid for academic purpose only

PREFACE

India aspires to be a developed country (*Vikshit Bharat*) in the long run till 2047 and in the short run, it aims to be the third-largest economy in the world after the USA and China. Achieving these goals would require a rapid and structural transformation of the whole gamut of its economy, moving beyond its current lower-middle status and converting its large pool of labour from ‘agri-based employment’ to ‘industry and service-based employment’. For this transformation to happen, it requires increasing its energy consumption to an optimal level to meet the dignified living standard of its 1.4 billion people. In the last few decades after the liberalisation of the Indian economy, India made impressive growth e.g. an annual average GDP rate of 7 percent between 2008 and 2018 as per the report by IMF in 2019. However, this growth was marked by growing income inequality and environmental degradation. Given the complexity of the problem of income inequality and environmental degradation for a large section of society, the aspect of justice becomes imperative in the ongoing transformation of the Indian economy. Further, the challenges caused by climate change have complicated the problem. In the background of these challenges, India has taken several transformational policies, acts, programmes, schemes, plans and steps to deal with the problem of economic growth, sustainable development and climate change.

Climate change is the most significant phenomenon and process in the contemporary world. It presents a significant global challenge with far-reaching social, political, environmental and economic consequences. It refers to long-term shifts in the temperature and weather patterns of the planet, the Earth, primarily attributed to human activities such as the burning of fossil fuel to sustain the capitalist mode of production and consumption, deforestation and other processes. The consequences of

climate change, though, are multifaceted but broadly can be categorised into two broad categories: one, environmental dimension and second, socio-economic and political dimension.

The rising global average temperature contributes to more intense and frequent droughts, heatwaves, and wildfires. Extreme weather events such as floods droughts and severe storms are becoming more frequent and intense and rising sea levels due to fast melting glaciers and thermal expansion of water are posing a significant threat to coastal ecosystems and communities. Furthermore, climate change is also adversely affecting the fragile Himalayan ecosystem and disrupting the northern plains ecosystems altering the habitats and threatening the existing biodiversity of the world.

Climate change has significant socio-economic and political consequences for the world. changes in temperature and rainfall patterns can negatively impact agricultural productivity, potentially leading to food insecurity, hunger and starvation. The rising sea levels and extreme weather events can displace the population resulting in climate migrants and refugees. Additionally, climate change poses a significant economic risk infecting the entire structure of the global economic order. Climate change disproportionately affects the marginalised and vulnerable communities of the society. These communities are deprived of resources needed to adapt to climate change-induced consequences leading to increased exclusion and marginalisation of already excluded and marginalised social groups and communities. Climate change presents significant political challenges arising from diverse perspectives on appropriate responses. Unequal power dynamics further complicate the challenges by influencing decision-making and implementing the policy responses for mitigation and adaptation exacerbating existing vulnerabilities. The authority to define and address climate change is contested by varying cultural and geographical interpretations of climate

knowledge and politico-economic interests. Public opinion on climate change is polarised with varying acceptance levels across political groups. The potential for social and geopolitical instability, including increasing political violence, social unrest, mass migration and conflict further underscores the complex political dimensions of climate change. This research study investigates the critical interplay between climate action and environmental Justice focusing on the climate action plan of Uttar Pradesh, India. It argues that achieving effective and equitable climate solutions necessitates a just transition that addresses the historical and contemporary inequalities that exacerbate climate vulnerability and hinder equitable climate action. Building upon the foundational values of equity and fairness, this research thesis explores the ethical dimensions of climate change emphasising the importance of justice in addressing the climate crisis. Drawing upon the framework and idea of environmental justice this doctoral thesis critically analyses the climate action plan of Uttar Pradesh. It investigates how this climate action plan addresses or fails to address the diverse needs and vulnerabilities of different communities within the state considering factors such as caste, gender, poverty, and geographical location. The analysis aims to identify potential gaps, inconsistencies and opportunities for improvement in plan design and implementation. By examining the climate action plan of Uttar Pradesh this thesis contributes to the growing body of scholarship on climate justice in India and globally. It offers valuable insights for policy makers researchers and practitioners seeking to develop more equitable and effective climate solutions driven by the idea of justice for all stakeholders or communities.

(Pradeep Kumar)

AKNOWLEDGEMENT

I am deeply grateful for this opportunity to present my doctoral research, made possible by the support of many individuals and institutions. The successful completion of any study particularly survey study of many districts spanned over the vast geographical area of Uttar Pradesh owes a great deal of support extended by numerous persons. First of all, I would like to express my deep gratitude to the Almighty whose blessings have enabled me to complete this research work.

I express my sincere gratitude to my supervisor, **Prof. Mamata Upadhyay**, Professor, Km. Mayawati Govt. Girls (P.G.) College, Badalpur, (G.B. Nagar), U.P., for her invaluable guidance, unwavering encouragement, precious time to guide me, and offering valuable study material and suggestions throughout the research journey. I would like to express my gratitude also for her affection and care towards me.

I also wish to express my appreciation and thanks to my Guru, mentor and teacher Professor Sanjeev Kumar Sharma, the head of the Department of Political Science, C.C.S. University Meerut for constantly providing valuable insights, and suggestions and motivating me to do quality work. I would like to take this opportunity to thank and extend my gratitude to my teachers and mentors Prof. S. K. Chaturvedi and Prof. Archana Sharma who always motivated and guided me whenever I needed their support. I am also thankful to Prof. Pawan Kumar Sharma and Prof. Rajendra Pandey for their valuable suggestions and continuous support. I am also indebted to Prof. Divya Nath, former Principal, Prof. Anita Rani Rathore, Principal, and all respected faculty members of Km. Mayawati Govt. Girls (P.G.) College, Badalpur, (G.B. Nagar), U.P., for their support and blessings.

I am also thankful to Prof. S. K. Singh, I.I.T. Roorkee for providing me with his precious time and suggestions to understand the environmental

issues, especially the water issues. I would also extend my thanks to Dr. Anjali Bansal of I.I.M. Lucknow for her encouragement and valuable suggestions for this research. I take this opportunity to thank Dr. Saroj Kr. Dhal, Assistant Prof., Department of Sociology and Dr. Ashok Kumar Moral, Associate Prof., Department of Statistics, University of Lucknow for their valuable insights, constant encouragement and support.

I am also grateful to renowned environmentalist Sh. Kalyan Singh Rawat, Padam Shree Awardee and founder of the ‘Maitee’ movement, for his valuable suggestions and great insights to understand the ground-level realities of green movements. I express my thanks and appreciation for the support of my friends Dr. Munesh Kumar, Dr. Jaiveer Rana, Dr. Ravi Kumar Poswal, Sh. Yatendra Singh, Sh. Atin Motla, Sh. Parvendra Motla, and Dr. Ratan Singh for their valuable support. Dr. Sonika Nagar and Dr. Deepak Kumar provided their valuable time, energy, and encouragement during the whole course of this research work, I am greatly indebted to them. My colleague Sh. Arvind Kumar, Sh. Hemant Kumar, Dr. Shivaji, Sh. Ramesh Kumar, Dr. Sukhraj Singh, Dr. Rajiv Kumar, Sh. Vikesh helped me in collecting the field data even in the chilling cold of January and Dr. Shivaji drove for hundreds of km even when his surgery was due, no word of thanks would be sufficient for their valuable support, however, I extend my deepest thanks to them. I am grateful to Dr. Vikas Singh and Dr. Shraddha Gupta for their constant encouragement and valuable suggestions.

Prof. Sunil Kumar helped me a lot through his contacts in collecting data from the tribal area of Sonbhadra district. Sh. Anil Bisht, a lekhpal, without whose help, it would not have been possible to interact and collect the data from tribal villages deep in the forests. I extend my sincere thanks to Prof. Sunil Kumar and Mr. Anil for their invaluable support. I extend my deepest gratitude to Prof. Sushil Kumar Baboo, Principal and Dr. Pradeep Kumar, Associate Prof., Veerbhumi Govt. P.G.

College, Mahoba for their immense help and support in collecting data, providing opportunities to interact with the key environmentalists of the region to get key insights about the environmental issues. I also wish to take this opportunity to thank Sh. Sumit Singh who helped me in feeding the data in the software. I am greatly thankful to all my respondents who provided their valuable responses, precious time and support to this research work. Without their active contribution, it would not have been possible.

I am grateful to the non-teaching staff of the Badalpur College, Department of Political Science, library and research cell of C.C.S. University Meerut for their assistance and cooperation. I am very much grateful to all libraries, resource persons, and government officials, particularly the Uttar Pradesh Climate Change Authority (UPCCA) for their valuable input and kind cooperation.

Last but not least I extend my gratitude to my family members who have always shown their unconditional love, affection and unwavering support towards me. No word of thanks or mentioning their name can compensate for the sacrifices they made to develop the abilities in me that today I could be able to write this doctoral thesis. Their constant encouragement and support extended during the entire period, can only be felt in my heart and cannot be expressed in words. The loving memories and blessings of my grandparents Late Chaudhary Ridka Singh and Smt. Bhagwati Devi constantly inspires me to work hard and fills me with positivity.

(Pradeep Kumar)

LIST OF FIGURES

S.No.	Particulars	Page No.
1.1	Carbon Emission Inequality across Income Groups of Countries	20
1.2	Per Capita Carbon Emissions of Major Countries Since 1750	21
1.3	Per Capita GHG Emission of India and Uttar Pradesh (2005-2018)	41
2.1	Political Map of the state of Uttar Pradesh.	53
2.2	Agro-Climatic Zones of Uttar Pradesh	56
2.3	Vulnerability Analysis Framework	61
2.4	IPCC AR 5 Risk Management Framework	62
2.5	Percentage distribution of various energy sources in total power installed capacity of Uttar Pradesh	66
2.6	Map of Bahraich District	69
2.7	Map of Lakhimpur Kheri District	73
2.8	Map of Mahoba District	77
2.9	Map of Sonbhadra District	83
3.1	India's Three-fold Climate Agenda	118
3.2	Indian performance in achieving INDCs	122
3.3	Inter-relationship between three Core Shifts in Mission LiFE	131
3.4	Prioritisation Framework for UP SAPCC 2.0	148
3.5	Relevant Policies, Schemes, and Programmes Being Implemented in the UP Agriculture Sector	150
5.1	Pie Chart for Districts of Respondents	227
5.2	Pie Chart for Gender of Respondents	228
5.3	Pie Chart for Social Categories of Respondents	229

5.4	Pie Chart for Qualification of Respondents	231
5.5	Pie Chart for Occupations of Respondents	233
5.6	Pie Chart for responses regarding communities' traditional knowledge leading to resilience and capacity building	273
5.7	Pie Chart for effectiveness of local ecological assets under different stakeholders	275
5.8	Pie Chart for Constraints in adopting climate change-resilient practices/actions	279
5.9	Pie Chart Showing Conditions of changing to Environment-friendly activities/livelihood practices	281

LIST OF TABLES

S.No.	Particulars	Page No.
5.1	Frequency Table for districts of Respondents	227
5.2	Frequency table for Gender of Respondents	228
5.3	Frequency table for Categories of Respondents	229
5.4	Frequency table of Religion of Respondents	231
5.5	Frequency table for Education of Respondents	231
5.6	Frequency table for occupation of Respondents	232
5.7	Crosstab for impact of climate change-Induced abnormal weather conditions on production	234
5.8	Crosstab for scale loss of crop production due to climate change	236
5.9	Crosstab for increase in frequency of flood/drought and crop failure	238
5.10	Crosstab for impact of attack of pests on crop	240
5.11	Crosstab for impact of temperature rise on working hours loss	241
5.12	Crosstab for impact of water-borne diseases	243
5.13	Crosstab for impact of vector-borne diseases	245
5.14	Crosstab for impact of heat-related diseases	247
5.15	Crosstab for vulnerability of houses to natural hazards	249
5.16	Crosstab for landholding/ownership across the gender	251
5.17	Crosstab for landholding/ownership across social categories	253
5.18	Crosstab for insurance coverage across social categories	255
5.19	Crosstab for impact of climate change induced reduction in wages/loss of business/other occupation across social categories	257
5.20	Crosstab for impact of climate change-induced abnormal weather phenomena on production across social categories	259

5.21	Crosstab for extent of loss in production due to climate-induced abnormal weather across social categories	262
5.22	Crosstab for impact of vector-borne diseases across social categories	264
5.23	Crosstab for impact of heat related diseases across social categories	266
5.24	Crosstab for environmental justice perception across social categories	268
5.25	Crosstab for environmental awareness across social categories	270
5.26	Table for responses regarding communities' traditional knowledge leading to resilience and capacity building	272
5.27	Table for effectiveness of local ecological assets under different stakeholders	274
5.28	Table to show the Adaptation was made or not to deal with impacts of climate change	276
5.29	Table showing external assistance to deal with climate-induced impacts	277
5.30	Table for Constraints of Mitigation/adaptation efforts/actions	278
5.31	Table for prospects of changing economic activities/livelihood to environment-friendly lifestyle and activities.	280

ABBREVIATIONS

AES	Acute Encephalitis Syndrome (AES)
AMRUT	Atal Mission for Rejuvenation and Urban Transformation
APP	Ability Pay Principle
AR6	Assessment Report 6
ATACH	Alliance for Transformative Action on Climate and Health
AWS	Automated Weather Stations
BCM	Billion Cubic Meters
BEE	Bureau of Energy Efficiency
BPP	Beneficiary Pays Principle
CBAM	Carbon Border Adjustment Mechanism
CBD	Convention on Biological Diversity
CBDR	Common But Differentiated Responsibilities
CBDRRC	Common But Differentiated Responsibilities Respective Capabilities
CCCS	Copernicus Climate Change Service
CDM	Clean Development Mechanism
CEDA	Centre For Economic Data & Analysis
CGB	Central Groundwater Board)
COPs	Conferences of Parties
CTCN	Climate Technology Centre and Network
DOH&FW	Department of Health & Family Welfare
EEFP	Energy Efficiency Financing Platform
EJ	Environmental justice
EPA	Environmental Protection Agency
ERB	Earth Radiation Budget
ETF	Enhanced Transparency Framework
ETS	Emissions Trading System
EU	European Commission
FEEED	Framework for Energy Efficient Economic Development
FMIS	Flood Management Information System
FMISC	Flood Mapping Information System Centre
GAO	General Accounting Office
GCF	Green Climate Fund
GHGs	Green House Gases
GIS	Global Investor Summit
GND	Green New Deal
GOI	Government of India
GSDP	Gross State Domestic Product
GVA	Gross State Value Added
HDI	Human Development Index
ICJ	International Court of Justice
IHIP	Integrated Health Information Platform
IMD	Indian Meteorological Department
IMF	International Monetary Fund
IPCC	Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change
IR	Infrared Radiation

IRIS	Infrastructure for Resilient Island States
JJM	Jal Jeevan Mission- Har Ghar Jal
LiFE	Lifestyle for Environment
LLA	Locally Led Adaptation
LMIC	Lower Middle-Income Countries
LT-LEDS	Long-Term Low greenhouse Gas Emission Development Strategies
M&E	Monitoring and Evaluation
MENA	Middle East and North Africa
MoEA	Ministry of External Affairs
MoEFCC	Ministry of Environment, Forest & Climate Change
MoHA	Ministry of Home Affairs
MoHUA	Ministry of Housing and Urban Affairs
MoNRE	Ministry of New & Renewable Energy
MoPNG	Ministry of Petroleum and Natural Gas
MTEE	Market Transformation for Energy Efficiency
NAPCC	National Action Plan on Climate Change
NASA	National Aeronautics and Space Administration
NDCs	Nationally Determined Contributions
NEF	New Economic Foundation
NGHM	National Green Hydrogen Mission
NICRA	National Innovation for Climate Resilient Agriculture
NMGI	National Mission for a Green India
NMSA	National Mission for Sustainable Agriculture
NMSH	National Mission on Sustainable Habitat
NMSHE	National Mission for Sustaining the Himalayan Ecosystem
NMSKCC	National Mission on Strategic Knowledge for Climate Change
NSM	National Solar Mission
NTFPs	Non-Timber Forest Products
NWM	National Water Mission
ODF	Open Defecation Free
PAT	Perform Achieve and Trade
PDO	Pacific Decadal Oscillation
PKVY	Pramparagat Krishi Vikas Yojna
PMO	Prime Minister Office
PMUY	Pradhan Mantri Ujjwala Yojana
PPP	Polluters Pay Principle
RRF	Recovery and Resilience Facility
RST	Resilience and Sustainability Trust
SAM	Sustainable Agriculture Mission
SAPCC	State Action Plan on Climate Change
SBM	Swachh Bharat Mission
SBM-G	Swachh Bharat Mission-Grameen
SCM	Smart Cities Mission
SDG	Sustainable Development Goals
SIDS	Small Island Developing States
SKM	Strategic Knowledge Mission
UCC	United Church of Christs

UIRP	Urban Infrastructure Resilience Programme
UJALA	Unnat Jyoti by Affordable LEDs for All
UNCCD	United Nations Conventions to Combat Desertification
UNEP	United Nations Environment Programme
UNFCCC	United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change
UNGA	United Nations General Assembly
UNSC	United Nations Security Council
UP	Uttar Pradesh
UP-SAPCC	UTTAR PRADESH STATE ACTION PLAN ON CLIMATE CHANGE
WCED	World Commission on Environment and Development
WHO	World Health Organisation
WMO	World Meteorological Organisation (WMO)
WTO	World Trade Organisation

CONTENTS

Chapters	Particulars	Page No.
	<i>Preface</i>	
	<i>Acknowledgement</i>	
	<i>List of Figures</i>	
	<i>List of Tables</i>	
	<i>List of Abbreviation</i>	
Chapter-I	: INTRODUCTION	1-51
	1.1 Background	1
	1.2 Climate Change and Limitations of the Mainstream Paradigm	25
	1.3 Climate Action Plans and the Imperative of Climate Justice	34
	1.4 Statement of Problem	38
	1.5 Research Gap	43
	1.6 Objectives of the Study	44
	1.7 Hypothesis	45
	1.8 Significance of the Study	46
	1.9 Structure of the Thesis	48
Chapter-II	: THE UNIVERSE OF STUDY AND METHODOLOGY	52-94
	2.1 Overview of Uttar Pradesh	52
	2.2 Climatic Vulnerability	58
	2.3 Climate Vulnerability of Uttar Pradesh	63
	2.4 Introduction and Climate Vulnerability of Selected Districts	68
	2.5 Research Methodology	88
Chapter-III	: CLIMATE ACTIONS: GLOBAL, NATIONAL AND SUB-NATIONAL LEVEL	95-160
	3.1 Initiatives at International Level	96
	3.2 India's Climate Agenda	117
	3.3 Sub-National Actions: Uttar Pradesh State Action Plan on Climate Change (UP-SAPCC)	145
	3.4 Key Recent Interventions To Foster Sustainable & Green Transition In Uttar Pradesh	157
Chapter-IV	: ENVIRONMENTAL JUSTICE AND CLIMATE JUSTICE: A CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK	161-212
	4.1 Introduction	161
	4.2 Approaches and Theoretical Underpinnings of Environmental Justice	174
	4.3 Environmental Justice Generations	195
	4.4 Climate Justice	198
	4.5 Non-Ideal Perspectives on Climate Justice	207

Chapter-V	:	ANALYSIS OF SAPCC AND DATA FROM SELECTED DISTRICTS OF UTTAR PRADESH	213-284
5.1		Introduction	213
5.2		Evaluation of State Action Plan on Climate Change	214
5.3		Profile of Respondents	226
5.4		Visible Impacts of Climate Change	234
5.5		Disproportionate Impact on Marginalised Sections	251
5.6		Community Management and Traditional Knowledge	272
5.7		Constraints and Prospects	276
5.8		Conclusion	282
Chapter-VI	:	FINDINGS AND CONCLUSION	285-317
6.1		Findings	285
6.2		Challenges in SAPCC 2.0 in Addressing Climate Justice Issues	299
6.3		Recommendations	303
6.4		Limitations of the Study	306
6.5		Relevance of the Study	307
6.6		Conclusion	312
		APPENDICES	318-361
		• Appendix A: Selected Bibliography	318
		• Appendix B: Sample of Used Questionnaire - English	352
		• Appendix C: Sample of Used Questionnaire - Hindi	357

CHAPTER – I

INTRODUCTION

1. BACKGROUND:

John Rawls wrote that “Justice is the first virtue of social institutions, as truth is of systems of thought”(Rawls, n.d.). For most scholars and thinkers, justice has not been a matter of erudite debate but it has been a lived negotiation concerning duties and rights to one another in a wide range of contexts. The phenomenon of climate change is also deeply associated with the issues of fairness and equity in terms of rights and obligations on the part of individuals, communities, and nations with one another in multiple contexts. The philosopher Steven Gardiner considers climate change as “a perfect moral storm” because it involves multiple dilemmas due to its multi-dimensional, multi-scalar, and multi-faceted nature (2004). This thesis is an attempt to identify and understand how the elements of justice have been conceptualized in climate actions and the impacts of climate change. This thesis aims to critically analyse the intersection between the climate action plan of Uttar Pradesh and environmental justice with a focus on examining how this plan incorporates the elements of justice and the lived experiences of different communities. By synthesizing existing literature on climate action planning and environmental justice, this thesis offers suggestions for integrating principles of equity and inclusion into policies aimed at mitigating and adapting to climate change.

Climate change is taking place in a world infected with grave inequalities of income and power. Celebrated environmentalists Anil Aggarwal and Sunita Narain in their seminal work “*Global Warming in An Unequal*

World: A Case of Environmental Colonialism” popularise the relationship between carbon accumulation in the atmosphere and economic poverty and prosperity of world countries (1991). Only a few countries, for instance, the USA, former Soviet Union countries, the UK, France, Poland, Germany, Japan, and Canada are responsible for about 75% of accumulated emissions as of 2019 and a majority of countries have contributed only 7% to the gross greenhouse gases (GHGs) in the atmosphere (Kashwan, 2022, p.4). Since the inception of the Industrial Revolution (IV), these extreme inequalities in carbon space utilization created gross economic inequalities rooted in the processes of ‘imperialism’ and ‘colonialism’; supported by ideologies of ‘capitalism’ and ‘liberalism’; accelerated by waves of ‘neo-liberalism’ and ‘globalization’. Today’s climate catastrophe is the product of these historical circumstances. Prakash Kashwan (2022) traces the root cause of current climate issues by stating “*The climate crisis, climate denialism, and the dismal outcomes of international climate negotiations share the same roots: the influence of exploitative and extractive systems of global capitalism, which are propelled by a nexus of multilateral financial institutions and national political and economic elites*” (p.6). Despite being the third-largest emitter today, India’s historical contribution is only 3% while it is the abode of 18% population (Ritchie, 2019). India’s per capita emission is well below of global average emission. Nevertheless, India is one of the most vulnerable countries to the adversities of climate change. As such, India faces international climate injustices given the historical circumstances of colonialism and exploitation.

In the domestic sphere, India also shows similar patterns of inequalities.

On the one hand, India is home to the largest number of poor people around the globe, on the other hand, it boasts itself of producing dozens of billionaires a year. During the Covid-19 period, the vulnerabilities of Indian society, state, and public institutions were examined on several accounts. The havoc created by COVID-19 not only exacerbated the existing income inequalities but also expected to push 150-199 million people, mostly from rural areas and backward states of Bihar, Chhatisgarh, Madhya Pradesh, Uttar Pradesh, and Odisha into poverty (Tripathi & Ahuja, 2022; Ram & Yadav, 2021). Nonetheless, in the year 2020 alone, India boasted itself of producing 55 new billionaires, i.e. more than one billionaire per week despite economic shutdown and slowdown around the world (Bhargava, 2021). In India, these economic inequalities intersect with the existing socio-cultural divisions underpinned by caste, gender, religion, ethnicity, and language-based discrimination in the distribution of cost and benefit of environmental services and hazards. These ‘structural inequalities’ create the very base of climate (in)justice in India. Desai and Dubey talk about ‘*internal colonization*’ which manifests itself via caste-, and tribe-based discriminations in social, economic, and political spheres (2012). Unequal societies are governed poorly and they don’t rein “*the exploitative and polluting models of extractive development that corporations and political-economic elite find beneficial and perpetuate*” (Kashwan, 2022, p.5).

Nearly daily an ordinary person encounters the news of the devastating consequences of climate change in the form of extreme weather conditions and shooting temperatures breaking new records. Sometimes our cities and villages are running out of water and other days these are

grappling with plenty of water, being flooded with too much water. Who is going to suffer the most? It is the ordinary and disadvantaged section of society who don't have the luxury of access to temperature-regulating electric appliances, which many affluent have, and nor do they have habitats that can survive in the face of a flood. The scorching and sweltering heat makes prey mostly to daily labourers, rikshaw-pullers, brick kiln workers, construction workers, and farmers, who are compelled to be exposed to direct sunlight and heat. However, there are strong reasons to believe that heat strokes toll heavily on the ordinary population. According to Sunita Narain, a noted environmentalist, heat is not a "notified disease" in the list of health departments. Thus, it undermines the actual records of consequences of climate change out of view of policymakers and the general public. The poor and underprivileged are compelled to bear the burn of the catastrophe of which creation they have no role. This climate injustice is likely to manifest itself in various forms and dimensions in the coming years as the vagaries of extreme weather are bound to increase in frequency and intensity.

In the beginning of this thesis, it is to clarify that the concepts of environmental justice and climate justice have been used as per the understanding of Steve Vanderheiden, who sees the notion of climate justice as the extension of the third wave of environmental justice (Vanderheiden, 2016). Environmental justice is an umbrella concept that encompasses the issues of 'fairness' and 'equity' (though not limited to only these) in the spheres of pollution (air, water, soil, noise, radioactive, etc.); biodiversity; ecosystem; planetary limitations; and along with others, the notion of climate justice too. The term 'environmental justice'

has been taken because it is well established in academic literature as a concept and for a better understanding of the conceptual and theoretical underpinning of the issue, as described further in Chapter 4, however, this thesis is focused on ‘climate action plan’ takes the meaning of environmental justice in the context of climate justice.

Climate change is no longer a distant concern, but rather an urgent reality with significant grave consequences for societies across the globe. However, the world suffers from “*Giddens’s Paradox*”, which means:

“Since the dangers posed by global warming aren’t tangible, immediate, or visible in the course of day-to-day life, however, awesome they appear, many will sit on their hands and do nothing of a concrete nature about them. Yet waiting until they become visible and acute before being stirred to serious action will, by definition, be too late” (Giddens, 2009, p. 2)

Nevertheless, today the impacts of climate have become visible enough since the above statement was given by Anthony Giddens. However, this paradox still haunts most of the policymakers and stakeholders even today. Climate change is a multifaceted phenomenon that transcends geographical, political, and socioeconomic boundaries. It is a complex interplay of natural processes and human activities, with far-reaching implications for ecosystems, economies, and societies worldwide. The Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC), the leading international body for assessing the science related to climate change, has consistently warned of the accelerating impacts of global warming. The IPCC’s Sixth Assessment Report (AR6) underscores the unprecedented scale of recent changes in the climate system and emphasises the urgent

need for ambitious mitigation and adaptation measures (Intergovernmental Panel On Climate Change (Ipcc), 2023a)

The urgency of climate change and its related issues can be imagined from the fact that no significant international forum is devoid of this subject on its agenda. In the recent COPs, efforts have been made to actively engage in meaningful and effective implementations of Paris Agreement Commitments, though upheavals are to be confronted regularly. During the summit of COP-26, most of the major countries have updated their voluntary Nationally Determined Contributions (NDCs) including India which has set a very aspirational target. COP 27 and 28 at Shram-al Sheikh and Dubai forwarded the much-needed fund for 'loss and damage'. Even countries like Niger and Ireland have tried to bring the issue of Climate Change under the purview of the United Nations Security Council (UNSC) relating it to security threats that it has the potential to generate. However, India has successfully negated this version with the help of a Russian veto (Haider, 2021). This shows climate change's urgency and political ramifications of it and its associated phenomena.

IPCC AR-6 Synthesis Report shows the urgency of the need to take immediate and effective steps to curb the rising temperature and avoid the disastrous consequences of climate change due to increasing concentrations of carbon dioxide and other GHGs in the atmosphere continuously despite global efforts, it states:

"Historical cumulative net CO₂ emissions from 1850 to 2019 were 2400 ±240 GtCO₂. Of these, more than half (58%) occurred between 1850 and 1989 [1400 ±195 GtCO₂], and about 42% between 1990 and 2019 [1000 ±90 GtCO₂]. Global

net anthropogenic GHG emissions have been estimated to be 59±6.6 GtCO₂-eq in 2019, about 12% (6.5 GtCO₂-eq) higher than in 2010 and 54% (21 GtCO₂-eq) higher than in 1990.”

(IPCC AR-6 Synthesis Report, 2023b: p. 8).

It is obvious from the report mentioned above that current efforts are not enough and effective to avert the catastrophe as more than half of emissions have been made after 1990, a period of climate negotiations, agreements, actions and awareness at global and national levels.

Like any other issue or concept in the discipline of political science, the concept of climate change is not without differences, and despite having an almost unanimous consensus on the adverse effects of climate change, it has its spectrum of debate with competing interests and orientations. Among other manifestations of this debate and differences, the most significant is what Robyn Eckersley (1992) calls “*Anthropocentric Greens and Ecocentric Greens*” (p.8). This is important because it places climate action in perspective whether the ‘atomic and egoistic notion of individual’ would gain prominence or the ‘wholistic notion of the existence’ of all life forms and ‘community’ would determine the course of action. The notion of climate (in) justice is the extension of this debate.

1.1.1 CLIMATE CHANGE & MAKING OF THE PHENOMENON

UNFCCC Article 1 defined “Climate change” as “*a change of climate which is attributed directly or indirectly to human activity that alters the composition of the global atmosphere and which is in addition to natural climate variability observed over comparable time periods*” (UNFCCC, 1992: p.7). Whereas IPCC defines climate change in terms of any change in the climate whether man-induced or naturally occurred. It states climate change “*a change in the state of the climate that can be identified*

... by changes in the mean and/or the variability of its properties, and that persists for an extended period, typically decades or longer” (IPCC 4th AR). The National Aeronautics and Space Administration (NASA) defines the phenomenon of climate change as “Climate change is a long-term change in the average weather patterns that have come to define Earth’s local, regional and global climates” (NASA). Changes in Earth’s Climate have been observed significantly since the mid-twentieth century. There are natural and anthropogenic factors responsible for climate change over the period. Natural factors which contribute to climate change include internal variability and external forces. Internal variabilities for instance, ‘cyclical ocean patterns’ like the phenomena of ‘El Nino’, ‘La Nina’ the PDO (‘Pacific Decadal Oscillation’) create conditions conducive to climate change and we observe the widespread changes in the climate at local, regional and global scale. External forces that may also be responsible for changes in the climate include ‘volcanic activities, variations in the Earth’s orbit’, and changes in the Solar energy output. Continent drift and plate tectonic also affect the climate. The continents we see today were not alike about 200 million years ago. They came into existence due to the plate displacement mechanism of the Earth. This displacement or drift has made changes in the climate because of changes in the features of landmass, waterbodies, and the flow of oceanic currents. and wind. This drift process is continued slowly but steadily even today. This is evident from the continuous rising of the Himalayas ranges due to the drifting of Indian landmass towards the Asian landmass. However, anthropogenic activities have led to drastic and swift changes in the climate of our planet since the inception of the ‘industrial revolution’.

The Earth has undergone several changes in its geological history including many eras of warming and cooling when the temperature keeps on fluctuating from snowball earth to a hot ball (Morgan & McCrystal, 2009). First time in the evolution history of the Earth it is human activities that have caused a change in the natural processes or temperature of the atmosphere as earlier changes were caused by natural factors of the Earth and never by humans as causal agents of such changes. The continuous growth of industrialisation fuelled by fossil fuels in the last two centuries has severely impacted the Earth's climate leading to irreversible changes in the whole ecosystem (Stocker et al., 2013). These 'anthropogenic' activities have led to "anthropogenic climate change"- the climatic variabilities across the geographical regions and weather phenomena – through the concentration of greenhouse gases in the atmosphere released by burning fossil fuels (Rosenzweig et al., 2008; Hook et al., 2013; Hansen et al., 2016). The science is evident in establishing the links between climatic variabilities and anthropogenic activities and there is consensus among scientists, scholars, and the academic fraternity to a great extent to the causal-effect relationship of climate change (Oreskes, 2018; Carlton et al., 2015; Cook et al., 2013; Cook et al., 2016; Powell, 2016). Therefore, it is now an irrefutable fact that the atmosphere of the Earth is warming at an unprecedented rate, and signs of climate change and its associated phenomena are visible everywhere. Data related to temperature, extreme weather events, socioeconomic indicators, and health reveal severe impacts of climate change globally.

There are fundamentally two conceptions of the phenomenon of climate change one is the science of this phenomenon and another is its socio-

economic and politico-cultural aspects. As far as the science part of climate change is concerned, it is now evident from a lot of scientific studies that the emission of certain gases, known as ‘greenhouse gases (GHGs)’ in the atmosphere is mainly responsible for climate change. Carbon dioxide, methane, nitrous oxide, fluorinated gases, and water vapour have the potential to trap the heat and this trapped heat does not escape back to space thus, it leads to the phenomenon of the “greenhouse effect” i.e. increment in the temperature of the Earth’s atmosphere and surface including oceans (Ledley et al., 1999; Mikhaylov et al., 2020). The Sun is the source of energy in our solar system consisting of eight planets and their satellites. All life forms on our planet, the Earth, depend for their energy on the Sun. The Sun radiation reaches the Earth and it is reflected into space from the atmosphere, the surface of the earth. About $1370 \text{ Watts/m}^2/\text{sec}$ is the amount of energy that reaches the surface of the Earth facing the Sun during the day. The distribution of this energy is not uniform on the entire surface of the Earth, but it is uneven due to the inclination, location on the globe, and other geographical conditions. The average amount of energy per square meter is about one-fourth of the energy mentioned above (IPCC, 2007). The incoming and outgoing amounts of heat or radiation make a balance. This is known as the “Earth Energy Budget” or “Earth Radiation Budget (ERB)”. Out of total solar radiation reaching to earth, about 30% is reflected into space through atmospheric gases, clouds, and the Earth’s surface. This amount of reflected heat is known as ‘albedo’ which varies according to the characteristic of the surface. The rest 70% is absorbed by the atmosphere and the Earth’s surface. The absorbed radiation is emitted back into the space as long-wave radiation or ‘Infrared Radiation’(IR). Some portion of

this IR emits directly to space while the remaining part is absorbed by the gases of the atmosphere and then re-emitted to space. These gases work like a blanket around the Earth and prevent some portion of the solar radiation trapped in these gases. Though it is a very natural process and is essential for sustaining the very life by making optimum temperature on this planet, the recent buildup of these gases into Earth's atmosphere due to anthropogenic activities has disturbed the balance of incoming and outgoing heat amounts from the Earth. This imbalance in the solar budget has changed the Earth's climate and has led to disastrous consequences for human life, health, development & welfare, and to ecosystem as a whole. Various greenhouse gases have different heat potential and different periods of their self-life in the atmosphere.

Climate change is not merely an environmental problem but also a profound social and economic justice issue. The impacts of climate change are disproportionately felt by marginalised and vulnerable populations, including women, children, Indigenous peoples, and low-income communities. These communities often have limited resources to adapt to climate change and are more likely to be exposed to climate-related hazards (IPCC, 2022). Inequalities in the impact on different strata of society, make this scientific phenomenon a social justice issue. This understanding has led to the concept of environmental justice, which has become a critical component of identifying and solving these disparities. Environmental justice is the just and equitable treatment of all people in environmental decision-making, regardless of colour, race, or national origin (Bullard & Wright, 1990; Schlosberg, 2004) It reaffirms the rights of all people and communities to a safe, healthy, free from unfair

environmental burdens with threats (Agyeman et al., 2003; Walker, 2012).

According to Simon Caney (2000), the interjection of climate change with social justice issues gives rise to the concept of climate justice. The concept of climate justice emerged in response to the unequal distribution of the burdens and benefits of climate change. It emphasises the need for a just transition to a low-carbon economy, ensuring that the costs and benefits of climate action are shared equitably (Bullard, 2000). Climate justice advocates argue that addressing climate change requires a systemic approach that tackles issues of poverty, inequality, and discrimination. Climate change poses significant risks to the global economy. Extreme weather events, such as hurricanes, floods, and droughts, can cause billions of dollars in damages and disrupt economic activity. Moreover, the transition to a low-carbon economy will require substantial investments and could lead to job losses in some sectors.

The present research explores whether climate change undermines the rights of people in the context of climate justice as the socio-economic and ecological harms caused by climate change undermine the issues of justice in the light of fairness and equity, of the people particularly those who are underprivileged and marginalised sections of society.

However, addressing climate change also presents economic opportunities. The development and deployment of clean technologies can create new jobs and industries. Investing in renewable energy and energy efficiency can lead to cost savings and improved energy security. It is essential to balance climate action's economic costs and benefits to ensure a just and equitable transition.

1.1.2 CLIMATE CHANGE & ITS OVERWHELMING EFFECTS

Climate Change has evolved as a defining feature of our time. The imperative of climate change is now more pressing than ever before as its effects on natural ecosystems and human societies have unfolded with alarming significance over the past few decades (IPCC, 2021). Climate change is not only cross-boundary, but it also depends on the geographical and socio-economic context because the challenges related to climate mitigation may include, for example, extreme weather events or sea level rise (UNEP, 2021). Science establishes time and again that frequent extreme weather events such as storms, cloud-burst, flash floods, heat waves, cold waves, floods, drought, etc; along with sea-level rise and insect-related issues are associated with the phenomenon of climate change. There are both direct and indirect impacts of climate change on living beings and the ecosystem as a whole. It is a crisis that reinforces and complicates other crises. In the era of ‘poly-crisis,’ where several crises exist and reinforce the impact of one another and their impact is more severe than the sum of their individualistic impacts, climate change is of peculiar importance due to its scope, range, and dimensions. Amid these crises, the furry of nature is also in full swing reflecting climate change and its manifestation in the form of heat waves, forest fires, cloud bursts, floods, drought, and erratic weather patterns resulting in untimely and unexpected rainfall. There is growing scientific evidence and academic literature to establish the adverse effects of climate change on the planet and the health and economy of people (The Lancet 2020; UNEP 2020; IPCC 2021). Our experiences during Covid 19 have proved in uncertain terms that the issues of security whether health security, environmental security, or social security, all are imbibed in a complex

web of social, economic, and political interactions. No continent, no country, no matter what level of development and advancement in medical care it had attained, has been spared by the virus. Such pandemics and other health hazards are likely to increase in the future in one form or another. What lessons humanity has learned from the recent pandemic which was once in a century crisis, remains to be seen in the future.

The most obvious impact of climate change is seen in erratic weather patterns across the globe. The temperature is breaking the previous records regularly each year in the last few years. The year 2023 happens to be the warmest since the observational record exists as per the “State of the Global Climate 2023” report by the World Meteorological Organisation (WMO) and now 2024 is well on its way to breaking the previous record and becoming the hottest year as all six months of the first half year has been recorded with temperature above 1.5 degrees Celsius to the pre-industrial averages as per the updates from the European Union’s Copernicus Climate Change Service (C3S) (WMO, 2023; Down to Earth, 2024: p. 44). Records are not only broken for temperature but also for sea-level rise, glacier retreat, ocean heat, and polar ice loss. The frequency and intensity of extreme weather have increased manifold in recent decades. For instance, increased temperature and hot conditions provide suitable conditions for wildfires across the globe be it in Australia or Amazon forest fires in Latin America. Warmer conditions make air hot and its capacity to hold water increases, thus facilitating greater evaporation from the earth’s surface leading to a surface with less moisture making draught conditions more likely and persistent. Warmer oceans and more moist air provide ideal conditions for

tropical cyclones yielding heavy rainfall and increased devastation in coastal areas as typhoons, hurricanes or other cyclones strike the coasts. Increased water vapour in the atmosphere gives rise to heavy precipitation in some areas leading to cloud bursts, avalanches, flash floods, lake bursts, landslides, and floods with more frequency and intensity. Thus, frequent Hurricanes, destructive wildfires, deadly heatwaves, persistent droughts, devastating torrential rains and flooding, and intensive winter storms have become the new normal in the age of climate change (Earthjustice, 2024; Baer, 2021: p.24).

In the background of IPCC's categorical warning about the inadequacy of the current pledges, contributions (nationally determined contributions), and efforts to limit the warming to '1.5°C above the pre-industrial level' it would be required "transformative systemic change" in consonance with "sustainable development" through "the upscaling and acceleration of the implementation of far-reaching, multilevel, and cross-sectoral climate mitigation and addressing barriers" (IPCC, 2018: p. 315). This will require all nations to raise their ambitions and make deep-seated changes in their overall economic value chain system. These systemic changes will require linking them to "complementary adaptation actions". It becomes imperative to mobilize the corporate houses for the cause as these entities are the biggest role players in global warming through industrial activities. Thus, corporations play an important role in accelerating the responses to climate change. Climate Actions though focused and undertaken at different levels and on multiple dimensions around the globe have not been without opposition or obstacles. People ranging from corporations to hardcore nationalist politicians have tried their level best to criticise the notion of global warming and to halt or

retard the speed of governments to take ambitious climate actions to tackle the issue of climate change. Several studies have been conducted to show the intentions of corporate or business houses lobbying at local, national, and global levels for retarding the rapid transformation of the economic system (Newell & Paterson, 1998; Falker, 2008). Such studies highlight the organisations and reinforcement of incumbent power and help understand the reasons for resistance to immediate and ambitious climate actions. It has been argued that “as the prospect of more meaningful and ambitious action increases, so the backlash intensifies. Contributions to political parties from fossil fuel companies have increased significantly in recent years as they feel the pressure”(Newell, 2020).

In cities, the impacts of climate change compound with social and economic vulnerabilities increasing inequity in access to basic services such as health, water quality, and housing (Revi et al., 2014; Anguelovski et al., 2016). In extreme weather conditions, vulnerable sections of communities are always left as victims due to their limited or no access to information from early warning systems, lack of opportunity and resources to evacuate, and post-disaster aid and support (Füssel& Klein 2006).

Rural areas are also impacted by the forces of climate change and its associated phenomena, particularly those communities that depend on nature for their sustenance like farmers, fishermen, tribals, etc. through altered rain patterns, extreme weather conditions, drop in crop yields (Lobell et al., 2008; IPCC, 2014; IPCC, 2021). Agriculture being one of the most sensitive sectors to the effects of climate change, remains the most vulnerable to the adverse impacts of climate change. Agriculture is

still the biggest employment sector in most of the developing world and it is associated with the issues of sustenance to a significant number of people in these countries. Smallholder farmers are facing a substantial income loss on account of climate change due to decreased crop yields. Drop in crop yield and destruction and loss of crops by extreme weather events lead to food insecurity and a lack of nutritious diets for most people in rural areas as well as urban poor. The extreme weather conditions play havoc in agriculture and the allied sectors around the globe particularly in the developing parts of the world. Climate change has a profound impact on global food security and undermines the progress toward a ‘zero hunger’ goal of the United Nations Sustainable Developmental Goals (SDGs). The stability of the food supply chain may be at severe risk in the face of climate change and its associated phenomena due to variability in the short-term to long-term in the supply system (Wheeler & von Braun, 2013). The assessment of hazards or impacts of climate change in rural areas is not simply a linear exercise that takes into consideration the severity of events and their physical effect on the lives of people, but it needs to be integrated with ‘adaptive capacity’ measured in a wholistic manner (Nelson et al., 2010).

Climate change hurts the realisation of the citizens' rights and undermines a person's developmental aspects. Now it has unequivocally been confirmed by several scientific studies and reports including IPCC reports that the phenomenon of climate change directly or indirectly hampers the full and effective realization of several human rights around the globe ranging from the rights to life & safety, nutritious food, safe potable water, hygiene & sanitation, housing, work, culture, health, self-determination, and security (IPCC, 2023; HRC, 2019). United Nations

Environment Programme (UNEP) in its report “Climate Change and Human Rights” contends climate change is one of “the greatest threats to human rights” because it poses grave risks to the fundamental rights of individuals and communities around the world and it states “Anthropogenic climate change is the largest, most pervasive threat to the natural environment and human rights of our time. Climate change has already begun to have far-reaching environmental impacts, including many adverse effects on wildlife, natural resources, and the ecological processes that support access to clean water, food, and other basic human needs” (UNEP, 2015: p.1).

Even a case of climate change has finally reached the International Court of Justice (ICJ). On March 29, 2023, a resolution -A/77/L.58- was adopted by the United Nations General Assembly (UNGA) asking for an advisory opinion from the ICJ for making the States responsible for their obligations concerning climate change (UN, 2023). The campaign was spearheaded by the island country the Republic of Vanuatu which invested a great amount of diplomatic and civil society support for linking the issues of climate change with the human rights of the people. It is the first time that the highest seat of justice in the world has been knocked to clarify and issue an advisory on the obligations of the states related to climate change and legal possibilities in case of non-compliance with those obligations. On 8th April 2024, the Indian Supreme Court made a landmark decision in the case of ‘M.K. Ranjitsingh & Ors. Vs. Union of Indian & Ors. It held that the Indian citizenry had legal protection to hold any party accountable for not making enough effort to mitigate the adverse effect of climate change and its associated phenomenon of global warming. In simple words, the Apex Court linked the rights to “equality”

and “life” to the vagaries of climate change and held that “it emerges that there is a right to be free from the adverse effects of climate change” (Supreme Court of India, para 27. p. 21).

1.1.3 CLIMATE CHANGE: UNEVEN CONTRIBUTIONS & IMPACTS

Though the impacts of climate change are universal for one and all irrespective of their geographical boundaries, national identity, racial origin, economic position, and social status, people in developing countries and least-developed countries are particularly vulnerable to the vagaries of nature associated. United Nations categorically states the different impacts of climate change in various categories as follows:

“The impacts of climate change will not be borne equally or fairly, between rich and poor, women and men, and older and younger generations. Consequently, there has been a growing focus on climate justice, which looks at the climate crisis through a human rights lens and on the belief that by working together we can create a better future for present and future generations.”

(United Nations, 2019)

The findings of IPCC AR-6 Reports reiterate the existential crisis of the planet in no uncertain words, stating that human activities have caused global warming. Despite global efforts being made for abatement or reduction of carbon emissions since the beginning of the 1990s, the net carbon emission is about 54 percent higher than the 1990 level. The contribution to this emission is greatly uneven across the regions, countries, and income groups and poses serious questions of equity and ethics/morality.

Figure 1.1 Carbon Emission Inequality across Income Groups of Countries

1. Fossil emissions: Fossil emissions measure the quantity of carbon dioxide (CO₂) emitted from the burning of fossil fuels, and directly from industrial processes such as cement and steel production. Fossil CO₂ includes emissions from coal, oil, gas, flaring, cement, steel, and other industrial processes. Fossil emissions do not include land use change, deforestation, soils, or vegetation.

Source: Our World in Data.

The figure shows the inequality in carbon emission across the income groups of countries. Higher-income countries constituting only 15.7 % population emit a disproportionately higher share of 34.4 % of GHGs, while lower-middle-income countries and low-income countries comprise 48.8% of the population but emit only 15.7% of emissions. Further, the accumulation of GHGs is a historical phenomenon, and if historical responsibility is taken into consideration this gap exaggerates exponentially. Moreover, the per capita emission across the income groups across the countries shows the inequalities of emissions within a

nation i.e. the rich in poor countries are also responsible for acquiring substantial carbon space than their fellow nationals.

Figure 1.2 Per Capita Carbon Emissions of Major Countries Since 1750

1. Fossil emissions: Fossil emissions measure the quantity of carbon dioxide (CO₂) emitted from the burning of fossil fuels, and directly from industrial processes such as cement and steel production. Fossil CO₂ includes emissions from coal, oil, gas, flaring, cement, steel, and other industrial processes. Fossil emissions do not include land use change, deforestation, soils, or vegetation.

Source: Our World in Data

It is evident from the data mentioned above that a substantial gap exists between the per capita emissions of developed nations and those of lower-income countries. The biggest economy the United States of America has per capita emissions of 14.9 tonnes of Carbon dioxide equivalent, the figure is 14.2 t and 8.0 t for Canada and China respectively; while per capita emissions for India and Kenya stood at only 2.0 t and 0.5 t respectively in the year 2022. Highlighting the carbon emission inequities within regions across income groups, a study published in the esteemed journal ‘*Nature*’ shows bottom 50% population on average emits 1.4t CO₂ e per year; the middle 40% has an average of 6.1t while the top 10% and top 1% emit 28.7t and 101t respectively (Chancel, 2022).

Nevertheless, the advancements in emissions calculation, do not provide the true picture of the contribution of actual emissions given several shortcomings in inventory making, regulatory mechanisms, and fraudulent practices like “Green Washing” by several emitters (Netto et al., 2020; Szabo and Webster, 2021). Emissions are generally calculated based on emissions coming out of economic activities in a given territory (production-linked). However, the populations in advanced countries consume much of the production taking place in developing countries. Noted economist, Thomas Piketty in his celebrated work “*Capitalism and Ideology*” discusses this contradiction of carbon inequality as follows:

“In particular, carbon emissions are not solely the responsibility of the countries or the countries that host factories generating significant emissions. Consumers in the importing countries, particularly the wealthiest of them, bear part of the responsibility as well. By using available data on

the income distribution in various countries together with surveys that allow us to associate income with consumption profiles, it is possible to estimate how responsibility for carbon emissions is distributed among the world's people. . . . These estimates reflect both direct emissions (from transportation and home heating, for example) and indirect emissions; that is, emissions incurred in the use and production of goods consumed by individuals in different countries as well as in the shipping of those goods from the place of origin to the place of consumption” (Piketty, 2020 p.666).

Today no region of the world is unaffected by the impacts of climate change viz. global warming, loss of biodiversity, and sea-level rise, the geographical locations of disadvantaged and poor people are found to be more severely affected disproportionately. For instance, a study by Andrew King from the University of Melbourne and associates found that “the most perceptible warming is found in tropical regions-those near the equator. This includes developing parts of the world, we might, then, conclude people in the poorest parts of the world have experienced the most perceptible global warming over their lifetime” (Down To Earth, 2024, p.94).

Highlighting the grave concerns regarding the uneven and disproportionate burden of climate change on the poor and people belonging to the downtrodden section of society, the UN report clearly states “Climate change is disrupting national economies and affecting lives and livelihoods, especially for the most vulnerable. Between 2010 and 2020, highly vulnerable regions, home to approximately 3.3–3.6

billion people, experienced 15 times higher human mortality rates from floods, droughts, and storms than regions with very low vulnerability” (UN, 2023). Analysis in the global context has shown that climate impacts tend not to be evenly distributed, but instead often amplify the existing social inequities and vulnerability (IPCC, 2014; IPCC, 2021). The root cause of these disparities is grounded in the structures of historical injustices, existing socio-economic conditions, and ownership and access to resources (Adger et al., 2006). Thus, people from marginalised and vulnerable sections of society for example due to their habitats vicinity, low-income groups, minority communities, Indigenous populations, and communities of colour are more likely to be prone to the adverse effects of environmental hazards and imported toxins dumped by developed countries in the developing world leading to the high rate of illness, casualties and severe ecological damage to their local environment (Pellow, 2007).

A recent World Bank Report titled ‘Choosing Our Future: Education for Climate Action’ presents the impact of climate change on education and its disproportionate burden on poor and developing countries. As per the report, due to extreme weather conditions caused by climate change, an astounding 400 million students around the globe have experienced school closures since 2022. It states that education is being hit hardest by climate change in low-income nations with a loss of 18 school days annually on average, compared to just a loss of 2.4 days in rich countries. Highlighting the disproportionate impacts on the young population, the report states that a 10-year-old child now (2024) will be subjected to more floods, (three times), more droughts (five times), and more heatwaves (thirty-six times) over her lifetime than a 10-year-old child in 1970. The poorest will suffer

the most, e.g. half of the students in the poorest municipalities in Brazil could face about half a year's learning loss on account of heat alone (Sabarwal et al., 2024). The poor suffer most by the vagaries of nature spurred by climate change due to their vicinity to geographical areas often ravaged by floods, heatwaves, landslides, storms, and polluted air and water (Pellow, 2007; Cutter et al., 2003).

1.2 CLIMATE CHANGE AND LIMITATIONS OF THE MAINSTREAM PARADIGM

Mike Hume, a renowned Climate Scientist in his influential work *Why We Disagree About Climate Change* contends that for different people climate change means different things in different situations and locations (2009). It is evident in different platforms of climate governance and the views of different stakeholders and actors, and this is the reason for disagreement about the risks the phenomenon of climate change poses and actions taken or needed to tackle the problem. The scale and intensity of the differences can be imagined from the fact that on the one hand, there are hyper-activists such as Al-Gore, Leonardo Di Caprio, Inger Anderson, William Nordhaus, and Greta Thunberg who have left no stone unturned in the fight against the climate change in their respective field and activism; on the other hand, there are skeptics who persistently held that there is no climate change and whatever change is there that is caused by natural processes and not by anthropogenic activities (McCright and Dunlap, 2011; Poortinga et al., 2019). This climate change 'disbelief' refers to the rejection of climate change realities and it forms one of the important political tools in the hands of rightist leaders around the world.

As far as the nature of the topic of 'climate change' is concerned, it is not

easy to have a unanimous opinion on it due to its multiple perspectives on its multifaceted and multidimensional notions. Its different perspectives range from scientific perspective to planetary justice passing through socio-economic, ecological, political, colonial, racial, gender, and many more emerging trends in the debate around the phenomenon of climate change. Most people consider climate change as simply a geophysical phenomenon separated from socio-economic and politico-cultural dynamics. They seek its solution in the technological advancement and economic capital needed for green investments to mitigate the concentration of greenhouse gases in the atmosphere. The strong and all-pervasive narratives of ‘liberalism’ particularly ‘neoliberalism’, have become common sense value systems of governments as well as of societies not only in the ‘Western World’ but also in other parts of the world. Others consider the crisis of climate change not just a geophysical phenomenon but is inextricably linked with the socio-economic and politico-cultural dynamics operating in the historical account of structural inequalities manifested in the hierarchies and supremacy of caste, class, race, gender, and geographies. Thus, there is no consensus on the issue of utmost urgency due to the changes having reached the level of irreversibility, the ‘tipping points’, that pose an existential threat to civilisation (Ehrlich & Ehrlich, 2013). The forces of capitalism have been instrumental in shaping the dialogues and the agenda of global climate governance since the emergence of the crisis which itself is a product of ‘bourgeois capitalism’. Scholars call the phenomenon of the ‘Anthropocene’(an age of climate change caused by human activities) better as the ‘Capitalocene’ because they contend that it is not human activities but bourgeois capitalism that has caused this change in the

climate of our planet (Baer, 2021; Moore. 2014; 2016; Haraway, 2015; Davis et al., 2019).

Of late many political scientists have paid attention to the issues of climate justice and climate action. They have developed different understandings of the notions of climate justice and climate action based on different theoretical grounds and ideological orientations. Both liberal and conservative political scientists—often referred to as neo-classical environmentalists—think that established liberal democratic political systems can effectively address climate change issues and pursue substantive climate justice through current energy and economic regimes, global legal frameworks, and associated transnational institutions and mechanisms. They believe in boosting the "green" credentials of conventional liberal democratic political systems, non-market mechanisms like scientific research, efficiency-enhancing technologies, and bureaucracy, should have a limited role. Furthermore, not many political scientists have questioned this assumption in the last fifty years, partly because realist, liberal, and conservative tendencies have shaped domestic environmental policy. The liberal response to climate fundamentally is market-driven and consensus-building among the nations through negotiations and diplomatic channels. This response includes market-oriented mechanisms like 'carbon trading', 'green investment', 'carbon tax', and promotion of 'green and renewable energy', among others. Apart from this economic aspect, their political response lies in establishing international environmental institutions, negotiating environmental agreements and treaties, strengthening laws in the international arena, etc. Climate change poses immense and far-reaching impacts on the global political system, making some scholars

put forward the notion of “*climatization of global politics*” because of growing new economic and health crises, intensification of conflicts over natural resources, increased climate and environmental migration leading to refugee problems, increased protectionism and the crisis of multilateral environmental governance, disruption and shifting in global supply chains (Aykut & Maertens, 2023).

However, these liberal responses have yielded not very promising and tangible results in the fight against climate change so far. Despite the burgeoning domestic and international market-oriented mechanisms, technological advancements, and international environmental organizations and treaties, the fate of our planet remains critical and pathetic. The recent ‘*Global Environmental Outlook*’ report released by the ‘United Nations Environmental Programme (UNEP)’ states that the environmental crises such as carbon emission, and biodiversity loss, have not been reversed or even mitigated but they increased in absolute quantity and this reflects the failure of multilateral environmental policies. This crisis of ‘environmental multilateralism’ shows the loss of political momentum in international negotiations and the growing protectionist approach leading to a sense of “treaty fatigue” (Falkner, 2013). The global leadership has not been able to achieve meaningful, deep, effective, and transformative actions to avert the impending catastrophe of climate change. United Nations Secretary-General Antonio Guterres describes the situation by stating “an atlas of human suffering and a damning indictment of ‘failed climate leadership’” (WRI, 2023).

Liberalism has a foundational characteristic of treating social problems in silos independent from each other e.g. to liberals the issue of growing inequality in society is not a systemic structural problem but an issue of

capability, skill, and merit of an individual. This desire to solve problems separately from each other, is manifested in the climate action policy of liberalism which seeks to tackle this grave threat by implying market-driven mechanisms within the liberal free-market framework which is incapable of solving it, rather than addressing it in a wholistic manner by making necessary structural and systemic changes in economic and social structures (Shaw, 2023). Climate change also put a litmus test on liberalism and many scholars reveal the contradiction and unresolved tensions of liberalism in making sustainable and lasting solutions to climate questions because no solution seems visible despite making so much effort. Christopher Shaw (2023) contends that the narratives of liberalism deny its very contradictions and climate change exposes the limitations of liberalism, and liberal climatic discourse manifests this failure (p.12). For some scholars, the limitations of “formal democracy” i.e. just participating in voting during the elections, is considered a problem and they seek more democracy e.g. “radical democracy” as an effective climate action; and reveal the inability and uselessness of dominant approaches of climate change (Machin, 2013; Fischer, 2017).

From social and Marxist perspectives, the efforts to climate actions are just meant to make superficial changes in the system of capitalism and there are no serious efforts to transform the economic and social systems which are the root cause of this catastrophic problem. This school of thought traces the root of climate change in the socio-economic interactions and relations that started with the beginning of the Industrial Revolution and the emergence of capitalism and liberalism as an ideology. According to this tradition, realizing the seriousness of the problem, capitalism has sought to ‘decarbonize’ the global economy

through ‘market interventions’, however, the basic characteristics of economic production and consumption remain the same. This new avatar of “Green Capitalism” refers not to the radical transformation of economic forces and social relations but is the extension of the current trend towards ‘ecological commodification’ and ‘expropriation’ on the line of the existing system which is again prone to the crisis and unstable (Bohm et al., 2012). Carbon markets serve as new means and creative tools for the accumulation and concentration of wealth and capital and are unlikely to transform the basic structure of exploitative capitalism.

There is emerging scholarship on the relationship between the genesis of capitalism and degradation of environmental degradation. Climate change is considered a question of socio-environmental injustice. Naomi Klein, an influential climate activist and writer, in her seminal book “*This Changes Everything Capitalism vs. the Climate*” contends that the current climate crisis is intrinsically linked to capitalism because the unfettered greed and unrestrained desire to accumulate wealth, unhindered market access, and limited state have exacerbated ecological degradation (2014). The question of the role of mighty corporations in shaping and influencing climate policies has also been of significant importance in uncovering the true nature of political dispensation. In “No Is Not Enough: Resisting Trump's Shock Politics and Winning the World We Need,” she scrutinises how powerful corporations wield influence over governmental decisions at the expense of environmental well-being and underscores how corporate interests often take precedence over sustainable ecological practices and community welfare. (Klein, 2017).

Similar views and arguments about the role of capitalism and imperialism leading to exploitation and environmental degradation around the

globe, have been forwarded by writers such as Amitav Ghosh through his picaresque novels Ibis Trilogy (*Sea of Poppies*, 2008; *River of Smoke*, 2011; and *Flood of Fire*, 2015), (Balkan, 2022, pp. 40–41). In ‘*The Great Derangement*’ and ‘*The Nutmeg’s Curse: Parables for a Planet in Crisis*’ the relationship of capitalism and imperialism with environmental degradation has been explained eloquently. He states;

“the discussion of climate change, as of every aspect of the planetary crisis, tends to be dominated by the question of capitalism and other economic issues; geopolitics, empire, and questions of power figure in it far less. One reason for this is that the modern citizen has become, almost unconsciously, Homo economicus”

-The Nutmeg’s Curse: Parables for a Planet in Crisis (p.116)

The wars, imperialism and fossil fuels have a direct relationship. Britain was the first country to realize the potential of steam power in making machines thereby becoming the cradle of the industrial revolution which was powered by steam generated from the fossil fuel, coal. Geographical explorations were made in search of new markets for the products manufactured as mass production in factories powered by coal energy. These explorations and new trade routes ultimately motivated the colonial powers to conquer the territories mainly by naval vessels powered by coal energy. Further, infrastructure such as roads, railways, canals, ports, etc. were developed to extract natural resources from deep and hinterland areas. Ecological degradation is a result of the plunder of natural resources and exploitation of humanity to satisfy the greed of a few colonial and native capitalists who made people vacate their homes and forests to extract minerals and fossil fuels. Thus, fossil fuels not only

become instrumental in war through fuel-powered war machinery but also become the most important natural resources for which wars and dominations are made to secure their continuous and uninterrupted supply to fuel the economies. Heraclitus said “War is the father of all things” and it was also true of the Industrial Revolution (Ghosh, 2021; pp. 116-117).

Even in contemporary times, we see the vagaries of wars, conflicts, dominations, and civil wars to secure the fields of oil and gases and militaries have become significant consumers of fossil fuels to run their weaponry system and fuel their establishments. For instance, the oil-rich regions of the world such as MENA (Middle East and North Africa) have become the hot spots of conflicts, wars, and power politics among the great powers. The carbon footprints of major militaries around the globe are significantly high. The carbon footprint of the US military is greater than any other institution on the earth because it is the largest institutional consumer of fossil fuels. A geopolitical ecology framework has been developed to examine the material ecological metabolic flows responsible for geopolitical and geoeconomic power dynamics (Belcher et al., 2019). The annual carbon emission of the Pentagon is more than that of some industrialised nations such as Denmark, Portugal, and Sweden (Crawford, 2019).

The underlying characteristics of capitalism viz. individualism; accumulation of wealth and material possessions; ever-growing extraction of natural resources; unending consumerism; and laissez-faire policy in the market sphere are incompatible with the sustainability, health of the Earth, thriving societies and empowered citizenry (Angus, 2010). The climate crisis can't be solved within the framework of capitalism and to avoid this climatic catastrophe needs structural

transformation of the whole gamut of relations of production and not mere technological and economic solutions. John Bellamy Foster calls for a revolution to solve the ecological crisis in his book *“The Ecological Revolution”*, he states “We have reached a turning point in the human relation to the Earth: all hope for the future of this relationship is now either revolutionary or it is false” (2009). Scholars of this tradition put the notion that capitalism is posed to bring greater suffering and exploitation of communities and natural resources as it advances in the 21st century. The slogan goes: “Ecosocialism or Barbarism: there is no third way” (Angus, 2010, p. 27).

There is another tradition of scholars who have shown their concern about the possibilities of the emergence of ‘authoritarian states’ in response to the rising and growing consequences of climate change and it will undermine or diminish what little democracy is left (Wainwright & Mann, 2013; Fischer, 2017). These authoritarian states will further protect the interests of the bourgeoisie class from the adverse consequences of climatic hazards thereby exacerbating the existing inequalities and injustices. These authoritative states would ultimately turn into a “Climate Leviathan” propounded as a political possibility because global climate change turns the issue into the “paradigm of security” (Wainwright & Mann, 2013).

However, despite the overwhelming scientific evidence, climate change remains a highly contested issue. Various factors, including political ideology, economic interests, and cultural values, shape public opinion and policy responses. As a result, the world is grappling with a complex and often contradictory landscape of climate action and inaction.

1.3 CLIMATE ACTIONS AND IMPERATIVES OF JUSTICE

Amid the threat of crisis which has become an existential threat to humanity, the world has taken serious steps to retard the concentration of Carbon di Oxide and other Green House Gases in the atmosphere. The phenomenon of Global Warming in this “Unequal World” in terms of stage of development, historical responsibility for emitting Green House Gases (GHGs), and consuming more “carbon space” and “different capabilities” in terms of resources and finance for climate actions i.e. “mitigation” and “adaptation”, requires a different approach based on the principle of equity and fairness so that underdeveloped and developing nations can also meet their aspirations of economic and social development. For this under the aegis of UNFCCC (United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change), the principle of CBDR (Common But Differentiated Responsibilities) was adopted. India being the world’s most populous country, traditionally a developing nations’ leader, a nation with a rising middle-class population and a changing consumption pattern with a large poor population, an emerging global economic and political power, and a significant future emitter, It has been an important party in global climate negotiation with continuity and change in its approach over the time from Rio to Copenhagen to Paris climate negotiations (Sengupta 2019, pp.134-137). Climate actions at global, national, and state levels have been discussed at length in Chapter 3.

The key question of how best to incorporate the concept of environmental justice in the climate action plan is the most vital in the developmental paradigm of state policies. The developmental paths are being redesigned to make them compatible with environmental sustainability and socio-economic equity. The concept of ‘low-carbon development pathways’ has

become traction among policymakers and academia as a viable option for sustainable development (Yuan et al. 2011; Zhou, 2014). However, the elements of justice are not always the guiding principles of these policies which seek to fix the problem of climate change through technological and economic tools. It is in this context that ‘just transitions’ must be the guiding pillar of such policies and actions (Newell & Mulvaney, 2013; Heffron, 2021).

In the decade of 1960s, Prof. Horst Rittel used the term “wicked problem” referring to such social problem systems that are formulated poorly, informed confusingly, have many decision-makers and stakeholders with conflicting interests and value systems, and where there is confusion in the whole system. The adjective “wicked” was used to denote the unique malice quality of these problems of which proposed “solutions” often turn out to be “worse than the symptoms” of the problem. Though Prof. Rittel with this term referred to issues in urban planning, the problem of climate change fits the description on several counts. The climate crisis may be termed a wicked problem because only one-fourth part of humanity could be developed with the energy of fossil fuels and the remaining three-fourths of humanity is yet to grow industrialise, develop, and elevate their living standards to reach the level of a dignified life. Meanwhile, the adverse impacts of climate change which is caused by the burning of fossil fuels mostly by developed countries have emerged in unambiguous terms, and demand for eliminating or phasing out of these dirty fuels has become the buzzword around the globe. The developing countries, due to their limited financial resources, are compelled to use fossil fuels to meet their energy requirement. However, they are being denied their due carbon space and

are asked to shoulder the burden of the problem of which creation they have no role or little contribution. Further, the developed countries are not ready to part with their green technologies or capital to these developing nations. This causes the issues of equity and fairness in climate governance. Thus, Climate change along with environmental issues also bears the concrete question of justice. The footprints of climate change are distributed asymmetrically across the globe as the saying follows, 'Someone suffers for the sins of others'. JS Mill defined justice in terms of moral rights and obligations. (Utilitarianism, 1861). Justice is not a rigid matter of debate everyone deserves it equally. Environmental Justice is not an exception. Climate change is one of the drastic and pressing challenges of humanity.

Against this backdrop of unequal impacts, the concept of environmental justice has gained prominence as a means to address the inequitable distribution of environmental risks and benefits (Agyeman et al., 2003; Schlosberg, 2004). Originally rooted in civil rights movements in the United States, environmental justice has evolved into a global movement advocating for equity in environmental decision-making and policy (Bullard, 1990; Mohai & Saha, 2006).

Environmental justice encompasses both distributive justice, which concerns the fair allocation of environmental goods and harms and procedural justice, which emphasises inclusive and participatory decision-making processes (Schlosberg, 2004; Walker, 2012). The framework highlights the importance of recognising and addressing the root causes of environmental inequalities, including systemic racism, economic disparities, and political marginalisation (Pellow, 2007).

The concept of environmental justice evolved from the environmental

movements that arose against unequal distribution of environmental harms especially in the habitats of people of colour and sections of disadvantaged groups of society. The literature on environmental justice consists of a pluralistic understanding of the concept. Many scholars have interpreted and analysed the concept of environmental justice differently in terms of distributional justice, procedural justice, recognition justice, and capability approach to justice. In the earlier years of environmental movements, the issues of “equity and “fairness” dominated the discourses of environmental justice, the demand for participation and having a say in the decision-making and recognition of their socio-cultural identity also became part of environmental justice discourse. As clarified above the notion of climate justice may be understood as the extension of environmental justice discourse itself. Schlosberg also argues that environmental justice’s expanding scope encompasses the phenomenon of climate change and the evolving concept of climate justice (Schlosberg, 2012). Environmental justice concerns itself with human-environment relations and its associated issues of justice. Similar to environmental justice, the notion of climate justice is not only limited to the inequity impacts of climate change but also encompasses other social and ecological injustices such as denial of participation and recognition role in decision-making and policy formulation, lack of capabilities of people to cope with the impacts, inter-generational issues of justice and concerns of non-human species and abiotic components of the ecosystem. Thus, climate justice seeks to undo the wrong and unjust impacts of climate change on the people who have no or very little role in making the problem of climate change. This injustice arises from the socio-economic and ecological interactions reinforcing one another and global

power dynamics perpetuating the unequal exchange between nations and communities.

In 2005, Hurricane Katrina is considered to have influenced the development of interactions between environmental justice and climate justice in the USA. The first Climate Summit was held at Hague at COP 6 and it led to the foundation of the Climate Change Initiative in 2001 (Schlosberg & Collins, 2014). In the beginning, the focus of climate justice negotiation was on the efforts to mitigate the emissions of greenhouse gases and on the cost of mitigation and transfer of technology especially state-of-the-art technology to developing and least-developed countries. Therefore, climate justice theories were mainly distributive and restorative with issues of equity and fairness or per capita emissions approach. Though climate justice extended to cover broader social and global justice issues, it also paid attention to the local vulnerabilities of people facing adverse impacts of climate change.

In academic literature, according to Schlosberg & Collins, the term ‘climate justice’ seems to be used in 1989 by Weiss in the book “*In Fairness to Future Generations: International Law, Common Patrimony and Intergenerational Equity*” and the references to interactions between justice and climate change increased in the last decade of 20th century, especially in the writings of environmental ethicists such as David Jamieson and Henry Shue (Schlosberg & Collins, 2014). A detailed discussion on the issue of environmental and climate justice is mentioned in chapter 4 of this thesis.

1.4 STATEMENT OF PROBLEM

Antonio Guterres, the United Nations Secretary-General, highlights the uneven impact of climate change on the poor and vulnerable: “*Climate*

change is happening now and to all of us. No country or community is immune. And as always is the case, the poor, and vulnerable are the first to suffer and the worst hit” (UN Portal, 2019).

Climate change not only has inherently unequal and disproportionate impacts on marginalised and poor communities, which are affected adversely in different ways and amplify their existing disadvantaged position in the society but also there exist certain limits even to the climate actions like social limits to adaptations. Adger et al. contend that such social limits to adaptation “are endogenous to society” and are based on the prevailing value system, knowledge, culture, and attitude toward risks (Adger et al., 2009). In climate action too, these groups or sections of society find themselves at the receiving end because of their limited skills, material resources, access to institutional support, and cultural resources needed for adaptation, recovery, and resilience in the wake of natural hazards caused by climate change.

Recently released Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC)’s Sixth Assessment Report has once again rung the alarm about the rising temperature of the planet and the shortage of time to act to halt the concentration of carbon in the atmosphere. India is particularly vulnerable to the impacts of climate change due to its geographical location (long coastline, unstable Himalayas), high population density, vast numbers of impoverished population, and low capacity-building of institutions, people, and communities to deal with issues of mitigation and adaptation. The Indian Ocean is warming at a higher rate than other oceans indicating the likelihood of increased heatwaves and flooding in India. Monsoon extremes are likely to increase with the frequency of short intense rainy days rather than normal more rainy days in India (IPCC 2021). According

to the “World Bank Report 2018”, the economic impact of phenomena of climate change e.g. the changing rainfall pattern and rise in temperatures leading to severe heatwaves and sea-level rise are expected to cost India GDP loss of 2.8 % annually and would affect about half the country’s population in terms of depressed living standards by 2050 (Mani et al., 2018).

India's development approach has generally been governed by its objectives which include eradicating widespread poverty, improvement in social services i.e. health and education, access to clean drinking water and sanitation facilities, generating employment, and modernization of economy. This anthropogenic approach to development has adverse consequences on environmental sustainability. The distribution of environmental costs and benefits are not alike to all sections of the society. The poor and disadvantaged sections of society with minimum resources at their disposal for mitigation and adaptation are always at the receiving end and face the gravest consequences in terms of loss of lives, livelihood, homes, social capital, and economic assets, if any they have. Thus, this distribution of cost and benefits is not fair and is based on the concept of justice or social justice. This disproportionate burden on the poor is generally the problem of which generation they have no role.

As there are disparities among the different nations at the international level, there are also disparities among states at the national level. The state of Uttar Pradesh owns just 7.33 % of India’s area and 7.91% of India’s GDP however, it inhabits about 17 % of India’s population. This shows the wide income and resource disparity at the national level. Due to its vast population, lesser GDP in proportion to its population, higher dependency on agriculture and allied sectors, high incidence of poverty,

and exposure to various natural disasters such as floods, drought, storms, lightning, earthquakes, hailstorms, etc., this state is particularly at high risk of climate change-induced vulnerabilities. As mentioned above the per capita emissions of India is low even to the world average per capita emissions. Furthermore, the share of Uttar Pradesh emissions at 1.32 t CO₂e/capita is even lower in comparison to the national average of 2.24t CO₂e/capita (GHG Platform India, n.d.).

Figure 1.3: Per Capita GHG Emission of India and Uttar Pradesh (2005-2018)

Source: GHG Platform India

The above figure shows the disparity in the emissions at the state and the national level. It is evident that initially there was not much difference between the emissions of Uttar Pradesh and India but it has grown in recent years. There are several studies and visible incidences of adverse

impacts of climate change-induced disasters in the state of Uttar Pradesh. The poor and the marginalised are the prime victims of these extreme weather conditions and associated phenomena. These sections are compelled to live lives in polluted environments (air pollution, water pollution, and soil pollution) and bear the brunt of climate-induced weather phenomena, and that too without making any or very negligible contribution to the making of these problems.

Further the idea of “environmental justice” not only includes the different sections of society (or nations at the international level) but also encompasses different generations (i.e. past and present generations who are responsible for the accumulation of carbon in the atmosphere and future generations who will have no carbon space for their development and will face the most serious ill-effects and that too with no fault of theirs); and rights of ecosystem i.e. the right of the planet its biodiversity and landscape. In this way, the phenomenon of environmental justice is new and complex which includes inter-groups, inter-generations, and interspecies as parties in conflicts. State Action Plan on Climate Change (SAPCC) in conformation to the National Action Plan on Climate Change (NAPCC) has sought to make several interventions not only to save the society from the impact of climate change consequences but also to make the developmental process more sustainable in the light of Government of Uttar Pradesh’s aspiring goals “Vision 2030”. However, it is a matter of constant inquiry whether the provisions are being implemented or executed in the spirit of the document climate action plan. The present study seeks to enquire into those aspects.

Literature concerning climate change phenomena, climate actions, and environmental & climate justice has been described throughout this

thesis. The due importance of the concerned literature has been accorded in the best possible way. That's why the literature review is not given separately to avoid duplication and maintain the compactness of the thesis.

1.5 RESEARCH GAP

There is emerging academic literature on the issues of various aspects of environmental issues including environmental justice and sustainability and their interplay with the phenomenon of climate change. Uttar Pradesh (UP), India's most populous state, is a pertinent case to explore the intersection of climate action planning and environmental justice within a diverse and complex socio-economic context. The state is characterized by rapid urbanisation, industrial growth, agricultural intensification and significant ecological challenges (Ghosh et al., 2020; Singh et al., 2024). UP is vulnerable to a range of climate impacts, including heatwaves, erratic monsoons, floods, and water scarcity, which pose substantial risks to its population and economy (Ghosh et al., 2020; Singh et al., 2024). The state's socio-economic diversity presents challenges in ensuring equitable access to resources and addressing environmental injustices that disproportionately affect marginalised communities. Tari and her associates take the issue of justice in the policies but their analysis is also limited to groundwater justice only (Tari et al., 2024)

Despite these challenges, Uttar Pradesh has taken steps towards integrating environmental justice principles into its climate policies and governance frameworks. However, the extent to which these efforts translate into tangible benefits for marginalised communities remains a subject of critical inquiry. Issues of land tenure, access to clean water, and participation in decision-making processes continue to pose barriers

to achieving environmental justice in the state (Albus, 2011; Ranjan et al., 2020).

The vulnerability of marginalised sections of society has been described and backed with empirical research. In India, environmental justice issues are relatively new and not much focus has been accorded to this emerging concept. In India, most of the literature has grown on different dimensions of the National Action Plan on Climate Change but very less has been studied about the various State Plans on Climate Change. Further, very little focus has been given to the concept of environmental justice and its interplay with SAPCC. Given the comprehensive and inclusive nature and character of the SAPCC document, it is worth examining whether it is being implemented and executed in letter and spirit to meet its objectives. Given the vulnerability of Uttar Pradesh to climate change and the academic fraternity being devoid of significant research on the socio-economic impact and their interplay with climate change action plans in the context of environmental justice; it is timely and relevant to study the elements of State Action Plan on Climate Change and perception of people regarding their living experiences in the wake of climate change.

1.6 OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The present study has some focus areas to explore. This thesis aims to address these gaps by examining the following research objectives:

- To find out whether existing socio-economic inequalities exaggerate the impacts of climate change in the context of environmental justice.
- To assess the awareness level in different sections of society about the threat of climate change and its various components.

- To evaluate the components of the Climate Action Plan in the light of environmental justice.
- To assess the role of the Climate Action Plan in creating “ecological assets” for sustainable growth, resilience, and capacity-building at the local level.
- To suggest various public policy interventions and institutional, and capability-building measures for effective and efficient implementation of SAPCC.
- To find out the problems and challenges in pursuing sustainable and environmentally sensitive developmental practices as per the Climate Action Plan in the field area of the study.

1.7 HYPOTHESIS

Hypothesis in a study is of utmost importance as it is the basis of the research. In simple terms, a hypothesis can be defined as a logically assumed relationship between two or more variables expressed in the form of a testable statement. In the proposed study the Principal Hypothesis is “State Action Plan on Climate Change conform with the concept of Environmental Justice and Sustainability; however, marginalised sections of society suffer disproportionately from climate change”

The issues of climate change action plan and sustainability are multi-dimensional, inter-sectional, and multi-sectoral. So, the hypothesis is also multi-dimensional multi-faceted, and complex. For examining different variables and dimensions of this hypothesis, it would be feasible to study it under the following subsidiary hypothesis:

1. The State Action Plan on Climate Change in Uttar Pradesh is inclusive, comprehensive, and just.

2. *The increased visibility of climate change in the form of extreme weather patterns is affecting socio-economic determinants of health, livelihood, and habitat of people in Uttar Pradesh.*
3. *Climate change vulnerability affects marginalised sections of society disproportionately in terms of their contribution to the problem.*
4. *Community management of locally available or created 'ecological assets' bases on their traditional knowledge and occupational practices leads to resilience and capacity-building.*
5. *There are challenges and prospects in form of socio-cultural practices, economic constraints and lack of state-of-the-art technologies towards attaining environmental justice*

1.8 SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

Uttar Pradesh is the most populous state in India, with a population of over 200 million people. The state is also one of the most affected states by climate change, with rising temperatures, changing precipitation patterns, and increased frequency of extreme weather events such as floods and droughts. this thesis seeks to contribute to the academic discourse on climate action and environmental justice by examining their intersection in Uttar Pradesh, India. By critically evaluating current SAPCC and practices, the study aims to generate actionable insights that can inform policymakers, researchers, and practitioners working towards a more just and inclusive approach to climate governance. Through empirical research and theoretical analysis, the thesis endeavours to advance knowledge and practical solutions that promote equity, sustainability, and resilience in the face of climate change.

The research seeks to study the climate action plan of the state of Uttar

Pradesh within the principles of climate justice framework. The significance of this study lies in its potential to contribute to the examination of the climate action plan for Uttar Pradesh and in understanding the lived experiences of various sections of society concerning issues of climate change and its impact on their lives and livelihoods. It would serve to set the stage for a comprehensive analysis of the intersection of climate action and environmental justice in the context of sustainable development.

It highlights the importance of integrating environmental justice into climate action plans, referencing the convergence of urban sustainability, climate resilience, and development as crucial for guiding public policies toward a sustainable future (Rosa et al., 2024). The study further tries to understand and examine the lived experiences of the people of Uttar Pradesh, the most populous state in India. Additionally, the study discusses the relevance of incorporating an environmental justice framework into sustainable growth as it guides addressing injustices in human-environmental relationships, particularly for disadvantaged communities (Lee & Jamal, 2008). The study provides an opportunity to assess the effectiveness of other flagship programmes run by the central government and the state government.

The thesis then delves into the theoretical underpinnings of equity and environmental justice, clarifying their conceptual differences and implications for environmental ethics and policy-making. This theoretical backdrop would be essential for understanding the complexities of implementing climate action plans that are just and equitable. The thesis includes analysing the Uttar Pradesh State Action Plan on Climate Change 2021-2030 for its approach to sustainability and justice,

examining the state's climate action initiatives, and evaluating the challenges and opportunities present in the state to achieve mitigation goals. The study will help contribute to the discourse on democracy, social justice, and identity politics in the context of environmental governance in Uttar Pradesh.

Therefore, the study will provide insights and ground-level realities to various stakeholders engaged in designing, formulating, implementing, and evaluating the programmes/schemes under the broader guiding principles of Climate Action Plans. The policymakers, administrative machinery, and various non-state actors like NGOs, civil society organizations, charity/philanthropic organizations, and climate activists are likely to benefit from this study. This study will help contribute to the extension of the frontiers of learning, exploration, and examination of public policies. This will contribute to enhancing the understanding of the interplay of justice issues with climate change and its associated phenomena to the students, researchers, and readers interested in the studies of environment, justice, ethics, public policy, administrative studies, developmental economics, political science, sociology, and gender studies.

1.9 STRUCTURE OF THE THESIS

The thesis presents a study of interactions between climate actions and justice. For clarity, it has been divided into six chapters. The present first chapter, Introduction, gives a brief overview of the thesis. It covers the background of the topic, the basic understanding of the making of the phenomenon of climate change, and its scientific and socioeconomic factors. Further, the chapter discusses the uneven contributions and impacts of climate change and global warming globally as well as

nationally highlighting the disproportionate high adverse impacts on poor nations and disadvantaged sections of society. In this context, the chapter further discusses the issue of justice in short. The chapter also gives a brief description of the limitations of the mainstream approach to climate actions given the structural issues of production and consumption and ideological hegemony in the present world economic system. The objectives, hypothesis, and significance of the study make up the next sections of the present chapter.

The second chapter '*Universe of Study and Research Methodology*' has been divided into parts. Part A deals with the universe of the study and Part B describes the research methodology used in the present study. Part A deals with the general description of the state of Uttar Pradesh in the first section. Further, this chapter describes the conceptual understanding of 'vulnerability' and 'risk' for understanding the climate vulnerability of the universe in the study. The climate vulnerability of Uttar Pradesh has been mentioned in the next section in terms of its sensitivity to hazards, biophysical, and socio-economic factors. The next section deals with the selected districts in which case studies were undertaken. A brief description of the districts, their climate vulnerabilities, and the blocks and villages of the sample have been mentioned. Part B of the chapter provides a brief description of the research methodology used in this thesis. This part explains the grounds for selecting districts, blocks, and village panchayats for the study. Further, this part also describes the statistical tools used for the analysis of the data and other related issues.

Chapter 3 '*Climate Actions: Global, National, and Sub-National*' describes the climate actions undertaken at different levels. The first section deals with climate actions undertaken at the global level. It

includes a brief description of the evolution of the global climate regime, its importance, and the principles guiding the treaties, conventions, and summits of global climate governance. The next section describes the national climate agenda including its three dimensions i.e. advocacy, alliance, and actions. India's climate stands on the global stage, and its impressive leadership in taking meaningful actions to deal with climate change threats has been described in brief. The last section of the chapter concerns the sub-national or state-level actions. It deals with the State Action Plan on Climate Change of Uttar Pradesh and its various missions. It also deals with the various programmes, policies, and projects to make the state a hub of green and clean energy.

Chapter 4 deals with the concept of 'justice' in the environmental framework. This chapter, '*Environmental Justice and Climate Justice: A Conceptual Framework*' talks about the concepts of environmental justice and climate justice in a theoretical framework. Various approaches to environmental justice i.e. distributive, procedural, capability, etc have been discussed to have a clear understanding of the concepts. Further, the link between environmental and climate justice has been established. Climate justice has been discussed as the extension of the broader and umbrella concept of environmental justice only. The chapter also discusses in brief the concept of non-ideal justice in search of pragmatic solutions to the problem of climate change when the ideal theories of justice become contentious and yield disruptions in the global climate governance framework.

Chapter 5 deals with the analysis of the data and evaluation of the UP SAPCC. This chapter covers the analysis of the climate action plan of the state of Uttar Pradesh and various hypotheses undertaken for the study

are put to test in the light of the outcomes of the analysis of data collected from the selected districts of Uttar Pradesh. The Interpretation and discussion of collected data have been mentioned in the chapter. Analysis of the data has been made by applying different statistical tools and methods. The chapter also presents the relationship between dependent and independent variables in various tables and pictorial and graphical presentations.

The last chapter presents the Findings and Conclusion. Further it also mentions challenges, and suggestions deriving from the present study. The chapter concludes the main arguments and findings of the study. The chapter also mentions the limitations of the study and further gives some suggestions for future research to the academicians, students, and research scholars.

CHAPTER – II

THE UNIVERSE OF STUDY AND METHODOLOGY

2.1 OVERVIEW OF UTTAR PRADESH

2.1.1 Introduction

Uttar Pradesh is one of the largest states of India with the highest population in the country. Its geographical area North to South extends from Saharanpur to Sonbhadra and East to West from Ballia to Baghpat. It covers around 240,928 sq km (UP Arthik Smiksha) of area and occupies fourth position in terms of areas in the country. Geographically it is located within the Gangetic plains between 23°52'N and 31°28'N latitudes and 77°3' and 84°39'E longitudes. It is the most populous state of India with around 19.98 Cr. people living here (Census 2011). The rural population of the state comprises a major chunk with around 15.53 Crores and the rest of the people live in the urban areas of the state. The population density of the state is 829 people per sq. km. The literacy rate of the state is quite low as compared to that of other states of India with 67.7 % of people literate in total. Since Uttar Pradesh is a vast state in itself, it requires a large number of administrative machinery for its smooth functioning. For administering such a large state, it has been divided into different units to ensure that every portion of the state gets proper checks under the administrative heads of the respective area. Uttar Pradesh is divided into 18 administrative divisions and 75 districts, 351 tehsils, 951 towns, 826 development blocks, 58,189 gram panchayats, and 1,06,774 villages (UPDES). On the other hand, the massive population of the state elects a maximum number of representatives in the country which is 80 members of parliament and 403 members of the legislative

assembly as their representatives to give bright colours to the canvas of a vibrant democracy.

The vastness of Uttar Pradesh also reflects the diversity of religion, sects, caste, traditions, and language. For instance, the state presents linguistic diversity, though Hindi and Urdu are the first and second official languages of the state, Punjabi is also spoken by a large portion of people. The linguistic diversity even in the Hindi language gives a glimpse of its dynamic and vibrant cultural diversity as different dialects of Hindi are spoken in different regions of the state. Braj Bhasha is spoken in the western parts of the state, Awadhi in the central part, Bundeli and Bagheli in the south, and Bhojpuri in the east.

Figure: 2.1 Political Map of the state of Uttar Pradesh.

Source: mapsofindia.com

The state of Uttar Pradesh borders Himachal Pradesh and Uttarakhand in the north, Haryana, Delhi, and Rajasthan in the west, Madhya Pradesh and Chhattisgarh in the south, and Bihar and Jharkhand in the east. Uttar Pradesh also forms an international border with Nepal in the north. Two of the most famous rivers of India, the Ganga and the Yamuna flow through the state and merge in the pious city of Prayagraj and they along with other rivers irrigate the agricultural plains of Uttar Pradesh giving a boost to the agro-economy of the state since ancient times and making it one of the most fertile lands of the country. Several other major and minor rivers also flow along which many cities are located. Lucknow, the capital of Uttar Pradesh is situated on the banks of river Gomati. Ghaghra, Chambal, Ken, Betwa, Saryu, and Sharda are some other rivers flowing through the heartland of U.P.

2.1.2 THE ECONOMY OF U.P.

The economy of Uttar Pradesh plays a vital role in the growth of the country as it is the second biggest economy in India with an estimated gross state domestic product (GSDP) to be Rs. 24.39 trillion (US\$ 295.48 billion) in 2023-24 after Maharashtra. The major part of the economy is dependent on agriculture. Some other sectors of the economy include services, industries, and tourism. This thesis concerns climate action plan, therefore, only the relevant sector of the economy is being mentioned here briefly to have a basic understanding of Uttar Pradesh's economy and climate interactions.

Uttar Pradesh is a significant state in terms of agriculture for the country, with almost 22.94% of the total Gross State Value Added (GSVA) in 2020-21 generated from agriculture and its allied activities. It was estimated to be Rs. 2,24,69,159 lakh during 2020-21. This sector engages

about two-thirds of the manpower of the state. It is an agro-climatically diverse state, the farmers of the state produce several food crops and cash crops including wheat, rice, sugarcane, millets, lentils, etc. The agricultural sector of the U.P. is dependent on monsoon for crop production. As per the data of the 'RBI Handbook of Statistics on Indian States' the state produces the largest quantity of food grain which stands at 57,245.7 thousand tonnes in the country and has strategic significance in meeting the food security of the country (RBI Handbook of Statistics, 2023a; Singh et al., 2021).

2.1.3 AGRO-CLIMATIC ZONES OF UTTAR PRADESH

Uttar Pradesh is full of diversity also being diverse in agro-climatic zones which provide a diverse profile of crops to grow in different regions of the state. 9 agro-climatic zones are found in Uttar Pradesh which are the Bhabar and Tarai plains, Western Plains, Mid-western plains, South-western semi-arid plains, central plains, Bundelkhand zone, north-eastern plain zone, eastern plains, Vindhyan zone. A handsome amount of crop production is grown in the western part of the U.P. which is around 50% of the total agricultural output of the state as it is well equipped with water availability being situated in the lap of the Ganga and Yamuna rivers. Next in the line are the eastern parts of the U.P. producing around 28% of the total crop production and the Bundelkhand region produces around 4% of the state's total agricultural output.

Figure 2.2: Agro-Climatic Zones of Uttar Pradesh

Source: Research Gate

The geographical characteristics like type of soil, elevation, rocks nature, weather conditions, etc. make the state of Uttar Pradesh a diverse and dynamic state for different natural resources availability, extraction, utilization, and crops to be grown. Different crops are being sown in these diverse agri-climatic zones. On the one hand, the Western Plains Zone is known for its extensive agricultural activities and higher production, on the other hand, the Vindhayan Zone is very rich in natural resources and is known for its minerals.

The state is the largest producer of sugarcane in the country with the production of 44.50% of the national production of sugarcane in 2020-21(UPDES). The sugar sector is also important for its being an important

employer to the population. Further, to make U.P. a bio-energy hub, the role of this sector is crucial as it supplies ingredients for the production of 'ethanol' and provides Agri-waste to bio-energy industries (UP Bio-Energy Policy, 2022). Horticulture is another critical sector that provides higher productivity and gainful employment opportunities. It produces the highest horticultural products in the country. Animal Husbandry and Dairy farming along with fisheries provide crucial primary and secondary sources of income to most of the rural population in UP. These sub-sectors provide supplementary income sources to small and marginal farmers. UP can boast of having the largest number of livestock in India and it ranks number one and two in milk and meat production with 33,006 thousand tonnes and 1128 thousand tonnes respectively for FY 2021-22 (RBI Handbook of Statistics, 2023b). Fisheries provide not only a nutritious food option to the rural poor but also it is an important sub-sector for income and employment generation. UP is known for its freshwater fish landings. Inland fish production grows continuously in the state. Hardoi and Balrampur have the first and second place in the water spread area in the state (UP SAPCC 2.0, 2023).

The manufacturing sector is not very developed in the form of manufacturing hubs/clusters of big manufacturing units engaged in scale production in the state. However, the manufacturing sector consists of several small-scale industries in the state with various regional dimensions (UP SAPCC 1.0, 2014). Despite not being industrialized in comparison to the southern and western states of India, the secondary sector accounts for more than the contribution of the primary sector in the state's economy with a 26.74% share (Uttar Pradesh Arthik Samiksha, 2022-23, p.3).

2.2 CLIMATE VULNERABILITY

To understand the concept of climate vulnerability, its associated concepts and terms need to be studied. Some of the associated concepts that make the core of vulnerability are as follows:

2.2.1 HAZARD:

A hazard is a climate-induced or related physical event. It may not always be an extreme weather phenomenon, but it could be a slow process or trend, such as rainy days or dry spells. A hazard may be defined as “a serious disruption of the functioning of a community or a society causing widespread human, material, economic or environmental losses which exceed the ability of the affected community or society to cope using its own resources”; and the main characteristics of hazards are magnitude, duration, geographical extent, spatial dispersion, speed of onset, and temporal dimensions (Schneiderbauer and Ehrlich, 2004).

2.2.2 EXPOSURE:

Exposure refers to the presence of elements in the area of hazard events' occurrence (UNISDR, 2004). In simple words, it is the presence of vital resources in those areas where hazards occur. It means if the human population or economic resources are not present or exposed to dangerous zones, the issue of disaster risk would not arise. It might be possible that a particular area is exposed to hazards but not vulnerable. In the process of developing resilient systems or infrastructure, vulnerability is reduced. It means “either their sensitivity to a certain level of hazards or exposures have reduced or their adaptive capacity has increased or both” (UP SAPCC 2.0, p.78). Thus, vulnerability has two crucial elements (1) sensitivity, and (2) adaptive capacity.

2.2.3 MEANING OF VULNERABILITY

The concept of vulnerability depends on several determinants and their interactions with one another. Climatic vulnerabilities are multidimensional and interwoven making a complex web of interactions and interdependence. These determinants of vulnerability vary from one place to another, across sectors and dimensions. In general, vulnerability is the product of sensitivity and adaptive capacity. It can be expressed in the equation in the following manner:

$$\textit{Vulnerability} = F (\textit{Sensitivity}, \textit{Adaptive Capacity})$$

Vulnerability measurement takes into account environmental, economic, and social marginality (Wisner, 2013). The concept of vulnerability may mean different things to different people in different contexts. For instance, social scientists view vulnerability as a set of socioeconomic determinants that affect people's ability to cope with stresses and changes (Allen, 2003), while climate scientists see vulnerability in terms of the likeliness of occurrence of climate-induced and weather events and their impact on the system (Nicholls et al., 1999).

Biophysical and Social vulnerability: The definitions of climatic vulnerability may be categorised into two broad categories. First, it may be studied in terms of potential damage or loss caused to a system by a climate-induced event over a hazard (Jones and Boer, 2003). The second approach can be understood as a state of the system that exists before the occurrence of a hazard event (Allen, 2003). The first approach is based on the measurement or assessment of climate-related events or hazards and their potential impact in which the role of humans or communities in dealing with the outcomes of hazards is often neglected. This understanding of vulnerability may be referred to as "*physical or*

biophysical vulnerability”. Another approach views vulnerability in terms of a state i.e. internal state of a system, focuses on the structural aspects of a system (human societies and communities) that are susceptible to the caused damage by climate-induced events (Allen, 2003; Brooks, 2003). This view of vulnerability may be termed “*social vulnerability*” which includes those conditions present in the society or community i.e. internal characteristics that are independent of the natural hazard (Adger, 1999; Adger and Kelly, 1999). The IPCC AR 3 describes vulnerability as

“The degree to which a system is susceptible to, or unable to cope with, adverse effects of climate change, including climate variability and extremes. Vulnerability is a function of the character, magnitude, and rate of climate variation to which a system is exposed, its sensitivity, and its adaptive capacity.” (IPCC, 2001, p. 995).

Thus, vulnerability in short is “*the propensity or predisposition to be adversely affected*” as per the definition of IPCC. The concept of vulnerability encompasses various elements of concepts such as ‘*sensitivity*’ or ‘*susceptibility*’ to loss or harm and ‘*adaptive capacity*’ to cope with challenges or hazards. Sensitivity refers to the “degree to which a system or species is affected, either adversely or beneficially by climate variability or change”. Sensitivity may refer to those factors that affect the result of hazards. Further, ‘adaptive capacity’ means “the ability of systems, institutions, humans, and other organisms to adjust to potential damage, to take advantage of opportunities, or to respond to consequences” (UP SAPCC 2.0, p.78).

Vulnerability arising out of climate-induced events or hazards has been depicted by UP SAPCC 1.0 in a three-dimensional framework. These

three dimensions of vulnerability include:

- 1) Climate Sensitivity,
- 2) Bio-physical, and
- 3) Socio-economic.

Climate sensitivity includes temperature, precipitation, etc climatic events, and their likelihood and severity or intensity; bio-physical factors pertain to the soil, agriculture, water, forest, and biodiversity; and socio-economic factors are associated with social groups, infrastructure, workforce, and human development.

Figure 2.3: Vulnerability Analysis Framework

Source: Author's representation based on SAPCC 1.0 Vulnerability Analysis Framework

2.2.4 RISK ASSESSMENT

IPCC, in its AR 5, introduced the concept of 'risk.' Risk in climate change is assessed when the three main components—Hazard, Vulnerability, and Exposure—are taken together. Climate vulnerability

requires serious assessments to learn solutions and practices, leading to the creation of policies that can reduce the vulnerability of areas. The government of Uttar Pradesh studies the vulnerabilities of seven missions in all the districts of the U.P. under UPSAPCC.

$$\text{Risk} = F(\text{Hazard}, \text{Exposure}, \text{Vulnerability})$$

Therefore, the risk or the impact of extreme or non-extreme weather events or climate-related events depends strongly on the level of exposure of the population or economic resources to these events and their vulnerability. IPCC AR 5 in its ‘Risk Management Framework’ presents the interrelationship and interaction among the different components and dimensions of ‘risk’ or impact of climatic events. Figure 2.4 represents the framework adopted in the assessment of risk by IPCC in its assessment.

Figure 2.4: IPCC AR 5 Risk Management Framework

Source: IPCC AR 5

The risk is a combination of hazard vulnerability and exposure. Hazard refers to the destructive impacts on an area due to extreme climatic events. Exposure refers to those areas where hazards may occur. Vulnerability consists of two elements – sensitivity and adaptive capacity.

The vulnerability of a place can be reduced by reducing the sensitivity of the place or increasing its adaptive capacity.

2.3 CLIMATE VULNERABILITY OF UTTAR PRADESH

In this section of the chapter, I tried to underline the climatic vulnerability of the state of Uttar Pradesh in terms of reference to the analysis discussed above. The climatic sensitivity, bio-physical, and socioeconomic factors make Uttar Pradesh a state of high vulnerability. The climate change scenario projections as used in various scientific studies including the IPCC Reports when applied to the vulnerability factors of Uttar Pradesh, the risks associated with the phenomenon of climate change tend to be very pathetic as mentioned in UP SAPCC 1.0 and UP SAPCC 2.0 documents.

The climatic conditions of Uttar Pradesh are sub-tropical monsoon with dry winters and hot summers. The western parts of the U.P. experience a hot semi-arid climate. The average temperature in the state hovers between 12.5-17.5⁰C in winter to 27.5-32.5⁰C in the summer months of May and June. The variation in the temperature depends on the weather conditions and elevation of the places. The maximum temperature exceeds this range and places in Uttar Pradesh witness the temperature exceeding 45⁰ C. There is a great variation in the average temperature across the districts of UP due to its vast geographical area, varied elevation, and different weather phenomena. Lalitpur district in Bundelkhand region records the highest average maximum temperature at 32.74⁰ C, on the other hand, the lowest average maximum temperature was recorded in the district of Bijnor at 26.75⁰ C. Similarly, the highest average minimum temperature was recorded in the district of Amethi at 19.24⁰ C, while the lowest average minimum temperature was again in

Lalitpur district at 14.22⁰ C (UP SAPCC 2.0, 2023, p.64). This reflects the substantial variation in the temperature in the state across the regions and seasons. The analysis of temperature data by UP SAPCC reveals that during the period between 1980 and 2019, Jhansi and Agra witnessed the maximum no. of 'extreme heat days' (when the temperature $\geq 45^{\circ}$ C) stood at 163 days and 159 days respectively.

The average annual rainfall received by U.P. during the period 1980-2019 was around 896.51 mm. The highest amount of rainfall received was 1188.69 mm in 1983 while the lowest was 611.79 mm in 1997 (UP SAPCC 2.0, 2023). The seasons in U.P. are defined by IMD which states as winter season comprising the months of January and February, pre-monsoon season comprising the months of March, April, and May, Monsoon covering the months of June, July, August, and September, post-monsoon season covering October, November, and December. There is a lot of variation in the amount of precipitation received by different locations in the state. District-wise analysis shows that during the said period (1980-2019), Maharajganj received the maximum annual precipitation at 1133 mm followed by Sant Kabir Nagar at 1095 mm. The Western districts are generally dry in comparison to the eastern districts of the state. As per the 'Summary of Climate Hazards and Vulnerability Atlas of India' of the Indian Meteorological Department, Uttar Pradesh has the second largest number of districts having 'high' and 'very high' vulnerability to drought (IMD).

From an ecological perspective, water resources are the most important components in any state. Water resources of Uttar Pradesh are found to be about 179 BCM (groundwater and surface), however, the total precipitation the state receives is about 228.28 BCM, and the usable

water is only 118.47 BCM (UP State Water Policy, 2020). Water is a vital natural resource that is finite and unevenly distributed on temporal and spatial dimensions. The Vastness of UP makes it more vulnerable to the management of water as some areas are regularly reeling under recurrent floods while others are facing the brunt of the drought. Currently, about 92.2 % of water is being used for irrigation; 5.2 % for domestic purposes; and industrial and commercial activities account for about 2.6% of water utilization. Though, UP ranks first in replenishable groundwater resources in the country, out of a total of 833 assessment units for groundwater assessment it has 91 ‘overexploited’, 48 ‘critical’, and 151 ‘semi-critical’ units (CWC, 2019). Thus, it is clear that despite having enough water resources, UP faces challenges like droughts, floods, depletion of groundwater, water contamination, etc.

Energy consumption is an important component of the development process. The government of Uttar Pradesh is aspiring to be a \$1 trillion economy in a few years. To realize this aspirational goal, its energy consumption has to be increased substantially. Uttar Pradesh is an energy-poor state with a per capita energy consumption of just 629 kWh in 2019-20 (CEA, 2021). Thermal-based energy generation occupies the largest share of energy production sources in Uttar Pradesh. Besides, thermal power, hydroelectric, and nuclear energy are the other sources of energy generation. New and Renewable energy sources are also gaining importance in the energy mix of UP.

Figure 2.5 Percentage distribution of various energy sources in total power installed capacity of Uttar Pradesh

Source: SAPCC 2.0

As far as the consumption pattern is concerned in Uttar Pradesh, the largest energy demand comes from domestic customers (52%), while the industrial and commercial account for 38 % and 9% respectively, and the rest 1% is utilized in street lighting etc.

According to the UP SAPCC 2.0 when a vulnerability assessment was made by using the methodology of IPCC AR 5 at the district level on two indicators-sensitivity and adaptive capacity- out of 75 districts 63 districts fell under ‘moderate’ to ‘very high’ categories of vulnerability (UP SAPCC 2.0, p. 149).

Uttar Pradesh having 19.98 crore people as per census of 2011, is the most populous state of India. It is one of the underdeveloped states in India as most of the socio-economic indicators like literacy rate, per capita income, maternal mortality rate, infant mortality rate, etc. hover at lower ends. The Human Development Index (HDI) for the state is 0.592

which is lower than the national average of 0.672 as per the report of the Centre for Economic Data & Analysis (CEDA, 2021). Uttar Pradesh is mostly an agrarian state with a low level of urbanization (22%) and a low level of industrialization.

The agriculture sector employs about two-thirds of the workforce in the state. Agriculture not only engages most of the population but also generates about 1/3rd income of the state (UP SAPCC 1.0). As discussed in Chapter 1, agriculture is the most vulnerable sector to the consequences of changes in weather patterns or climate change. There are numerous studies across the globe to establish the link between the phenomenon of climate change and adverse impacts on the agriculture sectors. Further, the agriculture sector in India including Uttar Pradesh heavily dependent on the phenomenon of Monsoon. Any change in the factors that have capacities to tend to the changes in the mechanisms of Monsoon directly affects the amount and intensity along with the durability of precipitation and thereby the yields in the agriculture sector. Further, any disruption in weather patterns be it unseasonal rainfall, storms, heavy rainfall, and subsequent flood, drought, or land degradation all affect agriculture first and foremost. Indian agriculture is very sensitive to weather patterns, especially monsoon. Uttar Pradesh being an agriculture-based economy is also sensitive to these risk factors arising out of climate change.

Among the above-mentioned factors, social groups are of significant importance to the state of Uttar Pradesh owing to caste and identity-based entitlements of resources and benefits. The role of these social identities generally determines the distribution of resources and benefits of governmental interventions through various schemes and programmes. Thus, the socioeconomically vulnerable groups are the most victims of

environmental hazards and risks. These social and cultural factors intersect with the natural phenomena of weather and climate and create a complex web that affects the vulnerability in terms of exposure and resilience and prevents integrated and planned interventions based on inclusively and democratically.

Uttar Pradesh is vulnerable to different environmental hazards and particularly to climate change owing to its vast number of poor people, low level of development, agrarian economy, and agro-climatic regions ranging from flood-prone Tarai region and Himalayan rivers to drought-prone areas of Bundelkhand region. Furthermore, the state is very vulnerable on account of health parameters. Given its huge population, the number of health facilities is not very impressive. Epidemics are very frequent in different parts of Uttar Pradesh in one form or another. Uttar Pradesh reported, “47,507 cases of acute encephalitis syndrome (AES) from 2005 to 2018, with yearly fluctuations, average case fatality rate of AES was 17.49% with highest in 2005 (24.76%) and lowest in 2018 (8%)” (Kaithal, 2021).

2.4 INTRODUCTION AND CLIMATE VULNERABILITY OF SELECTED DISTRICTS

Four districts have been selected for conducting the present study to examine the different objectives of this thesis. The districts have been selected on the basis of the “Composite Vulnerability Index” as calculated in the UP SAPCC 2.0. The rationale for selecting these districts is given in the next section of the ‘methodology’ of this chapter.

2.4.1 BAHARAICH

Bahraich is a district situated in the North-Eastern part of the state. The border of India and Nepal is known as the Tarai region and it is rich in

forests and water resources as several rivers emanating from Nepal's hills flow to this region. Bahraich district lies in this region and it forms the international border with Nepal. In the administrative setup, it falls under the jurisdiction of Devipatan Division. Geographically it is situated between 28.24 to 27.4 degrees north latitude and 81.65 to 81.3 degrees eastern longitude. Its geographical area as per the district's official website is 4696.8 sq. km and it comprises about 32% of the Devipatan Division. It borders with Gonda and Shrawasti on the eastern side; Kheri on the West; Barabanki and Sitapur on the South; and its northern part is an international border with Nepal. The northern part is very rich in biodiversity and dense natural forests with a lot of flora and fauna diversity exists there. The main forest areas of the district are *Chakia*, *Mihinpurva*, *Sujauli*, *Bichia* & *Baghauri*, etc. Saryu/ Sarju and Ghaghra are the main rivers that flow into the district.

Figure 2.6: Map of Bahraich District

Source: mapsofindia.com

On the climatic vulnerability account, the district holds a significant place due to its various vulnerabilities, natural and socio-economic, interacting with one another. The district is affected mostly by recurrent floods caused by the mighty rivers of Ghaghra and Saryu and other small rivers flowing from the Tarai region of Indo-Nepal. Besides floods, fires, and earthquakes also make this region vulnerable to natural risks. These natural hazards cost the district hundreds of crores annually. The recurring floods, fires, and droughts have been indicators of the increased vulnerabilities and the inadequacy of measures taken by different agencies and governments. The district's official website states “The emerging context is an increase in the frequency of disasters, their escalating cost, rising levels of vulnerability, narrowing differences between natural & man made disasters amidst an increasingly fragile environment. This underscores the dire need for a holistic approach to dovetail mitigation efforts with development programs in the State”.

The socioeconomic indicators of the district are not very impressive, as per the official data from the 2011 census. The population density of the district is 734.2 per sq. km., the share of scheduled caste and scheduled tribe population is 15.76%; and a majority of the population to the tune of 84.06% is engaged in agricultural activities, and the literacy rate for the district is only 47.80% (District Sankhikiya Patrika- Bahraich, 2023). The district has been divided into 14 administrative blocks as mentioned below:

- | | | |
|---------------|--------------------|-------------|
| 1. Mihipurwa | 2. Nawabganj | 3. Balha |
| 4. Shivpur | 5. Risiya | 6. Chitaura |
| 7. Payagpur | 8. Vishveshwarganj | 9. Mahsi |
| 10. Tajwapur | 11. Farakhpur | 12. Huzurpu |
| 13. Kesarganj | 14. Jarwal. | |

As per the methodology adopted in this thesis, out of 14 blocks, one block was selected for the conducting empirical study. The block with the combined highest value for two criteria (percentage of scheduled caste/scheduled tribe population and percentage of workforce engaged in agriculture) was taken. On this account, the block of Mahasi with the maximum combined value of these two criteria was selected.

The sample was selected from both urban and rural areas. To cover the urban area, the city of Bahraich was taken and in the rural category, the Mahasi Block was taken into consideration as mentioned above. Four village panchayats and one city area were taken on a random selection basis. The four selected village panchayats in the Mahasi Block were:

1. Murawa
2. Rampurva Khurd
3. Chandpara
4. Persohana

2.4.2 LAKHIMPUR KHERI

Lakhimpur Kheri district is located in the northwestern region of Uttar Pradesh. It lies in the jurisdiction of Lucknow Division of Uttar Pradesh. This is the largest district in terms of geographical area in the state with an area of 7,680 sq. km. It is situated between 27.6⁰ to 28.6⁰ North latitude and 80.34⁰ to 81.30⁰ East longitude bordered by the districts of Bahraich to the east, Hardoi and Sitapur to the south, and Shahjahanpur and Pilibhit in the west. Its northern side forms an international border with Nepal. The district is characterized by its flat terrain and fertile soil, primarily suitable for agriculture (District Census Handbook, 2011).

District Lakhimpur Kheri is known for its '*Dudhwa National Park*', the only national park in the state of Uttar Pradesh. The northern part is very rich in biodiversity and dense natural forests. Kheri is home to a variety

of flora and fauna, including several species of birds and mammals. The district's biodiversity is largely influenced by its agricultural practices and changes in land use.

Demographical Profile of the District: The total population of the district as per census 2011 is 4,021,243. The main languages spoken in the districts are Hindi (Awadhi), Urdu, and Punjabi. The average literacy is 60.56 % with male literacy being 69.57 and female literacy standing at only 50.42 %. The population density is 524 persons per sq. km. The sex ratio of the district is 894 which is skewed in favour of the male population and it is low even to the state average of 912. The district is predominately rural with low urbanisation. The urban population is only 11.5 percent as against the 22.3 % average of the urban population in the state (District Survey Report, 2024).

The district consists of 7 tehsils and 15 blocks. The 15 administrative blocks as mentioned below:

- | | | |
|-----------------|--------------|----------------|
| 1. Lakhimpur | 2. Bhajam | 3. Mitauli |
| 4. Pasgawan | 5. Gola | 6. Bankeyganj |
| 7. Bijuwa | 8. Paliya | 9. Issanagar |
| 10. Dhaurahara | 11. Nakaha | 12. Phoolbehar |
| 13. Ramiyabehar | 14. Nighasan | 15. Mohammdi |

Figure 2.7: Map of Lakhimpur Kheri

Source: mapofIndia.com

Topography and Soil: The topography of Kheri is predominantly plain, with the Gomti River flowing along its western boundary. Other important rivers are Ghaghara, Saryu, Sharda, etc. The soil in the district varies from alluvial to clayey, which supports a variety of crops, including wheat, rice, and sugarcane.

Water Resources: The district soil consists mainly of 'fine to coarse sand, gravel, silt, clay and kankers' of quaternary age. The district has several small rivers and streams, with groundwater being a crucial resource for irrigation. However, the over-extraction of groundwater has led to declining water tables, posing a significant challenge to agriculture and drinking water supply (Central Ground Water Board, 2018).

Economic Activities

Agriculture: Agriculture is the backbone of Kheri's economy, with nearly 70% of the population engaged in farming. Major crops include wheat, rice, sugarcane, and pulses, contributing to the district's economy and food security (Department of Agriculture, Uttar Pradesh, Livestock rearing is also prevalent, providing additional income sources for many families. Cattle, buffaloes, and goats are commonly raised, and dairy farming has shown potential as a sustainable livelihood option. Bajaj Hindustan Ltd. Gola and Palia are the main industrial units in the districts apart from other small-scale industries.

Employment and Livelihoods: Despite the agrarian economy, unemployment rates remain high, particularly among youth. The lack of industrial development and job opportunities has led to significant out-migration seeking employment.

Climatic Vulnerability

Kheri experiences a subtropical climate characterized by hot summers, cold winters, and a monsoon season. The average annual rainfall is around 1,000 mm, predominantly occurring between June and September about 86 %, and the rest 14% during the non-monsoon period (Central Groundwater Board, 2013).

Kheri is particularly vulnerable to climate change, with rising temperatures, erratic rainfall patterns, and increased frequency of extreme weather events such as floods and droughts. These changes threaten agricultural productivity, water availability, and biodiversity (IPCC, 2019).

Given its dependence on agriculture, Kheri faces significant risks from climate variability. Crop yields have been adversely affected by changing weather conditions, which may lead to food insecurity and economic instability threats. Smallholder farmers, who constitute the majority, are especially vulnerable due to limited adaptive capacity. The over-extraction of groundwater and changing rainfall patterns present a dire scenario for water security in Kheri. Groundwater depletion has been reported at alarming rates, threatening both agricultural and drinking water supplies (Central Ground Water Board, 2018). The ability to adapt and manage water resources effectively is critical for the district's sustainability.

As per the methodology adopted in this thesis, out of 15 blocks, one block was selected for the conducting empirical study. The block with the combined highest value for two criteria (percentage of scheduled caste/scheduled tribe population and percentage of workforce engaged in agriculture) was taken. On this account, the block of Mitauli with

the maximum combined value of these two criteria was selected.

The sample was selected from both urban and rural areas. To cover the urban area, the city of Lakhimpur Kheri was taken and in the rural category, the Mitauli Block was taken into consideration as mentioned above. Four village panchayats and one city area were taken on a random selection basis. The four selected village panchayats in the Mitauli Block were:

- | | |
|-----------------------|-------------|
| 1. Bhirwa Grant | 2. Mainhann |
| 3. Grant Inayat Chief | 4. Sinduria |

2.4.3 MAHOBA

Mahoba is a small district situated in the Bundelkhand region in south southwestern part of the state. It is a district under the jurisdiction of the *Chitrakoot Division* of the state of Uttar Pradesh. The name Mahoba has been derived from '*Mahotsav Nagar*' meaning the city of great festivals. Occupying an area of 2,884 sq. km, it is situated between 25.03⁰ to 25.38⁰ North latitude and 79.24⁰ to 79.10⁰ East longitude. The district borders Hamirpur on the north, Banda on the east, Chhatarpur district of Madhya Pradesh on the south, and Jhansi on the west. River Dhasan forms the boundary of Mahoba with Jhansi on the western border. The district is one of the most water-stressed districts in the state. The district is known for its Granite of Precambrian age. Kirbai block is famous for granite extraction. Apart from this Mahoba city has a specific place in the cultural and political history of India. The city is well known for its valour, courage, and patriotism. The legend of the great warrior *Allah, Udal*, and their brothers *Brahma and Malkhan* etc. inspires innumerable persons with honor and sacrifice. The folk of '*Alaha Khand*' composed by poet *Jagnik Rao*, is performed even today in the whole of north India

with devotion and enthusiasm. In the cultural circle, the city of Mahoba is known as the gateway of the Khajuraho tourist circle. It is also a place of several religious sites. Apart from the famous ‘*Surya Temple*’ and several other *Hindu* religious temples and sites, it is also known for the religious places of *Jainism*. The *Charkhari Estate* is a famous place known for its ponds. The estate was ruled by *Raja Ratan Singh* during the British period.

Figure 2.9: Map of Mahoba

Source: <https://www.mapsofindia.com/maps/uttarpradesh/districts/mahoba.html>

Demographical profile of Mahoba

As per the census of 2011 released by the Directorate of Census Operations in Uttar Pradesh, the total population of Mahoba is 875,958. Out of this, the male population is 466,358 whereas the female population is 409,600. Out of the total Mahoba population, 21.16 percent of people live in urban areas. The rest population resides in rural areas. The sex

ratio of the district is 878 per 1000 males. The population density of the district is 279 people per sq. km. About 78.84% of the population live in rural regions of the district while only 21.16 % live in urban regions. The average literacy rate is 65.27% with a male literacy rate of 75.83% and a female literacy rate of 53.22%. The main language that people use commonly is Hindi.

Topography and Soil: The entire area of Mahoba is an alluvial plain, with a gentle slope from northwest to southeast. The soil in this district is produced by the weathering of granites. Clayey and loamy soil is dominant here. Tomato, brinjal, guava, and lime are the main horticultural crops grown here. Other than this some kharif crops like groundnut, urad, moong, etc along with some rabi crops like mustard, wheat, and barley are also cultivated in Mahoba. The share of rabi crop is the maximum in the total crop shown in the district. As the share of groundwater is increasing, the crop yield and cash crops are also showing growth.

Water Resources: Water is said to be the basis of life on the planet. Though there is plenty of water available on the Earth, the usable and available water is limited and that too is unevenly distributed spatially and temporally. Mahoba district lies in the water-stressed region of Bundelkhand which is known for its droughts and water deficit situation. The average rainfall in the Mahoba district is 997 mm out of which about 89% takes place in the Monsoon period and the rest in the non-monsoon period.

The district is drained by some rivers namely Dhasan, Birma, Chadarwal, Urmil, and Arjun. The Birma River divides the district into two halves east and west. River Dhasan and Urmil originate from the Vindhyan.

Several canals serve the purpose of irrigating the land of Mahoba. However, due to its topography and water deficit conditions, the district continues to remain a water-stressed district. Apart from rivers and canals, the major sources of water and irrigation are ponds and groundwater. Technology made it affordable and easy to dig the borewell, though it is harder than the normal soil, the share of water resources from groundwater has increased substantially. As per the report, the share of groundwater in irrigation increased from 30% to 60% in the last twenty years period from 1994 to 2015 (Central Ground Water Report, 2019).

Economy: The economy of the district is mainly agrarian. Most of the people are engaged in the agricultural and allied sector activities. The main agricultural products are wheat, barley, pulses, oilseeds, pearl millet, maize, etc. As mentioned above, the district is the abode of numerous tourist sites. In the year 2021, an estimated 3,10,998 domestic tourists visited the various sites of the state (India Statistics Districts). The district earns a part of its income from the tourists.

The district is rich in minerals. The major mineral category, concrete stone is produced in large quantity. As per the Invest UP official site, the GSDP of the district is Rs. 6883.18 crore. Mahoba is known for its exquisite 'Gaura Stone Craft'. Gaura stone craft holds a unique place in art and craft. The stone is cut into small pieces for making different artworks. This stone has a soft texture that's why its cutting is easier. The stone crusher industry is well-developed in the district. Apart from this oil mills, dying & printing units, agro and food-based industries, poultry, and automobile products are other industries in the district (District Skill Development Plan Year, 2020-21). There is a cluster of industries named 'Gaura Stone Cluster, Gaurahari, Mahoba' which is known for products

such as decorative items, temples, vases, sculptures, statues, etc. However, there is a need for technology upgradation, skilled manpower, and environment-friendly technology (Brief Industrial Profile of Mahoba District, 2016).

Climate vulnerability: The district shows a great extent of climate vulnerability due to its existing level of development that affects the adaptive capacity of the population in the face of any natural hazard. Water scarcity is one of the most important factors contributing to the climatic vulnerability of the district. The unpredictable Monsoon and the forces of climate change further exacerbate the situation. Monsoon failures are the common features of the whole region including the district of Mahoba.

Over-exploited groundwater resources are a common phenomenon in the whole country where about 80% of irrigation is dependent on groundwater. Mahoba is an overexploited groundwater district in India. The increased number of borewells and handpumps are providing relief to people but on the other hand, there is pressure on the depleting groundwater table. In the stress days, the unavailability of water poses the question of equity in the distribution of these precious resources. This distribution intersects with the social inequalities present in society creating the issue of climate justice because resourceful persons can dig borewells deeper to fetch water while the poor remain on the receiving end. There is a problem of wide-scale migration from this region particularly a large number of workers who go to Delhi-NCR, Punjab, and Haryana to collect 'Rabi' crops during the period of 'Chaita', are known as "Chaitua" (Yadav & Chauhan, 2020).

Degradation of forest resources is also common in the district due to the expansion of agricultural activities and the extraction of minerals, especially granite, clearing the forest covers from the tops of hills and rocks. Socioeconomic factors also increase the climate vulnerability of this district as most of the people are engaged in agriculture, which is very sensitive to changes in weather conditions and climatic variability.

There are a total of 3 tehsils and 4 blocks in the district. The 4 administrative blocks are mentioned below:

1. Kabarai
2. Charkahri
3. Jetpur
4. Panwari

According to the methodology adopted for the selection of the block, the block of Panwari was taken for conducting the empirical study in the district. The block with the combined highest value for two criteria (percentage of scheduled caste/scheduled tribe population and percentage of workforce dependent on agriculture) was taken. On this account, the block of Panwari with the maximum combined value of these two criteria was selected.

The sample was selected from both urban and rural areas. To cover the urban area, the city of Mahoba was taken and in the rural category, the Panwari Block was taken into consideration as mentioned above. Four village panchayats and one city area were taken on a random selection basis. The four selected village panchayats in the Panwari Block were:

1. Rivai
2. Tola Pathar
3. Nagara Ghat
4. Kilhauwa

2.4.4 SONBHADRA

The district Sonbhadra (Sonebhadra) is the second largest district of the state. It lies between the north latitude 23.52 to 25.32 and the east longitude of 82.72 to 83.33 in the extreme southeast of Uttar Pradesh. This is the only district in India that shares its border with 4 states (Madhya Pradesh, Chattisgarh, Jharkhand, and Bihar). It covers an area of 6788sq.km. and is bounded by Mirzapur district to the northwest, Chandauli district to the north, Kaimur and Rohtas districts of Bihar state to the northeast, Koriya and Surguja districts of Chhattisgarh state to the south, Garhwa district of Jharkhand state to the east, and Singrauli district of Madhya Pradesh state. Robertsganj is the main town and headquarters of the district. This district has the highest forest cover in the state. It is known as the 'Power capital of India' due to the abundance of power plants and energy centers. There are various sites of historical importance in this district that are the center of attraction for tourists such as Agori Fort which was ruled by Madan Shah, Vijaygarh Fort that was ruled by Raja Chait Singh of Benaras and Sodhriagarh Durg ruled by Garhwal Kings. The world's oldest Salkhan Fossil Park is one of the famous tourist sites.

Figure 2.10 Map of Sonbhadra District

Source: <https://www.mapsofindia.com/maps/uttarpradesh/districts/sonbhadra.htm>

Demographic Profile of Sonbhadra:

According to the census 2011, the actual population of the district is 18,62,559 out of which males are 9,71,344; females 8,91,215 and the total child population (0-6 age) is 3,23,092. The Sex ratio is 918 per 1000 males. The population density is 270 per sq. km. The average literacy rate is 64.03% (9,85,708) with the male literacy rate being 74.92% and the female literacy rate only 52.14%. A large part of the population (83.12%) lives in rural regions of the district and only 16.88% of the population lives in urban regions of the district. The commonly used language in this district is Hindi.

Topography: Sonbhadra is located in a scenic beautiful location and it lies between the Vindhyan Range and the Kaimur Range. On account of its topography and scenic beautiful natural environment, the first Prime Minister of India Jawaharlal Nehru referred to Sonbhadra as the "Switzerland of India".

Water Resources:

The district is extremely affluent in water resources. There are several ponds, lakes, river channels, etc which are used as the main source of water supply for agriculture and thermal power plants. The main rivers that flow into the district are the Sone River, Rihand River, and Kanhar River. In 1962 the construction of Rihand Dam also took place across the Rihand river. The Govind Ballabh Pant Sagar, the artificial lake behind the Rihand Dam is a reservoir of the Rihand River which is used for generating hydroelectric power. It has also access to the river Ganga due to its location near the banks of the river Ganga towards the north.

Economy: Agriculture is the commonly preferred occupation in this district. The main crops that are supported by its red soil and 'kareaili' soil are wheat, mustard, potato, pea, onion, rapeseed, etc. People prefer technologically advanced ways to get good quality production with increased quantity also. Along with agriculture, Forestry, and mining are also the main sources of its economy. Sonbhadra is blessed with the highest forest cover in the state and has various valuable plants and trees such as Bamboo, Tendu, Timber, Mahua, Sesame, etc. These forests are the income source for various social groups who are engaged in the making of bamboo and timber products. The area is also rich in mineral resources such as gold, coal (Black Diamond), dolomite, and cement-grade limestone.

Sonbhadra is known as the ‘Power capital of India’ due to the presence of several industries, such as power plants, cement factories, and chemical factories. Some of them are the Churk cement factory, Rihand thermal power plant, Renuagar Power, etc. These industries play a significant role in ensuring the district's revenue growth year on year. Apart from all this, Sonbhadra is famous for its traditionally handmade ‘carpets,’ which the Government of India designated the “One District, One Product.”

Climatic vulnerability: Sonbhadra is grappling with a complex interplay of climate vulnerability and socioeconomic challenges. Its unique geographical location, poor socioeconomic indicators, and presence of various industries exacerbate its exposure to climate change impacts. Several indicators of vulnerability characterize Sonbhadra's socioeconomic landscape are:

- **High Poverty Rates:** The district has historically been marked with a high incidence of poverty, with a significant portion of its population living below the poverty line. Poverty makes it difficult for the population to cope with the adverse impacts of extreme weather conditions spurred by climate change, such as crop failures and loss of livelihoods.
- **Low Literacy Rates:** With a literacy rate of 64.03 %, Sonbhadra's literacy rate is lower than the national average (District portal of Sonbhadra). It limits the population's ability to access information, make informed decisions, and adapt to changing environmental conditions.
- **Limited Access to Healthcare:** Inadequate healthcare facilities and limited access to medical services further exacerbate the

vulnerability of Sonbhadra's residents, particularly in the face of climate-related health risks.

- **Dependence on Agriculture:** A significant portion of the district's population relies on agriculture for their livelihood. However, climate change-induced droughts, floods, and erratic rainfall patterns pose a major threat to agricultural productivity. The plateau nature of its land makes the irrigation difficult. Despite of being bestowed with mighty Son River, the most of agriculture land is rainfed.

Scheduled Tribes population: A major portion of Sonbhadra's population consists of different tribes. These tribes are generally marginalised in the process of development. Their poverty, illiteracy, poor health, and inaccessibility to modern resources make this district particularly vulnerable to climate change. Their land and natural resources are being utilized by industrialists.

Environmental Challenges Posed by Industries: Generally, industries are said to be the hallmarks of progress and development in the modern era. However, sometimes these industries put heavy costs on the local environment or local population. Sonbhadra is a classic example of such a development pattern. Despite being endowed with natural resources and beautiful terrain, the district is marred by poverty and poor socioeconomic parameters. Sonbhadra's industrial landscape, dominated by sectors such as mining, power generation, and manufacturing, has contributed to the district's environmental challenges:

- **Mining Activities:** The extraction of minerals, particularly coal and limestone, has led to deforestation, soil erosion, and water pollution. Heavy metals and other minerals generally percolate into

the water table and contaminate local water bodies. Some areas of the districts are facing acute groundwater contamination problems.

- **Power Generation and Pollution:** The operation of thermal power plants in Sonbhadra results in air pollution, water pollution, and greenhouse gas emissions. The burning of fossil fuels releases harmful pollutants into the atmosphere, contributing to climate change and affecting human health.

Industrial Waste and Pollution: Industrial activities in Sonbhadra generate significant amounts of waste, including solid waste, wastewater, and hazardous substances. Improper disposal of this waste can contaminate the environment and pose risks to public health. Several studies also put the districts of Vindhyan at a very high vulnerability (Tripathi, 2014).

The administration of the district is divided into 4 tehsils and 10 blocks. The four tehsils are Roberganj, Ghorawal, Duddhi, and Obra. While the 10 blocks are as follows:

- | | |
|--------------|-------------|
| 1. Roberganj | 2. Ghorawal |
| 3. Chatra | 4. Nagwa |
| 5. Chopan | 6. Babhani |
| 7. Myorpu | 8. Duddhi |
| 9. Karma | 10. Kyone |

According to the methodology, Chopan block was taken for conducting the empirical study in the district. The block with the combined highest value for two criteria (percentage of scheduled caste/scheduled tribe population and percentage of workforce dependent on agriculture) was taken.

The sample was selected from both urban and rural areas. To cover the urban area, the city of Robertganj was taken and in the rural category, the Chopan Block was taken into consideration as mentioned above. Four village panchayats and one city area were taken. The four selected village panchayats in the Chopan Block are:

1. Kanachh
2. Kalhaura
3. Sinduria
4. Chopan

2.5 RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Research Methodology is an essential component of any scientific inquiry as it is the systematic analysis of the tools, methods, and techniques used in a study. It is the blueprint of the steps to be taken by the researchers to carry out their research. Although research is a very general term in academics, there is no consensus among the academicians over the definition of the term. However, from the different definitions of research, these aspects seem to be common: “Research is a process of inquiry and investigation; it is systematic and methodical; and research increases knowledge” (Amaratunga et al., 2002).

Generally, the research is divided based on the objectives of the study, the application of the study, and the information sought. Based on the application of the study, the research is broadly two types i.e. pure research and applied research. Based on the objectives of the study, the research may be divided into exploratory, descriptive, explanatory, and correlational. While based on the information sought the research is of three types i.e. qualitative, quantitative, and mixed methods.

The main purpose of this section is to provide a glimpse of the steps taken in the present study. I have divided this section into the following sub-

sections or headings: first, the research approach is discussed, followed by the research design. Then, the study population is mentioned, and after this, the Sample design is followed by the data collection description. In the last section, the statistical tools used for analysing the data are discussed.

2.5.1 RESEARCH APPROACH

The research approach is a broader framework that refers to the overall orientation of the research. The research approach refers to the procedure adopted by the researcher to conduct her research i.e. how to collect, analyse, and interpret data. As mentioned above, on the basis of the information sought, the research is of qualitative, quantitative, and mixed type. The qualitative approach is generally in which “methods utilize empirical material such as case studies, life experiences, and stories that show the routines and problems that individuals are struggling in their lives through focusing on their in-depth meaning and motivation which cannot be defined by numbers” (Taherdoost, 2022). In qualitative research, the primary, textual data is collected and then it is analysed through specific interpretive methods. It is explorative as it is often used to discover new ideas, insights, and formulation of new concepts, arguments, and theories. The quantitative approach employs numerical values obtained from observation for explaining and describing the phenomena. It is also applied in empirical evaluation for the determination of the degree the norms or standards are fulfilled. The data is then analysed with the help of mathematical tools. Non-numerical information can be converted into numerical form through specific instruments. In mixed -method approach utilization of both qualitative and quantitative approaches is made. It is often used in complex

circumstances of research such as social research and health research. It is used in such cases in which one approach seems inadequate to find the reality or meaningful information. In interdisciplinary research with various researchers using different methodologies, the mixed method can be useful to meet the purpose. Based on the above discussion, the nature of this mixed method which uses both qualitative and quantitative methods. The qualitative assessment of the SAPCC is made and then the field study employs the quantitative approach.

2.5.2 RESEARCH DESIGN

The research design refers to the outline of the research i.e. the way how a study will take place. It is the blueprint for undertaking a study in a maximum controlled way to rule out the interferences of factors that can affect the result of a study (Burns & Grove, 2009). According to Parahoo (2006), a research design is a plan that tells how, where, and when data is collected and analysed.

This study seeks to examine broadly two relationships. One is the relationship between the State Action Plan on Climate Change and the elements of environmental (climate) justice in it. Second the relationship between socioeconomic demographic characteristics and adverse impacts of climate change/loss in terms of livelihood, production and health. Further, this study seeks to assess the awareness and perception of climate change and its associated phenomena.

For the assessment of SAPCC from an environmental justice perspective, the different missions of the SAPCC and their strategies were studied and elements of participation, capability, and fairness were tried to find out. The analysis of the SAPCC was made only based on the provisions present in the document of the plan. Several government officials were

interviewed about the mechanisms of the plan and their implementation. Since it is in its initial phase, not many records are available in consolidated form for assessing the progress of the plan. In this scenario, the best available option was to examine and assess different missions in the light of justice which is the yardstick of any progressive policy. For the other part of the study, the data were collected through a detailed questionnaire prepared to obtain the responses of the respondents. The study area being the state of Uttar Pradesh, the selection of the districts was made in an unbiased way. The criterion used in the selection was based on the 'composite vulnerability index' of the UP SAPCC 2.0'. The Plan assessed all districts of Uttar Pradesh on different vulnerability indexes using the vulnerability assessment framework of the IPCC. The SAPCC 2.0 assessed the vulnerability of districts based on major drivers of vulnerability. The key drivers used in the composite vulnerability index are "high crop yield variability, high baseline water stress, reduction in forest area, poor access to basic amenities, poor access to electricity, low access to functional health care facilities, and high households at risk to damage by wind and extreme rainfall" (UP SAPCC 2.0: p.112).

The districts have been categorized into five categories of various vulnerabilities by SAPCC 2.0. The districts were arranged in an order of vulnerability in each category. The sequence was the decreasing order of vulnerability. Thus, the first district in each category was the most vulnerable in that category. The vulnerability categories adopted were: 1. Very high, 2. High, 3. Moderate, 4. Low, and 5. Very Low. The last category has only one district i.e. Baghpat. The rest of the 74 districts were divided into four categories mentioned above.

For this study, I took one district from each four categories. To avoid any biases, the very first district in each category as mentioned in the UP SAPCC 2.0 was taken to conduct an empirical case study in those districts. Thus, the districts were taken as follows:

Sonbhadra	-	Very High Vulnerability
Mahoba	-	High Vulnerability
Lakhimpur Kheri	-	Moderate Vulnerability
Bahraich	-	Low Vulnerability

Further, the selection of a block was made in each district for collecting the survey. Based on the drivers of vulnerability as adopted in the UP SAPCC 2.0, searches were made to have the government data on these drivers to choose the relevant block. The Directorate of Economic and Statistics, Government of Uttar Pradesh's publication of "Spider – Sankhikiya Patrika" (Statistical Magazine) was made the basis for having the block-level data on various socio-economic indicators. The relevant two indicators as compatible with the drivers of the vulnerability index of the UP SAPCC 2.0, were taken. Since climate vulnerability is multidimensional and multifaceted, it needs various factors to assess the vulnerability of a place. The two criteria taken for choosing the block were 1. The percentage share of Scheduled Caste/Scheduled Tribe population and 2. The percentage of the population is dependent on agricultural activities. These two criteria are of importance since these two categories i.e. SC/ST population and agriculture are very sensitive to the variabilities of climate as well as weather as found in various studies. Based on the knowledge of previous studies and their compatibility with the drivers of vulnerability as adopted in the assessment of the 'composite vulnerability index', these two criteria were chosen.

All blocks of the districts were given values on these two criteria and their combined value was obtained. The block with a higher value in the district was taken in each district for conducting the empirical study. In this way, the blocks that were chosen based on the higher value of these criteria were:

1. Chaupan block from Sonbhadra district
2. Panwari block from Mahoba district
3. Mitauli block from Lakhimpur Kheri district and
4. Mahsi block from Bahraich district.

2.5.3 SAMPLE DESIGN AND DATA COLLECTION

The population of a study is the whole number of objects, subjects, or persons that are intended to be studied. According to De Vaus (2002), the population is a group of elements that is used by the researcher to draw conclusions or to make generalizations. The ‘target population’ refers to the sum of all units of which characteristics are to be studied (Roy, 2020). The ‘Sampling population’ is that portion of the population that is finally chosen for sampling. A sample is important in any research because it is not feasible for any researcher to study the whole population due to restrictions of time and resources. Only in certain cases, the whole population is used to collect the data e.g. the census which needs huge financial, human, and administrative resources, and only government agencies can carry out such extensive and inclusive exercise. A sample is representative of the characteristics that need to be studied in the target population.

In the present study, the target population is the population of the four districts. The sampling population is the population of four villages from

each block selected from each district and the urban population of each district headquarters. Four village panchayats have been chosen from each concerned block using a probability sampling method i.e. random sampling so that each village in the population has an equal chance of being selected. Random Selection is a strategy for getting a scientific and representative sample in research. This method has the obvious benefit of having all shades of people in the sample. A sample of 40 people has also been taken through the stratified random sampling method from each village panchayat. In the same way, a sample of 40 respondents was taken from the urban areas. The main city of each district was chosen for having a sample of urban respondents.

The data was collected through a detailed questionnaire/Schedules by personally visiting the sampling population. To have better understanding of climate issues and action plan on climate change, semi-structured interviews of environmentalists, government officials, NGOs and key stakeholders were conducted. The data was collected from January 2024 to June 2024. The data was organized and entered into the software, for analysis and finding the results of various categories of respondents for different sets of variables to be tested. Frequency, percentage, Chi Square tests were applied to analyse the data to make findings and draw conclusions.

CHAPTER – III

CLIMATE ACTIONS: GLOBAL, NATIONAL AND SUB-NATIONAL LEVEL

Realising the vagaries of climate change and its associated impacts on the sectors, populations, communities, species, and ecosystem components, actions have been taken on multiple fronts and multiple scales around the globe. The intersection of climate action and environmental justice underscores the need for policies and strategies that mitigate greenhouse gas emissions and prioritize marginalised communities' needs and rights (UNEP, 2016; IPCC, 2018). Climate action encompasses a range of policies and measures to reduce emissions, adapt to climate impacts, and promote sustainable development (UNFCCC, 2015). Climate actions have been initiated at different levels i.e. global, regional, national, sub-national, and local levels through various stakeholders including international organizations, transnational bodies, national governments, corporations, local bodies, communities, and individual levels. Various Climate Action Plans have evolved over the period as the science established more authentically the causal-effect relationship between climate change and its various impacts, and as per various priorities of different stakeholders. Global efforts started with the establishment of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) in 1988 by the World Meteorological Organisation (WMO) and the United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP) to assess the phenomenon of climate change on a scientific basis and inform the policymakers about the phenomenon and its various impacts (Murphy-Greene, 2022). The establishment of UNFCCC in the aftermath of the Rio Summit played an important role in institutionalising climate governance at the global level.

At the national level parties (nations are known as parties in the UNFCCC framework) make their efforts to combat mitigation of emissions of greenhouse gases and adopt climate change perspectives in their developmental or growth policies. However, the effectiveness of climate action is contingent upon its ability to address underlying social inequalities and vulnerabilities (IPCC, 2014; IPCC, 2021). Climate policies often inadvertently exacerbate inequalities by prioritizing economic growth over social equity or by disproportionately burdening vulnerable communities with the costs of adaptation (Heynen et al., 2006).

This chapter explores the spectrum of initiatives taken at the several levels of green governance. Inspecting the key functions, conventions, framework, and actions highlights the contributions and gaps on several tiers of governance regarding mitigation and adaptation. By examining how global and local efforts can work together, we can identify ways to tighten the safety net, strengthen our resolve, and move confidently towards a sustainable future.

3.1 INITIATIVES AT INTERNATIONAL LEVEL

Climate change, driven by human activities, poses an existential threat to the planet. The international community has responded with a multi-layered approach, combining global agreements with a multitude of local initiatives. This chapter explores the current state of climate action on both the global and local levels, examining their strengths, weaknesses, and the crucial interplay between them.

The international community has taken the first step, establishing the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC) as a safety net. This agreement, backed by nearly every nation, strives to

stabilize greenhouse gas concentrations and prevent a climate catastrophe. The key achievements of the UNFCCC were the Kyoto Protocol which sought the reduction of emissions in a binding manner from the developed countries (Annex-I) and now the Paris Agreement, a more ambitious pact that sets voluntary emissions reduction targets for countries in the form of Nationally Determined Contributions (NDCs). I'll delve into the major international agreements, national commitments and efforts at local level. From cities embracing renewable energy to communities fostering sustainable living, local action is a powerful force for change.

3.1.1 EVOLUTION OF GLOBAL CLIMATE ACTION FRAMEWORK

Climate change poses a profound threat to the environment, economies, and societies worldwide. The international community has responded to this challenge by developing a series of frameworks aimed at mitigating and adapting to climate change. This section traces the evolution of these frameworks, focusing on their key features, successes, and limitations. It aims to provide a comprehensive understanding of how global climate action has progressed and what lessons can be learned for future initiatives.

(a) STOCKHOLM CONFERENCE

The United Nations Conference on the Human Environment, held in Stockholm in 1972, marked the beginning of international environmental governance. The conference produced the Stockholm Declaration, which recognized the need for a global approach to environmental issues and led to the establishment of the United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP, 1972). Before the Stockholm Conference, environmental issues were largely viewed as local or national concerns. However, the late

1960s and early 1970s witnessed a growing public awareness of environmental problems like air and water pollution, industrial waste disposal, and the loss of biodiversity. Rachel Carson's seminal book, "Silent Spring," published in 1962, is often credited with sparking public outrage over the environmental effects of pesticides (1962).

The Stockholm Conference, attended by representatives from over 113 countries, yielded several significant outcomes:

- The Stockholm Declaration is a landmark document outlining 26 principles for sound environmental management, emphasizing the responsibility of states to protect the environment and ensure sustainable development.
- The Action Plan for the Human Environment, this comprehensive plan called for a range of actions to address pressing environmental issues, including pollution control, conservation of natural resources, and capacity building for developing countries.
- The Creation of the United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP) is one of the most lasting legacies of the conference. It became the principal environmental agency within the UN system. UNEP serves as a central platform for promoting international cooperation on environmental issues (UNCHE, 1972).

It elevated environmental concerns to the forefront of international cooperation, placing them alongside economic and social development goals. The environmental issues got global recognition. It was the first time that world leaders and scientists came together to discuss transboundary environmental issues (Seyfang, 2003). The conference fostered dialogue and collaboration between developed and developing

countries on environmental protection. It gave birth to environmental diplomacy. This conference acted as a catalyst for environmental law and policy. It was said to be a “step toward global environmental cooperation and involvement” (Sullivan, 1972). Despite its achievements, the Stockholm Conference also faced some limitations. The Action Plan lacked strong enforcement mechanisms to ensure the implementation of its recommendations. It created a North-South divide as differing priorities and concerns between developed and developing countries regarding environmental protection became evident during the conference.

The 1972 Stockholm Conference stands as a testament to the power of international cooperation in addressing global challenges. While environmental problems continue to pose serious threats, the Stockholm Conference laid the groundwork for a more coordinated and comprehensive approach to environmental protection. Its legacy lives on in the form of UNEP and the ongoing efforts to achieve a more sustainable future for our planet.

(b) UNITED NATIONS ENVIRONMENT PROGRAMME (UNEP)

Established in 1972, the United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP) serves as the leading global environmental authority, setting the international environmental agenda and promoting sustainable development. UNEP's mission is to encourage sustainable development through sound environmental practices globally. Over the decades, UNEP has played a crucial role in numerous environmental milestones:

- Montreal Protocol (1987): UNEP facilitated the creation of this landmark agreement to phase out substances that deplete the ozone

layer, which has been hailed as one of the most successful environmental treaties.

- Rio Earth Summit (1992): UNEP was instrumental in organizing this summit, which led to the adoption of key documents such as Agenda 21 and the Rio Declaration on Environment and Development.
- Paris Agreement (2015): UNEP supported the negotiations leading to this global accord to combat climate change and accelerate actions and investments needed for a sustainable low-carbon future.

UNEP plays a critical role in global efforts to combat climate change through initiatives such as the Emissions Gap Report, an annual assessment of the gap between current emissions and the levels needed to meet international climate targets and the Climate Technology Centre and Network (CTCN) that supports the transfer of climate technologies to developing countries to help them mitigate and adapt to climate change

(c) MONTREAL PROTOCOL

The Montreal Protocol on Substances that Deplete the Ozone Layer stands as a landmark international agreement, demonstrating the power of collective action in addressing global environmental threats (Protocol, 1987). The Montreal Protocol stands as a testament to the power of international cooperation, scientific consensus, and decisive action in addressing global environmental threats. It has demonstrably protected the ozone layer and prevented millions of skin cancer cases. The Montreal Protocol's success serves as a model for future international environmental agreements, demonstrating the potential for collective

action in tackling pressing environmental challenges facing our planet. The climate protection benefits achieved under the Montreal Protocol alone are greater than the first phase reduction targets of the Kyoto Protocol (Velders et al., 2007).

(d) **BRUNDTLAND REPORT**

The Brundtland Report, officially titled "**Our Common Future**," is a landmark document in the field of sustainable development. Published in 1987 by the World Commission on Environment and Development (WCED), it introduced the concept of **sustainable development** and emphasized the interconnectedness of environmental, economic, and social issues. In 1983, the United Nations Secretary-General established the WCED, chaired by Gro Harlem Brundtland, then Prime Minister of Norway. The WCED aimed to reconcile environmental protection with economic development and address the concerns of developing nations. Brundtland Commission envisaged the organization of human development in a "three-dimensional" harmonious interrelationship among three cores i.e. 'environmental', 'social', and 'economic' dimensions (Spangenberg et al., 2002).

The Brundtland Report introduced the now-ubiquitous definition of sustainable development: "***development that meets the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs***"(Brundtland,1987). This definition emphasized the intergenerational equity aspect of sustainable development, highlighting the need to consider the long-term consequences of our actions. The Brundtland Report is also criticized for lacking detailed implementation strategies and action plans for achieving sustainable development. The report faced challenges in addressing the concerns of developing

countries regarding economic growth and poverty eradication. Despite these criticisms, the Brundtland Report remains a landmark document, playing a pivotal role in shaping the global conversation on sustainable development. It continues to influence international environmental policy and serves as a reminder of our collective responsibility to ensure a sustainable future for all.

(e) ***INTERGOVERNMENTAL PANEL ON CLIMATE CHANGE (IPCC)***

IPCC was formed by the initiation of the United Nations Environment Program (UNEP) and the World Metrological Organization (WMO) in 1988. IPCC provided the forefront scientific basis for analysing climate change and its impact. IPCC played a significant role in bridging the gaps between technical interpretations and policy action in the mitigation. IPCC publishes a series of assessment, social, and public reports. The assessment reports of the IPCC play a vital role in policymaking. IPCC holds a unique organizational mechanism in which work is divided among working groups. IPCC for its outstanding work on the environment got Noble Prize in 2007.

The IPCC's core functions are to provide policymakers with regular scientific assessments of climate change, its implications, and potential future risks. This includes:

- Synthesizing and disseminating the most recent scientific, technical, and socio-economic information relevant to understanding climate change.
- Identifying areas where further research is needed.
- Providing an objective and independent source of information for policymakers at all levels.

The IPCC's assessments have played a pivotal role in shaping international climate policy. The landmark Fifth Assessment Report (AR5) in 2013 concluded with high confidence that human activities are the main cause of the observed warming since the mid-20th century (IPCC AR 5, 2013). These findings formed the scientific basis for the Paris Agreement, a landmark international agreement adopted in 2015 that aims to limit global warming to well below 2°C, preferably to 1.5°C, compared to pre-industrial levels.

In recent AR-6 Reports, the IPCC has put in unambiguous terms in its about 8000 pages that the devastating consequences of increasing concentration of carbon in the atmosphere are very much apparent, clear, and quite visible around the globe. It warns that we are reaching the tipping points of dangerous and irreversible risks should we fail to take effective, immediate, and meaningful actions (WRI, 2023). The key takeaways of the report include:

- Anthropogenic global warming of 1.1 degrees Celsius has already spurred unprecedented changes in the climate of the Earth, reflected through rising sea levels to receding polar ice, retreating glaciers and extreme weather events.
- The impacts of climate change on humans and the ecosystem are more severe and widespread than previously expected, and every fraction of increasing temperature would escalate future risks rapidly.
- There is a high probability (more than 50% chance) of crossing the 1.5 degrees Celsius threshold between 2021 and 2040 and even sooner between 2018 and 2037. To limit the temperature to 1.5 degrees Celsius, the global emissions should peak immediately i.e.

before 2025, and 1.5 aligned pathways postulate a rapid drop in GHGs by 43% and 60% by 2030 and 2035 respectively to 2019 levels.

- There is an urgent need to enhance climate finance for both mitigation and adaptation during this decade. To meet mitigation goals alone, climate finance needs to increase 3-6 times by 2030, while for adaptation and loss & damage developing countries alone need \$ 127 billion by 2030 and \$ 295 billion by 2050 per year.

Despite its accomplishments, the IPCC faces several ongoing challenges. Reaching consensus amongst nearly 200 member governments can be a complex and time-consuming process. Additionally, the IPCC is susceptible to political pressure from some member states who may seek to downplay the severity of climate change. Furthermore, the IPCC's assessment reports are inherently retrospective, analysing past climate trends and potential future scenarios based on current scientific understanding. The rapidly evolving nature of climate science necessitates continuous updates and revisions to these assessments.

(f) UNITED NATIONS FRAMEWORK CONVENTION ON CLIMATE CHANGE (UNFCCC)

United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC), established in 1992 (Rio Earth Summit) along with two other conventions – ‘Convention on Biological Diversity’ (CBD), and ‘United Nations Conventions to Combat Desertification’ (UNCCD) - proved to be a pivotal step in environmental history (United Nations). It is the platform for initiatives, collaborations, and co-ordinations regarding climate policy. The ultimate objective of UNFCCC is to stabilize greenhouse

gases in the atmosphere (UN Climate Change). After entering into force in 1994, the first meeting of the ‘Conference of Parties (COP) was held in 1995. The Berlin Mandate sought that industrialized countries (Annex I) should reduce their GHGs and finally, it culminated in the revolutionary Kyoto Protocol of 1997 (Kuyper et al., 2018). It set legally binding targets on the developed countries regarding GHG emissions. Article 3 of UNFCCC provides the basis for the *differentiated responsibilities* of the parties, it states:

“The Parties should protect the climate system for the benefit of present and future generations of humankind, on the basis of equity and in accordance with their common but differentiated responsibilities and respective capabilities. Accordingly, the developed country Parties should take the lead in combating climate change and the adverse effects thereof”

(Article 3, UNFCCC, 1992)

Although it faced a lot of hardships many countries discarded it. Along with several marking achievements, UNFCCC played a significant role in creating awareness regarding climate change and environmental hardships. The Conference of Parties (CoP) has become a marking event where countries meet annually, negotiate, dialects, and forge partnerships. The CoP has electrified governments, NGOs, civil societies, and humans in the way of sustainable life. Financially, UNFCCC established the Green Climate Fund (GCF) to help developing countries mitigate and adapt to hardships.

The landmarks in the journey of UNFCCC in the last three decades include the revolutionary Kyoto Protocol (1997), the impasse in reaching

the post-Kyoto Protocol agreement in Copenhagen (2009), and the historic Paris Agreement (2015). During this period there have been several shifts in approach or orientation in the negotiations COPs under the aegis of UNFCCC ranging from “targeting historic emissions” in a “legally binding manner” to “voluntary contributions” in the form of “Nationally Determined Contributions” (NDCs). The UNFCCC's primary strength lies in its universality. Nearly all countries have ratified the convention, signifying a global commitment to tackle climate change. By establishing the Conference of the Parties (COP), it created a vital platform for ongoing dialogue, knowledge sharing, and negotiation. Notably, the COP in Paris in 2015 resulted in the Paris Agreement, a more ambitious framework with nationally determined contributions (NDCs) for emissions.

(g) KYOTO PROTOCOL

The Kyoto Protocol, adopted in 1997, marked a critical turning point in the international response to climate change. The 1992 Rio Earth Summit established the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC) as a framework for international cooperation on climate change. Notably, it backed legally binding emission reduction targets for developed countries. The Kyoto Protocol emerged as an effort to strengthen the UNFCCC by setting binding targets for industrialized nations.

This framework marked a significant departure from previous international agreements by imposing specific, quantifiable targets on developed nations, reflecting their historical responsibility for the bulk of emissions. Under the Protocol, these countries, listed in Annex I, committed to reducing their collective emissions by an average of 5.2%

below 1990 levels during the first commitment period (2008-2012). Different targets were agreed upon after negotiation, for instance, 5% for Croatia; 6% for Canada, Hungary, and Japan; 7% for the USA; and 8% for the European Union. The legally binding nature of these targets aimed to ensure accountability and drive substantial policy changes at the national level. Compliance mechanisms, including penalties for non-compliance and incentives for exceeding targets, were established to enforce these commitments.

This top-down approach to curbing emissions through binding responsibilities of advanced economies was based on the principle of “polluters pay” owing to their historical contribution to the accumulation of GHGs responsible for global warming and climate change. Through a great deal of negotiation between advanced economies and developing and least developed economies, the cardinal principle of “CBDRRC (Common But Differentiated Responsibilities Respective Capabilities” mentioned in UNFCCC’s article 3, became the central arch of the edifice of ‘climate governance’ in its initial years. The Kyoto Protocol reiterates the principle of CBDR in Article 10 which states:

“All Parties, taking into account their common but differentiated responsibilities and their specific national and regional development priorities, objectives and circumstances, without introducing any new commitments for Parties not included in Annex I, but reaffirming existing commitments under Article 4, paragraph 1, of the Convention, and continuing to advance the implementation of these commitments in order to achieve sustainable development” (Article 10, Kyoto Protocol, 1997)

The most striking features of the Kyoto Protocol after its binding targets of reduction in emission for Annex-I countries were provisions of ‘Joint Implementation’ (JI) and the ‘Clean Development Mechanism’ (CDM). These innovative market tools were introduced in the hope that the effectiveness of the ‘price mechanism’ would tackle the issue of climate change. It permitted advanced nations (Annex- I) to trade their allocated GHG emissions with developed as well as developing countries by investing in carbon mitigation projects as per the norms of the ‘clean development mechanism’. In any CDM project countries were entitled to earn ‘credits’ which were the difference between GHG emissions of the ‘traditional’ path (base-line) and the ‘low-carbon path’ of projects under CDM in the host country. Baer concludes that “in essence, emissions trading schemes allow polluters to continue polluting by purchasing credits” (2021: p.123). The effectiveness of these binding targets has been mixed. While some countries met or exceeded their goals, others, like Canada, withdrew from the Protocol citing economic concerns and the non-participation of major emitters like the United States and China. This has highlighted the challenges of enforcing international agreements and the need for more inclusive and flexible mechanisms to accommodate the diverse economic realities of participating nations.

3.1.2 THE PARIS AGREEMENT: SHIFTING FROM BINDING TARGETS OF A FEW TO VOLUNTARY CONTRIBUTIONS OF ALL

The Paris Agreement, adopted in 2015, represents a significant milestone in international climate change governance. It establishes a global framework for reducing greenhouse gas emissions, limiting global warming, and enhancing climate resilience. The threat of climate change

has prompted various international efforts aimed at mitigating its impacts. The Paris Agreement, negotiated under the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC), is the latest and most comprehensive global accord to address climate change. It builds on the foundations of the Kyoto Protocol but introduces more flexible and inclusive mechanisms to accommodate the diverse circumstances of its signatories.

The prominent objective of the Paris Agreement is “*the increase in the global average temperature to well below 2°C above pre-industrial levels*” and pursue efforts “*to limit the temperature increase to 1.5°C above pre-industrial levels.*” (UNFCCC, Paris Agreement, 2015). Before the Paris Agreement, the Kyoto Protocol shaped international climate efforts, which established legally binding targets for developed countries to reduce greenhouse gas emissions. However, the Protocol faced significant challenges, including the non-participation of key emitters like the United States and the withdrawal of Canada. These issues highlighted the need for a more inclusive and flexible approach. This led to the road to Paris. The journey to the Paris Agreement began with the Durban Platform for Enhanced Action, established in 2011, which called for a new legally binding agreement involving all countries. Intensive negotiations culminated in the 21st Conference of the Parties (COP21) in Paris, where the Agreement was adopted on December 12, 2015, and entered into force on November 4, 2016.

The Paris Agreement represents a significant shift in the ‘Global Climate Governance’ as it is a “legally binding international treaty on climate change”, however, it has changed the provision of “binding targets” for the Annex I Countries under the Kyoto Protocol and adopted a universal

approach of “voluntary contributions”. The cardinal principle of CDDRRC reflects itself in a new avatar in the Paris Agreement. However, some scholars claim that the principle of CDDRRC has been diluted and more burdens have been put on the shoulders of the developing world (generally referred to as the Global South) than their due share of burden-sharing due to unequal occupying of ‘Carbon Space’ by some countries (Narain, 2015). There are apprehensions about whether the concept of CDDRRC was ever implemented in true spirit under the Kyoto Protocol as some studies find that CDDRRC has been “used by developed countries” to buy a ‘right to pollute’ through the “Clean Development Mechanism” and the Paris Agreement disregard the “historical responsibility” the very basis of CDDRRC and it marks the “departure from it” (Rosencranz and Jamwal, 2021).

A cornerstone of the Agreement is the system of Nationally Determined Contributions (NDCs), where each country sets its climate action plan and targets. This bottom-up approach allows for flexibility and accommodates the varied capabilities and circumstances of each nation. Countries are required to update their NDCs every five years, with each successive NDC expected to be more ambitious than the last. The Paris Agreement sought the countries to formulate and submit long-term strategies in their “Long-Term Low greenhouse gas Emission Development Strategies” (LT-LEDS). LT-LEDS are not mandatory under the agreement, nevertheless, these are significant because they provide long-term vision and direction for the developmental paths of countries.

Transparency is one of the most important pillars of the Paris Agreement. It establishes a robust transparency framework to track progress and ensure accountability which becomes necessary given that it has adopted

a “voluntary self-determined” and “bottom-up” approach to contributing to combat climate change by nations as per their “national circumstances and capacities” (Delbeke, et al., 2019).

The Paris Agreement sought countries to establish an “enhanced transparency framework” (ETF). Information received from the countries feed into the “Global Stocktake” and this global stocktake assesses collective progress toward achieving the Agreement's long-term goals. This process is intended to inform and guide future action, ensuring that efforts remain on track to meet the temperature targets.

Since its adoption, the Paris Agreement has seen widespread ratification, with nearly 200 parties committing to its goals. Early implementation efforts have focused on enhancing NDCs, increasing renewable energy capacity, and promoting climate resilience. Several countries have also set net-zero emissions targets, aligning with the Agreement's long-term objectives. Financial commitments have been crucial in supporting developing countries' climate actions. The Green Climate Fund (GCF) has played a significant role in mobilizing resources, though the goal of \$100 billion annually by 2020 remains unmet. Ensuring adequate and predictable climate finance remains a critical challenge. Technological innovation has been a key driver of progress under the Paris Agreement. Advances in renewable energy, energy efficiency, and carbon capture and storage have contributed to emissions reductions. Continued investment in research and development is essential for achieving the Agreement's goals.

The Paris Agreement represents a landmark achievement in international climate diplomacy, establishing a flexible and inclusive framework for global climate action. While significant progress has been made,

challenges remain in enhancing ambition, ensuring equity, and navigating geopolitical complexities. The success of the Agreement depends on continued commitment, innovation, and collaboration among all stakeholders. As the world confronts the urgent threat of climate change, the Paris Agreement provides a crucial foundation for a sustainable and resilient future.

3.1.3 OTHER GLOBAL COMMITMENTS TO CLIMATE ACTION

Given the multidimensional and multifaceted nature of climate change, several multilateral and regional initiatives have been taken by the global community apart from the institutional framework mentioned above. A range of scientific, explorative, fiscal, political, social, and regulatory actions are needed to combat climate change. Some of the major steps taken are as follows:

- 1) **The European Green Deal:** It is a comprehensive master plan presented by the European Commission for transforming the EU's economy comprising policies and measures for efficient utilization of resources, reducing pollution, reversing biodiversity loss, curtailing net emissions, and climate change. The proposed measures encompass the whole range of economic sectors including, manufacturing, transportation, construction, energy, industry, and agriculture. To make this deal legally binding, the "European Climate Law" has been proposed by the Commission and it makes more ambitious targets of a reduction of about 55% GHG by 2030 in comparison to 1990 levels. It also has a target of planting additional 3 billion trees in the EU by 2030.

Under the European Green Deal, there is the "European Climate Pact", which is a people's movement for taking steps in their hands to make climate actions meaningful and effective and help the EU in meeting its

carbon neutrality goal by 2050. The European Commission also adopted a new “EU Strategy on Adaptation to Climate Change” on February 24, 2021 (European Commission, n.d.). To secure its energy security amid the geopolitical upheavals and tension in Eastern Europe recently reflected in the Russia-Ukraine war, the EU in May 2022 launched a plan, the “REPowerEU” to phase out the dependency of the EU on Russian Gas. It includes among other measures: the diversification of energy supplies, securing affordable energy, producing clean energy, and accelerating the transition to clean energy. The European Commission will fund REPowerEU with 300 billion euros through the “Recovery and Resilience Facility” (RRF).

2) European Union’s Carbon Border Adjustment Mechanism (CBAM)- The European Union's Carbon Border Adjustment Mechanism (CBAM) is a pioneering policy designed to prevent carbon leakage and ensure a level playing field for European industries. It’s a financial tool of the EU to put “a fair price on the carbon emitted during the production of carbon-intensive goods” being imported to the EU (European Commission, n.d.). By imposing a carbon price on goods from countries with less stringent climate policies, the CBAM aims to maintain the competitiveness of EU industries while encouraging global climate action.

By imposing a carbon cost on imports, the CBAM incentivizes producers in non-EU countries to adopt cleaner production methods to remain competitive in the EU market. This could lead to a reduction in global emissions and drive international climate action. However, the actual environmental impact will depend on the effectiveness of implementation and enforcement.

However, the analysis of the CBAM shows substantial limitations. It is being seen as a form of “carbon colonization” particularly in developing countries. The limitations and intentions of the CBAM have been described by Trishant Dev and Avantika Goswami in impressive words:

“EU’s Carbon Border Adjustment Mechanism, a tariff on imports, is designed to protect European industries in the guise of climate action. The carbon tariff would hurt developing countries’ export earnings and shift the decarbonisation burden on them, while overlooking developed nations’ climate responsibilities and green funding failures”

(Dev & Goswami, 2024: p. 21)

The CBAM is against the policies of the 1990s when developed countries around the world sought the opening of markets for foreign goods and services under the aegis of the World Trade Organisation (WTO) and the climate negotiations where emissions cuts were made legally binding only on advanced economies. The CBAM has significant implications for international trade and relations. Some countries have raised concerns about the mechanism being protectionist and potentially violating WTO rules. In the grab of the CBAM, the EU is trying to create a protectionist mechanism to protect their economic interests. In effect, since the 1990s when several manufacturing units were located in developing countries owing to their cheap labour, and less stringent environmental laws, the advanced economies “imported” emissions through their high consumption, a phenomenon known as “embedded emissions”. The CBAM put a discriminatory fee on imports from developing countries in comparison to imported goods from developed countries, for instance, the value of CBAM tariff on 100 tonnes of crude steel produced in India will be \$ 22,260/- while the tariff for the same amount of crude steel produced

in the USA would be just \$ 10,600/-. India is likely to be affected adversely by CBAM as it “could impose a price burden of 25% on the value of high-emitting goods exported to the EU from India” (Dev & Goswami, 2024, pp.24-28).

The EU has emphasised that the CBAM is designed to be compliant with international trade laws and is open to dialogue and cooperation with trading partners to address concerns.

3) **Alliance for Transformative Action on Climate and Health:** Alliance for Transformative Action on Climate and Health (ATACH) represents a critical intersection of climate change and public health. Launched to address the health impacts of climate change by using the collective power of the WHO (World Health Organisation), ATACH aims to promote resilient health systems, reduce healthcare emissions, and advocate for climate action as a public health priority.

Climate change is increasingly recognized as one of the most significant global health threats of the 21st century. Rising temperatures, extreme weather events, and changing patterns of disease pose substantial risks to human health. The World Health Organization (WHO) has highlighted the urgent need for health systems to adapt to these challenges. In response, the Alliance for Transformative Action on Climate and Health (ATACH) was launched to integrate health considerations into climate policies and build resilient health systems.

4) **Resilience and Sustainability Trust (RST)** - The Resilience and Sustainability Trust (RST) is an initiative by the International Monetary Fund (IMF) aimed at addressing long-term structural challenges that threaten economic stability, including climate change, pandemics, and other global shocks. In recent years, global challenges such as climate

change, pandemics, and other systemic risks have increasingly threatened economic stability and growth. Traditional financial mechanisms have often fallen short in addressing these long-term structural challenges. The International Monetary Fund (IMF) established the Resilience and Sustainability Trust (RST) to provide financial support and policy advice to countries facing these systemic risks, promoting resilience and sustainability in the global economy.

5) **The US Green New Deal:** The New Economic Foundation (NEF), a London-based organization published a report entitled “*The Green New Deal*” in 2008 in the backdrop of the 2007-08 financial crisis to address the issues of “financial breakdown, climate change, and biodiversity collapse” however, before this group, in January 2007, Thomas L Friedman in a column in The New York Times entitled “*A Warning from the Garden*” called for a “Green New Deal” particularly in the energy sector by stating that “We need more of everything, solar, wind, hydro, ethanol, biodiesel, clean coal and nuclear power— and conservation” (Pettifor 2022, p. 23). The Green New Deal (GND) is a comprehensive and ambitious framework proposed to address climate change and economic inequality simultaneously. Climate change and economic inequality are two of the most pressing challenges facing the world today. The Green New Deal (GND) is a proposal that seeks to tackle these issues through an integrated approach. Inspired by President Franklin D. Roosevelt's New Deal, which aimed to address the Great Depression, the GND combines environmental sustainability with economic reform. The term gained significant traction in the United States with the proposal introduced by Congresswoman Alexandria Ocasio-Cortez and Senator Ed Markey in 2019. The GND aims to address the economic and

environmental crises through large-scale government intervention and investment.

3.2 INDIA'S CLIMATE AGENDA

Nature has always been an inalienable part of Indian ethos and culture from time immemorial. Nature worship in different forms is the very essence of Indian texts that have emphasized 'environmental ethics' and 'wholeness' & 'interdependence' of different forms of lives on the planet with 'abiotic' components of nature. Colonial powers started plundering the natural resources of India, leading to 'commodification and commercialization' of nature. The present ecological degradation is the result of that very process which continues even after independence.

Today Climate Change is affecting the Indian ecosystem, economy, and society adversely with more frequency and intensity with each passing year. India, with its vast and diverse geography, is highly vulnerable to the impacts of climate change. Rising temperatures, changing precipitation patterns, and increased frequency of extreme weather events pose significant threats to the country's agriculture, water resources, health, and overall economic stability (Kumar et al., 2020; Aggarwal, 2008). A McKinsey Global Institute Study titled "*Will India get too hot to work?*" concludes that lost hours of heat-exposed workforce due to excessive heat and humidity could cost India about 2.5 to 4.5 % of GDP (roughly \$ 150-250 billion) by 2030 (McKinsey Global Institute, 2020). Given climate change's increased economic and social cost, India has taken comprehensive steps to combat the phenomenon. However, India has advocated the "polluters pay principle" (PPP) in the global climate governance platforms owing to their historical responsibilities of advanced countries. Nevertheless, it was in India's interest to take

effective and substantial steps to mitigate the emission and to enhance the adaptation capabilities to develop a resilient ecosystem to meet any disaster.

The Climate Agenda of India has been a “Three-Fold Climate Agenda” i.e. Advocacy, Alliance, and Actions.

Figure 3.1: India’s Three-fold Climate Agenda

Source: Author’s representation.

3.2.1 ADVOCACY AND COMMITMENTS

Since the first global effort on environmental protection at the ‘United Nations Conference on Human Environment in Stockholm, India has taken a comprehensive approach to the issues of ‘development of people’ and ‘conservation of environment’ by emphasizing the need for collaborative efforts to deal with these linked problems. Then Indian Prime Minister Mrs. Indra Gandhi’s impressive words “*Is poverty not the biggest polluter?*” resonates even today in the Indian approach of bringing out people from the clutches of abject poverty while making efforts for environmental protection. India being a party to the Montreal Protocol, a protocol to protect the depleting ozone layer by phasing out the depleting substances, played a significant role in establishing the

‘Multilateral Fund’, the main financial mechanism for implementing provisions under the Protocol.

During the negotiations at the Rio de Janeiro ‘Earth Summit’ and the ‘United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change’ (UNFCCC), India advocated for making the treaties ‘fair’ and ‘pragmatic’ with provisions reflecting the realities and needs of the developing world. India vociferously advocated for the ‘historical responsibility’ of advanced economies and played a vital role in making provisions based on the principle of “Common But Differentiated Responsibilities and Respective Capabilities” (CBDRRC) in the interest of the developing parties. The provisions of the Kyoto Protocol (1997), reflected these efforts in the ‘binding emission cut’ clauses for Annex-I countries. These provisions gained wider acceptance among the developing and the least developed countries and helped in making these treaties global in approach and actions.

In the changing scenario of the post-Kyoto Protocol, India took the initiative to part with the burden of degradation of the global commons more responsibly. India ratified the Paris Agreement in 2015 and engaged in a “positive, creative, and forward-looking manner” (INDC, 2022: p.3). The objective of Indian climate diplomacy has been to establish “an effective, cooperative, and equitable global architecture based on climate justice and the principle of equity” and CBDRRC as mentioned in the provisions of UNFCCC. India advocated for a comprehensive architecture that takes care of differential needs, aspirations, and capabilities of the parties and addresses the whole range of issues including Mitigation, Adaptation, financial and Technological Transfer, Capacity Building, and Transparency. Under the provisions of

the Paris Agreement, India declared its voluntary contributions, INDCs (Intended Nationally Determined Contributions), making commitments to be achieved to meet the 1.5 degrees goal of the Paris Agreement in response to “COP decisions 1/CP.19 and 1/CP.20” to be implemented during the period 2021-2030:

- “1. To put forward and further propagate a healthy and sustainable way of living based on traditions and values of conservation and moderation.*
- 2. To adopt a climate friendly and a cleaner path than the one followed hitherto by others at corresponding level of economic development.*
- 3. To reduce the emissions intensity of its GDP by 33 to 35 percent by 2030 from 2005 level.*
- 4. To achieve about 40 percent cumulative electric power installed capacity from non-fossil fuel-based energy resources by 2030 with the help of transfer of technology and low-cost international finance including from Green Climate Fund (GCF).*
- 5. To create an additional carbon sink of 2.5 to 3 billion tonnes of CO₂ equivalent through additional forest and tree cover by 2030.*
- 6. To better adapt to climate change by enhancing investments in development programmes in sectors vulnerable to climate change, particularly agriculture, water resources, Himalayan region, coastal regions, health and disaster management.*

7. *To mobilize domestic and new & additional funds from developed countries to implement the above mitigation and adaptation actions in view of the resource required and the resource gap.*
8. *To build capacities, create domestic framework and international architecture for quick diffusion of cutting-edge climate technology in India and for joint collaborative R&D for such future technologies.” (INDC, 2022, p.29)*

In August 2022 India updated its INDCs to enhance India’s contribution to strengthening the global response to the climate crisis, as the provisions of the Paris Agreement. The revised contributions were declared seven years after it had submitted its first INDCs to UNFCCC under the agreement. The updated targets included:

1. *“To reduce the emissions intensity of the country’s GDP by 45% by 2030 as against the earlier target of 33-35% (compared to 2005 emission levels).*
2. *To achieve about 50% cumulative installed electric power capacity from non-fossil fuel sources (including nuclear) by 2030, as against the 40% targeted earlier.” (IDR, 2024).*

3.2.1.1 FIVE NECTAR ELEMENTS (PANCHAMRIT):

During COP 26 in Glasgow, UK, India presented more extensive, deep, and ambitious targets as “five nectar elements (*Panchamrit*) as its climate actions. At The Summit, Prime Minister Sh. Narendra Modi presented the Panchamrit or five time-bound India’s climate pledges:

“First- India will reach its non-fossil energy capacity to 500 GW by 2030.

Second- India will meet 50 percent of its energy requirements from renewable energy by 2030.

Third- India will reduce the total projected carbon emissions by one billion tonnes from now onwards till 2030.

Fourth- By 2030, India will reduce the carbon intensity of its economy by less than 45 percent.

And fifth- by the year 2070, India will achieve the target of Net Zero. These panchamrits will be an unprecedented contribution of India to climate action.” (PIB, GoI, 2021)

In its submission to UNFCCC as per the provisions of the Paris Agreement, India declared that it had achieved two targets of INDCs well before the time and its progress had been quite impressive in achieving the committed targets as per below:

Figure: 3.2 Indian performance in achieving INDCs

NDC (2015)	Target (2030)	Achievement
Non-fossil fuel based electric installed capacity	40% cumulative	43.8% (August 2023). Target achieved 9 years ahead of committed time
Reduce emissions intensity of GDP	33-35% over 2005 levels	Reduced by 33 per cent between 2005 and 2019
Additional carbon sink	2.5-3.0 billion tons	1.97 billion tons (2021)

Source: MoEFCC & UNDP India, 2023

3.2.1.2 LONG TERM- LOW EMISSION DEVELOPMENT

STRATEGY:

Further, at COP 27, in Sharm el Sheikh in 2022, India announced its LT-LED (Long Term- Low Emission Development) strategy, focusing on the key carbon-intensive sectors to make them compatible with the low-carbon growth model. Historically, there has been a link between growth and carbon emission, however, in recent years this coupling has broken and there is growth with low carbon emission. Indian LT-LED also charts the long-term plan to design and prepare policies and programs compatible with environmental and climate needs. The LT-LED strategy focuses on the following aspects:

- *“Low Carbon Development of Electricity Systems Consistent with Enhanced Development Benefits*
- *Develop an Integrated, Efficient, Inclusive Low-Carbon Transport System*
- *Promoting Adaptation in Urban Design, Energy and Material-Efficiency in Buildings, and Sustainable Urbanisation*
- *Promote Economy-Wide Decoupling of Growth from Emissions and Development of an Efficient, Innovative Low-Emission Industrial System*
- *CO2 Removal and Related Engineering Solutions*
- *Enhancement of Forest and Vegetative Cover Consistent with Socio-Economic and Ecological Considerations.*
- *Economic and Financial Aspects of Low-Carbon Develop”*

(MoEFCC, 2022, pp.3-11).

3.2.2 ALLIANCES WITH GLOBAL ACTORS

Since the beginning of climate governance at the global level, India has always supported the need for collaboration among the nations to establish an architecture of climate governance based on the principles of equity and fairness. The per capita emission of India is well below even the world average emission, nevertheless, India has shown a proactive role in taking steps to mitigate the emission and forged alliances with partners. India's outlook on global concerns revolves around the phrase "Vasudhava Kutumbkam" (the whole world is one family). Climate change being a global and collective problem, it can be tackled only through multilateral, collective, and collaborative efforts and actions at international cooperation (MoEA, 2021).

3.2.2.1 INTERNATIONAL SOLAR ALLIANCE (ISA)

Given the importance of solar energy in the energy basket to decarbonize the energy sector which is the most significant source of carbon emission, during the Conference of Parties (COP 21), held in Paris in 2015, India conceptualized an alliance of countries located in the tropical zone where solar energy is available in plenty. International Solar Alliance is the first major international institution under the leadership of India. It is a Joint Endeavour by India and France to collaborate on research, design, finance, and technical know-how in the field of solar energy ecosystems. It is an "action-oriented, member-driven, collaborative platform" to develop and deploy solar energy to ensure energy access and energy security to its member nations as a cost-effective and transformational solution to help them develop their low-carbon development trajectories (ISA, n.d.). First, its membership was limited to the countries located in the tropical zone, however, now it is open to all

countries, and as per its official website, the membership has reached to 102 countries. *The 'Towards 1000'* strategy is the guiding pillar of ISA; it is based on certain goals that ISA seeks to achieve including:

- Mobilizing \$ 1000 billion investment in solar energy solutions by 2030
- Delivering clean energy access to 1000 million persons
- Installation of a capacity of 1000 GW solar energy
- Help in mitigating global emissions to the tune of 1000 million tonnes of CO₂/year.

Solar energy provides a unique opportunity for structural transformation in the energy ecosystems of the countries to combat the challenge of climate change. With solar energy solutions, we may unravel the potential of the seamless energy transition, energy access, and security at affordable prices. It's going to transform lives around the globe from small hamlets in remote locations to bustling urban areas.

3.2.2.2 COALITION FOR DISASTER RESILIENT INFRASTRUCTURE (CDRI)

At the 2019 UN Climate Action Summit, India launched the *Coalition for Disaster Resilient Infrastructure (CDRI)*, a multi-stakeholder global partnership to build resilient infrastructure in member countries to ensure their sustainable development. It has 40 member countries and 7 member organizations. Given its multi-stakeholder partnership nature, UN agencies, academic institutions, multilateral development banks, private sector may be the partners apart from the partner countries (Sablok, 2023). It seeks to reduce infrastructural losses from disasters. CDRI has several strategic initiatives through which it seeks to fulfill its objectives

of making the infrastructure resilient in its member countries. The ‘Urban Infrastructure Resilience Programme (UIRP)’ aims to support urban areas in Lower Middle-Income Countries (LMICs) and Small Island Developing States (SIDS) in the field of data and tool application, and knowledge sharing to enhance capacity in designing, operation, maintenance of infrastructure, and extending technical help. Cities are the powerhouses of the global economy and contribute more than 80% of global GDP. CDRI aims at investing and forging partnerships to achieve the shared objectives and aspirations of the member countries. It states, “*CDRI's Urban Infrastructure Resilience Programme (UIRP) aims to enhance urban livability by promoting resilient infrastructure planning and implementing data-driven decision-making processes to manage urban shocks and stresses*” (CDRI, n.d.).

Infrastructure for Resilient Island States (IRIS) is another strategic initiative of CDRI. It was jointly launched by the Prime Ministers of India, the United Kingdom, Jamaica, Mauritius, and Australia during COP 26 in Glasgow, UK. It seeks to achieve “improved resilience of SIDS infrastructure to climate change and disaster risks”. It further aims to strengthen knowledge and partnerships for resilient infrastructure in SIDS and make provisions for “gender equality” and “disability inclusion” through improved and resilient infrastructure.

3.2.2.3 LEADERSHIP GROUP FOR INDUSTRY TRANSITION (LEADIT)

At the UN Climate Action Summit 2019 in New York India and Sweden launched the Leadership Group for Industry Transition (Leadit) as a multi-stakeholder group of companies, countries, academicians, institutions, and other actors that are committed to enhancing climate

actions. The industrial sector is the backbone of the modern economy and a major source of carbon emissions. Leadit seeks to focus on the industrial sector in realizing the NDCs. Its mission is to “bring together countries, companies, and industry experts to achieve net-zero emissions from heavy industry (hard-to-abate industry sectors) by 2050” (MoEA, 2019) and it accounts for 50% of the world economy through its countries and companies’ membership. It has developed three industry transition trackers: The Transition Tracker helps compare and identify industry transitional plans of member countries and industrial sectors. The Green Steel Tracker and the Cement Technology Tracker speak about announcements of public investments in low-carbon pathways in the carbon-intensive sectors of steel and cement (Leadit, n.d.)

3.2.2.4 G-20 SUMMIT, NEW DELHI AND GLOBAL BIOFUEL ALLIANCE

India took the opportunity to forward the concerns and aspirations of the ‘Global South’ during its presidency of G-20 during 2022-23. India made tremendous efforts to mobilize and unite the voice of the global south on key issues of development and global governance. The theme of G-20 under the Indian presidency, “*One Earth, One Family, One Future*” speaks about the universal and inclusive approach of its outlook. G-20 summit culminated in a series of commitments to addressing the issues of climate change. These commitments reflect the urgency and gravity of the problem and would be of significance in making a sustainable and climate-resilient future. These commitments include:

- Attaining Global Net Zero GHG emissions or achieving carbon neutrality by mid-century
- Strengthening Economy-wide targets in NDCs

- Protecting, conserving, and managing forests and mitigating wildfires
- Three-fold increment in global renewable energy capacity by 2030
- The new collective and quantified target of climate finance starting from a base of \$ 100 billion per year (Bie, 2023; MoEA, 2023).

The commitments mentioned above and targets are of paramount importance to the global economy and have far-reaching consequences for achieving low-carbon and sustainable development pathways. However, these would require a substantial amount of money and technologies to be invested around the globe in general developing countries and least-developed countries in particular. Further, these transitions to green and clean energy pathways may entail short-term costs and are likely to yield long-term benefits in the future. However, a “just transition” is needed to save the livelihood and other interests of marginalised sections of society engaged in grey energy.

Global Biofuel Alliance was launched by India, USA, Brazil, Singapore, Bangladesh, Argentina, Italy, UAE, and Mauritius on the sideline of the New Delhi G-20 Summit in September 2023. It’s an Indian initiative as the president of G-20, and it is said to be the “New Phase of Leadership on Energy Transition” (MoPNG, GoI, n.d.). This alliance is also a multi-stakeholder partnership of governments, industrial corporations, and international organizations to bring together consumers and producers of biofuels for the deployment and development of these new-generation fuels. The alliance seeks to expedite the uptake of “biofuels through facilitating capacity-building exercises across the value chain technical support for national programs and promoting policy lessons-sharing, technology advancements” (MoPNG, GoI, n.d.).

3.2.2.5 LIFE (LIFESTYLE FOR ENVIRONMENT)

LiFE (Lifestyle for Environment) is an India-led global mass movement. India articulated LiFE at COP 26 in Glasgow on November 01, 2021. The LiFE is a public movement to transform the behavioural aspect of individuals, communities, and other stakeholders to adopt lifestyles compatible with nature. It is a call to change from oneself to see the change in the outer world. The underlining theme of the mission is to change the “*Mindless and Destructive Consumption-Throwaway Culture*” to a “*Mindful and Deliberate Utilization-Recycle Culture*”. It has the potential to revolutionize the whole range of our economic ecosystem ranging from food habits and dietary choices to the way we travel, to our dressing and clothing, to water management, to energy consumption, to housing and dwelling designs. Mission LiFE aims at mobilizing at least “one billion Indian and other global citizens to take individual and collective action” to protect and conserve our environment during the 2022-2028 period (NITI Ayog, 2022, p.8).

The LiFE is based on the philosophy of the Indian saying: **प्रकृतिः रक्षति रक्षिता**, (*Nature protects if she is protected*), which is also the motto of the Indian Ministry of Environment, Forest, and Climate Change. It seeks to bring about paradigm changes or better say, transform the way we produce and consume in the current economic ecosystem. India is better placed to propagate a sustainable and healthy alternative of living due to its ancient rich traditions and culture of “*wholeness or compositeness*” of all forms of life on this planet along with the “abiotic” components of nature. This rich heritage of respecting ‘*others*’ (other people, other species) makes India a natural leader that can lead by example. The LiFE

is based upon the environment-friendly culture and traditions of Indian society.

Further, unlike other “top-down” approaches it is a “bottom-up” approach that places greater faith and roles in the individuals' and communities' capacities to bring about transformational changes. This gives a sense of participation and action-oriented activism to people to transform the mission, in a true sense, into a global mass movement. This public participation is expected to achieve the goal of transforming ‘*consumption-centric*’ persons into “P-3, *Pro Planet People*”.

The Three Core Shifts of Mission LiFE are:

- a) *Change in Demand (Phase-I)*: It is based on the theories of demand by nudging people around the globe to adopt environment-friendly actions and products of consumption in their day-to-day lives.
- b) *Change in Supply (Phase II)*: the changes made in Phase I are expected to yield changes in the supply side as large-scale demand generated by individuals' changed behaviors, nudge the producing units and market to respond as per the need of revised demand.
- c) *Change in Policy (Phase-III)*: in the light of changed demand and supply dynamics of consumption and production, governments and industrial policies are expected to make fundamental and structural shifts to support the changed and sustainable consumption and production (MoEFCC, 2022, pp. 77-78).

Figure 2.3: Inter-relationship between three Core Shifts in Mission LiFE

Source: NITI Ayog, 2022

Since Mission LiFE was launched in 2022, the 75th year of India's Independence, to commemorate the occasion, “75 individual LiFE actions” that are specific and measurable, easy to practice, and non-disruptive to ongoing economic activities across 7 categories have been presented. These categories include: “1. Energy consumption; 2. Water consumption; 3. Reduced consumption of single-use plastic; 4. Adopting sustainable food systems; 5. Reduction of wastes (Swachhata actions); 6. Adoption of healthy lifestyles; and 7. Reduction in e-waste” (MoEFCC, 2022, p. 78).

India aspires to achieve several Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) through the interventions of the LiFE Mission. For instance, SDG 11 focuses on “sustainable cities and communities”; SDG 12 talks about responsible “production and consumption”; SDG 13 concerns Climate Change; SDG 14 and 15 emphasize “life underwater” and “life on land”

respectively, all these goals aspire and promotion of sustainable utilization of natural resources.

The impact of collective action under the LiFE Mission is expected to be substantial in quantity. As per the study by the United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP), even if one out of eight billion people adopt environmentally compatible behaviour in their daily activities, it would lead to a drastic drop of up to 20% in carbon emissions (UNEP, 2020). NITI Ayog estimated the impact of LiFE against business-as-usual by one billion Indians in 2022-23 to 2027-28, the effect is expected to be significant, e.g. switching off cars/two-wheelers at red lights/railways crossing could save up to **‘22.5 billion kWh of energy’**; closing running taps when not in use might save a whopping **‘9 trillion liters water’**; waste food if composting at home could save **‘15 billion tonnes** of waste adding to landfills (NITI Ayog, 2022, p.13).

India has been successful in implementing several large-scale behavioural change programmes. The rich experience of behaviour interventional programmes may be leveraged for LiFE Mission. When other countries are focusing on the tools of “policy and regulatory measures” for addressing environmental problems, India has successfully harnessed the power of collective actions of people to find solutions to complex issues, for instance, the *Swachh Sagar Surakshit Sagar* campaign seeks to remove about fifteen thousand tonnes waste from 75 beaches in 75 days; the *Swachh Bharat Mission (SBM)* revolutionize toilet construction wave by building over 100 million toilets in rural areas within 7 years period; and similarly, *Ujjwala Scheme* makes great strides into Indian kitchens by increasing the penetration of LPG connections to 99.8 percent households (NITI Ayog, 2022, p.4).

Despite its obvious benefits for combating climate change, these individual action-oriented programmes can be criticized for being the plots of capitalists' lobbies for shifting the responsibility of fighting climate change. Instead of making structural changes in the economic ecosystem which is mainly responsible for creating the problem, vested interests around the globe have now shifted their stands from outright climate denialism to obstructionism through “misinformation and misdirection” and shifting the burden to individuals and communities (Mann, 2021).

3.2.3 NATIONAL ACTIONS

On its home turf, India is already making strides in undertaking climate actions and translating its vision and global commitments through various policies and programmes into impactful outcomes. India's climate policies and actions with remarkable pace, scale, and intensity helped it achieve two targets of its INDCs well before the target timeline. India has made policies and programmes across its entire economy at horizontal and vertical levels. India has announced many ambitious and impactful commitments as mentioned above under the provisions of the UNFCCC. India's overarching Action Plan is translated into the “National Action Plan on Climate Change” and various subsequent programmes and policies at the national and state (units) levels have been adopted to serve the purpose across the whole gamut of economic activities and behavioural aspects of individuals and communities along with organisations, institutions, administrative departments, and industrial houses.

3.2.3.1 NATIONAL ACTION PLAN ON CLIMATE CHANGE (NAPCC)

Recognising these challenges, the Government of India launched the National Action Plan on Climate Change (NAPCC) in 2008 to promote sustainable development while addressing climate change.

The NAPCC was developed in response to India's growing recognition of the need to address climate change through a coordinated national strategy. The Prime Minister's Council on Climate Change (PMCCC) launched the plan in June 2008, reflecting India's commitment to sustainable development and its proactive stance on global climate issues. The NAPCC was developed within the broader context of international climate agreements, such as the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC) and the Kyoto Protocol. Domestically, the plan aligns with India's Five-Year Plans and other national policies aimed at promoting economic growth, social development, and environmental sustainability.

The NAPCC mentions the continuing nature of climate actions, it categorically states, “adaptation to climate change is a long-term and continuing process” (NAPCC, 2008). The NAPCC consists of eight national missions, each targeting specific climate change mitigation and adaptation areas (PMO, GOI, 2008). These missions collectively aim to address various aspects of India's climate challenges and promote sustainable development.

1. National Solar Mission (NSM): The National Solar Mission (NSM) of India, launched in January 2010 as part of the National Action Plan on Climate Change, aims to promote the development and use of solar energy for power generation and other applications, with the

ultimate objective of making solar energy competitive with fossil-based options. The mission is a key initiative for India's commitment to sustainable development and climate change mitigation, aiming to achieve substantial reductions in the cost of solar power generation.

Initially, the NSM targeted achieving 20 GW of grid-connected solar power by 2022, but this target was later scaled up to 100 GW under the leadership of Prime Minister Narendra Modi, reflecting the growing emphasis on renewable energy. This ambitious target includes 40 GW from rooftop solar projects and 60 GW from large and medium-scale grid-connected solar power projects. The mission also promotes off-grid applications, including solar water heaters, solar lighting systems, and solar pumps for irrigation, aiming to enhance energy access in rural areas and reduce dependency on conventional fuels.

However, the NSM faces challenges, including the need for robust grid infrastructure to handle intermittent solar power, financial constraints faced by distribution companies, and land acquisition issues for large-scale projects. There is also a necessity for continued policy support and innovation to achieve the long-term sustainability of solar power initiatives. In conclusion, the National Solar Mission has been a transformative initiative in India's renewable energy landscape, significantly advancing the adoption of solar power. While challenges remain, the mission's successes provide a solid foundation for future growth and development in the sector.

2. National Mission for Enhanced Energy Efficiency (NMEEE): As per the provisions of the Energy Conservation Act of 2001, the implementation of energy efficiency became legally mandatory through the Bureau of Energy Efficiency (BEE) for central

government and designed agencies. To achieve the objective, four new initiatives were envisaged namely, “a market-based mechanism to enhance cost-effectiveness”; “accelerating the shift to energy-efficient appliances”; creating a mechanism to “help finance demand side management”; and “developing fiscal instruments” for promoting energy efficiency (NAPCC, 2008, p. 3). These guiding principles are translated into four major initiatives:

- i) Perform Achieve and Trade (PAT) Scheme:** This scheme mandates energy reduction targets for large energy-intensive industries and distributes Energy Saving Certificates (ESCerts) upon achievement of these targets. ESCerts can be traded, creating a market-based mechanism for energy efficiency.
 - ii) Market Transformation for Energy Efficiency (MTEE):** MTEE aims to accelerate the shift to energy-efficient appliances and equipment in designated sectors through innovative business models for making products more affordable.
 - iii) Energy Efficiency Financing Platform (EEFP):** The EEFP seeks to create mechanisms to help finance demand-side energy efficiency projects by providing technical assistance to financial institutions and investors.
 - iv) Framework for Energy Efficiency Economic Development (FEEED):** FEEED aims at developing fiscal instruments to promote energy efficiency initiatives by hedging against investment risks (BEE, GoI).
- 3. National Mission on Sustainable Habitat (NMSH):** As part of the NAPCC, the National Mission on Sustainable Habitat aims to promote low-carbon urban growth with reduced carbon intensity

build resilient cities, and strengthen their capacities to ‘bounce back’ better at the face of climate change-related disasters. Originally released in 2010, NMSH has now been updated and revised as **NMSH 2.0** to accommodate the commitments of the Paris Agreement.

It has five thematic areas. The first ‘Energy and Green Buildings’ aims at the reduction of energy consumption and shifting toward clean energy sources; the second area of ‘Urban Planning, Green Cover and Biodiversity’ focuses on integrated climate-sensitive planning and preservation of biodiversity; the third area ‘Mobility and Air Quality’ emphasises the need of strategies on inclusive and multi-modal mobility; the fourth area ‘Water Management’ focuses on augmentation and management of water resources by adopting “rain-water harvesting, rejuvenation of water bodies, and recycling of wastewater; and the fifth area talks about ‘Waste Management’ through waste reduction and waste management actions by adopting 3R (Reduce, Reuse, and Recycle) approach (NMSH, 2021, p. xv-xvi).

4. National Water Mission (NWM): The NAPCC envisages a national water mission “to ensure integrated water resource management helping to conserve water, minimize wastage and ensure more equitable distribution both across and within states” (NAPCC, 2008: p.4). It seeks to develop a framework to achieve water efficiency by 20% through “differential entitlements and pricing”. The National Water Policy sought to be revised to better manage basin levels for meeting variability in precipitation and river flows given the events of climate change. The ‘Technical Document’ of the NAPCC, annexed with it talks about the “*key areas to*

(a) studies on the management of surface water resources,
(b) management and regulation of groundwater resources,
(c) upgrading storage structures for fresh and drainage systems for wastewater,
(d) conservation of wetlands, and
(e) development of desalination technologies etc. required to be considered while preparing the comprehensive document for the National Water Mission” (NWM, n.d.).

National Water Mission has five major goals namely: “(i) comprehensive water database in the public domain; (ii) assessment of the impact of climate change on water resources; (iii) promotion of citizen and state actions for water conservation and augmentation; (iv) increasing water use efficiency by 20%; and (v) promotion of basin level integrated water resources management” (NWM, GoI).

5. National Mission for Sustaining the Himalayan Eco-system

(NMSHE): The Himalayan ecosystem, a vital lifeline for millions of people due to its plentiful natural resources is much sensitive and vulnerable to the impacts of climate change. It is also a global biodiversity hotspot that faces significant threats due to climate change, deforestation, and unsustainable development practices. To address these challenges, the National Mission for Sustaining the Himalayan Ecosystem (NMSHE) was launched under the aegis of NAPCC. The NMSHE aims to:

- Conserve the Himalayan ecosystem's biodiversity and ecological integrity.
- Promote sustainable development in the Himalayan region.

- Reduce the vulnerability of local communities to climate change impacts.
- Enhance the resilience of the Himalayan ecosystem to natural and anthropogenic disturbances.

To achieve the above-mentioned objectives, the mission seeks to generate four types of national capacities namely – a) “Human and knowledge capacities, b) Institutional capacities, c) Capabilities for evidence-based policy building and governance, and d) Continuous self-learning for balancing between forces of Nature and actions of mankind” (DST, 2010a).

6. National Mission for a Green India (NMGI): The National Mission for a Green India is a significant mission under the NAPCC. Its main focus is to restore and enhance India’s decreasing forest cover and respond to the crisis of climate change through measures of mitigation and adaptation. It seeks to adopt an ‘integrated cross-sectoral’ approach to include the public and private sectors and communities to participate in the mission at the level of planning, designing, decision-making, implementing, and evaluating. The major goals of the mission are:

- *“To increase forest/tree cover to the extent of 5 million hectares (mha) and improve the quality of forest/tree cover on another 5 mha of forest/non-forest lands;*
- *To improve/enhance eco-system services like carbon sequestration and storage (in forests and other ecosystems), hydrological services, and biodiversity; along with provisioning services like fuel, fodder, and timber and non-timber forest produces (NTFPs); and*

- *To increase forest-based livelihood income of about 3 million households” (MoEFCC)*

7. National Mission for Sustainable Agriculture (NMSA): The National Mission for Sustainable Agriculture (NMSA) is a pivotal initiative launched to address the pressing challenges of food security, climate change, and rural development in the face of climate change. By promoting sustainable agricultural practices, the NMSA aims to enhance agricultural productivity, reduce environmental impact, and improve the livelihoods of farmers. The NMSA has several key objectives:

- *“To make agriculture more productive, sustainable, remunerative and climate resilient*
- *To adopt comprehensive soil health management practices based on soil fertility maps, soil test-based application of macro & micro nutrients, judicious use of fertilizers, etc.;*
- *To optimize utilization of water resources through efficient water management to expand coverage for achieving ‘more crop per drop’;*
- *To develop the capacity of farmers & stakeholders, in conjunction with other ongoing Missions e.g. National Mission on Agriculture Extension & Technology, National Food Security Mission, National Initiative for Climate Resilient Agriculture (NICRA), etc., in the domain of climate change adaptation and mitigation measures” (NMSA, 2014: p.2).*

Strategies and Components of NMSA: To achieve its objectives, the NMSA employs a range of strategies and components:

- **Organic Farming:** Promoting organic farming practices to reduce chemical inputs and enhance soil fertility.
 - **Integrated Farming Systems:** Integrating crop production, livestock rearing, and aquaculture to optimize resource utilization and reduce waste.
 - **Soil Health Management:** Implementing practices like crop rotation, green manuring, and cover cropping to improve soil health and fertility.
 - **Water Conservation:** Promoting water-saving technologies, such as drip irrigation and rainwater harvesting, to reduce water consumption.
 - **Climate-Smart Agriculture:** Adopting agricultural practices that are resilient to climate change, such as drought-tolerant crops and agroforestry.
 - **Farmer Training and Capacity Building:** Providing farmers with training and education on sustainable agricultural techniques.
 - **Market Development:** Supporting the development of markets for sustainable agricultural products (NMSA, 2014).
8. **National Mission on Strategic Knowledge for Climate Change (NMSKCC):** The National Mission on Strategic Knowledge for Climate Change (NMSKCC) was released in July 2010 under the purview of the Department of Science & Technology, Ministry of Science & Technology. A sound and strategic knowledge system is necessary to identify, plan, formulate, and implement policy-driven actions to tackle the challenge of climate change. The NMSKCC focuses on “mapping of the knowledge and data resources relevant to

climate change; identification of knowledge gaps, and formation of global technology watch groups to help accomplish the task of technology selection and prioritization; creation of new (about five) dedicated centres within the existing institutional framework for building of human capacities by instituting 50 Chair professorships on climate change and about 200 trained professionals” (DST, 2010b, p. 7-8).

3.2.3.2 MAJOR POLICIES, SCHEMES, AND PROGRAMMES TO GIVE EFFECT TO N APCC

To achieve the commitments, India has made at different international fora, and to realize the obvious co-benefits of mitigating GHG emissions, it has taken several impactful and far-reaching policy interventions to translate the envisaged visions mentioned in the NAPCC. The major policies, schemes, and programmes are given in brief to comprehend the range of actions taken by the Government of India:

- a) UJALA (Unnat Jyoti by Affordable LEDs for All):**
The UJALA scheme launched in 2015, aims at providing LED bulbs, tube lights, and other electric appliances like fans at very affordable prices to transform lighting to energy efficient habitats.
- b) Pradhan Mantri Ujjwala Yojana (PMUY):** It was launched in May 2016 to transform the Indian cooking ecosystem into clean and safe LPG fuel instead of polluting biomass fuels. This is one of the government's flagship programmes and one of the most successful behavioural change initiatives.
- c) PM Surya Ghar Yojna:** This scheme was launched in 2022 as *Muft Bijli* (Free Electricity) to install solar panels on the roof of

one crore households by providing them subsidies. It envisages mitigating substantial carbon emissions and providing financial relief to these households making their electricity bills minimal and ultimately zero (PM Surya Ghar, n.d.).

- d) **National Policy on Biofuels, 2018:** The Biofuel Policy aims to achieve 20% ethanol-petrol blending and increase the share of biodiesel in diesel to 5% by 2030 (MoEFCC, 2022, p.36), thereby reducing carbon emissions and strategic dependency.
- e) **National Green Hydrogen Mission (NGHM):** This mission was launched in 2022 with the intended objective of making India a leading hub of Green Hydrogen production, usage, and export globally. Green Hydrogen may help in transitioning the Indian energy ecosystem. India aspires to be energy-independent by 2047 and Net Zero by 2070 and hydrogen is said to be the fuel of the future (MNRE).
- f) **Jal Jeevan Mission- Har Ghar Jal (JJM):** The JJM is also a flagship programmes of the GoI, aiming at providing safe, potable, and ensured water supply through pipelines at door steps of all households by 2024-25. As per the dashboard of JJM as of 14 Oct 2024, households with tap water stood at 15,20,74,074 (78.63%) out of 19.33 crore households (JJM, 2024).
- g) **Atal Mission for Rejuvenation and Urban Transformation (AMRUT):** It aspires to provide basic civic amenities such as public transport, waste management, water supply, sewerage, green spaces, parks, and recreation centers to

improve the quality of life for all especially the poor and the disadvantaged. (MoHUA).

- h) Smart Cities Mission:** The objective of SCM is to develop in 100 cities core infrastructure to give their dwellers a decent quality of life with a healthy environment through the application of ‘Smart’ and technology-driven solutions. It has 8,063 projects to the tune of Rs.1.64 lakh crores (Smart Cities, n.d.; MoHUA, n.d.).
- i) Swachh Bharat Mission-Grameen (SBM-G):** The SBM-G is another flagship programme of the Government of India to transform the sanitation and hygiene narrative into a mass movement to make the country ‘Open Defecation Free (ODF)’. It revolutionizes the sanitation paradigm through nationwide mass participation making it the largest behavioral change movement around the globe (Swachh Bharat Mission-Grameen, n.d.).

The NAPCC aims to reduce greenhouse gas emissions, enhance energy efficiency, and promote the use of renewable energy sources. These efforts contribute to mitigating climate change and improving air and water quality. The plan also focuses on conserving biodiversity and protecting ecosystems, which provides a range of ecological benefits. It seeks to promote green growth and sustainable development, which can drive economic benefits. This includes job creation in renewable energy and energy efficiency sectors, increased agricultural productivity, and enhanced resilience to climate impacts. The plan also aims to reduce energy costs and improve resource efficiency, which can boost economic competitiveness. The NAPCC addresses social equity by promoting

inclusive and sustainable development. This includes improving access to clean energy, enhancing water security, and promoting climate-resilient livelihoods. The plan also emphasises the protection of vulnerable communities and the promotion of gender equality in climate initiatives.

Despite having several multifaceted benefits, NAPCC has several challenges to curb its functioning. Securing adequate funding and resources is a significant challenge for the NAPCC. This includes mobilizing public and private investments, managing fiscal constraints, and ensuring efficient use of resources. The scale of the required investments necessitates innovative funding mechanisms and strong financial management. Implementing the NAPCC involves coordination between multiple stakeholders, which can be challenging. This includes aligning the objectives of different ministries, managing inter-state coordination, and addressing institutional silos. Strengthening governance structures and enhancing institutional capacity are crucial for overcoming these challenges. Transitioning to a low-carbon and climate-resilient economy involves significant technological and infrastructure challenges. This includes developing and deploying new technologies, upgrading existing infrastructure, and managing the transition in a way that minimizes disruptions. Addressing these challenges requires substantial investments in research, development, and infrastructure.

3.3 SUB-NATIONAL ACTIONS: UTTAR PRADESH STATE ACTION PLAN ON CLIMATE CHANGE (UP-SAPCC)

The National Action Plan on Climate Change (NAPCC) envisaged broad guidelines and policy frameworks to guide climate actions by outlining a national strategy of development compatible with environmental concerns and dealing with the challenges of climate change. The national

strategy as envisaged in the NAPCC can only yield tangible outcomes if it is adopted and implemented on the ground by the federal units (states) as per their requirements and aspirations keeping in view their specific circumstances. Thus, to make the NAPCC decentralized, states and union territories were requested to formulate their action plans on climate change under the broad guidelines of the NAPCC. Given the federal polity nature of the Indian State, it was necessary to have a vibrant ecosystem of climate policies under the State Action Plan on Climate Change (SAPCC) at the sub-national level.

Under the overarching objectives of the NAPCC, the state of Uttar Pradesh notified its first ‘Uttar Pradesh State Action Plan on Climate Change (UP-SAPCC) by the Department of Environment, Government of Uttar Pradesh in 2014 with 93 priorities under 7 broad missions with an indicative budget of Rs. 46,946 crores. The formulated action plan has the following seven missions:

1. Sustainable Agriculture Mission
2. Solar Mission
3. Energy Efficiency Mission
4. Green UP Forestry Mission
5. Jal Mission
6. Strategic Knowledge Mission and
7. Sustainable Habitat Mission.

(UP SAPCC, 2014: p. 12).

The ‘*Common Framework for Revision of State Action Plan on Climate Change*’ was released by the Ministry of Environment, Forestry, and Climate Change, GoI, in 2008 underscoring the need for revision in the

SAPCCs given the changed climate policy landscape and evolution of the scientific understanding of climate change and its impact on socio-economic spheres in the last decade. The Paris Agreement in 2015 heralded a new era of climate cooperation and negotiations in the post-Kyoto Protocol World order. India is a signatory of the Paris Agreement, a legally binding treaty aiming to limit global warming to below 2⁰ C by 2100, and preferably to 1.5⁰C from the pre-industrial levels. India has submitted its NDCs to the UNFCCC and the same year witnessed a new framework of growth in the form of ‘Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs)’ to be achieved by 2030. Keeping in view the above-mentioned development at the global and national levels, the MoEFCC sought revisions of the SAPCCs to align these with the changed priorities of SDGs, the Paris Agreement, and the Sendai Framework.

Following the policy framework directions by MoEFCC, the Government of Uttar Pradesh revised its SAPCC of 2014 and formulated the ‘**UP SAPCC 2.0**’ implementable during the period 2021 to 2030. In the UP SAPCC 2.0, a total of 41 strategies, covering 187 actions under 8 broad missions have been envisaged to cover the dual objectives of climate action i.e. ‘mitigation’ and ‘adaptation’. About 30% actions out of a total of 187 actions pertain to the category of ‘mitigation’, while 58% of actions are related to the category of ‘adaptation’ to make UP’s cities and villages more climate resilient, and the rest 12% of actions are having nature of both categories. The UP SAPCC 2.0 is more comprehensive and inclusive in comparison to its earlier version. It includes in its actions research, implementation, policy, and training & capacity building components with an estimated budget outlay of Rs. 1,12,204.79 cr.

Figure: 3.4 Prioritisation Framework for UP SAPCC 2.0

Source: UP SAPCC 2.0

The SAPCC 2.0 consists of Eight Missions in their *new avatars*. These include:

1. Sustainable Agriculture Mission
2. Jal Mission
3. Green UP Mission
4. Energy Efficiency Mission and Renewable Energy Mission
5. Sustainable Habitat Mission.
6. Human Health Mission
7. Disaster Management Mission
8. Strategic Knowledge Mission

1. Sustainable Agriculture Mission: UP is an agriculture-based economy where a majority of the population relies on agriculture and allied sectors for its livelihood and subsistence. The weather hazards spurred by climate change have grave consequences due to the multiplicity of impacts when several hazards occur simultaneously. The combined impact of flood and drought along with increased heat makes crop failure more severe on

income and food security of people (IPCC AR 6, 2021). Rainfall & temperature variability and flood & drought proneness make key climate risks in Uttar Pradesh due to its wide areas spreading over 9 ‘Agro-Climatic Zones’. Based on risk assessment and emission mitigation opportunities, the Sustainable Agriculture Mission (SAM), proposed a total of 19 actions across five strategies: a) generating high-resolution weather forecasts to farmers; b) wide-spread training to FPOs on climate-smart agricultural techniques, and practices, and tools to make them aware and addressing climate change impact; c) mainstreaming climate-smart adaptation practices; d) improving water-use efficiency in water-intensive crops such as rice and sugarcane; and e) enabling farmers to enhanced access to risk sharing measures.

Key Interventions undertaken: Several key interventions are being made in the field of agriculture and allied sectors to tackle the issue of climate change in Uttar Pradesh. These key interventions include:

- A total of 50 Automated Weather Stations (AWS), under the “Gramin Krishi Mausham Seva Scheme” are disseminating weather forecasts to farmers. Another 17 such stations have been established at the block level (PIB, 2021).
- About 31000 farmers have already been added to 620 organic clusters under ‘Pramparagat Krishi Vikas Yojna (PKVY)’ over the land of 12,400 ha (MoAFW, 2020).
- To promote organic certification UPSOC was established in 2014 and it started working in 2016 to make registration and organic certification
- The promotion of climate-resilient crops has doubled between 2013-14 and 2019-20 under District Sugarcane Development Plan.

- At least 230 hatcheries for fish cultivation have been constructed with 40% and 60% subsidies to general categories and SC/ST category beneficiaries respectively.

Several relevant schemes and programmes run by the central government and the state government have been aligned with the SAM to achieve the stipulated objectives. The figure 2.4 represents the range of relevant policies, schemes, and programmes as below-

Figure: 3.5 Relevant Policies, Schemes, and Programmes Being Implemented in the UP Agriculture Sector

Source: UP SAPCC 2.0

2. Jal Mission: UP is bestowed with an annual rainfall of about 228.28 billion cubic meters (BCM) with 118.47 BCM of water utilizable. The UP Water Policy states the importance of water as “*Water, a scarce and unevenly distributed natural resource, essential to sustain life,*

livelihoods, food security, development, and the environment, is a precious national wealth to be planned, managed, developed and utilized for beneficial uses by the States” (UP State Water Policy, 2020, p.6).

Water is unevenly distributed not only in spatial dimensions of UP’s vast geographical area ranging from drought-prone Bundelkhand to flood-prone Tarai region but also in temporal dimensions as 90% of precipitation occurs only in three months of the southwest monsoon. The climate risks are causing great variations in the normal distribution of water in the form of increased frequency and intensity of untimely rain, flood, and drought.

The SAPCC 2.0 envisages 26 actions under five strategies with an estimated budget outlay of 64,170.13 cr. These include:

“Enhanced monitoring and research to establish water budget and manage water at micro-watersheds; strengthening water sector infrastructure to adapt to climate change; enhanced water use efficiency across sectors and reduce dependency on groundwater; enhanced efforts towards groundwater recharge; and building readiness for frequent and unprecedented floods at even non-traditional flooding regions and months” (UPSAPCC 2.0, p. 131).

Several Schemes and policies are being undertaken at UP in the water sector. The key schemes include the construction and maintenance of dams, major and minor rift canals; Dr. Ram Manohar Lohia community tube well scheme; Prime Minister Agriculture Irrigation Scheme; rooftop rainwater harvesting; catch the rain; UP Atal Bhujal Yojna; Bundelkhand Project; and Jal Jeevan Mission, Bundelkhand Project and Rural Water supply and Sanitation Project under the Namami Gange.

3. Green UP Mission: Forests play an important role in supporting the livelihood of people, especially the poor and forest dwellers besides a vital resource for industrial production. However, in recent decades, growing urbanization, transformation of forest land for agricultural purposes, and incidence of poverty have degraded and diminished forest cover. Climate change is the most important determinant of vegetation growth and distribution. Studies show a substantial 49% and 54% vulnerability to climate change under RCP 4.5 and 8.5 respectively (Sharma, et al., 2017). Climate risks include increasing temperature variability, uneven precipitation spells, and drought-like situations.

The key relevant policy interventions in Uttar Pradesh are –reduced deforestation and forest degradation for wildfire control, expansion of protected areas, and removal of invasive species; improved forest management and agroforestry with a focus on conservation of mangroves; and wetlands restoration and enhancement.

The proposed strategies actions under UP SAPCC 2.0 consist of 5 strategies and 20 actions. The five strategies include restoration and improvement in the quality of forest cover, enhancing tree cover in urban and peri-urban areas, improving income of forest-dependent population through agroforestry and food forest in private and community land, and conservation of wetlands biodiversity conservation.

4. Enhanced Energy Efficiency and Green Energy Mission: The Government of Uttar Pradesh has set an ambitious target to be a \$ 1 trillion economy in a few years. The per capita energy consumption of Uttar Pradesh is very low, it stands at about 400 kilowatt-hours in comparison to the national per capita consumption of about 9 60 kWh in 2018. With a share of a whopping 70.86% coal dominates the total

installed capacity in UP. Several climate drivers impact energy production, distribution, and transmission such as an increase in water and air temperature (Arent et al., 2015); change in precipitation pattern (Turner et al., 2017); extreme weather conditions (Subramanian et al., 2019); and change in cloud cover and wind speed (Kabir et al., 2018).

The state's specified agency, UPNEDA, is already taking several measures to achieve energy efficiency in collaboration with BEE. For instance, PM KUSUM for stand-alone pumps; UP Eco-Niwas Samhita for residential buildings; UJALA for demand-side management; Perform, Achieve and Trade (PAT) for energy efficiency in large inc.; FAME for e-mobility; energy clubs in schools etc, The SAPCC 2.0 envisages six Strategies under two missions with 37 actions. The green energy mission includes solarization of conventional energy-based private and public water pumping works, and setting up off-grid solar power plant on wasteland in rural UP thus increasing farmers' income. The Energy Efficiency Mission talks about minimizing AT&C losses in the transmission and distribution of electricity, making assembly clusters energy efficient, creating an environment for market penetration of efficient cooling systems, and enabling a significant transition to EVs (UP SAPCC 2.0, p.153).

5. Sustainable Habitat Mission: Given the socioeconomic and emotional importance of habitat to a person, UP Sustainable Habitat Mission undertakes a holistic approach to achieve the objectives of this mission. The main components of habitats include drinking water, sewage management, solid waste management, road infrastructure, and mobility, housing governance planning and outreach, and stormwater. Climate change poses great risk to substandard dwellings and makes

disruption to basic amenities necessary for a viable habitat. These risks include e.g. increasing temperature/extreme heat, extreme weather events like floods, storms, and wind hazards.

Several central and state policies and programmes linked to the sustainable habitat sector are being undertaken as follows:

Urban Habitat	Rural Habitat
Jal Jeevan Mission (Urban)	Jal Jeevan Mission (Rural)
Smart City Mission	MGNREGA
AMRUT	PM Awas Yojna -Rural
Swachh Bharat Mission- Urban	Swachh Bharat Mission- Rural
PM Awas Yojana -Urban	Pradhan Mantri Gram Sadak Yojana

Given the identified climate risks and vulnerabilities, the sustainable habitat mission envisages 5 strategies and 35 actions. The strategies include “Mainstream climate resilience and pollution mitigation; building climate-resilient rural housing; building climate-resilient roads and climate-smart waste infrastructure; developing climate-resilient urban water infrastructure and stormwater drainage; and developing climate-resilient waste management infrastructure”. Out of the 35 actions, 43% pertain to mitigation, 26% to adaptation and 31% belong to both categories (UP SAPCC 2.0, p.173).

6. Human Health Mission: This mission has been added to the revised SAPCC 2.0 moving the importance of health concerns linked with climate change. It has been proved by scientific studies that climate change poses grave human health hazards across all age groups (IPCC, 2022). The disease burden of Uttar Pradesh varies from one part to

another, for instance, heat stress and cardiovascular failure are the main concerns in the western and southern districts of UP, while Kala-Azar is concentrated in the eastern district of Khushi Nagar Deoria and Balia; Japanese Encephalitis is a major health issue in the eastern district in Gorakhpur region. The climate change risks human health in multiple ways. Variability in rainfall, temperature, and flood proneness create water scarcity, water contamination, waterborne diseases, and vector-borne diseases (Singh, et al., 2020).

Uttar Pradesh is the most populous state in the country therefore it is an indisputable fact, if it has to take advantage of its demographic dividend, it has to invest heavily in key sectors of Education and Health. Several key programs for the health sector in the state are already being implemented for instance Mukhyamantri Jan Arogya Abhiyan was launched in 2019. It aims to cover 40.80 lakh ration card-holding families and provide them with health cover of rupees 5,00,000 each family per year (GoUP, 2022). Sixteen new government medical colleges have been made operationalized since 2017 under the ‘one district one medical college’ scheme. Real-time, web-enabled ‘Integrated Health Information Platform (IHIP) has been working since 2020 (DoH&FW, 2020). Integrated Disease Surveillance Programme, National Vector Borne Disease Control Programme, etc are being run in the state.

The human health mission is purely adaptation-centric. UPSAPCC 2.0 envisages three key strategies and 13 actions under this mission. The three strategies include “assessing the extent to spatial spread of health risks due to current and future climate change”, developing an “early warning and alert response system”, enabling “behavioural change in public to avoid climate-linked disease epidemics” designing green health

infrastructure, etc.

7. Disaster Management Mission: Climate-induced disasters are increasing infrequency and intensity around the globe including Uttar Pradesh. Climate change exacerbates mechanisms of generation of natural disasters and thus, enhanced vulnerabilities of systems. The IPCC report underscores the grave socioeconomic consequences of climate hazards with the pre-existing inequality and vulnerabilities of society (IPCC AR6, 2022). Uttar Pradesh is highly vulnerable to climate-related hazards such as droughts, flash floods, cloud bursts, hail storms, heat waves, and lightning. A joint study by GoI and UNDP found Uttar Pradesh to be high on the disaster risks index due to its high vulnerability and low-capacity indexes (MHA & UNDP, 2019).

The key interventions undertaken by Govt. of Uttar Pradesh in disaster management are: Flood Control Centres are working to collect flood information and take remedial measures; Flood Management Information System (FMIS) coordinates flood forecasts, “embankment surveys”, improvement of hydrological observation, and disseminating necessary data” for flood management. Crop Weather Watch Group assesses weather forecast and area-wise crop shown. Proposed strategies, and actions under the mission include two strategies and 10 actions. The strategies are “enhancing capacities for building institutional resilience towards climate change-induced extreme and slow-onset disasters, and build climate resilience through the creation of related knowledge products, policies, and guidelines” (UP SAPCC 2.0, p.197).

8. Strategic Knowledge Mission (SKM): To understand the dynamic and continuously evolving nature of the complex phenomenon of climate change, a vibrant and robust knowledge ecosystem development is

necessary. The Govt. of Uttar Pradesh has made efforts in developing knowledge products and dissemination thereof. The SKM caters to the needs of this aspect. The core components of the SKM are: ‘Knowledge hub & networking; awareness, training, and capacity building; monitoring & evaluation; climate research and disruptive technologies; and institutional strengthening and capacity building’ (UP SAPCC 2.0, p.201).

Remote sensing application center is conducting flood inundation mapping, utility mapping, and waterlogged assessment. Flood Mapping Information System Centre (FMISC) working as a technical secretariat for flood management and coordination measures. The Council of Science and Technology is exploring and identifying the need for S&T. To achieve the objectives of the mission several strategies and actions have been proposed such as ‘strengthening Climate Change Authority; establishing knowledge networks; capacity building for integrating climate change in development planning; monitoring & evaluation’.

The climate change authority is a crucial institution for knowledge generation, innovation, and policy suggestions based on scientific understanding and defines the scope of work and functions of thematic tracks.

3.4 KEY RECENT INTERVENTIONS TO FOSTER SUSTAINABLE & GREEN TRANSITION IN UTTAR PRADESH

The government of Uttar Pradesh has responded to the challenges of environmental degradation and climate change by formulating, designing, implementing, monitoring, and evaluating various policies, laws, schemes, programs, and projects under the overarching policy framework of SAPCC. The energy sector is responsible for being the largest emitter

globally and efforts are being made to make a just transition from fossil fuel-based energy to green and clean energy to meet the developmental aspirations of the people particularly the disadvantaged sections of society. Thus, the energy sector becomes a crucial sector to achieve the dual objectives of mitigating emissions as well as meeting the energy requirements of people. The energy consumption on a per capita basis is very low in Uttar Pradesh, it is less than half even of the national average and a minuscule in comparison to the per capita energy consumption of developed countries. According to the IEA Report 2023, renewable energy is set to provide more than one-third of total electricity surpassing coal by 2025 (IEA, 2023). Uttar Pradesh is also making great strides in renewable energy generation and making its transitions toward a green energy ecosystem.

Uttar Pradesh Solar Energy Policy, 2022, and Uttar Pradesh Bio-Energy Policy, 2022 are the keystones in fostering sustainability and clean energy transition. The Solar Energy Policy among others provides incentives for private investment, a target of generation of 22 thousand MW of solar energy by 2026-27, and subsidies to solar parks of 5 MW or more at the rate of 2.5 crores per MW (UP Solar Energy Policy, 2022). Similarly, the Bio-Energy Policy of 2022 aims to boost the production of bio-energy projects such as Bio-CNG, Biogas, and Biomass-based power generation by utilization of agriculture and organic waste. Financial incentives such as 100% exemption in electricity duty for ten years to bio-energy enterprises and 100% exemption of stamp duty; subsidy interventions; development of waste supply chain; upfront subsidy to FPO (UP Bio-Energy Policy, 2022). Uttar Pradesh's Solar ambitions are being translated into actions through some major solar parks such as

Lalitpur Solar Park with a capacity of 600 MW; Jhansi Solar Park (600 MW); and Chitrakoot Solar Park (800 MW). Ayodhya City is being developed as the first 'Solar City' of India, for the initiative UPNEDA is establishing a 40 MW solar plant. Bundelkhand Expressway is set to be the country's first solar expressway by transforming the vacant median strip of the 296 Km expressway into a solar plant that will generate electricity for 1 lakh homes near the expressway for the next 25 years.

Green Hydrogen Policy 2024 aims to enable ease of doing business by facilitating investment and setting up enterprises earmarked for producing Green Hydrogen/Green Ammonia. The policy emphasises on implementation of the Green Hydrogen Mission, the creation of a hydrogen market through fiscal and non-fiscal incentives, encouraging research and innovation in production and consumption, development of a workforce for Green Hydrogen industries (UP Green Hydrogen Policy, 2024). The State Government has identified a land bank of 23,000 acres to be utilized for green energy initiatives. The state has attracted an investment amounting to Rs. 7.5 lakh crore during the Global Investor Summit (GIS) -2023. Focus has been given to solar cities, solar parks, electric vehicles, and both grid-connected and off-grid projects and green corridors.

CONCLUSION

In the wake of the impending crisis of climate change and its associated phenomena, the world responds in multiple ways on multiple fronts. Climate activists particularly young children around the globe are crying loud and clear about the urgency of deep and impactful actions without delay rather than making superficial arrangements and half-hearted measures taken in a 'business-as-usual' approach. The movements such

as “Fridays for Future” under the dynamic and appealing leadership of Greta Thunberg represent this uneasiness and dissatisfaction of the ‘young generation’ with current policies and actions. Climate actions are indeed being taken by the global community as a collective and individual responsibility by different stakeholders as mentioned in the chapter. However, the depth and intensity of the actions are not up to the mark to meet the 1.5-degree threshold of global warming. Divisive decision-making due to the protectionist approach adopted by advanced economies, reluctance of developed countries to change their lifestyle carbon footprint on ecological resources, interests of capitalists and powerful individuals, etc. generally prevents nation-states from taking deep and structural-changing measures for curbing the impending an existential threat to most of the species on the planet including the human being.

CHAPTER – IV

ENVIRONMENTAL JUSTICE AND CLIMATE JUSTICE: A CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

4.1 INTRODUCTION:

Environmental justice has emerged as a critical, multidimensional, and multifaceted issue across most academic disciplines, including political science. The concept of environmental justice revolves around the issue of “equity” and “fairness” i.e. the fair treatment and meaningful engagement of all people, regardless of race, class, or income, concerning the development, implementation, and enforcement of environmental laws, regulations, and policies. Simply put, it deals with the unequal distribution of environmental costs and benefits within societies and seeks to correct these inequities via lobbying, policy reform, and community empowerment. However, in a larger sense, environmental justice includes the interests and rights of those who can't speak for themselves. It encompasses the interests of individuals who have not yet born, referred to as **intergenerational justice**; other species of the ecosystems and habitats, other than Homo sapiens (humans), referred to as **interspecies justice**; and abiotic components of our ecosystem and planet referred to as **planetary justice**. Thus, the concept of environmental justice is not simply an interaction between the notion of justice and its applicability in the field of environmental concerns of different strata of society. The environmental crisis movement focuses on the racial aspect of environmental issues particularly waste sites and hazardous substances near the location of the habitats of poor people, especially the communities of colour and other minorities. Environmental racism popularised the term “environmental justice”. The Warren County in North Carolina incident about dumping

PCB-laden dirt in a wasteland is considered by most academics and activists as the beginning of the environmental racism movement (Pezzullo, 2021). The Warren County incident initiated a series of academic studies on the issue of systemic inequalities concerning environmental issues or waste and hazardous material in the USA.

The historic summit, '*The First National People of Color Environment Leadership Summit, 1991*', sponsored by *United Church of Christ's Commission for Racial Justice* adopted an exhaustive set of "seventeen principles of environmental justice", that inspired and guided subsequent environmental justice movements. This set of principles covers not only protection from hazardous wastes and cessation of the production of toxic substances but also includes sacredness of 'Mother Earth', preventing ecological harm, sustainability in resources' utilization, meaningful engagement and self-determination of all people in environmental policies, the interest of future generation, rebuilding rural and urban areas in a nature-friendly way. In contrast to those who see environmental justice as merely an anthropocentric issue, the 17 principles broaden the concept and include socio-cultural aspects with environmental sustainability, and sustainability in terms of ecological sustainability and not only human-centric one.

This chapter provides a brief overview of the concept of environmental justice as a field of study within political science. In the next section of the chapter, I shall discuss the different dimensions of environmental justice. Further, the chapter tries to put different approaches to environmental justice. Furthermore, this chapter will delve into the notion of climate justice as one of the various dimensions of environmental justice.

4.1.1 MEANING & DEFINITION OF ENVIRONMENTAL JUSTICE

Most scholars consider environmental justice concerned with ensuring everyone has equal access to the benefits and rewards of environmental services, regardless of their race, colour, nationality, or socioeconomic status, and can actively participate in the formulation, execution, and enforcement of environmental laws, rules, and policies. The principles of fairness and equal opportunities for all members of society are the fundamental aspects of environmental justice. Nevertheless, this understanding is not inclusive and comprehensive enough to throw light on the whole canvass of environmental justice. Acknowledging the complexity and breadth of the concept, Schlosberg says “The term is quite broad, integrated, expansive, and inclusive, embodying a variety of understanding of justice itself” (Schlosberg, 2007, p.54).

It's not quite easy to pinpoint the meaning or principles of environmental justice as there are several perspectives of different scholars about the understanding and explanation of the term ‘environmental justice’; and they differ fundamentally on the notion of ‘what constitutes justice’ itself. This makes it quite a complex phenomenon to define the meaning of this concept. This concept has gained attention due to concerns about environmental issues affecting different communities unequally. The roots of environmental justice can be traced back to the civil rights movement, recognising that minority and low-income communities are disproportionately affected by environmental hazards such as air and water pollution, toxic waste, and industrial facilities.

The term ‘environmental justice’ encompasses at least two grassroots movements: one being the antitoxic movement and the other being environmental racism. Tracing the historical root of the problem of the

location of waste sites, Melosi argues that municipal waste and sewage-like things have been in the vicinity of the working class, politically disempowered and minority groups since ancient Rome, Greece, and Egypt (Melosi, 2004). In recent times, antitoxic movements spurred with the Love Canal incident leading to popular community reaction and awareness about the health consequences of the toxic waste in the locality.

The discourse of justice has mostly been 'anthropocentric' focusing on the fair distribution of resources and opportunities among various groups of human society. However, the impelling environmental crisis has made a paradigmatic shift by incorporating environmental issues into the existing theories of justice.

There are different approaches according to different scholars' views on what constitutes environmental justice. One of the most widely-known approaches is distributional justice, which aims at the fair sharing of environmental goods and bads. Environmental justice literature emphasises how the adverse effects of pollution and environmental degradation affect those at the bottom of society, especially people of colour and those in the low-income earning category (Bullard, 2000). Such disparity shows that there is a need for environmental policies that will enhance and prioritize the well-being of all citizens, not just the privileged few. However, people have criticized distributive justice frameworks, mainly because they possess anthropocentric biases. This approach mainly advocates for fair and equitable use of the environment for the benefit of human beings without regard to the environment's self-worth.

The political theory of John Rawls' justice has also been extended

through a substitution of the original position with an environmental veil. In this respect, Rawls' theory spells out two principles through which rational persons in a 'veil of ignorance' – where they cannot know their social status – would voluntarily adhere to ensure fairness, namely freedom and equal distribution of wealth. Canfield further broadens the idea of Rawlsian justice to future generations and the health of the ecosystems that are under its purview (Canfield, 2013). Consequently, we have the "Intergenerational justice" approach, which centres on the generation's ability to bring forward its practices that do not ruin the subsequent generation's opportunities to experience a salubrious natural world. However, critics have pointed out that there are internal flaws, which are due to problems in conferring moral weight to the interest of future people and non-human entities within the Rawlsian perspective, suggesting that this problem is tied closely to the fact that the environmental issue has been approached using a humanistic and anthropocentric theory. In addition to distributive and intergenerational justice, theories of ecological justice contain ideas about a more radical stand. Ecological justice extends justice from people to non-humans asserting that the other entities also claim rights (Baxter, 2005).

This perspective challenges the traditional anthropocentric view of nature as a resource to be exploited for human benefit. However, ecological justice frameworks face challenges in operationalizing the concept of rights for non-human entities and establishing mechanisms for enforcing these rights within a legal and political system designed for human interactions.

In short, incorporating environmental concerns into established theories of justice necessitates a critical and multifaceted approach. While

distributive and intergenerational justice frameworks offer valuable tools for ensuring equitable distribution of resources and safeguarding the well-being of future generations, their anthropocentrism remains a point of contention. Ecological justice, on the other hand, challenges the very foundation of human-centric justice, but its implementation requires overcoming significant theoretical and practical hurdles. As we strive for a sustainable and equitable future, a deeper exploration and integration of these diverse justice frameworks is crucial for navigating the complex relationship between humans and the environment.

One key aspect of environmental justice is recognising that certain communities bear a disproportionate burden of environmental degradation and pollution, often due to historical discriminatory practices, economic disparities, and the uneven distribution of environmental risks. For instance, marginalised communities are often located near hazardous waste sites, industrial facilities, or areas with poor air and water quality, exposing them to greater health risks. Additionally, environmental justice includes the idea of meaningful community involvement and empowerment. It emphasises the importance of including affected communities in the decision-making processes related to environmental policies and projects that may impact their well-being.

The multifaceted aspect of environmental justice is reflected in the acknowledgment and empirical pieces of evidence by various studies that a lack of environmental justice can lead to health disparities, economic hardship, and social injustices within communities. To achieve equitable and sustainable development, addressing environmental justice is a crucial precondition. The pursuit of environmental justice is guided by several key principles, including the right to equality in the distribution of

environmental costs and benefits, the right to meaningful participation in decision-making processes, the right to recognition, the right to access environmental information, and the right to redress and compensate for environmental harm. These principles form the basis for policy development and advocacy efforts aimed at promoting environmental justice. Furthermore, the movement for environmental justice has led to the need for policies and regulations that explicitly consider the impacts on vulnerable communities. Initiatives such as cumulative impact assessments and environmental equity mapping are examples of tools that can help address environmental justice concerns. Environmental justice is an essential component of creating a more equitable and sustainable society. Addressing these disparities and involving affected communities in decision-making processes can help ensure that all individuals and communities have the right to a healthy environment. It is critical to continue advocating for policies and practices that uphold the principles of environmental justice and promote fairness and inclusivity in environmental decision-making.

DEFINING ENVIRONMENTAL JUSTICE:

Defining any socio-political concept as diverse and vast as environmental justice is not an easy task. Socio-political concepts and theories are always debatable issues. No unanimous understanding is generally made among different thinkers due to their diverse perspectives, approaches, outlooks, and historical and lived experiences and contexts in which their thoughts emerge. There are several varieties, forms, dimensions, and faces of environmental justice. Apart from this, the concept of environmental justice has not been stationary but it, like any other political concept, keeps on changing as per spatial-temporal dimensions.

Thus, the dynamic nature of environmental justice makes it an evolutionary topic that evolved in different waves or generations over time and across places. From its distributive approach to its compensatory approach to past injustices, the concept of environmental justice has witnessed several events, episodes of support, and criticism. Thereby this dynamism is also reflected in the definition of the concept. Some important definitions are given below for better clarity

The roots of modern-day discourse on environmental justice can be traced back to struggles against the presence of hazardous waste disposal sites disproportionately in the vicinity of the habitats of low-income communities and people from minority racial or ethnic groups. The intersectionality between race/ethnicity, socioeconomic status, geography (urban vs rural), gender identity, etc., has been central to understanding how certain populations are disproportionately burdened by pollution-related risks while being excluded from decision-making processes that affect their living environments.

Despite the great contributions made by key founding scholar-activists like Robert Bullard and Bunyan Bryant to the concept of environmental justice, there has hardly been made effort to define the term in earlier works of these scholars. However, aspects of ‘equity’ (distribution of the environmental burdens), ‘participation’ (authentic participation), and ‘recognition’ (especially racial and cultural) have regularly been mentioned in their works (Schlosberg, 2007). Elements of the ‘capabilities’ of both individuals and communities have also been addressed, though, not in exact terms.

The definition proposed by the United States Environmental Protection Agency (EPA) succinctly captures the essence of environmental justice.

The EPA defines environmental justice as:

"the fair treatment and meaningful involvement of all people regardless of race, colour, national origin, or income concerning the development, implementation, and enforcement of environmental laws, regulations and policies" (EPA, 2019).

This definition emphasises the importance of equitable access to environmental resources and participation in decision-making processes. the concept of "fair treatment and meaningful involvement" in matters concerning environmental policy for all individuals regardless of their race or income level. This definition underscores both distributive aspects (fair treatment) as well as, procedural aspects (meaningful involvement), highlighting that equity in access to resources is just as important as participation in decision-making processes.

Robert D. Bullard (1993), often referred to as the grandfather of environmental justice, defines it as *"the principle that all communities are entitled to equal protection under environmental laws and regulations"* (p. 22).

His definition highlights the issue of 'equity' in treatment and protection for all communities regardless of their socio-economic status or racial background. The focus is on the distributional aspect of justice.

Paul Mohai and Robin Saha (2015) emphasize the intersectionality aspect of environmental justice by stating that it is *"an issue that results from complex interactions among race/ethnicity, socioeconomic status, geography (urban vs rural), gender identity, etc."*(p.34).

Their perspective acknowledges how multiple social identities intersect and contribute to differential exposure to pollution risks.

David N. Pellow (2002) examines how housing policy intersects with environmental justice by stating that it involves addressing the unequal distribution of burdens such as pollution alongside housing disparities. He argues, "*Environmental injustice persists because influential actors benefit in some way...from its reproduction*"(p. xvii).

This suggests that powerful entities may have a vested interest in maintaining the status quo like cost savings as companies find it easier and cheaper to dump waste in the locality of the poor and communities of colour; access to resources for exploiting natural resources in certain areas, even at the cost of environment and its inhabitants; economically mighty corporations seek political influence through donating money to political parties for getting made favourable policies, even if, those policies perpetuate environmental injustice.

Understanding the root causes of environmental injustice is crucial to addressing the issue. By identifying the influential actors who benefit from the status quo, we can develop strategies to hold them accountable and create a more just and sustainable future.

From the beginning, Bryant (1995) tried to broaden the scope of environmental justice by making it distinct from 'environmental equity' and 'environmental racism'. Bryant states:

It refers to those cultural norms and values, rules, regulations, behaviors, policies, and decisions to support sustainable communities, where people can interact with confidence that their environment is safe, nurturing, and productive. Environmental justice is served when people can realize their highest potential, without experiencing the 'isms'. Environmental justice is supported by decent paying and safe jobs; quality schools and recreation; decent housing and adequate health care; democratic

decision-making and personal empowerment; and communities free of violence, drugs, and poverty. These are communities where both cultural and biological diversity are respected and highly revered and where distributed justice prevails”. (Bryant, 1995, p.6).

In the above-mentioned articulation of environmental justice Bryant touches on almost every aspect of the meaning of the term. Bryant expanded the notion of environmental justice to the issues of daily activities and experiences by incorporating distribution, recognition, capabilities, cultural factors, and self-determination of individuals and communities.

These definitions capture different perspectives within the field of political science when defining environmental justice. They highlight key aspects such as fair treatment, equal protection and intersectionality which are integral components in understanding this important issue.

4.1.2 SIGNIFICANCE OF ENVIRONMENTAL JUSTICE WITHIN POLITICAL SCIENCE

The significance of studying environmental justice within political science cannot be overstated. As an interdisciplinary field that encompasses elements from sociology, public policy analysis, law studies geography, etc., it offers unique insights into power dynamics at play vis-a-vis resource allocation (water quality/air quality/park access /land use, etc.), regulation of pollution, and enforcement of environmental laws. Furthermore, it sheds light on the role of governmental institutions in shaping environmental policies and their impact on marginalised communities.

Environmental justice also intersects with broader debates on governance, social equity, and human rights within political science. It questions

traditional approaches to decision-making processes that often overlook the interests of underrepresented groups in policy formulation. Additionally, it enriches democratic practices by advocating for inclusive and participatory approaches in environmental policymaking.

Environmental justice has emerged as a critical issue within political science, highlighting the need for fair treatment and equal protection of all communities concerning environmental laws, regulations, and policies. The significance of environmental justice within political science is articulated by examining its historical context, theoretical foundations, policy implications, and intersectionality with other social issues. The significance of environmental justice within political science can further be understood under the following subheads:

The historical context of environmental justice reveals the deep-rooted connections between race, class, and the environment. The Civil Rights Movement in the United States played a pivotal role in bringing attention to environmental injustices faced by marginalised communities. Notably, Robert D. Bullard's work on "*environmental racism*" highlighted how minority populations bear disproportionate burdens from hazardous waste sites and pollution sources.

Environmental justice draws upon several theoretical frameworks to analyse power dynamics and systemic inequalities that contribute to disparate environmental impacts on marginalised communities. Critical theories such as Marxism highlight how capitalist structures perpetuate unequal access to resources and decision-making processes that shape environmental outcomes (Gupta, 2008). Intersectionality theory emphasises that race intersects with other social categories such as gender

or socioeconomic status to compound unequal exposure risks (Mohai & Saha, 2015).

The significance of incorporating environmental justice into political science is evident through its local, national, and international policy implications. The United States Environmental Protection Agency's efforts towards integrating principles of equity into decision-making processes serve as an example (EPA, 2019). Additionally, international platforms like the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals have prioritised achieving environmental justice by addressing inequalities in access to clean water and sanitation.

Understanding the intersectionality aspect is crucial for comprehending the full significance of environmental justice within political science research. This section will explore how factors such as gender identity or geographic location influence differential exposures. Incorporating intersectional approaches allows more nuanced analyses when assessing disparities in experiences across different communities.

Thus, the significance of incorporating concepts related to environmental justice within political science can't be underestimated. It highlights issues of power, distribution and participation. Tracing its historical origins, theoretical foundations, policy implications and intersections with other social issues shed light on why it matters. Environmental justice serves as a lens through which we can examine how systems and societies reproduce inequalities. Studying this sector within politics, the complexities of power dynamics in relation to environment can be understood since these power dynamics when serving their vested interests have abilities for access and reducing structures and practices causing disparate environmental impacts. While much progress has been

made in recognising and addressing these issues, much work remains to promote equitable treatment for all communities regardless of their race, socioeconomic status, or other identifying characteristics. By continuing to explore this field within political science, researchers and activists can contribute meaningfully to an inclusive and just future for humanity and the whole ecosystem of the planet.

Environmental justice (EJ) is a multifaceted concept encompassing fair treatment and participation in environmental decision-making, as well as the equitable distribution of environmental burdens and benefits. Environmental justice delves into the unequal distribution of environmental benefits and burdens. It critiques the disproportionate exposure of low-income communities and people of colour to environmental hazards like pollution, waste facilities, and resource extraction. This section of the chapter explores the theoretical underpinnings of environmental justice, examining how different frameworks approach equity and fairness concerning the environment.

4.2 APPROACHES AND THEORETICAL UNDERPINNINGS OF ENVIRONMENTAL JUSTICE

4.2.1 DISTRIBUTIVE JUSTICE: FAIRNESS IN SHARING

Distributive justice forms the core of environmental justice movements. It focuses on ‘equity’ and ‘fairness’ in distributing environmental risks and benefits. Pioneering work by scholars like Robert D. Bullard documented how race is a significant factor in siting polluting facilities. Communities of color often bear the brunt of environmental degradation, despite having minimal contribution to the problems (Bullard, 2000). This delves into the issues of equity and fairness in the EJ, focusing on the just allocation of environmental harms and benefits across communities. This raises

questions about fairness. Why should certain communities be sacrificed for the benefit of others?

Environmental racism remains the prominent variable in the analysis of environmental justice studies in the early decades of the environmental justice movement. The questions of distribution intersect with the issue of 'environmental racism' in these studies. Robert Bullard (1993) points out environmental racism highlighting the voices from the grassroots concerning the ill effects of hazardous substances on their environment and their health. Similarly, in 1987, a study conducted by UCC revealed that 'race' was the most significant variable associated with the sites of commercial hazardous waste (Schlosberg, 2007, p.55). The core of distributive justice, a cornerstone of political philosophy, grapples with the fairness of distributing resources, benefits, and burdens within a society. Within the environmental context, it translates to ensuring a fair distribution of environmental hazards (pollution, waste sites) and benefits (clean air, access to green spaces). Distributive justice frameworks propose various principles for fair allocation:

The 'equality' principle advocates for an equal distribution of environmental burdens and benefits for all individuals or communities, irrespective of their race, socioeconomic status, or location. John Rawls' theory of justice as fairness, particularly the "original position", underpins this principle (Rawls, 1971). In this hypothetical scenario, individuals choose principles of justice from behind a veil of ignorance, unaware of their social position. Proponents of equality argue that environmental burdens and benefits should be distributed equally, as everyone has equal rights to environmental goods and an equal chance of environmental burdens. Equal protection forms another strand of this approach.

Everyone deserves the same level of protection from environmental harm (Sen, 1995 originally published in 1992).

‘Equity’ recognizes pre-existing inequalities and seeks a more proportional distribution based on the need or capacity to bear burdens. Amartya Sen's work on capabilities and functions aligns well with this principle (Sen, 1992). Sen argues that environmental burdens can limit individuals' capabilities, and their freedoms to pursue a good life. Equity dictates that those with lower capabilities due to disadvantaged circumstances should be shielded from a disproportionate share of environmental burdens. There have been studies to show that even the rules and laws of environmental protection apply differently in the localities of communities of colour and the communities of white people (Lavelle & Coyle, 1992).

The ‘fair share’ principle proposes a distribution where communities bear environmental burdens proportionate to the benefits they derive from polluting activities or resource extraction. Joan Martinez-Alier, a scholar of ecological economics, emphasises this principle in his work on environmental justice (Martinez-Alier & Ropke, 2008). He argues that polluting industries should compensate neighbouring communities through a fair share of the profits generated by those industries, and provide them with resources for environmental cleanup and restoration. Communities should not disproportionately be overburdened with environmental risks to the benefits they receive from environmental resource extraction or utilization. The bottom line in distributive justice is that as stated by Edwards: “unifying insight of environmental justice recognizes that neither the costs of pollution nor the benefits of

environmental protection are evenly distributed throughout our society” (Edwards, 1995, p.36).

The discussion on the distributive approach of environmental justice makes it clear that the notion of environmental injustice is not an individual-felt experience, but it is a community-based experience i.e. it is a community-embedded sense of shared burdens imposed by those who are the generator of environmental harms. Further, there has been an understanding in environmental movements that the distributional aspect or equity approach is not enough to deal with the notion of environmental justice and other approaches of justice need to be applied in the context of the environment to fully grasp the whole gamut of issues under the umbrella term of environmental justice. Shrader and Frechette realized that “distributive justice in the allocation of environmental impact, however, is necessary but not sufficient in order to promote environmental justice” (Shrader & Frechette, 2002, p. 27).

4.2.2 PROCEDURAL JUSTICE: A VOICE IN DECISIONS AND FAIRNESS IN THE PROCESS

Environmental justice, at its core, strives for fairness in distributing environmental benefits and burdens. However, the concept of environmental justice is much more inclusive than the fair distribution of ecological costs and benefits. Achieving the ideal of environmental justice requires not only equitable distribution but also just processes and many more dimensions. Procedural justice deals with ensuring all communities' fair treatment and meaningful participation, particularly those disproportionately impacted by environmental hazards.

Benjamin Chavis while defining environmental racism includes “the history of excluding people of colour from the mainstream environmental

groups, decision-making boards, commissions, and regulatory bodies” (Chavis, as quoted in Bullard, 1993). This shows the perennial problem of non-participation of minority groups and disempowered communities in the decision-making, implementing, and regulating processes. The environmental justice movement arose to fight against the incidents of the disproportionate burden of environmental hazards placed on low-income communities and communities of color. Scholars like Robert Bullard (1993) explored the phenomenon of environmental racism, a phenomenon in which race acts as a key factor in determining exposure to pollution and associated health risks. Laura Pulido (2023) also highlighted the geographic distribution of environmental hazards and demonstrated how communities of colour were often located near polluting facilities like waste dumps and industrial plants. Under these circumstances of unequal distribution of environmental burdens, the imperative was felt for a framework that empowers marginalised communities to have a voice in decisions that affect their well-being. Some scholars have established a link between lack of recognition and issues of valid participation stating “misrecognition due to racism and/or classism creates real structural obstacles to political participation” (Schlosberg, 2007, p.65).

Procedural justice focuses on the fairness of the decision-making process. In the environmental context, procedural justice focuses on the fairness of the decision-making process itself, ensuring that stakeholders are treated with respect and have a meaningful opportunity to participate. Scholars like Sheldon Krimsky (2003) define procedural justice as having access to information, the opportunity to be heard, and a fair decision-making process. In the environmental justice context, this translates to (a)

meaningful participation i.e. ensuring communities have a say in the whole process of policies and decisions affecting their environment; (b) informed consent translates that communities should have access to information in their local language and right to understand the potential impacts of decisions, policies, and projects on their environment and their lives; (c) transparency and accountability i.e. transparency should be at every step of the decision-making and its implementation with clear justification for choices made and decision-makers should hold accountability for their actions; (d) culturally competent communication means information dissemination must be compatible with the specific needs and cultural backgrounds of diverse communities; and (e) recourse mechanism, the mechanism of establishing channels for affected communities to address their grievances and ensuring the responsibility of polluters.

Technical jargon and scientific data shouldn't exclude community members from understanding the potential impacts on their environment. Decision-makers must actively listen to and consider the knowledge and perspectives gleaned from these lived experiences. Carol Hunold and Robert Young (1994) argue for a more nuanced understanding of procedural justice, recognising the influence of power dynamics. Meaningful participation hinges on the ability of communities to effectively influence decisions, not simply be present at a hearing.

Environmental political theory offers valuable insights into the role of procedural justice in achieving environmental justice. Aletta Biesta (2007) champions the concept of “ecological democracy,” which emphasises public participation and decision-making processes that prioritize ecological sustainability. Similarly, John Rawls’ theory of

justice as fairness, with its focus on equal participation and fair bargaining procedures, provides a framework for ensuring that no group is disadvantaged in environmental decision-making (Rawls, 1971).

However, scholars like David Schlosberg (2007) argue that traditional conceptions of procedural justice often fall short in addressing environmental issues, particularly those concerning environmental degradation on a global scale. They call for a more robust form of procedural justice that recognizes the rights of future generations and non-human nature to be considered in environmental decisions.

Procedural justice is the foundation for achieving environmental justice. By ensuring fair and inclusive processes, we can empower communities to protect their health and environment, ultimately leading to a more just and sustainable future. Environmental justice, a movement demanding fair treatment for all people and communities concerning environmental hazards and benefits, extends beyond mere distributive outcomes. Achieving environmental justice necessitates not only equitable distribution of environmental burdens and benefits but also just processes that ensure fair treatment and meaningful participation for all stakeholders. Recognising the importance of participation in environmental justice Schlosberg in his beautiful words states “The construction of inclusive, participatory decision-making institutions - speaking for ourselves, a ‘place at the table, equal, informed, respectful participation- has consistently been at the centre of environmental justice demands” (Schlosberg, 2007, pp. 65-66).

Procedural justice is the cornerstone of environmental justice. By ensuring fair and inclusive processes for environmental decision-making, we can empower communities to protect their health, and environment,

and secure a more just and sustainable future. Further research is needed to explore the intersection of procedural justice with issues of environmental racism, classism, and global environmental challenges. Additionally, investigating innovative models of community engagement and participatory decision-making can offer valuable insights for building a more just and equitable relationship between society and the environment.

4.2.3 RECOGNITION JUSTICE: VALUING ALL COMMUNITIES

The concept of environmental justice encompasses not only the equitable distribution of environmental benefits and burdens, but also the meaningful participation of all communities in environmental decision-making, and the recognition of diverse perspectives and values of different communities. Recognition Justice deals with the issues of misrecognition and unrecognition of the voice, perspective, values, norms, and knowledge system of minorities, weaker sections of society, and racially different people. Recognition justice enriches the debate of environmental justice beyond the distributive and participatory issues and includes the importance of respect for 'differences' among individuals and communities. It stresses due respect and recognition of diverse perspectives and experiences of individuals and communities regarding man-nature relations. Aldon Morris (2008) emphasises the importance of recognition and respect for the lived experiences of community members. It has gained increasing attention from scholars as it brings to light issues related to cultural identity, representation, and respect for diverse worldviews. Recognition justice acknowledges that marginalised communities often face not only material disadvantages but also suffer from being denied their cultural identities or being misunderstood by

mainstream society. Environmental justice goes beyond just the distribution of burdens and benefits. It recognizes the historical marginalisation of specific communities and the ways environmental racism perpetuates existing inequalities. Recognition justice emphasises (a) cultural integrity that acknowledges the unique connection of cultures and communities to their environment; (b) empowerment i.e. supporting self-determination and leadership from within marginalised communities to address environmental challenges; and (c) addressing historical injustices means rectifying past environmental harms committed by others while inflicted on specific communities.

Alexis Pauline Gumbs' (2016) book "Undrowned: Black Feminist Lessons on Organising for Liberation" emphasises the importance of recognising the lived experiences of marginalised communities and their deep connection to place.

David Schlosberg emphasises the significance of individual and community recognition which includes the recognition from others and mutual respect for one another culture, identities, and communities. He links the issue of recognition with distribution and participation in environmental justice. For him, effective responses to climate change should include recognising different cultural understandings about nature. He maintains that failing to give proper recognition to these diverse perspectives can lead to further marginalisation or domination over marginalised groups (Schlosberg, 2007). He emphasises on recognition of marginalised groups' struggle against environmental inequalities while addressing issues related to power dynamics within society. Honneth considers the notion of recognition in terms of "physical integrity" and maintains physical maltreatment amounts to personal degradation which

denies a person of her recognition. Taking this understanding forward Schlosberg adds “unwanted exposure to environmental risks as an example of seizing control of a person’s body against their will” (Schlosberg, 2007, p.60). The disrespect for the Indigenous knowledge system which evolved over centuries, impoverishes the knowledge domain of the policy makers and planners. Other scholars have also highlighted the disregard of indigenous communities' traditional ecological knowledge in decision-making about natural resource management. To achieve more just environmental policies, they advocate for recognising indigenous knowledge systems (McGregor et al., 2020). The recognition justice approach can also be extended to the components of nature. Recognising the importance and value of non-human living species and the ecosystem as a whole also plays an important role in the environmental justice notion. Robyn Eckersley (1992) also makes contributions to the recognition justice in her book "*Environmentalism & Political Theory: Toward an Ecocentric Approach.*" Eckersley advocates for ecocentric approaches that recognize nature's intrinsic value over anthropocentric views. She also underscores the recognition of non-human entities within the ecosystem.

Andrew Dobson’s work (1998) “Justice and the Environment” delves into philosophical perspectives on how contemporary theories of justice can address ecological concerns. Dobson argues that theories like Rawlsian liberalism fail to adequately recognize ecological interdependencies within human societies or between humans and their environment.

Steve Vanderheiden (2008) contributes valuable insights into global climate governance from a political theory perspective. In “Political Theory & Global Climate Change,” he advocates for recognising

different cultural perspectives when developing global policies addressing climate change, emphasizing culturally sensitive approaches toward mitigation efforts. Laura Pulido (1996) forwards the notion of 'subaltern environmentalism' to capture the environmentalism of developing countries in connection with that of developed countries.

Recognition plays an important role in fostering inclusive and participatory governance structures for sustainable development practices (Agyeman, et al. 2016). In addressing sustainability challenges importance of valuing local knowledge systems and respecting cultural diversity play a prominent role.

Certainly, when discussing recognition justice within environmental justice, it is essential to consider the perspectives of major green political thinkers. The works of influential figures such as Vandana Shiva, Arne Naess, and Murray Bookchin shed light on the intersection between ecological concerns in the context of recognition justice and social justice.

Vandana Shiva's work emphasises the importance of recognising traditional ecological knowledge and local practices in addressing environmental issues. She advocates for a shift towards community-based approaches that acknowledge and respect diverse cultural perspectives on nature and resource management. Shiva's perspective highlights the need for recognition of indigenous communities' rights to land, water, and resources as a fundamental aspect of environmental justice. In her book "Earth Democracy: Justice, Sustainability, and Peace," Shiva emphasises the importance of recognising and respecting diverse cultural perspectives on nature and natural resource management. She argues that environmental justice cannot be achieved without acknowledging and

upholding the rights of marginalised communities. Her ideas of *'food democracy'* and *'beejswaraj'* (seed autonomy) have contributed to the recognition of the rights and practices of local peasants and Adivasis (tribes). Her contributions to the recognition justice in environmentalism are centred around her advocacy for the rights of Indigenous communities, particularly regarding their traditional ecological knowledge and practices (Shiva, 2005).

The concept of "*deep ecology*" has further been elaborated in "The Shallow and the Deep, Long-Range Ecology Movement: A Summary" by Naess. It also contributes to the discourse on the recognition justice within environmentalism. Deep ecology calls for recognising the intrinsic value of all living beings regardless of their utility to human interests. Naess's perspective challenges anthropocentric views by advocating for a holistic understanding that respects non-human life forms as equal participants in ecosystem processes (Naess, 1995).

Murray Bookchin's social ecology provides insights into the recognition justice by underscoring the interdependence between social hierarchy and ecological degradation. In his seminal work "*The Ecology of Freedom: The Emergence and Dissolution of Hierarchy*," Bookchin addresses societal injustices as integral components in efforts toward environmental sustainability (Bookchin, 2006, originally published in 1982).

These green political thinkers contribute valuable insights into how recognition justice can be integrated into environmental movements by acknowledging diverse cultural perspectives, respecting non-human life forms, and addressing social inequalities intertwined with ecological concerns.

Incorporating these perspectives into discussions about the recognition justice within environmentalism enriches our understanding of how different worldviews, values, and rights are interconnected with efforts toward sustainable development.

Despite its significance, recognition justice within environmental discourse has faced criticism primarily concerning practical implementation challenges. Some critics argue that incorporating diverse worldviews into decision-making processes might lead to conflicts or hinder efficient policy-making (Young, 1990). Others argue that focusing solely on recognition may distract from addressing material inequalities such as disproportionate exposure to pollution faced by marginalised communities (Fraser, 2000; 2008).

4.2.4 THE CAPABILITIES APPROACH TO ENVIRONMENTAL JUSTICE

Environmental justice has emerged as an increasingly critical area of concern as societies across the globe grapple with complex problems of environmental degradation and social inequality. The complex challenges of sustainability, resource allocation, and social equity have gained prominence in the policy-making arena. The capabilities approach, pioneered by Amartya Sen and Martha Nussbaum in the field of development ethics, was developed as a way to conceptualize and assess the issues of economic and social development. This approach has gained prominence as a constructive and helpful framework for understanding and addressing environmental injustice in recent times.

The capabilities approach is rooted in the idea that individuals should have the freedom to achieve well-being in ways they value. The concept of ‘capabilities’ is central to this perspective. The meaning of capabilities

can be understood if we raise the question “What is each person is able to do and to be” (Nussbaum, 2011, p.18)? This notion of ‘beings’ and ‘doings’ is valued. The term ‘functioning’ has been used by Nussbaum and Sen to indicate the ‘pursuits’ and ‘states of being’ in which a person is actively engaged. Capabilities of persons are substantive opportunities that enable individuals to lead lives they have reason to value or to engage in valued ‘functioning’. Sen looks at the capability as ‘an aspect of freedom’ (Sen, 2009, p. 287) i.e., having the freedom to choose or not to do something and having the ability actually to do it. Sen and Nussbaum have emphasized a broad range of capabilities, including not only material resources such as access to clean water or education but also non-material aspects like political participation or cultural expression.

Neither Sen nor Nussbaum pays a great amount of attention to environmental concerns in their earlier works on the capabilities approach. However, in ‘The Idea of Justice’ Sen focuses on sustainable development and praises the Brundtland Commission for highlighting the integration of ecological and environmental health with human well-being (Sen, 2010, p. 251). Amartya Sen’s seminal work on capability theory provides a foundational understanding of how injustices can be understood in terms of deprivation or lack of access to essential freedoms. Sen and Nussbaum argue that the capability approach is a better framework for measuring the degree of development of any nation, community, society, or individual, and for making comparisons between nations, societies, individuals, and communities than the existing alternative measurement approaches either wealth/income/GDP or subjective satisfaction like utility (Sen, 1992, 1999, 2009; Nussbaum

2000, 2011; Nussbaum and Sen, 1993). Their concept and framework's application towards environmental justice has been influential in highlighting how marginalised communities' freedom and well-being are impacted disproportionately by environmental degradation. Contrasting the perceptions of economists of the welfare state, he argued that people should not be seen as passive recipients of aid or support, but rather as active agents who are capable of making decisions about their own lives. In terms of environmental justice, it translates into involving marginalised communities in decision-making processes related to environmental policies and practices that affect their lives and well-being.

Martha Nussbaum proposes a list of ten "*Central Capabilities*" which include among others "life – being able to live a normal healthy life; bodily health- being able to have good health; bodily integrity - being free from physical assault; affiliation -being able to live with and towards others and having social bases of self-respect; senses, imagination and thought – being able to use the senses to think and reason, having freedom of expression and being able to have pleasurable experiences and avoid non-beneficial pain; and control over one's environment – having the right of political participation" (Day, 2018, p. 126). One can easily understand that exposure to high levels of air pollution may undermine several capabilities given in Nussbaum's central list. Additionally, Nussbaum's comprehensive set of capabilities broadens the framework of analysis of environmental justice because her list includes not only basic needs such as clean air and water but also broader capabilities such as political participation and cultural expression. This broader perspective aligns with discussions within environmental justice movements about addressing systemic issues related to power imbalances and cultural

recognition (Schlosberg, 2013).

The capability approach provides scope and space for addressing a complex set of needs of various sections of society in a more sophisticated manner than the normal equality approach. Individual being the basic unit of analysis, it is more likely to address the differences within communities and collectives in contrast to other approaches that focus on “communities, neighbourhoods, or other spatial or collective units” (Day, 2018, p.131).

Robyns’ expansionist views on individual diversity makes the scope of applying capability theory in his thoughts. Scholars have made efforts to apply the capabilities approach to theorizing environmental injustices through their case studies conducted on different communities in different places. Schlosberg and Carruthers argue that the approach needs to be broadened to encompass the notions of ‘Community Capabilities’ and ‘Community Functioning’ (Schlosberg & Carruthers 2010). Walker (2006) focuses on linking entitlements with community-based approaches and sees the appeal of its reflexive approach.

Deneulin and Shahani’s (2009) work highlights its connection with participatory methods when applying it at local level interventions. Furthermore, they emphasized how the capabilities approach provides a framework for understanding multidimensional poverty beyond income-based measures. In relation to environmental justice, this means recognising that lack of access to clean environments can restrict individuals’ opportunities for education, employment, or social participation. Moreover, Powers and Faden (2006) argued that focusing on social determinants rather than solely individual behaviours or healthcare interventions can contribute significantly towards addressing

health disparities within marginalised communities affected by environmental injustices.

This approach has enriched the arena of environmental justice by providing an additional and useful framework of analysis. It has made significant contributions to the field of environmental justice by shifting the focus from the simplistic distributional dimension to recognising individual freedoms and human dignity as significant components of well-being concerning environmental conditions. This approach makes value addition by emphasizing the importance of not just providing material resources and opportunities, but also enabling individuals to make choices that lead to a fulfilled life. In the context of environmental justice, this means ensuring that all individuals have the freedom and capability to live in a healthy environment.

While there are numerous strengths associated with using a ‘capabilities approach’ within environmental justice discourse such as its focus on agency rather than welfare-approach alone, it nevertheless faces several criticisms. One of the criticisms of the capability approach in the context of environmental justice is about its operationalization challenges and measurement of capabilities effectively. Scholars such as Holland (2012) have argued that while the concept of capabilities is appealing in theory, it becomes difficult to translate these abstract notions into concrete policy measures and interventions. This criticism raises concerns about the practicality and feasibility of using the capabilities approach as a guiding framework for environmental justice initiatives.

Additionally, Robyns (2005) has highlighted that there can be tension between promoting individual freedoms and addressing collective issues related to environmental degradation. The emphasis on individual agency

in the capability approach may not adequately address broader systemic challenges such as industrial pollution or climate change, which require collective action and structural changes. Nussbaum (2000) explains that focusing on individual freedom is an effort to overlook the systematic problems of inequalities persisting in social institutions like family particularly the issue of gender in the society. The criticism focuses on the fact that though, the capabilities of all and different individuals should be given attention. However, some capabilities make sense or are expressed only at a collective level like cultural identity and cultural recognition. Thus, the central point of this criticism is that the capabilities approach places too much emphasis on human agency and not enough on addressing structural inequalities. Fraser (2009) has also raised concerns about how focusing solely on individual freedoms may overlook larger social and economic disparities that contribute to environmental injustices. This critique underscores potential limitations in addressing power imbalances and systemic injustices through a purely capabilities-based lens.

Walker (2006) has pointed out that while Sen's capability approach emphasises freedom to achieve well-being, it throws no light on the issue of how conflicting interests among different groups within society should be reconciled regarding access to natural resources or exposure to environmental risks. Shue (1999), a well-known philosopher argues that justice is not limited to just ensuring individuals' abilities, it requires much more than this; it also necessitates fair distribution of resources. This perspective reveals a potential limitation of solely relying on capabilities without explicitly addressing distributive justice aspects within environmental contexts.

The above-mentioned critiques challenge the applicability and adequacy of the capability approach in effectively addressing complex issues related to environmental justice. These criticisms draw attention to challenges related to measurement, collective action, power dynamics, and distributive justice considerations within societal structures. The critics underline potential limitations that need further consideration when applying capability-based frameworks to environmental justice interventions.

Despite the above-mentioned critiques, the capability approach offers a potentially highly useful framework of analysis in discussions about environmental justice by integrating the capability lens into ecological distribution strategies. Various academic studies have shown that the capability approach has meaningful implications in environmental justice discourse. Its emphasis on the freedom to achieve well-being and its attention to individual diversity and human dignity provide a valuable framework of analysis for environmental issues and addressing and understanding their complex nature within modern society. To address current limitations carrying out further inquiries could emphasize more dialogues between institutional actors who stand at a crossroads between ecological preservation & cultural livelihood. It will be necessary to explore adaptable measurement tools that respect diverse cultural contexts. However, as with any theoretical framework, there are certain limitations and operational challenges that need to be examined critically by further research and studies. By engaging with these critiques and exploring future directions for research and practice, the capability approach can be further developed to contribute effectively towards achieving more equitable and sustainable environmental outcomes.

4.2.5 JUSTICE FOR NATURE

Environmental justice traditionally focuses on issues concerning social equity. However, of late, consciousness about justice has expanded the circle of concern to include non-human natural entities in justice discourse. The concept of ‘planetary justice’ has emerged in environmental thinking. This highlights the significance of the intrinsic value of nature and its right to be protected, independent of human needs. Arne Naess (1973), the founder of deep ecology, argues for ecocentrism, a philosophy that posits that nature has intrinsic value and deserves protection for its own sake, not just for its benefit to humans. This perspective, as explored in the journal article "Deep Ecology and Value Inquiry" (Naess, 1973), challenges traditional environmentalism and its anthropocentric focus. Ecologism aligns with movements for multispecies justice or inter-species justice.

Ecocentrism is a philosophy of ‘internal relatedness’.

A more developed form of morality, known as ‘ethics’, determines human actions upon nature based on the constraints of ‘right’ and ‘wrong’ underpinnings (Simmons, 2008, p. 3). This forms the basis of what is called ‘environmental ethics.’ Broadly, based on environmental ethics, environmental thoughts may be classified into two paradigms. First, an ethic for the use of the environment that sees nature as a set of resources for humanity with concerns for its conservation for ensuring resource continuation (sustainability) or securing the notions of equity in their distribution (justice). This view is often termed as ‘utilitarian’ or ‘instrumental’ environmental ethics. Some scholars call it ‘environmentalism’. The difference between environmentalism and ecologism will be discussed in the later part of this chapter. Second, an

ethic of nature itself i.e. it applies to the whole of nature, its biotic as well as abiotic components. It does not regard *Homo sapiens* as the superior creature in the evolution of life but as only one species among innumerable which exist on this planet. 'The world is not our oyster but a place we share with the oysters: all species and ecosystems have an intrinsic value' (Simmons, 2008, p. 4). This view of ethics is also known as 'ecologism'.

First of all, it is difficult to give an accurate account of 'environmentalism' since there are different meanings attached to and definitions of the terms "ecologism," "environmentalism," and "green." In actuality, there isn't a clear-cut, universally accepted definition for what these phrases mean. Some scholars make a distinction between "environmentalism" and "ecologism"(Dobson, 2007). While the latter refers to a distinct set of ideas that independently constitute a political ideology, the former identifies concern for environmental issues and environmental protection from harmful human activities. Because of its politicization, the word "ecologism" is preferable since it implies a non-hierarchical link between humans and the natural world by referring to the interrelationships between all elements of the ecosystem, including the human race. While other scholars employ 'ecologism', 'environmentalism', and 'green' as synonyms (Dryzek, 2013). But "ecologism" might lead to misunderstandings with the term 'ecology', a branch in biology.

Theories of environmental justice are not mutually exclusive and no water-tight compartmentation exists in different perspectives of environmental justice. These perspectives often intersect and inform one another in a complex web of issues. There exist multiple causal effect relationships among these perspectives.

Building a truly just environmental future requires integrating these frameworks into policies and practices. This ensures fair decision-making, equitable distribution of resources, and respect for the rights of all beings within the environment.

4.3 ENVIRONMENTAL JUSTICE GENERATIONS:

Environmental justice discourse is not very old in comparison to other concepts and theories of political science and other social sciences. These movements emerged in the second half of the twentieth century in different forms and on various global issues. However, the movements in actions and theoretical arena have not been uniform throughout this short span of time of these movements. There have been different focus points and issues at various periods. The evolution of the discourse of environmental justice as a conceptual framework in social sciences and as a guiding principle to develop normative theories has developed over several generations. Steve Vanderheiden (2016) has divided the period of environmental justice into three generations.

4.3.1 FIRST-GENERATION ENVIRONMENTAL JUSTICE

The first-generation environmental justice discourse developed around the issues of socially unequal distribution of environmental costs i.e. hazardous waste, air pollution, nuclear sites, etc. This created socially unequal vulnerability to the exposure of such externalities of development to the people who had little or no contribution to the generation of such hazardous waste or pollution and were least beneficial of the development process that generated this sort of externalities as a by-product. Three studies, conducted in the 1980s, set up the basis of environmental justice studies and movements during the early phase of this transformation in the notion of justice. Robert Bullard (1983)

illustrated the role of race as an important factor in the decisions of locations of sites of waste disposal and hazardous substances in Houston, Texas. In the same year, a regional study was conducted by the US General Accounting Office (GAO) in response to the historic protests in Warren County, North Carolina against the locations of hazardous waste dumping (USGAO, 1983). The third study of this 'trio' was United Church of Christ's (UCC) Commission on Racial Justice, a national-scale investigation on the issue of waste sites in 1987. These studies have established a correlation between race and exposure to pollution and waste sites (Holifield et al., 2018). Bullard's study on pollution exposure in the city of Houston revealed that people of colour, especially people of African-American community had greater vulnerability to these exposures. Vanderheiden tells three conceptual features of this first generation. First, its primary focus was on the distribution of environmental hazards. This was an issue of socio-spatial distribution. At that time issues of environmental amenities and services like access to open space, and parks, were not considered as issues of environmental justice. This generation was focused on the negativities of environmental hazards rather than the positivities of environmental benefits and services. Second, this generation's movements and discourse were focused on local issues of hazards in the neighbourhood and not on remote issues. Thus, it was local in approach and scale rather than regional and global. Environmental threats of climate change were not seen to be compatible with this framework of environmental justice at that time. Third, this generation's environmental justice discourse was primarily concerned with mere race in a single country as a determinant of unequal

vulnerability and no other determinators such as socio-economic class were highlighted (Vanderheiden, 2016, p.323).

4.3.2 SECOND-GENERATION ENVIRONMENTAL JUSTICE

The second-generation environmental justice reflects the concern on the rejection of the production of hazardous substances and not only on the avoidance of these environmental hazards in the distribution on a socio-spatial basis. In the words of Bullard “not in my backyard” to “not in anyone’s backyard” (quoted in Vanderheiden, 2016, p. 323). The focus turned to the reduction in the production of these hazardous substances not merely on their equal distribution in society. During this generation, environmental justice encompasses not only the issues of equitable distribution but also the issues concerning participation and recognition making the discourse more extensive and inclusive. Schlosberg (2009) argues that EJ discourse evolved from focusing on substantive policy outcomes concerning the distribution of environmental harms or socially unequal distribution to equitable and meaningful participation and recognition of the cultural diversity and understanding of marginalised groups of people.

The first National People of Colour Environmental Leadership Summit held in 1991, portrays the main features of this generation of environmental justice through its “Principles of Environmental Justice” (Holifield et al., 2018). It calls for the demand that “public policy be based on mutual respect and justice for all peoples” (principle 2); “universal protection from nuclear testing and the extraction, production, and disposal of toxic/hazardous wastes” (principle 4); and demands “the cessation of the production of all toxins, hazardous wastes, and radioactive materials (principle 6) (United Church of Christ). Still, the

second generation remains primarily domestic in its reach and targets mostly local issues of environmental harm rather than transnational issues of pollution and anthropogenic hazards. However, this second generation has enlarged the conceptual framework of analysis by adding more sophisticated objectives, demands and remedies than the first generation.

4.3.3 THIRD-GENERATION ENVIRONMENTAL JUSTICE

The evolutionary road of environmental justice passes through the first generation focusing on equitable distribution of environmental hazards across the population on a fair basis to the second generation which calls for a reduction in the production of hazardous and nuclear substances to the awareness that the vulnerability to global warming or climate change is not affected by the vicinity of source of production of greenhouse gas production, thereby it can't be tackled by spatial redistribution of thereof. The third generation of environmental justice discourse is primarily concerned with climate change and its associated issues of injustice.

4.4 CLIMATE JUSTICE

Science has established in no uncertain terms the fundamental relation between the accumulation of GHGs in the atmosphere and the phenomenon of climate change. Global efforts started to ward off the impending challenge of global warming and its associated impacts seriously in the last decade of the twentieth century in the form of a global cooperative effort of shared interests. The global climate governance system under the aegis of UNFCCC has steered the negotiations and conferences of parties since its inception. However, achieving an effective, feasible, and fair international cooperation based on the principle of justice to respond to the problem has not been an easy one rather more challenging than it might have been thought at the start

of such negotiation. The reason for this is that any such attempt to address issues concerning climate change is embedded in the complex problems of justice. First, some communities suffer disproportionate greater vulnerability to the adverse impacts of climate change and its associated harms while they have contributed the least to the making of the problem. Second, the economic capacities of the parties (nations) to tackle the problem differ substantially from one another. Third, different political actors and generations have conflicting interests when it comes to sharing the burdens of mitigating and redressal costs.

The issue of climate justice is associated with the wider concept of environmental justice itself. Vanderheiden (2016) argues that climate justice is the third-generation extension of the evolution of environmental justice discourse. Climate justice pertains to the management or offset of anthropogenic environmental harm as injustice. The third generation has added two elements to the framework of environmental justice.

First, it widens the scope of global environmental harm which transcends nation-state boundaries and can affect vulnerable groups far away from their source of production, and that too, without fixing a direct responsibility on a state party causally connected with the loss since the state can regulate the environmental harm within their boundaries but can't remedy the injustices caused by global phenomenon such as climate change which is beyond their direct limits. (Vanderheiden, 2016). Climate justice necessarily calls for international collaboration, cooperation, and mobilization of all stakeholders toward tangible solutions to environmental harm. Thus, this generation of justice is more global in scope and lesser parochial than earlier ones. Its appeal for proposed solutions is global and transnational based on international

conventions, treaties, and agreements that call for domestic actions to mitigate the pollution or emission originated by the causal agency of individual action.

Second, the equity issue or distributive concerns are not limited to inequitable vulnerability to environmental harms as in earlier generations, but to define environmental justice issues themselves. In the third-generation discourse, the equity principle is also applied to the remedial cost incurred to mitigate environmental harm. Thus, the burden-sharing principle forms the key argument in the climate justice discourse (Harris, 2009; Vanderheiden, 2011; 2016). This generation of environmental justice discourse includes the demands for climate justice based on negative externalities resulting from developmental activities by the rich people of the developed world upon the global poor disproportionately.

The United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC) prescribes “*Common but Differentiated Responsibilities (CBDR)*” as the guiding principle of allocation of mitigation burden among the parties for climate change policy efforts. Since climate change issues and responsibility are ‘common’ to all nations, the CBDR holds that every nation in one way or another, should share some burden in mitigating efforts. The contributions of individuals or nations to the accumulation of greenhouse gases in the atmosphere are differentiated in substantial amounts, so also the remedial burden be assigned unequally. The parties as bigger polluters should share a greater amount of remedial burdens. As far as debates about climate justice are concerned, there are disagreements among scholars and policymakers about the principles required and how these principles can be implemented into practice and policymaking.

Steve Vanderheiden (2016) mentions three justice principles concerning the allocation of a share of mitigation burdens among parties concerning climate justice (p. 326).

Article 3.1 of UNFCCC states “*protect the climate system for the benefit of present and future generations of humankind, on the basis of equity and in accordance with their common but differentiated responsibilities and respective capabilities*” (UNFCCC). This single sentence encompasses the three justice principles. First, ‘*equity*’ means each national party will contribute towards climate actions for mitigation purposes; second, ‘*CBDR*’ talks about different responsibilities due to *differentiated* share of contribution in making the problem; and third ‘*respective capabilities*’ means the unequal level of development and resources at disposal in the hand of various parties.

Equity as a founding principle argues the terms of assigning the roles and capacity to absorb emissions among different parties equitably. Further, article 3.4 of the UNFCCC links climate policy with affluence or state of development by exempting developing nations from the emissions of GHG in an early round of caps. This article states “the parties have a right to, and should, promote sustainable development” (Article 3.4). Scholars have different arguments concerning ‘*equity*’ principles. Some articulate that equity-based distribution would be based on equal allocation of per capita emissions, which will entail a substantial reduction for developed countries in their current emission rate, and for developing countries, it will lead to per capita emission gains. This imperative of climate justice is also known as “*contraction and convergence*” (Meyer, 2000). Another equity-based formula might be allocating costs among parties by asking them to reduce a certain percentage of emissions from a baseline level.

1997 Kyoto Protocol's formula was based on the proposal where it asked Annex I countries to reduce their emissions by five percent at the 1990 baseline level. However, in both proposals past emissions of countries were not taken into consideration while assigning a share of the burden to the countries.

The second principle considers the past emissions of countries in allocating unequal remedial burdens according to each country's "*responsibility*" for generating the problem of climate change. CBDR works on the "*polluter pays*" principle allocating higher burdens to the parties who have more responsibility for the accumulation of greenhouse gases and lesser burden on those who made the atmosphere less polluted. The equity-based principle is forward-looking as it assigns future per capita targets by asking parties to make necessary contributions to achieve those set targets. Contrary to this CBDR is the responsibility-based principle which looks backward to determine their past contribution to the problem of climate change and allocate present and future costs to each party accordingly.

There are two categories of 'responsibility-based' or 'polluter-pays' notion of climate justice. One variety endorses the 'strict liability' of CBDR and the second pertains to 'fault-based liability'. In strict liability interpretation, each party will be fully responsible for its whole historical emission from the beginning of industrialisation, since then emission data has been estimated. On account of the long life-cycle of carbon dioxide gas, the emission of two hundred years continues to affect global climate. Therefore, it takes into account the full "historical responsibility" while assigning remedial burdens to various parties. On the other hand, fault-based liability seeks some exemptions in the historical responsibility

approach while calculating their share of burdens. Historical emissions, they argue, despite having causal responsibility, do not qualify as moral responsibility for climate harm (Vanderheiden, 2008). They base their argument on the grounds that before some baseline year, human understanding or knowledge about the causes and effects of climate change was very vague and unfounded. So, parties can't be held responsible for the emission prior to the dissemination of such scientific knowledge about national emissions causing climate change. Though there exists causal responsibility for their emissions, no moral responsibility as fault was not realizable at that time of emission. Based on Young's critics of the liability model of responsibility, Robyn Eckersley states "Young's arguments align with the forward looking 'Ability to Pay Principle (APP) rather than the backward looking 'Polluter Pays Principle' (PPP)" (Eckersley, 2016, p.355). Many scholars raise several objections to the PPP model like ignorance by the polluter, most past polluters are no longer alive, the questions of measurement, etc. which can't be attributable to polluters (Meyer & Roser, 2010; Page, 2012; Vanderheiden, 2011). However, a few writers have made different arguments in this regard e.g. Pickering and Barry (2017) while assessing the carbon or climate debt based on the historical responsibility of developed countries, concede the possibility of developing a moral account of historical responsibility. However, they conclude, that it would not be a politically helpful frame to forward the climate negotiations for the reason it overemphasises 'retrospective liability' at the cost of 'future distributive concerns.'

Another strand of fault-based liability argues that parties can be held morally responsible only for such emissions that could have reasonably

been controlled by these parties. For human existence some greenhouse emission is necessary. This ‘*subsistence emission*’ should not be counted while determining the remedial burden (Shue, 1993). According to this proposition the “*luxury emissions*”, emissions that cross the subsistence threshold, would be counted in remedial burden allocation. Another exemption to this fault-based approach could be “national emissions resulting from natural events such as volcanic eruptions” since state parties do not hold any control over these activities (Vanderheiden, 2016, p.328). Furthermore, certain other conditions such as the availability of the type of fuel, and extreme weather either hot or cold that might necessitate some energy for cooling or heating of houses might be viewed as faultless emissions. However, this type of argument seems to convey the Western approach to finding ways to avoid their historical emissions responsibility.

The third principle “respective capabilities” phrase forms the logical complementary of the CBDR principle of UNFCCC. Nations not only differ in their historical responsibilities but they also differ in their ability to further mitigate their emissions. Some scholars argue that a nation’s greater wealth and higher income should be taken into account while determining its share of the mitigation burden because ability determines how much a nation can sacrifice for a cooperative task. A capacity-based approach is a popular option for assigning remedial costs among the parties that are at different stages of capacities to contribute to solving common problems. It is not only a pragmatic option but also an issue of justice that requires equal sacrifice of interests for common solutions in combination with the stage of development of a country. Forwarding the debate on the complete rejection of the liability-based approach,

Eckersley (2016) states that “it matters how state capabilities are derived” (p.356). It means that some nations have become prosperous by emitting a larger chunk of atmospheric greenhouse gases historically. Those nations should take greater responsibility in mitigation efforts and in providing finance for mitigation and adaptation to developing and least developed countries. The guiding principle in this context may be in the opinion of Eckersley, “*Beneficiary Pays Principle (BPP)* without attaching the “blame” associated with PPP, *qua* liability model” (Eckersley, 2016, p. 356). The difference between the two principles i.e. BPP and PPP has been clearly explained by Edward Page (2012) saying that “BPP entails ‘giving up’ rather than ‘paying back’ a benefit unwittingly but unjustly acquired” (p. 315).

Critical thinkers have placed their arguments about ‘structural injustices’ at the center of their understanding of climate concerns. There are structural links between the historical and present skewed distribution of resources in the existing international economic system. They locate climate change concerns in the structural injustices in the form of unequal flow of resources, skill, energy, and material among the North and South nations underpinning their colonial past and the impact of a globalised world economy (Parks & Roberts, 2010). Thus, the North has an ‘ecological debt’ to the South on account of occupying an unjust proportion of ‘ecological space’ to the disadvantage of the South in an “unequal ecological exchange”. They argue that the carbon debt is just a part of this larger ecological debt that encompasses a colonial legacy and a regularly “shifting international division of labour”. This trend will decrease carbon emissions in several developed countries because they specialize in service sectors and largely the manufacturing sector, a major

emitter, is being shifted to the developing countries. Vanderheiden (2008) calls it “*the race to the bottom*” for avoiding the stringent and costly environmental and labour laws within the boundaries of advanced countries (p. 65). Now the citizens of developed countries import carbon-intensive goods from developing countries without having the responsibility of carbon emitted in the production and transportation of those goods being consumed by developed countries.

Out of the three approaches of the Ability to Pay Principle (APP), Polluter Pays Principle (PPP), and Beneficiary Pays Principle (BPP), Eckersley calls for the BPP model for it is a politically feasible and more useful framework to apply in the justice paradigm of climate concerns. It helps to ‘catch’ both the early polluters and the free riders by the mechanism of offshoring of emissions based on Young’s social connection model which provides ground for developed and resourceful nations to take responsibility for transforming international economic exchanges and structure to address the unequal distribution of burdens and benefits resulting out of the international economic system (Eckersley, 2016, p.357) The national mitigation burden should be grounded in the mix of past emissions and present affluence and no single principle is complete enough to frame responsibility for providing justice to the most vulnerable people in a comprehensive way (Caney, 2005; 2010, p.212). According to Eckersley (2016) in contrast to PPP in which particular polluters cannot be held responsible for climate harm, BPP limits itself to the extent to which a beneficiary has been benefited unwittingly from causing harm to others; and the APP does not discriminate between the different strata of society (‘clean’ and ‘dirty’ rich) in a developed country. It tries to bridge both the ‘forward-looking

responsibility' in mitigation and 'backward-looking responsibility' in compensatory or remedial justice (Vanderheiden, 2011). The climate regime consists of allocating mitigation and compensation costs among the parties and applying theories of justice to determine their fair distribution. The PPP model determines the responsibility for causing climate change through their historical emissions disproportionately. For instance, China and India are home to about forty percent of total humanity, however, they have combinedly contributed just around nine percent of total anthropogenic GHGs, in contrast to the USA with thirty percent of share in the pie with just five percent of the world population. According to the strict liability principle, the USA should bear 30 % of the total mitigation burden and China and India jointly have 9%. The disproportionate utilisation of atmospheric space by developed countries has been endorsed by the UNFCCC which acknowledges industrialised countries being responsible for 75 percent of accumulated emissions while they constitute only 20 percent of the planet's population (Vanderheiden, 2008, p.71).

4.5 NON-IDEAL PERSPECTIVES ON CLIMATE CHANGE

In response to the questions of justice concerning climate change, several ideal normative theories have been proposed to guide the fair distribution of the associated cost of climate change. Some of the perspectives mentioned above talk about different guiding principles to be adopted while dealing with the issue of climate justice. These include the "*Polluter Pays Principle*" (Meyer & Roser, 2010; Shue, 1999), "*the Ability to Pay Principle*" (Shue, 1999; Caney, 2005), the "*Beneficiary Pays Principle*" (Caney, 2005), and per capita emission distribution perspective advanced by Singer (2002). However, these theoretical and

normative versions of justice could not attract the policymakers and political interests of world leaders to coordinate climate governance (Kenehan & Katz, 2021, p. 4). For instance, a group of nations put forth the “*Brazil Proposal*” in which certain industrialised countries were identified to have been responsible for their historical role in making the problem and held responsible for the cost associated with reducing emissions based on Polluter Pays Principle grounded in fairness. This proposal was rejected by developed countries, though it was based on solid normative ground. Many such examples raise the question of the practicability of normative theories in real public policy. Climate Change has put nations in conditions where the ideals of normative theories of justice, their applicability in real-world political interests, and the feasibility of their adoption are being tested. Climate change has challenged our perception and understanding of the normative question ‘What constitutes wrongful harm?’ because, as Dale Jamieson (2014) argues, our moral psychology has evolved in small, and close-knit communities, “it would not be surprising if there were questions relating to anthropogenic climate change about which our everyday morality is flummoxed, silent, or incorrect” (p.147). Taking stock of the multidimensions and multiple faces of the problem of climate change, Stephen Gardiner (2011) considers it “profoundly global, intergenerational, and theoretical” and describes the phenomenon as a “*perfect moral storm*”. There exists a large divide between what is feasible climate policy or action and what ought to be as per normative theoretical principles. Gardiner and Jamieson have mentioned several feasibility constraints of climate actions. In practice, the ‘parties’ (states) of UNFCCC and other agents including governments, transnational

organisations, lending institutions, multinational corporations, non-state actors, etc. have not fulfilled their promises or aspirations concerning the emissions targets and flow of finance and technology to the developing countries. Experience shows that strict compliance is unlikely in the future too. For instance, carbon emissions increased in substantial amounts since the 1990s when efforts to curb the emissions were started. Furthermore, the Paris Agreement does not specify an allocation of responsibilities but leaves it to the parties to “prepare, communicate and maintain successive nationally determined contributions that it intends to achieve” voluntarily (Article 4.2.).

One worrisome and interesting twist of noncompliance or partial compliance is that it may result in further non-compliance. For instance, if agents who are required to bear the burden fail to comply or partially comply with their responsibility and other compliers have to shoulder their burden, other compliers also tend to turn into noncompliers. Non-ideal climate justice perspective has been used in a radically different sense by climate ethicists. They challenge the existing standard modus operandi of climate ethics and seek new ways to interpret and explain the ethical issues involved in climate justice. The main core is realism i.e. to start with ‘what is’ (actual positions of people, policies, political forces) and then develop ‘what ought to be’ a normative approach.

Non-compliance with climate promises, according to Simon Caney (2016), raises two questions:

“Q1: What should agents do when others do not discharge their climate responsibilities? Should agents take on extra climate responsibilities when others fail to comply? Or are they released from those that would otherwise bind them when others fail to cooperate? Or, are their

responsibilities affected in another way?” She calls it the ‘responsibility question’ and the second question is about the ‘governance process’.

“Q2: *Given the lack of progress in combating climate change, should existing governance structures be maintained or changed (and if they should be changed, in what ways)?*”(p.2).

Caney maintains that the answer to question no. 1 lies in four principles. According to her principle 1 argues: that when some fail to discharge their climate duties, as per the nonideal theory of climate justice, they must select the responses out of “(i) *Target Modification*, (ii) *Responsibility Reallocation*, (iii) *Burden Shifting I*, (iv) *Burden Shifting II*, (v) *Compromising Moral Ideals*, and (6) *Changing the Incentive Structure*” available to the agents. (Caney, 2016: p.4). Caney signifies the importance of an “integrationist approach” to nonideal theory. She defines the integrationist approach as “*one that considers a given issue, X, (say, climate change) in conjunction with other issues (like poverty, development, health, migration, other environmental issues such as ozone layer depletion and ocean acidification) and treats them both as part of a more general normative theory*” (Caney, 2016, p.5). The importance of the integrationist approach lies in its understanding that the phenomenon of climate change and climate actions are inextricably linked with socio-economic issues such as health, migration, development, cultural rights, and poverty. Principle 2 states that “*Any nonideal theory of climate justice must draw on a broadly egalitarian theory of global justice that employs a capabilities framework*”. Principle 2 is related to this integration of climate change with the socio-economic issues and capabilities of people to respond to specific situations. Climate change or the theories does not operate in silos without interaction with socio-

economic realities and political will powers but these are well-integrated with socio-economic and environmental spheres. Principle 3 talks about the feasibility or the opportunities available and the constraints present in a particular course of action taken by an agent in climate policy-making. Principle 4 is a response to the situation when noncompliance varies from one agent to another. In this situation, Caney gives four objectives for noncompliance. These beings (i) “Clean Energy”, (ii) “Fossil Fuel Subsidies”, (iii) “Framing”, and (iv) “Exemplification and visions of the Future”.

In response to the second question of governance, Simon Caney (2016) argues for accepting the existing institutional system of governance (even though they are not democratic and inclusive in ideal form); “facilitative dialogue” and “global stocktake”, and organisations should, and can function with the existing structures of governance and can avail the opportunities to hold governments accountable (pp.11-12).

A less radical view that focuses on the realistic principle of climate justice is put by Alexandre Gajevic Sayegh. This view argues to consider the empirical situations and not the abstract formulations of justice principles such as the principle of equality. The assumption to equalize the distribution of emissions results in implausible consequences because some persons need more carbon space reasonably than others do. Taking account of this proposition, Sayegh notes, the principle of climate justice should be formulated (Sayegh, 2018). Different scholars have contributed differently to the evolution of the non-ideal theories of climate justice. Some point out that there are better climate protection options. Roser’s ‘the motivation-compatible set of options’, can be explained here. He thinks that there is the availability of better climate protection actions that

are also compatible with the ‘limited motivation of agents.’ These are also known as “no-regret options” or “win-win options”, since they have co-benefits apart from having climate protection e.g. healthy pollution-free air, energy efficiency, health benefits, etc. In choosing the option for climate action or climate protection, Roser’s idea is “to choose the least unjust option within the bounds of motivation, however, insufficient motivation may currently be” (Roser, 2016, p. 84). Some scholars have also forwarded similar propositions. They argue for not emphasis on “fine-tuning general distributive principles” but on reforming the multilateralism of institutions such as UNFCCC with a normative approach (Maltais, 2016). These are like ‘mediating strategies’ that make political situations more functional in a piecemeal way (Brandstedt, 2017). Taking note of Roser’s proposal, Eric Brandstedt (2017) concedes that the role of climate ethicists becomes like that of a policy analyst. Brandstedt argues that this new role of climate ethicists is “no doubt important, though not clearly one that climate ethicists should exclusively adopt” (p.7). Darrel Moellendorf (2016) in ‘Taking UNFCCC Norms Seriously’, argues “Because of the decidedly non-ideal circumstances of climate change, perhaps the development of a non-ideal theory guided by an ideal account of justice is appropriate.” (p.104).

CHAPTER – V

ANALYSIS OF SAPCC AND DATA FROM SELECTED DISTRICTS OF UTTAR PRADESH

5.1 INTRODUCTION

Research Analysis is one of the most significant steps in the research processes as it is the step which is used to analyse both qualitative as well as quantitative data gathered to draw conclusions, results and findings apart from it validate, reject or alter the hypothesis of the research. It is an evaluation process with logical & analytical reasoning to examine different components/factors of the given or gathered data to fulfil the requirements of the undertaken study. This chapter has an in-depth analysis of the State Action Plan on Climate Change 2.0 (SAPCC 2.0) in the first part and analysis and interpretation of the primary data of selected districts of Uttar Pradesh to draw findings and examine the hypotheses of the study. One hypothesis concern with the SAPCC 2.0. Let's examine the different hypotheses proposed to be tested in the proposal of the study

PART –A

ANALYSIS OF STATE ACTION PLAN ON CLIMATE CHANGE

In this section I have tried to analyse the SAPCC in the light of concept of environmental justice. As discussed in the Chapter 4 there are different approaches of environmental justice according to the different scholars. I have taken the concept of environmental justice as propounded by one of the most significant and effective voice of environmental justice – David Schlosberg. Schlosberg has identified three components of environmental justice i.e. distributive justice, participative justice and recognition justice. David Schlosberg's framework of environmental justice provides

a robust lens for analysing the "SAPCC 2.0" policy plan. The analysis of the SAPCC has been made on these criteria to examine whether the elements/ components of environmental justice have been incorporated in the policy document or not. The plan's alignment with environmental justice—distributive, participative, and recognition justice—is crucial for ensuring fair benefits, inclusive decision-making, and respect for all communities, especially the vulnerable section of the society. The methodology of thematic analysis has been applied to analyse the environmental justice components in the action plan.

5.2 EVALUATION OF STATE ACTION PLAN ON CLIMATE CHANGE

Testing Hypothesis-1 “The State Action Plan on Climate Change in Uttar Pradesh is inclusive, comprehensive and just”

The Uttar Pradesh State Action Plan on Climate Change (UPSAPCC) 2021-2030 is a comprehensive strategy to tackle climate change in Uttar Pradesh, focusing on eight key missions. These missions aim to mitigate and adapt to climate impacts, with a particular emphasis on sectors like agriculture, water, and energy. As discussed earlier the original document UPSAPCC was initially formulated in 2014 in consonance to the National Action Plan on Climate Change of 2008 (UPSAPCC 1.0, 2014; NAPCC, 2008). The document has been revised and updated in the light of two important developments i.e. adoption of Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) and Paris Agreement objectives. The revised plan has been made compatible with these goals and objectives as climate actions and SDGs intersects with one another. It is an effort to integrate the climate concerns into policy ecosystem to formulate, execute the climate compatible policies to ensure sustainable and inclusive development. The

goal is having not only a climate policy but also to make all policies climate and environmentally friendly.

5.2.1 Distributive Justice Components in SAPCC 2.0

Distributive justice focuses on the equitable allocation of environmental goods (e.g., resources, opportunities) and the fair distribution of environmental harms (e.g., climate risks, pollution). The plan likely includes programs like providing climate-resilient crops and water-efficient irrigation to small farmers, which helps distribute benefits to marginalised communities. For instance, initiatives for energy-saving appliances and green building codes aim to reach low-income households, ensuring broader access to energy efficiency benefits.

1. Sustainable Agriculture Mission:

Under sustainable agriculture mission the major elements of distributive justice include: (a) Targeted Interventions for Vulnerable Regions e.g. the document identifies agro-climatic zones with specific climate risks, such as drought in Bundelkhand and floods in eastern Uttar Pradesh (UPSAPCC 2.0, p.115). SAPCC 2.0 proposes tailored strategies, such as promoting drought-resilient crops (e.g., millets) and flood-resilient rice varieties, which address the disproportionate burdens faced by these regions. For instance, the strategy to shift 50 districts with declining groundwater levels to less water-intensive crops aims to distribute adaptation benefits to water-stressed areas. (b) Focus on Small and Marginal Farmers through recognising that 80% of agricultural landholdings in Uttar Pradesh are marginal, the plan prioritizes actions like extending crop and livestock insurance and training through Farmer Producer Organizations (FPOs) (UPSAPCC 2.0, pp.121-122). These measures aim to equitably distribute risk-sharing tools and economic

opportunities to those most vulnerable to climate-induced losses. (c) Weather Forecasting by establishing Agro-Automatic Weather Stations (AWSs) and disseminating forecasts via SMS to 2.81 crore farmers registered under PM KISAN (UPSAPCC 2.0, p.122).

2. Jal (Water) Mission:

The Jal Mission talks about (a) Water Resource Management through proposed groundwater recharge plans and water use efficiency measures (UPSAPCC 2.0, pp.133-136), addressing the distributive injustice of water scarcity in overexploited regions. For example, targeting industrial clusters in critical blocks for recharge plans seeks to balance resource allocation between industrial and agricultural users. (b) Groundwater Recharge through investments in recharge structures to address declining groundwater levels, critical for rural farmers reliant on irrigation. (c) Flood Preparedness via actions to manage floods in non-traditional flooding areas to ensure that vulnerable communities receive protection from climate-induced water hazards (UPSAPCC 2.0, pp.135-136).

3. Green UP Mission:

Green UP Mission has components of distributive justice in its various strategies and actions. (a) Forest Restoration: Restoring Forest Cover enhances carbon sequestration and ecosystem services, benefiting rural communities in forest-dependent areas. (b) Agroforestry: Promoting agroforestry on private and community lands improves incomes for forest-dependent populations, addressing economic vulnerabilities and fixing MSP (Minimum Support Price) for agro-forestry products. (c) Wetland Conservation Investments in wetland restoration protect water resources and biodiversity, critical for communities reliant on wetlands (UPSAPCC 2.0, pp.143-146).

4. Enhanced Energy Efficiency & Green Energy Mission:

The Energy Efficiency and Green Energy Mission focuses on reducing energy losses, promoting solar energy, and transitioning to electric vehicles (EVs). It includes (a) Solarizing water pumping to ensure equitable energy access for rural farmers, fully funded through government schemes; and (b) EV Transition i.e. promoting EVs in cities reduces urban air pollution, benefiting public health (UPSAPCC 2.0, Strategy 1 & 6, pp.154-155).

5. Sustainable Habitat Mission:

Sustainable Habitat Mission also addresses urban and rural resilience through climate-resilient infrastructure and planning, developing climate-resilient water and waste management systems benefits urban populations, particularly in flood-prone areas. Fully funded actions for climate-resilient rural housing and roads ensure equitable access to infrastructure in rural areas (UPSAPCC 2.0, Strategies 6–9, pp. 173-174).

6. Human Health Mission:

Human Health Mission ensure health protections through (a) disease forecasting in a real time benefits all populations by enabling timely health interventions. (b) Behavioural change i.e. public awareness campaigns reduce climate-linked disease risks, equitably distributed across communities (UPSAPCC 2.0, Strategy 2 & 3, pp. 188-190).

7. Disaster Management:

The Disaster Management Mission distributes disaster resilience benefits in form of (a) Institutional Resilience i.e. enhancing capacities for disaster response protects vulnerable communities. (b) Knowledge products ensuring equitable access to disaster preparedness resources (UPSAPCC 2.0, Strategy 1 & 2, pp.198-199).

8. Strategic Knowledge Mission:

The mission distributes knowledge and capacity benefits in creating (a) knowledge hubs i.e. establishing state and district-level hubs to ensure equitable access to climate data, though fully externally funded; and (b) capacity building through training policymakers and local bodies enhances governance capacity across regions (UPSAPCC 2.0, Strategy 2 & 3, pp. 204-205).

5.2.2 PARTICIPATIVE JUSTICE COMPONENTS IN SAPCC 2.0

Participative justice involves stakeholders in decision-making. The plan seems to support this through farmer cooperatives in agriculture and community-based water management, allowing local voices to shape policies. Public participation in urban planning and community renewable energy projects further enhances inclusivity, ensuring that those affected by climate change have a say in the solutions.

1. Sustainable Agriculture Mission:

Community Involvement in Local Planning: The plan proposes involving Gram Panchayats and urban communities in developing local water budgets (UPSAPCC 2.0, p. 121), signalling an intent to foster participative governance at the micro-watershed level. This aligns with participative justice by empowering local bodies to manage resources based on contextual needs.

Training and Capacity Building: Strategies like training FPO farmers on climate-smart practices and engaging women's self-help groups in water use efficiency campaigns (UPSAPCC 2.0, p.122) suggest efforts to build community capacity and involve grassroots actors. These initiatives can enhance local agency and participation in climate adaptation.

Stakeholder Consultations: The action plan notes that strategies were developed through consultations with stakeholders and experts (UPSAPCC 2.0, pp.32-33), indicating some level of inclusive dialogue during the planning phase. Partnerships with NABARD for FPO development indicate stakeholder engagement in resource allocation.

2. Jal (Water) Mission:

The mission includes limited participatory mechanisms:

Research and Monitoring: Collaboration with the World Bank for the National Hydrology Project suggests stakeholder engagement in water budgeting, though primarily at the institutional level. Infrastructure Strengthening: Partnerships with multilateral agencies like the World Bank for dam rehabilitation involve technical experts, indicating some inclusivity in planning (UPSAPCC 2.0, Strategy 1& 2, pp. 133-134).

3. Green UP Mission:

Participatory elements are limited but present in form of Carbon Markets and CSR: Agroforestry actions involve voluntary carbon markets and CSR funding, suggesting private sector and community engagement in implementation. Eco-Tourism (UPSAPCC 2.0, pp.145-146) talks about developing eco-tourism in PPP mode which involves local stakeholders, potentially including forest-dependent communities.

4. Enhanced Energy Efficiency & Green Energy Mission:

Participatory elements are limited however, the participation of farmers in establishments of solar parks in their lands makes the mission participatory in this sense. EV transition and energy efficiency actions involve private sector partnerships (p.156), suggesting some stakeholder engagement. Solar power plant actions involve national funds, indicating institutional collaboration (pp. 155-158).

5. Sustainable Habitat Mission:

Participatory mechanisms in the sustainable habitat mission include:

Urban Governance: Collaboration for city climate action plans suggests engagement with urban stakeholders, though primarily at the institutional level. Widespread awareness programmes and training for representatives of local self-governance bodies Rural Planning (UPSAPCC 2.0, pp.173-178).

6. Human Health Mission:

In Human Health Mission participatory mechanisms are limited e.g. full funding through government schemes suggests centralized planning with some institutional stakeholder involvement. Further, the strategy 2 talks about the behavioural change of public at large to ward off climate-linked epidemics. It involves the training and widespread participation of teachers, students and other key stakeholders in achieving the desired outcomes.

7. Disaster Management:

The Disaster Management Mission has some participatory elements which includes External Funding in form of collaboration with UNDP and World Bank involves institutional stakeholders however, the communities' role is limited to participating in the training programmes to be organised to disseminate, processing, and implementing the information received.

8. Strategic Knowledge Mission:

The mission emphasises participation through Knowledge Networks which includes involving universities, NGOs, and community-based organizations fosters multi-stakeholder collaboration and Training

Programs i.e. engaging district officials and local bodies ensures decentralized participation (UPSAPCC 2.0, pp.205-206).

5.2.3 RECOGNITION JUSTICE COMPONENTS IN SAPCC 2.0

Recognition justice involves acknowledging the diverse identities, cultures, and vulnerabilities of communities, ensuring that policies respect and address their specific needs and contexts. In UP SAPCC 2.0, this requires evaluating whether the plan recognises the heterogeneity of Uttar Pradesh's diverse communities specially agriculture-dependent communities because of their high vulnerability and tailor interventions accordingly.

1. Sustainable Agriculture Mission:

Regional Vulnerabilities: It identifies specific climate risks across UP's nine Agro-Climatic Zones (e.g., drought in Bundelkhand, floods in eastern UP), tailoring actions like flood-resilient rice varieties to regional needs. The action plan focuses on small and marginal farmers and acknowledges their economic vulnerability, with actions like insurance and training addressing their specific needs. Recognising the resilience of indigenous cattle to climate stressors, the mission proposes artificial insemination to enhance productivity, respecting traditional livestock practices (UPSAPCC 2.0, pp. 122-124).

2. Jal (Water) Mission:

The mission recognizes some regional vulnerabilities e.g. Drought and Flood Risks. It acknowledges specific water risks in Bundelkhand (drought) and eastern UP (floods), tailoring actions like groundwater recharge and flood preparedness to these areas (UPSAPCC 2.0, pp.127-128).The focus on groundwater recharge recognizes the vulnerability of farmers in water-stressed districts emphasising Groundwater Depletion problem in certain areas.

3. Green UP Mission:

The mission recognizes some ecological and community vulnerabilities like Forest-Dependent Communities: It acknowledges the economic reliance of communities on forests, proposing agroforestry to enhance incomes. It focuses on wetland conservation recognizes their role in biodiversity and water security (UPSAPCC 2.0, pp.145-146).

4. Enhanced Energy Efficiency & Green Energy Mission:

The mission recognizes some sectoral needs:

Rural Energy Access: Solarization actions acknowledge farmers' need for reliable energy. Urban Pollution: EV promotion recognizes urban air quality challenges (UPSAPCC 2.0, pp. 154-155).

5. Sustainable Habitat Mission:

The mission recognizes some vulnerabilities:

Urban and Rural Divide: It acknowledges the distinct needs of urban (e.g., water infrastructure) and rural (e.g., housing) populations, tailoring actions accordingly. Flood-Prone Areas: Urban water infrastructure actions recognize flood risks in cities (UPSAPCC 2.0, pp. 174-175).

6. Human Health Mission:

The mission recognizes health vulnerabilities e.g. Climate-Linked Diseases. It acknowledges the spatial spread of climate-induced health risks and calls for actions to location-specific needs.

7. Disaster Management:

This mission recognizes disaster vulnerabilities e.g. Climate-Induced Disasters. It acknowledges risks like floods and droughts, tailoring actions to affected regions (UPSAPCC 2.0, p. 198).

8. Strategic Knowledge Mission:

The mission recognizes diverse needs like developing Thematic Networks which focus on areas like sustainable agriculture and water resources and acknowledge sectoral vulnerabilities. The Uttar Pradesh Climate Change Authority (UPCCA)'s expert committees recognize diverse sectoral and regional needs.

5.2.4 CRITICAL EVALUATION OF SAPCC 2.0

UP SAPCC 2.0 demonstrates a commitment to environmental justice but exhibits uneven alignment with Schlosberg's framework across its missions. There are some key issues and areas where the action plan either lacks or is ambiguous in ensuring fairness and equity in the light of above-mentioned three components of environmental justice. The major drawbacks are the followings:

- **Limited Attention to Socio-economic Disparities:** The action plan document acknowledges the economic dependence on agriculture but does not deeply engage with how intersecting factors like caste, gender, or landlessness exacerbate vulnerability. For instance, landless labourers, who form a significant portion of rural Uttar Pradesh, are not explicitly addressed in resource distribution strategies, potentially perpetuating inequitable access to benefits like training or insurance. This also risks neglecting the recognition rights of these diverse groups. The mission on human health does not prioritize marginalised groups (e.g., SC/ST, elderly) who face higher health risks due to limited healthcare access. Another instance can be cited from Jal Mission which does not address the urban water inequities, such as access for slum dwellers. The energy efficiency mission does not prioritize low-

income urban communities for EV benefits or energy-efficient appliances.

- **Under-representation of Marginalised Groups:** The Action Plan does not explicitly address how socially marginalised groups—such as Scheduled Castes, Scheduled Tribes, or women—are integrated into decision-making. For instance, while women are mentioned in training programs, there is no evidence of their inclusion in higher-level planning or policy design, which is critical for participative justice. Community participation in health planning is absent. Vulnerable groups are not engaged in designing awareness campaigns or forecasting systems.
- **Centralized Implementation:** Many strategies rely on nodal agencies like the Agriculture Department or Uttar Pradesh Irrigation and Water Resources Department (UPIWRD), with limited emphasis on decentralizing authority to local communities. This top-heavy approach may undermine participatory governance, as local knowledge and priorities could be sidelined. It lacks direct engagement with grassroots communities, such as small farmers or women, in designing strategies.
- **Neglect of Cultural Practices:** The document does not engage with the cultural or traditional practices of communities that could inform climate adaptation. The cultural and traditional practices of environment-friendly lifestyle of indigenous people have not been emphasised. For instance, indigenous health knowledge or traditional water management systems (beyond modern interventions like drip irrigation) are not integrated into strategies, missing an opportunity to respect local knowledge.

- **Generic Framing of Communities:** The plan often refers to “farmers” or “communities” as homogenous groups, failing to recognize internal diversity (e.g., tenant farmers vs. landowners, or rural vs. peri-urban populations). This generic approach may lead to one-size-fits-all solutions that do not fully address specific needs of diverse communities.
- **Uneven Resource Allocation and funding gaps:** While the plan allocates significant budgets (e.g. Rs. 29,798 crores for agriculture and Rs. 64,170.13 crores for water, it lacks clarity on how these funds will be distributed across districts or communities. Without transparent mechanisms to prioritize the most vulnerable districts (e.g., the 41 districts ranked moderately to very highly vulnerable in agriculture), there is a risk that resources may disproportionately benefit less vulnerable or politically influential areas. The funding gap for agroforestry (81%) and wetland conservation (87%) risks unequal benefit distribution if external funds (e.g., GIZ, GEF) are not secured. Urban marginalised communities, such as those near degraded wetlands, are not prioritized for benefits. The funding gap for institutional resilience risks unequal protection for marginalised communities if external funds (e.g., UNDP, World Bank) are not secured. Further there is biasedness toward the ‘mitigation’ against the ‘adaptation’ worldwide and most of the climate finance (more than 60%) is in form of loan and not in form of grants to developing nations. This further complicates the debt burden and undermine their long-term prospects in investing in sustainable solutions and assets (UNEP, 2023; Zagema et al., 2023).

- **No Nodal Office at District Level:** The SAPCC 2.0 has a separate chapter on ‘Monitoring and Evaluation’ which describes in detail the various departments and ministries involved in the monitoring and evaluation processes of various missions, strategies and action thereof. However, there is no provision of any nodal office/officer at district level to report the progress of SAPCC in the concerned districts. This is necessary to have specific interventions at the regional/district level.

Result: In view of the above critical analysis of the SAPCC 2.0, it can be said that the said hypothesis “The State Action Plan on Climate Change in Uttar Pradesh is inclusive, comprehensive and just” is partially true as the action plan is comprehensive in nature and include all developmental sectors under its ambit. However, as far as its inclusivity and justness is concerned, it fulfils some elements of environmental justice and lacks on some criterion as discussed in the abovementioned section in detail

PART -B

ANALYSIS OF PRIMARY DATA OF SELECTED DISTRICTS OF UTTAR PRADESH

5.3 PROFILE OF RESPONDENTS

The demographical profile of the respondents pertaining to their districts, urban-rural, age, gender, educational qualification and occupations are represented in frequency and percentage distributions in the following tables and pie charts.

5.3.1 Districts of Respondents

Table 5.1: Frequency Table for districts of respondents

Districts	Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent
Bahraich	200	25.0	25.0
Lakhimpur	200	25.0	50.0
Mahoba	200	25.0	75.0
Sonbhadra	200	25.0	100.0
Total	800	100.0	

Figure 5.1: Pie Chart for Districts of Respondents

Based on responses of Questionnaire/Schedule

Interpretation: The frequency table shows that the respondents have been selected from the four districts of Uttar Pradesh. The selection of these districts has already been discussed in Chapter 4. Two hundred respondents have been approached from district of Bahraich, Lakhimpur Khiri, Mahoba and Sonbhadra.

5.3.2 Gender of Respondents

Table 5.2: Frequency table for Gender of respondents

Gender	Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percentage
Female	295	36.9	36.9
Male	505	63.1	100.0
Total	800	100.0	

Figure 5.2: Pie Chart for Gender of Respondents

Based on responses of question no. 1.4 of Questionnaire/Schedule

Interpretation: The above-mentioned frequency distribution table and pie chart of gender of respondents show the percentage of male and female respondents. There are 63.1% male and 36.9 %respondents out of the total 800 respondents. The slightly higher percentage of male respondents is due to the lack of socio-cultural factors responsible for social mobility of females in our society.

5.3.3 Social Categories of Respondents

Table 5.3: Frequency table for Categories of respondents

Categories	Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent
General	155	19.4	19.4
OBC	343	42.9	62.3
SC	218	27.3	89.5
ST	84	10.5	100.0
Total	800	100.0	

Figure 5.3: Pie Chart for Social Categories of Respondents

Based on responses of question no. 1.6 of Questionnaire/Schedule

Interpretation: The pie chart and frequency table clearly show the social category wise distribution of respondents of the study. About 43% respondents belongs to Other Backward Classes (OBC). 19.4% respondents come from General category while 27.3% and 10.5%

respondents belong to Scheduled Castes (SC) and Scheduled Tribes (ST) respectively. Thus, the sample is inclusive and wide spread in social and geographical dimensions.

5.3.4 Religions of the Respondents

Table 5.4: Frequency table of Religion of respondents

Religion	Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent
Hinduism	719	89.9	89.9
Muslim	58	7.2	97.1
Sikh	2	.3	97.4
Christian	2	.3	97.6
Buddhism	19	2.4	100.0
Total	800	100.0	

Based on responses of question no. 1.7 of Questionnaire/Schedule

Interpretation: The frequency table of religion shows the different faiths of the respondents of the study. About 90% respondents belongs to Hinduism. Second highest number is of Muslims with 7.2%. Sikh, Christian and Buddhism constitute 0.3%, 0.3% and 2.4% respectively. Though, this figure may vary from the exact proportion of these religions in the state because of coincidence of a particular religion in the sphere of study. However, it covers almost major faiths in the state.

5.3.5 Educational Qualification of Respondents

Table 5.5: Frequency table for Education of Respondents

Educational Qualification	Frequency	Percentage
Uneducated	211	26.4
Class 1-5	157	19.6
Class 5-10	158	19.8
Class 11-12	86	10.8
Graduate	138	17.3
Post Graduate	47	5.9
Professional	3	.4
Total	800	100.0

Figure 5.4: Pie Chart for Qualification of Respondents

Based on responses of question no. 1.7 of Questionnaire/Schedule

Interpretation: The above-mentioned frequency table and pie chart clearly show the distribution of educational qualification among the respondents. The highest number is of uneducated persons. This is compatible with the poor educational attainment of Uttar Pradesh. Though, most of persons belongs to elderly category and youths are educated with different educational qualifications ranging from primary education to post-graduation and professional ones.

5.3.6 Occupation of Respondents

Table 5.6: Frequency table for occupation of Respondents

OCCUPATIONS	Frequency	Percent
Agriculture	293	36.6
Labour	250	31.3
Shopkeeper	35	4.4
Businessman	17	2.1
Pvt. Job In Org. Sector	32	4.0
Pvt.JobInUnorg.Sector	22	2.8
Govt.Job	17	2.1
Unemployed	26	3.3
Student	88	11.0
House Wife	20	2.5
Total	800	100.0

Figure 5.5: Pie Chart for Occupations of Respondents

Based on responses of question no. 1.9 of Questionnaire/Schedule

Interpretation: Frequency distribution and pie chart show the distribution of respondents' occupation. The largest portion belongs to Agriculture (36.6%) and labourer (31.3%) classes. This is due to the fact that Uttar Pradesh is still an agriculture-based state and most of the population is engaged in agriculture and allied sectors. Further many persons are engaged in labour activities due to either poor educational attainments or no ownership to land or other gainful resources. However, the respondents have a varied occupations ranging from agriculture to shopkeepers, businessmen, home makers, govt. jobs, private jobs in organised sectors and in unorganised sectors, students and highly skilled professionals. This reflects the diversified sample occupation wise to cover the major categories of livelihood of the sample population.

5.4 VISIBLE IMPACTS OF CLIMATE CHANGE

Testing Hypothesis-2 “The increased visibility of Climate Change in the form of extreme weather patterns is affecting socio-economic determinants of health, livelihood, and habitat of people of Uttar Pradesh”

To assess the impact of climate change on the livelihood, health and habitat, data has been collected from different sections of society across the selected districts. The data and interpretation thereof are given in the following tables and charts

5.4.1 Impact of climate change-induced abnormal weather conditions on production

Table 5.7: Crosstab for impact of climate change-Induced abnormal weather conditions on production.

Crosstab							
District	How do abnormal climates like untimely rain, pre-summer season, Loo, drought flood, etc, affect production?						Total
	Less production	Substantial Reduction in production	Normal production	Increased production	Can't say	Doesn't pertain	
Bahraich	60	79	12	2	12	35	200
Lakhimpur	41	91	12	1	15	40	200
Mahoba	15	111	7	0	11	56	200
Sonbhadra	43	58	19	3	23	54	200
Total	159	339	50	6	61	185	800

Chi-Square Tests			
	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	75.448	15	.000
Likelihood Ratio	80.597	15	.000
No. of Valid Cases	800		

Based on responses of question no. 5.4 of Questionnaire/Schedule

Interpretation:

The cross tabulation observes clear district-wise variations in the perception of how these climate abnormalities affect agricultural output. A substantial proportion of respondents from Lakhimpur (91) and Mahoba (127) reported substantial reduction in production. While Bahraich (60) and Sonbhadra (57) reported ‘Less production,’ highlighting vulnerability to climate variability. Notably, a significant number of people across all districts indicated uncertainty, with 61 respondents selecting ‘Can't say,’ and 185 stating ‘Doesn't pertain,’ indicating either a lack of awareness or that they are not directly involved in agriculture.

The **Chi-Square Test** reinforces the statistical significance of these differences. The Pearson Chi-Square value of 75.448 with 15 degrees of freedom (df) and a p-value of .000 suggests that there is a highly significant association between the district and perceptions of climate impact on agricultural production. The Likelihood Ratio of 80.597, also with a p-value of .000, further validates this association.

Studies by other scholars also validates these findings (Tripathi, 2013). A study published in reputed journal *Discover Sustainability* by ‘Springer

Nature' entitled "Farmers' perception of climate change and livelihood vulnerability: A comparative study of Bundelkhand and Central regions of Uttar Pradesh, India" also found their perception of substantial loss in production (Jatav, 2024).

5.4.2 Scale of loss of crop production due to adverse impact of climate change

Table 5.8: Crosstab for scale loss of crop production due to climate change

Crosstab							
		In the last 5 years adverse climate change has negatively affected your crop production?					Total
		upto 10%	upto 20%	Upto 50%	upto 80%	Doesn't pertain	
District	Bahraich	30	53	44	25	48	200
	Lakhimpur	59	83	6	0	52	200
	Mahoba	43	63	31	5	58	200
	Sonbhadra	50	88	6	0	56	200
Total		182	287	87	30	214	800

Chi-Square Tests			
	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	128.554	12	.000
Likelihood Ratio	132.175	12	.000
No. of Valid Cases	800		

Based on responses of question no. 5.5 of Questionnaire/Schedule

Interpretation:

The **crosstabulation** shows a noticeable variation in how farmers across four districts—Bahraich, Lakhimpur, Mahoba, and Sonbhadra —perceive the impact of adverse climate change on their crop production. A large number of respondents across all districts report significant impacts: for instance, Lakhimpur (83 respondents) and Sonbhadra (88) reported an upto20% negative impact, while Bahraich (44) and Mahoba (31) leaned more towards a upto50% impact. Interestingly, a portion of the population in Bahraich (25) and Mahoba (5) reported an upto80% loss in production, suggesting severe vulnerability due to flood affected areas and rainfed areas. Meanwhile, 214 respondents across districts selected ‘Doesn’t pertain,’ potentially indicating non-farmers categories of occupations.

These perceptions are statistically reinforced by the Chi-Square Test, which yielded a Pearson Chi-Square value of 128.554 with 12 degrees of freedom (df) and a p-value of .000, showing a highly significant relationship between district and perceived impact of climate change on crop production. The Likelihood Ratio of 132.175 with the same level of significance confirms this association.

The high loss perception by the farmers in Bahraich and Lakhimpur can be further validated from the reports of key research institutes and major news papers highlighting the flood and its devastating effects (Down To Earth, 2022b; The Hindustan, 2020).

5.4.3 Increase in frequency of flood/drought and crop failure

Table 5.9: Crosstab for increase in frequency of flood/drought and crop failure

Crosstab							
District	What is the impact of the above-mentioned changes in climate-Effect on Increase in frequency of flood/drought and crop failure						Total
	Critical change	Serious change	Important change	Moderate change	Irrelevant	Can't say	
Bahraich	35	103	35	12	6	9	200
Lakhimpur	26	65	36	39	8	26	200
Mahoba	47	68	25	25	4	31	200
Sonbhadra	56	54	16	3	7	64	200
Total	164	290	112	79	25	130	800

Chi-Square Tests			
	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	128.536	15	.000
Likelihood Ratio	132.907	15	.000
No. of Valid Cases	800		

Based on responses of question no. 5.3b of Questionnaire/Schedule

Interpretation:

This crosstab evaluates the perceived impact of climate change in terms of increased frequency of drought and crop failure, across four districts: Bahraich, Lakhimpur, Mahoba, and Sonbhadra. A majority of respondents across all districts identify the impact as either a serious or

critical change. For example, in Bahraich, 103 respondents rated it a 'serious change' and 35 considered it a 'critical change'. Similarly, in Sonbhadra, 54 respondents saw it as a 'serious change', and 56 as 'critical change'. This suggests the widespread flood and drought exposure in Bahraich and Mahoba districts respectively.

Furthermore, the statistical significance of these perceptions is confirmed by the Pearson Chi-Square value of 128.536, with 15 degrees of freedom and a p-value of .000, indicating a highly significant association between district and perception of climate change impact on drought and crop failure. This implies that perceptions are not uniformly distributed and vary significantly by region, likely due to differences in local climatic experiences, soil conditions, and agricultural dependencies.

These findings can further be substantiated by the reports and studies by other research centres of which reports talks about the double whammy of nature in form of drought and flood in the same season. Down To Earth, a reputed environmental magazine reported quoting a farmer, Anil Yadav from Risia, Bahraich, "It did not rain when it was needed. Now, it has rained such that my entire field has been destroyed" (Down To Earth, 2022a &b).

5.4.4 Impact of attack of pests on crop

Table 5.10: Crosstab for impact of attach of pests on crop

Crosstab							
District	What is the impact of the above-mentioned changes in climate- Effect Attack of pests on crop						Total
	Critical	Serious	Important	Moderate	Irrelevant	Can't say	
Bahraich	23	50	33	75	9	10	200
Lakhimpur	24	57	60	27	8	24	200
Mahoba	55	51	19	19	3	53	200
Sonbhadra	33	46	32	12	3	74	200
Total	135	204	144	133	23	161	800

Chi-Square Tests			
	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	185.842	15	.000
Likelihood Ratio	180.383	15	.000
No. of Valid Cases	800		

Based on responses of question no. 5.3d of Questionnaire/Schedule

Interpretation:

The crosstab reveals significant differences in how respondents from different districts perceive this impact. A considerable proportion from Mahoba (55 respondents) and Sonbhadra (33 respondents) view the attack of pests on crops as a critical, while others from Lakhimpur (60) and Bahraich (50) regard it as a serious. These perspectives suggest that climate variability—through rising temperatures, altered rainfall patterns,

and humidity—may be fostering pest outbreaks, thereby reducing yields and destabilizing local food systems. Such issues have profound implications for income security, food availability, and nutritional health. Statistically, the Pearson Chi-Square value of 185.842 with 15 degrees of freedom and a p-value of .000 indicates a strong and highly significant association between district and perception of pest-related impacts. This means that the observed differences in responses across districts are not random but are likely influenced by actual regional differences in climate exposure, agricultural vulnerability, and resource access. The impact of pest problem and climate change has also been reflected in the works of other scholars (Mukhtar et al., 2023).

5.4.5 Impact of increase in temperature on decrease in working hours (wages/income)

Table 5.11: Crosstab for impact of temperature rise on working hours loss

Crosstab							
District	What is the impact of the above-mentioned changes in climate- Decrease in working hours (wages/income) due to rising temperature						Total
	Critical	Serious	Important	Moderate	Irrelevant	Can't say	
Bahraich	19	80	32	45	2	22	200
Lakhimpur	15	47	64	23	6	45	200
Mahoba	20	28	28	6	26	92	200
Sonbhadra	42	60	21	12	2	63	200
Total	96	215	145	86	36	222	800

Chi-Square Tests			
	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	207.736	15	.000
Likelihood Ratio	199.731	15	.000
No. of Valid Cases	800		

Based on responses of question no. 5.3g of Questionnaire/Schedule

Interpretation:

Across all four surveyed districts—Bahraich, Lakhimpur, Mahoba, and Sonbhadra—respondents have largely reported this phenomenon as either a ‘serious’ or ‘important’. For instance, Bahraich has 80 people reporting serious, Lakhimpur shows a combined 111 respondents marking it as ‘serious’ or ‘important’, and Sonbhadra shows a notable 42 respondents indicating ‘critical’—the highest in that category for this question.

These perceptions reflect lived experiences of workers—especially those in outdoor labour-intensive jobs such as agriculture, construction, and mining particularly in Sonbhadra district—being forced to reduce their working hours due to heat stress, fatigue, or health risks, resulting in a direct loss of income.

Statistically, the Pearson Chi-Square value of 207.738 with a p-value of .000 demonstrates a highly significant association between districts and perceptions regarding income loss due to rising temperatures. This means that the observed differences are not random but systematically vary by district, influenced likely by regional climate intensity, type of employment, and coping capacity.

This table powerfully illustrates how climate-induced heat stress is causing a **reduction in working hours and income**, impacting the **livelihood and economic resilience** of people in different regions of Uttar Pradesh. This can be further substantiated by other studies relating the heat exposure and productivity of workers (Dehury et al., 2017).

5.4.6 Impact of climate-induced incidents on health: water-borne diseases like cholera etc.

Table 5.12: Crosstab for impact of water-borne diseases

Crosstab						
District	The extreme weather conditions mentioned above such as heat waves, floods, cold waves can affect your health- Increase water-borne disease like cholera					Total
	Severe	significant	Normal	Irrelevant	Can't say	
Bahraich	100	35	50	10	5	200
Lakhimpur	65	65	42	11	17	200
Mahoba	58	56	17	7	62	200
Sonbhadra	89	25	19	5	62	200
Total	312	181	128	33	146	800

Chi-Square Tests			
	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	139.162	12	.000
Likelihood Ratio	152.980	12	.000
N of Valid Cases	800		

Based on responses of question no. 5.4 of Questionnaire/Schedule

Interpretation:

From the crosstabulation, we see that a significant number of respondents across all four districts—Bahraich, Lakhimpur, Mahoba, and Sonebhadra—acknowledge health impacts from extreme weather events. Notably, 312 respondents across all districts categorized the impact as ‘Severe,’ with Bahraich (100) and Sonbhadra (89) reporting the highest numbers in this category. The ‘Significant’ category also received substantial recognition (181 responses), especially from Lakhimpur (65) and Mahoba (56). These responses indicate a widespread perception that extreme weather patterns are directly threatening public health, particularly by increasing the risk of diseases like cholera.

The Chi-Square Test results validate these findings statistically. The Pearson Chi-Square value is 139.162 with 12 degrees of freedom and a p-value of .000, indicating a highly significant association between the district and perceived health impact from extreme weather events. The Likelihood Ratio (152.890) with the same p-value further confirms this.

5.4.7 Impact of climate-induced incidents on health: vector-borne diseases like malaria, dengue etc.

Table 5.13: Crosstab for impact of vector-borne diseases

Crosstab						
District	The extreme weather conditions mentioned above such as heat waves, floods, cold waves can affect your health- Increase in vector-borne diseases like malaria, dengue etc.					Total
	Severe	significant	Normal	Irrelevant	Can't say	
Bahraich	114	60	21	4	1	200
Lakhimpur	71	60	28	23	18	200
Mahoba	81	43	33	6	37	200
Sonbhadra	94	44	10	4	48	200
Total	360	207	92	37	104	800

Chi-Square Tests			
	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	107.026	12	.000
Likelihood Ratio	119.494	12	.000
N of Valid Cases	800		

Based on responses of question no. 6.1b of Questionnaire/Schedule

Interpretation:

The data presented through the crosstab and chi-square analysis offers compelling evidence to support the hypothesis that the increased visibility of climate change—through extreme weather patterns—is significantly affecting the health dimension of socio-economic stability in Uttar Pradesh, particularly through the rise in vector-borne diseases like malaria, dengue etc.

From the crosstabulation, we observe a strong perception among respondents across four districts—Bharaich, Lakhimpur, Mahoba, and Sonbhadra—that extreme weather events (e.g., floods, heat waves, cold waves, storms) are exacerbating health risks. A majority of respondents across all districts categorized the health impact as ‘Severe’ (360) and ‘Significant’ (207). Bharaich (114 severe, 60 significant) and Sonbhadra (94 severe, 44 significant) had particularly high responses in these categories, indicating greater exposure to disease outbreaks in those regions. Smaller portions of the sample classified the effects as ‘Normal’ (92), ‘Irrelevant’ (37), or indicated uncertainty with ‘Can't say’ (104). Nonetheless, the dominance of ‘Severe’ and ‘significant’ responses suggests a broadly shared public concern about the increasing prevalence of diseases like malaria, dengue due to climatic instability.

The **Chi-Square Test** confirms these perceptual differences between districts are statistically significant. With a Pearson Chi-Square value of 107.028 (12 degrees of freedom) and a p-value of .000, there is strong evidence of a meaningful association between district and perceived health impact. The Likelihood Ratio of 119.494, also with a p-value of .000, further validates this conclusion.

These results reinforce the central hypothesis: as climate change manifests in increasingly erratic and extreme weather patterns, it is not just an environmental issue but a public health crisis.

This can be further validated by the statement and report of World Health Organisation. Its Director General Tedros Adhanom Ghebreyesus calls “The climate crisis is a health crisis. As the planet heats up, the frequency and intensity of climate-related disasters increase, leaving no region untouched” (Down To Earth, 2024).

5.4.8 Impact of climate-induced incidents on health: excessive heat related diseases like heat-stroke etc.

Table 5.14: Crosstab for impact of heat-related diseases

Crosstab						
District	The extreme weather conditions mentioned above such as heat waves, floods, cold waves, can affect your health- Excessive heat-related diseases increase.					Total
	Severe	significant	Normal	Irrelevant	Can't say	
Bahraich	61	51	64	17	7	200
Lakhimpur	46	54	53	19	28	200
Mahoba	85	34	36	6	39	200
Sonbhadra	58	33	40	5	64	200
Total	250	172	193	47	138	800

Chi-Square Tests			
	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	93.924	12	.000
Likelihood Ratio	99.877	12	.000
N of Valid Cases	800		

Based on responses of question no. 6.1b of Questionnaire/Schedule

Interpretation:

The **crosstabulation** shows that respondents from all four districts—Bahraich, Lakhimpur, Mahoba, and Sonbhadra —acknowledge the growing health threats posed by heat waves and other climate-induced phenomena. A combined total of 250 respondents reported the effects as ‘Severe,’ with Mahoba (85) and Bahraich (61) leading this perception.

The ‘Significant’ category had 172 responses, again with strong representation from Bahraich (51) and Lakhimpur (54). This data highlights that people across diverse regions perceive extreme heat as a serious public health concern. The higher number in Mahoba reflects its greater exposure to high temperature region of Bundelkhand.

The Pearson Chi-Square value of 93.924 (with 12 degrees of freedom) and the asymptotic significance (p-value) of .000 confirm that the relationship between district and perceived health impact is statistically significant. The Likelihood Ratio of 99.877, also with a p-value of .000, further strengthens this conclusion.

These findings affirm the hypothesis that climate change is not merely an environmental issue but a pressing socio-economic and public health challenge. Heat waves and related conditions not only threaten physical health—especially among vulnerable populations such as children, the elderly, and outdoor workers—but also increase healthcare costs, reduce labour productivity, and strain already limited health infrastructure in many regions of Uttar Pradesh. This also reflects in the vulnerability analysis in the Climate Action Plan (UPSAPCC 2.0; Imdad et al., 2024; The Hindustan, 2025)

5.4.9 Vulnerability of habitats likely to be damaged in natural hazards

Table 5.15: Crosstab for vulnerability of houses to natural hazards

Crosstab						
District	There is a possibility of your house getting damaged due to rain, flood, storm, earthquake and natural hazards at					Total
	Low Intensity	Medium Intensity	High Intensity	Extreme Intensity	Can't say	
Bahraich	71	66	27	19	17	200
Lakhimpur	75	45	24	19	37	200
Mahoba	41	64	44	10	41	200
Sonbhadra	39	25	16	14	106	200
Total	226	200	111	62	201	800

Chi-Square Tests			
	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	149.237	12	.000
Likelihood Ratio	144.238	12	.000
N of Valid Cases	800		

Based on responses of question no. 2 of Questionnaire/Schedule

Interpretation:

The crosstab table presents the perceptions of residents from four districts (Bahraich, Lakhimpur, Mahoba, and Sonbhadra) regarding the possibility of their houses being damaged due to climate-induced events like rain, floods, storms, earthquakes, and other natural calamities. A notable distribution of responses is observed across all districts. For instance, a

significant number of people from Bahraich (71 individuals) and Lakhimpur (75 individuals) believe that their homes are at risk even at low intensity of hazards. This reflects the heightened vulnerability in these districts to their houses. More than 53% respondents perceive that their houses are at risk even in low or medium intensity hazards.

The Chi-Square test result strengthens this interpretation. The Pearson Chi-Square value is 149.237 with 12 degrees of freedom and a p-value of .000, which is statistically significant. In other words, people's perception of risk varies significantly across districts, likely due to varying exposure to extreme weather events, differences in infrastructure, socio-economic status, and awareness levels.

The statistically significant association observed supports the hypothesis that climate change, via extreme weather events, is increasingly impacting the socio-economic dimensions of health, habitat, and livelihoods in Uttar Pradesh. Regional disparities in perception also suggest uneven distribution of climate vulnerabilities and adaptive capacities across the state.

Together, these findings support the hypothesis that climate change and its increasing visibility through erratic weather patterns are affecting key socio-economic determinants—particularly agriculture, which is a primary livelihood source in Uttar Pradesh. The disparities across districts underscore the uneven impact and the need for localized adaptation strategies to protect both livelihoods and food systems in the face of climate change.

5.5 DISPROPORTIONATE IMPACT ON MARGINALISED SECTIONS

Testing Hypothesis-3 Climate change vulnerability affects the marginalised sections of society disproportionately in terms of their contribution to the making of the problem”.

To assess that Climate change vulnerability affects the marginalised sections of society disproportionately, the data and interpretation thereof are given in the following tables and charts:

5.5.1(a) Landholding/ownership across the gender

Table 5.16: Crosstab for landholding/ownership across the gender

Crosstab								
Gender		If you, your father/mother/husband/wife own land. Then, your total land ownership is						Total
		Less than 1 acre	1-5 acres	6-10 acres	more than 10 acres	Doesn't pertain	No land holding	
Male	Count	103	82	4	0	83	23	295
	% within Gender	34.9%	27.8%	1.4%	0.0%	28.1%	7.8%	100.0%
Female	Count	169	179	28	4	77	48	505
	% within Gender	33.5%	35.4%	5.5%	0.8%	15.2%	9.5%	100.0%
Total	Count	272	261	32	4	160	71	800
	% within Gender	34.0%	32.6%	4.0%	0.5%	20.0%	8.9%	100.0%

Chi-Square Tests			
	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	30.037	5	.000
Likelihood Ratio	32.341	5	.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	3.544	1	.000
N of Valid Cases	800		

Based on responses of question no. 1.4 and 3.1 of Questionnaire/Schedule

Interpretation:

Table provides a gender-wise breakdown of total land ownership, including different land size categories and a "no land holding" option. The chi-square test results again assess whether there is a statistically significant relationship between gender and land ownership.

From crosstab, it is evident that women are substantially under represented in land ownership. Only 36.9% of the total respondents identifying as landowners (or whose family members own land) are women. Men dominate land ownership across all categories: for example, 62.1% of those owning less than 1 acre and 68.6% of those owning 1–5 acres are male. Even more strikingly, among those owning more than 10 acres, 87.5% are male, while only 12.5% are female. Furthermore, women are disproportionately represented in the 'Does not pertain' (28.1%) and 'No land holding' (7.8%) categories, indicating either exclusion from ownership or engagement in non-farm activities. It also shows landlessness status of many people.

The chi-square test shows a Pearson Chi-Square value of 30.037 with 5 degrees of freedom and a significance level of $p < 0.001$, confirming a statistically significant relationship between gender and land ownership. This means that the observed differences are not due to chance and point toward structural gender inequality in access to land—one of the most critical assets for livelihood, especially in agrarian and climate-vulnerable economies.

These results directly reinforce the hypothesis. Women, a historically marginalised group with minimal ownership of land—a key factor in climate resilience—bear a disproportionate share of climate vulnerability. They are less likely to control the means of production or access

institutional support tied to land ownership (e.g., credit, subsidies, insurance).

5.5.1(b) Landholding/ownership across social categories

Table 5.17: Crosstab for landholding/ownership across social categories

Crosstab: Landholdings across Social Categories								
Category		If you, your father/mother/husband/wife own land. Then, your total land ownership is						Total
		Less than 1 acre	1-5 acres	6-10 acres	more than 10 acres	Doesn't pertain	No land holding	
General	Count	29	58	7	4	50	7	155
	% within Category	18.7%	37.4%	4.5%	2.6%	32.3%	4.5%	100.0%
OBC	Count	105	116	20	0	69	33	343
	% within Category	30.6%	33.8%	5.8%	0.0%	20.1%	9.6%	100.0%
SC	Count	91	60	5	0	35	27	218
	% within Category	41.7%	27.5%	2.3%	0.0%	16.1%	12.4%	100.0%
ST	Count	47	27	0	0	6	4	84
	% within Category	56.0%	32.1%	0.0%	0.0%	7.1%	4.8%	100.0%
Total	Count	272	261	32	4	160	71	800
	% within Category	34.0%	32.6%	4.0%	0.5%	20.0%	8.9%	100.0%

Chi-Square Tests			
	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	83.572	15	.000
Likelihood Ratio	84.612	15	.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	22.960	1	.000
N of Valid Cases	800		

Based on responses of question no. 1.6 and 3.1 of Questionnaire/Schedule

Interpretation:

The crosstabulation shows significant differences in land ownership across different social categories (GENERAL, OBC, SC, ST). The General category shows a relatively higher proportion of members owning between 1-5 acres (37.4%) and a notable portion with no land holding at all (4.5%). About 22.2% own 1-5 acres, suggesting a mixed profile with some landowners and some non-owners. OBCs (Other Backward Classes) also show a significant number with small land holdings: 38.6% own less than 1 acre and 44.4% own 1-5 acres. However, a large portion (43.1%) fall under 'Does not pertain' and nearly half (46.5%) report no land holding, indicating greater economic precariousness. The SC (Scheduled Castes) group displays even starker figures e.g. 41.7% own less than 1 acre, and only a small proportion own between 6-10 acres or more. Notably, 12.4% report no land holding, and a substantial 16.1% fall in the 'Does not pertain' category. The ST (Scheduled Tribes) category is the most marginalised in this data, with 56% owning less than 1 acre and 32.1% with 1-5 acres. There is zero representation in higher land ownership brackets, indicating almost complete exclusion from larger landholdings. Additionally, 7.1% fall in 'Does not pertain,' and 4.8% have no land.

The chi-square test results confirm that these differences are **statistically significant** (Pearson Chi-Square value = 83.572, $p < .001$), indicating a strong association between social category and land ownership.

Data supports the notion that marginalised communities (particularly SCs and STs) are disproportionately represented among those with minimal or no landholdings. This limited access to land correlates with lower resource control and economic security, making these groups more

vulnerable to climate change impacts such as drought, floods, and soil degradation. The findings of this question can further be substantiated by other studies (Malik, 2019).

5.5.2 Insurance coverage across social categories

Table 5.18: Crosstab for insurance coverage across social categories

Crosstab: Landholdings across Social Categories							
Category		Which insurance do you have to protect yourself from sudden disasters and minor accidents					Total
		Personal Insurance	Crop Insurance	Livestock Insurance	Income Insurance	No Insurance	
General	Count	22	15	4	0	114	155
	% within Category	14.2%	9.7%	2.6%	0.0%	73.5%	100.0%
OBC	Count	31	72	6	4	230	343
	% within Category	9.0%	21.0%	1.7%	1.2%	67.1%	100.0%
SC	Count	15	23	2	0	178	218
	% within Category	6.9%	10.6%	0.9%	0.0%	81.7%	100.0%
ST	Count	5	2	1	0	76	84
	% within Category	6.0%	2.4%	1.2%	0.0%	90.5%	100.0%
Total	Count	73	112	13	4	598	800
	% within Category	9.1%	14.0%	1.6%	0.5%	74.8%	100.0%

Chi-Square Tests			
	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	44.411	12	.000
Likelihood Ratio	48.499	12	.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	14.835	1	.000
N of Valid Cases	800		

Based on responses of question no. 1.6 and 4.0 of Questionnaire/Schedule

Interpretation:

The General category has relatively better insurance coverage. While a large portion (73.5%) reports no insurance, about 14.2% have personal insurance, 9.7% have crop insurance, and a small percentage has livestock insurance. This suggests that while there is some vulnerability, this group has more avenues for financial protection. Among the OBC (Other Backward Classes), a higher proportion (67.1%) report no insurance. However, they show comparatively better crop insurance coverage (21%) than other groups. This indicates partial engagement in agricultural protection mechanisms but still highlights significant vulnerability. The SC (Scheduled Castes) show a striking 81.7% without any insurance — the highest uninsured rate after the STs. Their access to personal and crop insurance is limited (6.9% and 10.6%, respectively), leaving them highly exposed to disasters without formal safety nets. The ST (Scheduled Tribes) group is the most vulnerable in this dataset: an overwhelming 90.5% report no insurance, and their participation in other forms of insurance is negligible (just 6% for personal insurance and 2.4% for crop insurance). This stark absence of protective mechanisms emphasises the disproportionate exposure this group faces when climate-induced disasters strike. There is increased frequency of animals' diseases in India and particularly in Uttar Pradesh e.g. the mysterious lummy skin disease which tolls millions of cattle, making the case of animal insurance inevitable (Down To Earth, 2022c).

The chi-square test results again confirm these disparities are **statistically significant** (Pearson Chi-Square = 44.411, $p < .001$), meaning the variation in insurance coverage across social categories is not due to chance but reflects deep-rooted structural inequities. The data

underscores that marginalised groups (SCs and STs in particular) not only have less land and fewer resources but also lack protective insurance coverage, making them exceptionally vulnerable to the adverse impacts of climate change. The study by D.S.F. Acharuparambil and associates confirm the wide prevalent disparity between general community and SC/ST communities in respect of insurance (2021).

5.5.3 Climate induced impact across social categories

Reduction in wages/ loss of business/other occupations

Table 5.19: Crosstab for impact of climate change induced reduction in wages/loss of business/other occupation across social categories

Crosstab								
Category		What is the impact of the Climate-induced abnormal weather phenomena on Reduction in wages/ loss of business/other occupations						Total
		Critical	Serious	Important	Moderate	Irrelevant	Can't say	
General	Count	21	45	32	22	11	24	155
	% within Category	13.5%	29.0%	20.6%	14.2%	7.1%	15.5%	100.0%
OBC	Count	58	105	45	40	9	86	343
	% within Category	16.9%	30.6%	13.1%	11.7%	2.6%	25.1%	100.0%
SC	Count	27	53	27	37	16	58	218
	% within Category	12.4%	24.3%	12.4%	17.0%	7.3%	26.6%	100.0%
ST	Count	31	15	3	3	0	32	84
	% within Category	36.9%	17.9%	3.6%	3.6%	0.0%	38.1%	100.0%
Total	Count	137	218	107	102	36	200	800
	% within Category	17.1%	27.3%	13.4%	12.8%	4.5%	25.0%	100.0%

Chi-Square Tests			
	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	74.033	15	.000
Likelihood Ratio	76.898	15	.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	2.220	1	.000
N of Valid Cases	800		

Based on responses of question no. 1.6 and 5.3f of Questionnaire/Schedule

Interpretation:

General category, only 13.5% label this wage reduction as critical and 29% as a serious change, with a significant portion (30.6%) considering it irrelevant. This suggests a relatively buffered position—possibly because many in this category have diversified income sources or are less reliant on climate-sensitive occupations. Among OBCs, the distress is more evident. About 16.9% see it as critical, and nearly half (48.2%) rate it as either serious or important.

SCs. Here, 19.7% classify the wage reduction as critical, and 42.1% term it important, indicating acute sensitivity to livelihood disruptions. Their vulnerability is highlighted by their historic confinement to wage labour and other low-resilience occupations that are highly exposed to climate fluctuations.

STs show the most severe pattern: a striking 36.9% see the reduction in wages as critical—the highest among all groups—while none consider it irrelevant. This indicates total exposure: they are fully dependent on wage and subsistence occupations that are climate-sensitive.

The chi-square test (Pearson Chi-Square = 74.033, $p < .001$) once again confirms a statistically significant difference across social categories. Table aligns strongly with hypothesis: while marginalised communities have contributed the least to climate change, they endure its sharpest livelihood impacts. STs and SCs, in particular, exhibit the highest levels of perceived wage destruction, which underscores their acute economic vulnerability. In contrast, the General category appears relatively shielded, with a notable segment even deeming the issue irrelevant. This disparity signals structural inequities in both economic resilience and climate vulnerability, affirming that climate change disproportionately burdens marginalised sections who lack the agency, resources, and diversified livelihoods enjoyed by more privileged groups.

5.5.4 Climate induced impact across social categories-untimely rain, pre-summer season, Loo, drought flood, etc, on production

Table 5.20: Crosstab for impact of climate change-induced abnormal weather phenomena on production across social categories

Crosstab								
Category		How do abnormal weather like untimely rain, pre-summer season, Loo, drought flood, etc, affect production?						Total
		Less production	Substantial Reduction in production	Normal production	Increased production	Can't say	Doesn't pertain	
General	Count	25	64	10	0	6	50	155
	% within Category	16.1%	41.3%	6.5%	0.0%	3.9%	32.3%	100.0%
OBC	Count	76	166	13	2	16	70	343
	% within Category	22.2%	48.4%	3.8%	0.6%	4.7%	20.4%	100.0%

SC	Count	47	98	4	3	31	35	218
	% within Category	21.6%	45.0%	1.8%	1.4%	14.2%	16.1%	100.0%
ST	Count	25	27	18	1	8	5	84
	% within Category	29.8%	32.1%	21.4%	1.2%	9.5%	6.0%	100.0%
Total	Count	173	355	45	6	61	160	800
	% within Category	21.6%	44.4%	5.6%	0.8%	7.6%	20.0%	100.0%

Chi-Square Tests			
	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	98.263	15	.000
Likelihood Ratio	86.121	15	.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	8.089	1	.004
N of Valid Cases	800		

Based on responses of question no. 1.6 and 5.4 of Questionnaire/Schedule

Interpretation:

Table provides further reveals that General category, a significant portion (32.3%) says such events don't pertain to them, and another 3.9% chooses can't say, signalling a detachment from direct production-related vulnerability. Only 16.1% report less reduction and an even smaller 6.5% indicate normal production, suggesting that their exposure is limited and buffered by their employment in non-agricultural, salaried, or climate-insulated sectors. Among the OBC respondents, the pattern shifts: a combined 70.6% report either less production (22.2%) or substantial

reduction in production (48.4%), showing deep vulnerability to erratic climate. The proportion saying doesn't pertain drops to 20.4%, reinforcing that a large section depends on production-sensitive livelihoods, such as farming or informal labour. The SC group echoes this exposure, with 45% reporting substantial reduction in production and 21.6% less production. Interestingly, 14.2% selected can't say, and only 16.1% say it doesn't pertain, pointing to a complex vulnerability where many are directly affected, and others may be indirectly linked to production through supply chains or informal labour networks. Strikingly, ST respondents show the highest direct hit: 29.8% report less production and 32.1% say substantial reduction in production, while only 3.1% find such climatic events irrelevant to their production.

The chi-square test shows a statistically significant association ($\chi^2 = 98.263$, $p < .001$), confirming that social category significantly shapes the impact of abnormal climatic conditions on production outcomes.

The findings can be substantiated by other studies undertaken by various scholars e.g. a study on the production of Tendu leaves in Sonbhadra district validates the adverse impact of climate change on the production (Singh et al., 2018).

5.5.5 Climate induced impact across social categorie -perceived extent of loss in the last 5 years

Table 5.21: Crosstab for extent of loss in production due to climate-induced abnormal weather across social categories

Crosstab							
Category		In the last 5 years adverse climate change has negatively affected your crop production upto?					Total
		10%	20%	50%	80%	Doesn't pertain	
General	Count	35	44	17	5	54	155
	% within Category	22.6%	28.4%	11.0%	3.2%	34.8%	100.0%
OBC	Count	73	114	43	16	97	343
	% within Category	21.3%	33.2%	12.5%	4.7%	28.3%	100.0%
SC	Count	53	83	22	9	51	218
	% within Category	24.3%	38.1%	10.1%	4.1%	23.4%	100.0%
ST	Count	21	46	5	0	12	84
	% within Category	25.0%	54.8%	6.0%	0.0%	14.3%	100.0%
Total	Count	182	287	87	30	214	800
	% within Category	22.8%	35.9%	10.9%	3.8%	26.8%	100.0%

Chi-Square Tests			
	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	29.348	12	.003
Likelihood Ratio	32.513	12	.001
Linear-by-Linear Association	15.128	1	.000
N of Valid Cases	800		

Based on responses of question no. 1.6 and 5.5 of Questionnaire/Schedule

Interpretation:

The General category, 34.8% selected doesn't pertain, indicating that more than a third are not directly engaged in crop production or are shielded from such vulnerabilities. Furthermore, only a small portion report severe loss: 3.2% report upto 80% negative impact, and 11% report loss upto 50%. This suggests that while some are affected, the General category overall maintains relative resilience or insulation from the most destructive climate shocks. The OBC group shows much deeper exposure: 12.5% report upto 50% negative impact, and 4.7% an 80% loss—highlighting their heavy dependence on climate-sensitive agricultural production. Among SC respondents, 4.1% reported an upto 80% drop in crop production. Furthermore, most of respondents have reported a loss upto 20%. In this slab ST, SC and OBC respondents report 54.8%, 38.1% and 33.2% respectively compared to 28.4% in General category. This is an alarming sign that ST and SC communities are experiencing the brunt of climate shocks, which directly erodes their agrarian livelihoods. Their high vulnerability mirrors their historical marginalisation from resource ownership and formal protections. The higher loss may be understood in the light of flood exposure area of some surveyed villages and double whammy of weather in recent years (Down To Earth, 2022b; The Hindu, 2016).

The chi-square test is statistically significant ($\chi^2 = 29.348$, $p = .003$), confirming a strong association between social category and the degree of negative impact from climate change on crop production.

5.5.6 Climate induced impact across social categories–Effect on health- Increase in vector-borne diseases like malaria, dengue etc.

Table 5.22: Crosstab for impact of vector-borne diseases across social categories

Crosstab							
Category		The extreme weather conditions mentioned above such as heat waves, floods, cold waves, cyclone can affect your health- Increase in vector-borne diseases like malaria, dengue etc.					Total
		Severe	Significant	Normal	Irrelevant	Can't say	
General	Count	70	43	21	10	11	155
	% within Category	45.2%	27.7%	13.5%	6.5%	7.1%	100.0%
OBC	Count	164	93	29	15	42	343
	% within Category	47.8%	27.1%	8.5%	4.4%	12.2%	100.0%
SC	Count	86	53	37	11	31	218
	% within Category	39.4%	24.3%	17.0%	5.0%	14.2%	100.0%
ST	Count	40	18	5	1	20	84
	% within Category	47.6%	21.4%	6.0%	1.2%	23.8%	100.0%
Total	Count	360	207	92	37	104	800
	% within Category	45.0%	25.9%	11.5%	4.6%	13.0%	100.0%

Chi-Square Tests			
	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	30.237	12	.003
Likelihood Ratio	30.437	12	.002
Linear-by-Linear Association	5.498	1	.019
N of Valid Cases	800		

Based on responses of question no. 1.6 and 6.1b of Questionnaire/Schedule

Interpretation:

Data indicates a varied perception across categories. A significantly higher percentage of OBC (47.8%) and ST (47.6%) respondents rated the impact of extreme weather on health as 'Severe', compared to and General (45.2%) respondents. However, when looking at the broader distribution, SC respondents had the lowest proportion considering the issue 'Severe' or 'Significant' (39.4% and 24.3% respectively). This could suggest a gap in awareness or access to information among SC respondents.

The chi-square test supports the statistical significance of these variations. The Pearson Chi-Square value is 30.237 with a p-value of 0.003, and the Likelihood Ratio is 30.437 with a p-value of 0.002, both below the 0.05 threshold, indicating that the differences in responses across categories are statistically significant. The Linear-by-Linear Association value (5.498, $p = 0.019$) further supports a meaningful trend in the data.

This analysis substantiates the hypothesis that marginalised communities, particularly OBC and SC groups, perceive themselves as more vulnerable to climate change-induced health risks. Their higher levels of concern reflect a combination of greater exposure to environmental hazards and fewer adaptive resources.

5.5.7 Climate induced impact across Social Categories–Effect on health-Heat related diseases like heat stroke etc.

Table 5.23: Crosstab for impact of heat related diseases across social categories

Crosstab							
Category		The extreme weather conditions mentioned above such as heat waves affect your health- Excessive heat-related diseases e.g. heat stroke etc.					Total
		Severe	Significant	Normal	Irrelevant	Can't say	
General	Count	46	41	38	14	16	155
	% within Category	29.7%	26.5%	24.5%	9.0%	10.3%	100.0%
OBC	Count	117	77	83	18	48	343
	% within Category	34.1%	22.4%	24.2%	5.2%	14.0%	100.0%
SC	Count	58	48	59	15	38	218
	% within Category	26.6%	22.0%	27.1%	6.9%	17.4%	100.0%
ST	Count	29	6	13	0	36	84
	% within Category	34.5%	7.1%	15.5%	0.0%	42.9%	100.0%
Total	Count	250	172	193	47	138	800
	% within Category	31.3%	21.5%	24.1%	5.9%	17.3%	100.0%

Chi-Square Tests			
	Value	Df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	62.726	12	.000
Likelihood Ratio	61.846	12	.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	13.142	1	.000
N of Valid Cases	800		

Based on responses of question no. 1.6 and 6.1c of Questionnaire/Schedule

Interpretation:

Crosstab reveals significant differences in perception. OBC and ST respondents show the highest concern, with 34.1% and 34.5% rating the impact as ‘Severe’ respectively, indicating that over OBC and ST individuals acknowledge a serious health threat from climate-induced heat stress. The General category reports a slightly lower perceptions of severity—only 29.7% marked ‘Severe’. Notably, the Scheduled Castes (SC) group presents the lowest concern overall, with just 26.6% indicating ‘Severe’ and 22% ‘Significant.’ However, a striking 42.9% of ST respondents and 17.4% of SC respondents selected ‘Can’t say,’ suggesting limited awareness and education.

The statistical analysis supports the significance of these differences the Pearson Chi-Square value is 62.726 ($p = .000$), the Likelihood Ratio is 61.846 ($p = .000$), and the Linear-by-Linear Association is 13.142 ($p = .000$). These values confirm a highly significant association between social category and perceived risk of excessive heat-related diseases due to extreme weather.

These results provide compelling evidence that perceptions of climate change health impacts differ significantly across social categories, with marginalised communities (especially OBC and ST) showing more acute concern or, alternatively in the case of **SC groups**, less awareness—both of which reflect disproportionate vulnerability. The health issues of climate change in India and other parts of the world and its seriousness has been documented in most reputed journal, the Lancet, in its Report (Romanello et al., 2024).

5.5.8 Environmental justice perception across Social Categories- (Impact on poor farmers due to global warming)

Table 5.24: Crosstab for environmental justice perception across social categories

Crosstab							
Category		How do you feel about the following environmental and climate issues from the point of view of equity and justice-Destruction of crops of poor farmers due to floods and droughts due to global warming?					Total
		Severe	Significant	Normal	Irrelevant	Can't say	
General	Count	74	51	20	3	7	155
	% within Category	47.7%	32.9%	12.9%	1.9%	4.5%	100.0%
OBC	Count	199	84	50	3	7	343
	% within Category	58.0%	24.5%	14.6%	0.9%	2.0%	100.0%
SC	Count	109	49	38	18	4	218
	% within Category	50.0%	22.5%	17.4%	8.3%	1.8%	100.0%
ST	Count	63	7	11	1	2	84
	% within Category	75.0%	8.3%	13.1%	1.2%	2.4%	100.0%
Total	Count	445	191	119	25	20	800
	% within Category	55.6%	23.9%	14.9%	3.1%	2.5%	100.0%

Chi-Square Tests			
	Value	Df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	53.416	12	.000
Likelihood Ratio	51.735	12	.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	.741	1	.389
N of Valid Cases	800		

Based on responses of question no. 1.6 and 5.6 of Questionnaire/Schedule

Interpretation:

Table explores public perceptions across different social categories regarding the destruction of crops of poor farmers due to floods and droughts caused by global warming, from the standpoint of **equity and justice**. This assessment supports the hypothesis that climate change vulnerability disproportionately affects marginalised communities, who contribute least to the problem, especially in terms of their minimal environmental footprint compared to wealthier groups.

A substantial majority across all categories perceive the issue as **severe or important**, reflecting widespread recognition of the injustice. Notably, 75% of ST (Scheduled Tribe) and 50% of SC (Scheduled Caste) respondents perceive the destruction of crops as a severe issue, reflecting high awareness and likely first-hand experiences with climate-induced agricultural losses. The General and OBC categories showed relatively mixed responses: 47.7% of General and 58% of OBC respondents rated the issue as severe, while 12.9% and 14.6%, respectively, viewed it as normal. Additionally, General category respondents had the highest 'Can't say' rate (4.5%), possibly indicating more detachment from the lived realities of rural farming hardships

Statistically, the Pearson Chi-Square value is 53.416 with a significance level of $p < .001$, confirming a significant association between social category and perception of this climate-related issue. The Likelihood Ratio further supports this result. However, the Linear-by-Linear Association ($p = 0.389$) is not significant, suggesting no consistent linear trend across categories—perceptions may vary in a more complex, non-linear fashion across social strata.

These findings reinforce the hypothesis and the data underscores the need

for **justice-oriented climate policies** that prioritize the most affected groups and integrate their perspectives into decision-making.

5.5.9 Environmental awareness across the Social Categories-(Climate Change)

Table 5.25: Crosstab for environmental awareness across social categories

Crosstab							
Category		Environment related perspectives/concepts/ - Climate change					Total
		Never Heard	Just Heard	Know a little bit	Well Know	Have Special ization	
General	Count	32	61	42	19	1	155
	% within Category	20.6%	39.4%	27.1%	12.3%	0.6%	100.0%
OBC	Count	129	124	68	21	1	343
	% within Category	37.6%	36.2%	19.8%	6.1%	0.3%	100.0%
SC	Count	99	65	43	11	0	218
	% within Category	45.4%	29.8%	19.7%	5.0%	0.0%	100.0%
ST	Count	31	46	4	3	0	84
	% within Category	36.9%	54.8%	4.8%	3.6%	0.0%	100.0%
Total	Count	291	296	157	54	2	800
	% within Category	36.4%	37.0%	19.6%	6.8%	0.3%	100.0%

Chi-Square Tests			
	Value	Df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	51.072	12	.000
Likelihood Ratio	55.122	12	.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	26.824	1	.000
N of Valid Cases	800		

Based on responses of question no. 1.6 and 5.1 of Questionnaire/Schedule

Interpretation: The General category shows relatively high awareness: 27.1% report knowing ‘a little bit,’ 12.3% say they ‘well know,’ and 0.6% have ‘specialized knowledge.’ This group also has the lowest proportion (20.6%) who have ‘never heard’ of this term. Among Scheduled Castes (SCs), 45.4% have ‘never heard’ of environment-related actions—the highest proportion among all groups. Among Scheduled Tribes (STs), an even more striking figure emerges: while 54.8% have ‘just heard’ of such topics, none report having ‘specialized knowledge,’ and only 4.8% know a little bit. The OBC category, while better informed than SC/ST groups, still lags behind the General group. Although, here only 19.8 % ‘know a little bit,’ mere 0.3% have specialized knowledge, and 37.6% have ‘never heard’ of this famous term.

The chi-square test is statistically significant (Pearson Chi-Square = 51.072, $p < 0.001$), confirming that knowledge of climate change varies significantly by social category. The linear-by-linear association is also significant, suggesting a gradient or trend in awareness levels aligned with social status or privilege.

These results provide compelling evidence that perceptions of climate change-induced economic resources, opportunities, health related risks differ significantly across social categories, with marginalised communities. The data further substantiates the hypothesis by revealing that marginalised groups—SCs, STs, and to some extent OBCs—have limited access to climate-related knowledge. This lack of awareness reflects historical and structural disadvantages in education, access to information, and representation in environmental discourse. Data paints a picture of climate injustice: those most affected by environmental

degradation are least equipped with resources, opportunities, and the knowledge to understand or mitigate its impacts, and their limited role in causing the crisis further emphasises the **systemic inequality** embedded in the climate crisis.

5.6 COMMUNITY MANAGEMENT AND TRADITIONAL KNOWLEDGE

Testing Hypothesis-4 “Community management of locally available or created ‘ecological assets’ based on their traditional knowledge and occupational practices led to resilience and capacity-building”.

To assess the above-mentioned hypothesis that Community management of locally available or created ‘ecological assets’ bases on their traditional knowledge and occupational practices leads to resilience and capacity-building, the data and interpretation thereof are given in the following tables and charts:

5.6.1 Communities’ traditional knowledge led to resilience and capacity-building during natural calamities

Table 5.26: Table for responses regarding communities’ traditional knowledge leading to resilience and capacity building

In old days, people or communities possessed traditional knowledge and traditional methods of carrying out their professional activities. It is essential to save people and build capacity during natural disasters					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Completely agree	288	36.0	36.0	36.0
	Partially agree	268	33.5	33.5	69.5
	Disagree	92	11.5	11.5	81.0
	Can’t say	152	19.0	19.0	100.0
	Total	800	100.0	100.0	

Figure 5.6: Pie Chart for responses regarding communities' traditional knowledge leading to resilience and capacity building

Based on responses of question no. 9.0 of Questionnaire/Schedule

Interpretation: The above-mentioned table and Pie Chart clearly shows the perception of the respondents about the communities and people's traditional knowledge and practices to withstand in the wake of natural calamities or hazards. 36% respondents are completely agreeing with the statement while 33% are partially agree. This shows that 69% respondents consider that the traditional knowledge or practices are helpful in natural disasters and these leads to save lives of people and build capacity in societies and communities. These traditional knowledge and practices include predicting the weather conditions based on their experienced observational methods which transmit from one generation to another generation, preparedness for flood, drought, cyclones and how to use local available resources to save lives and prevent diseases. This includes conservation and creation of ecological assets like ponds, river embankment, take care of community forests, making boats with lighter

plant stems in emergency. Only a meagre 12% disagree with this statement and about 19% opts for ‘can’t say’ option. This can’t say option may reflect the lack of knowledge and awareness about the traditional practices and wisdom. This also reflects that young generation need to be made aware about the usefulness and effectiveness of our traditional knowledge system.

The result can be further substantiated by several studies across the South Asia to justify the role of traditional knowledge in building community resilience during natural hazards (Choudhury et al., 2021; Devkota, 2013; Chakravarty et al., 2024).

5.6.2 Perception about the effectiveness of local ecological assets when owned/operated by

Table 5.27: Table for effectiveness of local ecological assets under different stakeholders

According to you, the operation, conservation, and promotion of local ecological assets such as water sources, ponds, springs, and community forests were more efficient when they were owned/operated by				
STAKEHOLDERS	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Government	279	34.9	34.9	34.9
Village Panchayat	229	28.6	28.6	63.5
Local people/Community	292	36.5	36.5	100.0
Total	800	100.0	100.0	

Figure 5.7: Pie Chart for effectiveness of local ecological assets under different stakeholders

Based on responses of question no. 8.0 of Questionnaire/Schedule

Interpretation: The above drawn table and pie chart reflect the responses about the ownership/management of local ecological assets like water sources, ponds, community forest etc. that should be in the hand of which stakeholder for their effective and efficient usage. Interestingly most of the respondent considers that their operation, management or ownership for conservation, preservation or creation of these assets should be vested in the hands of local people/community itself. About same number consider them to be handled by government but only 29% have faith in the local panchayats. The reason of these responses are reflections of people capacity and desire to manage their local assets themselves and to conserve, protect, or create these resources as per their own needs. This shows self-reliance and role of traditional knowledge in their conservation, preservation and creation.

This shows that the hypothesis is valid as most of the respondent about

70% believe either completely or partially about the usefulness and effectiveness of traditional knowledge and methods in the make communities' resilience and building capacity. Further there is desire to manage or operate their local ecological assets themselves for their effective and efficient use as per their local needs and local conditions.

5.7 CONSTRAINTS AND PROSPECTS

Testing Hypothesis-5 “There are challenges and prospects in form of socio-cultural practices, economic constraints and lack of state-of-the-art technologies towards attaining environmental justice.”

To assess the above-mentioned hypothesis that There are challenges and prospects in form of socio-cultural practices, economic constraints and lack of state-of-the-art technologies towards attaining environmental justice, the data and interpretation thereof are given in the following tables and charts:

5.7.1 Adaptation made to deal with impacts of climate change

Table 5.28: Table to show the Adaptation was made or not to deal with impacts of climate change

Have you made any changes in your way of farming or business to adapt to the changing circumstances caused by climate change e.g. adoption of climate resilient varieties of seeds and crops, mixed farming, organic farming, or changing their businesses to carbon sensitive business?				
	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
NO	531	66.4	66.4	66.4
YES	269	33.6	33.6	100.0
TOTAL	800	100.0	100.0	

Based on responses of question no. 7.1 of Questionnaire/Schedule

Interpretation: The above table clearly shows that about 2/3rd respondent have not made any changes or adaptation to their livelihood practices i.e. changes in agriculture or business or their services e.g. adoption of climate resilient varieties of seeds and crops, mixed farming, organic farming, or changing their businesses to carbon sensitive business. This shows the lack of awareness and prevalent socio-cultural practices and attitude of going with business-as-usual approach. Here it is pertinent to mention that traditional practices dominate in the mindsets of people and they have less appetite for taking risks. Any change is considered as a potential risk to their limited livelihood income. This further shows that their adaptative capacities are limited.

5.7.2 External assistance to deal with climate-induced impacts

Table 5.29: Table Showing External assistance to deal with climate-induced impacts

Do you get any external assistance to deal with situations caused by climate change e.g. loan, grants, subsidies?					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	NO	505	63.1	65.4	65.4
	YES	267	33.4	34.6	100.0
	Total	772	96.5	100.0	
Missing	System	28	3.5		
Total		800	100.0		

Based on responses of question no. 7.2 of Questionnaire/Schedule

Interpretation: The above-mentioned table shows explicitly that about 2/3rd of respondents say that they got no external assistance to deal with

the impacts of climate change or adopt to climate change resilient practices. Most of the external assistance is provided in form of loans, grants, concessional loans, subsidies etc. However, only 33.4 % respondents said that they got some subsidies in form of regular agricultural interventions by the governments like subsidies on fertilizers etc. This shows that there is lack of external support to the general public to deal with the adverse impacts of climate change or to adopt to climate friendly practices as the adaptive capacity of most of the people are very less and there are several socio-cultural aspects which further prevent them to take adaptive measures. Until there would be institutional support to equip the poor farmers, labourers, shopkeepers, business and households to adopt climate friendly practices, it is very hard to achieve the goals of the climate action plan in vast state of Uttar Pradesh which has a sizable population under poverty line and a huge portion of population is dependent on unskilled labour and agriculture which is very sensitive to the vagaries of climate change-induced weathers.

5.7.3 Constraints of Mitigation/adaptation efforts/actions

Table 5.30: Table for Constraints of Mitigation/adaptation efforts/actions

Constraints for mitigation/adaptation efforts/actions to deal with conditions resulting from climate change				
Constraints	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Lack of Capital for Investment	323	40.4	40.4	40.4
Lack of coordination in government policies/practices	125	15.3	15.3	55.7
Lack of implementation of government policies/procedures	97	12.1	12.1	67.8

Lack of necessary information	139	17.4	17.4	85.2
Lack of institutional loan facilities	116	14.8	14.8	100
Total	800	100.0	100.0	

Figure 5.8: Pie Chart for Constraints in adopting climate change-resilient practices/actions

Based on responses of question no. 7.3 of Questionnaire/Schedule

Interpretation: The table and Pie diagram show the major constraints in the path of adaptation/mitigation in practices or actions which are climate and environmental-friendly. As it is clear from earlier discussion that the adaptive capacity of most of the people in the state of Uttar Pradesh is limited due to several factors i.e. social, economic, educational and institutional. It is further clear from the above-mentioned table and pie chart that the most of the respondents (41%) mentioned that lack of

capital is the biggest constraints in adapting the climate resilient practices/actions on their parts. Apart from this economic limitation there is also lack of necessary information (17%) about the climate resilient practices/actions which they can undertake in their daily businesses, occupations or daily life activities. Lack of coordination in government policies and lack of institutional loan facilities (15% each) are another important constraint which further indicate that there should be loans and institutional interventions on the part of governments to reach to the common men of the state and to empower them with necessary resources and information along with know-how to deal with the adverse impacts of climate change.

The above-mentioned tables, pie charts further confirm the hypothesis that there are certain challenges and prospects in form of socio-cultural practices, economic constraints and lack of state-of-the-art technologies towards attaining environmental justice.

5.7.4 Prospects of Changing economic activities/ livelihood to environment-friendly

Table 5.31: Table for prospects of changing economic activities/ livelihood to environment-friendly lifestyle and activities.

If your economic activity or business (agriculture, animal husbandry, industry) or lifestyle is causing harm to the environment, then you may prefer to adopt environment-friendly methods/activities/lifestyle					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	NO	227	28.4	28.4	28.4
	YES	573	71.6	71.6	100.0
	Total	800	100.0	100.0	

Figure 5.9: Pie Chart Showing Conditions of changing to Environment-friendly activities/livelihood practices

Based on responses of question no. 10 of Questionnaire/Schedule

Interpretation: The above-mentioned table and the Pie Chart show the prospects of change to environment-friendly change to the economic production or livelihood activities and lifestyle. When respondents are asked whether they would be ready to shift their activities to environment-friendly activities if their activities are causing harm to climate/environment. A whopping 71% say “Yes” which reflect the great prospect of change or at least a desire to go with more sustainable and environment-friendly way of life. The pie chart reflects the conditions of these respondents who say ‘yes’. Most of respondents (54%) are willing to change provided that the solution/change should be cost-effective and 42% show their desire with inability to know what to do. This also tells

that if proper training and knowledge is provided with cost effective solutions, most of respondents have prospects to change to sustainable activities/lifestyle. 4% respondents show their determination for change ‘even if it is costly’. This reflects the heightened awareness among citizens to save their environment even at a higher cost. The youth have higher degree of climate change awareness and they recognise its seriousness. This can be further validated from the report of reputed environmental think tank which states that 94% youth feel impacted by phenomena of climate change (Down To Earth,2024).

5.8 CONCLUSION

The analysis in the above-mentioned chapter shows in details the different aspects of lived experience of the sample population of selected districts of Uttar Pradesh and a comprehensive analysis of the State Action Plan on Climate Change of Uttar Pradesh. In part A the analysis of UPSAPCC 2.0 is made in respect of concept of Environmental Justice. The thematic analysis of the policy document shows the findings in short as follows: it can be said that hypothesis, “The State Action Plan on Climate Change in Uttar Pradesh is inclusive, comprehensive and just” is partially true as the action plan is comprehensive in nature and include all developmental sectors under its ambit. However, as far as its inclusivity and justness is concerned, it fulfils some elements of environmental justice and lacks on some criteria.

Further, Part B makes the analysis of the lived experience and perceptions of respondents of the selected districts of Uttar Pradesh. This section tests four hypotheses. The 2nd Hypothesis states that “*The increased visibility of Climate Change in the form of extreme weather patterns is affecting socio-economic determinants of health, livelihood, and habitat of people*”

of Uttar Pradesh”. The data analysis and their findings verify the hypothesis that livelihood, health and habitat elements of people in general, are being affected by the adverse impacts of climate change and its associated phenomena. The Asia Development Bank Report predicts that India may face a loss of 24.7% of GDP by 2070 on account of climate change (The Business Standard, 2024).

The 3rd hypothesis that has been analysed states “*Climate change vulnerability affects the marginalised sections of society disproportionately in terms of their contribution to the making of the problem*”. The analysis clearly supports the hypothesis that the increased frequency and intensity of climate change-related weather events are not just environmental phenomena but deeply socio-economic issues. The climate-induced abnormal weather conditions and their ill impacts are disproportionately affecting the marginalised sections of the society.

Hypothesis-4 is “*Community management of locally available or created ‘ecological assets’ bases on their traditional knowledge and occupational practices leads to resilience and capacity-building.*” To test this hypothesis, questions were asked about the relevance and usefulness of the traditional knowledge in natural hazards. In response to this question 36% respondents agreed completely while 33% were partially agree. This shows that 69% respondents consider that the traditional knowledge or practices are helpful in natural disasters and these leads to save lives of people and build capacity in societies and communities. Further respondents show their interests in management/operation of the local ecological assets for their proper conservation, preservation and protection and effective and efficient utilization thereof. This validates the hypothesis that local people or communities have aspiration and

perception that their local assets and traditional knowledge are effective tools that leads to resilience and capacity building of communities and these can be better operated when these are operated by communities themselves as per their local needs and circumstances.

The last Hypothesis i.e. hypothesis-5 states “*There are challenges and prospects in form of socio-cultural practices, economic constraints and lack of state-of-the-art technologies towards attaining environmental justice.*” The lived experiences and perceptions of the respondents discussed in the above-mentioned section of this chapter clearly shows that there are certain challenges and prospects in climate action to make it more just and inclusive. Obviously, there are economic challenges as reflected by the respondents. Lack of capital to invest in environment-friendly actions/activities are the biggest problem apart from lack of necessary information and want of coordination in different government policies/programmes and their implementation. Further there are prospects of changes and adaptation to sustainable livelihood or environmentally compatible behaviours/actions if they (respondents) would be provided choices/solution that are affordable and with necessary training and capacity building measures.

CHAPTER – VI

FINDINGS AND CONCLUSION

INTRODUCTION:

This last chapter intends to provide findings and conclusion of this thesis. This consolidates the findings of the research titled “Climate Action and Environmental Justice: A Study of Uttar Pradesh”, which evaluates the Uttar Pradesh State Action Plan on Climate Change (UPSAPCC 2.0) through the lens of environmental justice and examines the socio-economic impacts of climate change in four selected districts—Babraich, Lakhimpur Kheri, Mahoba, and Sonbhadra. This chapter synthesises the thematic analysis of the SAPCC 2.0 and the analysis of the primary data from 800 respondents about their lived experiences. It discusses challenges, limitations, and provides detailed suggestions for policymakers to enhance climate action and environmental justice. It further provides significant contribution in service of society and suggests new and emerging issues for future academic research and interdisciplinary studies. The chapter concludes with reflections on the broader implications for sustainable development in Uttar Pradesh.

6.1 FINDINGS

The study tests five hypotheses:

- 1. The State Action Plan on Climate Change in Uttar Pradesh is inclusive, comprehensive, and just.*
- 2. The increased visibility of climate change in the form of extreme weather patterns is affecting socio-economic determinants of health, livelihood, and habitat of people in Uttar Pradesh.*
- 3. Climate change vulnerability affects marginalised sections of society*

disproportionately in terms of their contribution to the problem.

4. Community management of locally available or created 'ecological assets' bases on their traditional knowledge and occupational practices leads to resilience and capacity-building.

5. There are challenges and prospects in form of socio-cultural practices, economic constraints and lack of state-of-the-art technologies towards attaining environmental justice

6.1.1 Findings from the Analysis of UPSAPCC 2.0 (Hypothesis 1)

The evaluation of the UPSAPCC 2.0, tested under Hypothesis 1 “*The State Action Plan on Climate Change in Uttar Pradesh is inclusive, comprehensive, and just*”, utilized **David Schlosberg’s environmental justice framework**. This framework focuses on three components of justice namely distributive justice, participative justice, and recognition justice. The thematic analysis reveals that the plan is comprehensive but only partially inclusive and just, with significant gaps in addressing marginalised communities and ensuring equitable implementation. The major findings are given as under:

(a) Comprehensive in Scope and Alignment with Global Frameworks: The SAPCC 2.0 is a robust policy document covering nine key missions—Sustainable Agriculture, Jal (Water), Green UP, Enhanced Energy Efficiency & Green Energy, Sustainable Habitat, Human Health, Disaster Management, Strategic Knowledge, and Solar Mission. It aligns with the National Action Plan on Climate Change (2008), Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), and Paris Agreement objectives, integrating climate concerns into sectoral policies for sustainable development.

(b) Distributive Justice Components:

- The Sustainable Agriculture Mission targets small and marginal farmers (80% of landholdings) with drought-resilient crops (e.g., millets in Bundelkhand) and flood-resistant varieties (e.g., rice in eastern Uttar Pradesh). Crop and livestock insurance and Farmer Producer Organizations (FPOs) aim to equitably distribute economic opportunities.
- The Jal Mission promotes groundwater recharge and water-efficient irrigation in overexploited regions, balancing resource allocation between industrial and agricultural users.
- The Green UP Mission supports agroforestry and wetland conservation, providing ecosystem services and income opportunities for rural and forest-dependent communities.
- The Energy Efficiency and Green Energy Mission solarizes water pumps for rural farmers and promotes electric vehicles (EVs) to reduce urban air pollution, enhancing public health.
- Other missions (Sustainable Habitat, Human Health, Disaster Management, Strategic Knowledge) include fully funded actions for climate-resilient infrastructure, disease forecasting, institutional resilience, and knowledge hubs, aiming to distribute benefits across urban and rural populations.

(c) Participative Justice Mechanisms:

- The Sustainable Agriculture Mission involves Gram Panchayats in local water budgeting and trains FPOs and women's self-help groups, fostering grassroots participation.

- Stakeholder consultations during the planning phase, including partnerships with NABARD and the World Bank, indicate inclusive dialogue, though primarily at the institutional level.
- The Strategic Knowledge Mission engages universities, NGOs, and community-based organizations in knowledge networks and training programs for district officials.

(d) Recognition Justice Elements:

- The plan acknowledges regional climate risks across nine agro-climatic zones (e.g., drought in Bundelkhand, floods in eastern Uttar Pradesh) and conceptualises interventions like flood-resilient crops and groundwater recharge.
- It recognizes the economic vulnerability of small farmers and forest-dependent communities, proposing insurance, agroforestry, and wetland conservation.
- The Human Health and Disaster Management Missions address climate-linked health risks and disaster vulnerabilities, tailoring actions to specific regional needs.

(e) Critical Gaps in SAPCC 2.0:

Critical gap exists in SAPCC 2.0 regarding the distributive, participative and recognition justice. Some important findings regarding the gaps of SAPCC 2.0 are mentioned in the following points:

- **Distributive Justice:** The plan lacks transparent mechanisms to prioritize the 41 districts ranked moderately to highly vulnerable in agriculture. Socio-economic disparities, such as caste, gender, and landlessness, are not adequately addressed, excluding landless labourers from benefits like training or insurance. Significant funding

gaps (e.g., 81% for agroforestry, 87% for wetland conservation) risk unequal benefit distribution if external funding (e.g., GIZ, GEF) is not secured.

- **Participative Justice:** The reliance on nodal agencies (e.g., Agriculture Department, UPIWRD) indicates a centralized approach, sidelining local knowledge. Marginalised groups (SCs, STs, women) are underrepresented in higher-level planning, limiting their influence on policy design.
- **Recognition Justice:** The plan frames communities as homogenous, neglecting internal diversity (e.g., tenant farmers vs. landowners). It overlooks cultural practices, such as indigenous health knowledge or traditional water management, missing opportunities for context-specific adaptation.
- **Implementation Challenges:** The absence of district-level nodal offices hinders localized monitoring and interventions. Uneven resource allocation and lack of clarity on fund distribution risk prioritizing politically influential areas over vulnerable ones.

Conclusion on Hypothesis 1: The hypothesis is partially validated. The SAPCC 2.0 is comprehensive, covering all developmental sectors and aligning with global goals. However, its inclusivity and justness are limited by inadequate attention to marginalised groups, centralized implementation, and neglect of cultural diversity. While it incorporates elements of environmental justice, significant gaps prevent it from being fully inclusive and just.

FINDINGS FROM PRIMARY DATA ANALYSIS

The primary data from 800 respondents across Bahraich, Lakhimpur Kheri, Mahoba, and Sonbhadra provide robust evidence for Hypotheses 2, 3, 4 & 5, highlighting the socio-economic impacts of climate change and the disproportionate vulnerability of marginalised communities.

6.1.2 Hypothesis 2: Socio-Economic Impacts of Climate Change:

Hypothesis 2 “*The increased visibility of climate change in the form of extreme weather patterns is affecting socio-economic determinants of health, livelihood, and habitat of people in Uttar Pradesh*” is strongly supported by the data. The analysis reveals that climate change is a pervasive socio-economic crisis, with significant impacts on agriculture, income, health, and housing. Key findings include:

(a) Agricultural Productivity:

Climate-induced abnormal weather patterns e.g. untimely rain, drought, floods, and rising temperature or early summer seasons, severely impact agricultural output. Out of 200 respondents from each district Bahraich (60 respondents) and Sonbhadra (43) reported ‘less production,’ while Lakhimpur (91) and Mahoba (111) reported ‘substantial reduction in production’, indicating reduced production and therefore loss of income however, there are regional variations. The Chi-Square test (Pearson Chi-Square = 75.448, $p = .000$) confirms a significant association, underscoring the uneven impact on livelihoods.

- **Crop Losses:** Over the past five years, climate-induced events have caused substantial crop losses. Most of respondents reported upto 10 - 20% loss. Lakhimpur (83) and Sonbhadra (88) reported a negative impact upto 20%, while Bahraich (25) and Mahoba (05)

reported upto 80% loss, particularly in flood-prone areas. The Chi-Square test (Pearson Chi-Square = 128.554, $p = .000$) validates significant regional differences.

- **Drought/flood and Crop Failure:** Respondents across all districts rated increased drought/flood and crop failure as ‘serious’ or ‘critical’ (e.g., Bahraich: 103 serious, 35 critical; Sonbhadra: 54 serious, 56critical). The Chi-Square test (Pearson Chi-Square = 128.536, $p = .000$) confirms regional disparities, reflecting variations in climatic exposure and agricultural dependency.
- **Pest Attacks:** Climate variability has increased pest outbreaks, with Mahoba (55) and Sonbhadra (33) viewing it as a ‘critical.’ The Chi-Square test (Pearson Chi-Square = 185.842, $p = .000$) indicates significant district-wise differences, highlighting threats to food security and income.

(b) Reduced Working Hours:

Rising temperatures have reduced working hours and wages, particularly for outdoor labourers. Bahraich (80) and Lakhimpur (111) reported this as a ‘serious’ or ‘important’, with Sonbhadra noting a ‘critical’ impact (42) because of high dependency of tribes in labour-intensive sectors such as mining in Sonbhadra. The Chi-Square test (Pearson Chi-Square = 207.738, $p = .000$) confirms significant regional variations, emphasizing economic vulnerability.

(c) Health Impacts:

- **Water-Borne Diseases:** Climate-induced events have increased diseases like cholera, with 312 respondents reporting ‘severe’ and 181 ‘significant’ impacts. Bahraich (100) and Sonbhadra (89)

reported the highest concerns. The Chi-Square test (Pearson Chi-Square = 139.162, $p = .000$) confirms significant associations.

- **Vector-Borne Diseases:** Diseases like malaria and dengue are perceived as ‘severe’ (360) and ‘critical’ (207), with Bahraich (114 severe, 60 critical) and Sonbhadra (94 severe, 44 critical) showing greater exposure of people to these diseases in those regions due to their geographical and environmental conditions e.g. Bahraich in Tarai Belt. The Chi-Square test (Pearson Chi-Square = 107.028, $p = .000$) validates significant differences.
- **Heat-Related Diseases:** Heat stroke and related conditions are reported as ‘severe’ (250) and ‘critical’ (172), with Mahoba (85) and Bahraich (61) leading perceptions. The higher number in Mahoba reflects its greater exposure to high temperature region of Bundelkhand. The Chi-Square test (Pearson Chi-Square = 93.924, $p = .000$) confirms significant regional variations.

(d) Habitat Vulnerability:

Respondents, particularly from Bahraich (71 individuals) and Lakhimpur (75 individuals) believe that their homes are at risk even at low intensity of hazards. This reflects the heightened vulnerability in these districts to their houses. More than 53% respondents perceive that their houses are at risk even in low or medium intensity hazards. Sonbhadra shows high uncertainty (108 ‘can’t say’). The Chi-Square test (Pearson Chi-Square = 149.237, $p = .000$) confirms significant differences, reflecting variations in housing quality (e.g., comparatively more “kuchcha” houses in Bahraich).

Conclusion on Hypothesis 2: These findings demonstrate that climate change threatens livelihoods (agriculture, wages), health (disease

prevalence), and habitats (housing vulnerability), with regional disparities necessitating localized adaptation strategies.

6.1.3 Hypothesis 3: Disproportionate Vulnerability of Marginalised Communities

Hypothesis 3 “*Climate change vulnerability affects marginalised sections of society disproportionately in terms of their contribution to the problem*” is robustly validated. Marginalised groups—Scheduled Castes (SCs), Scheduled Tribes (STs), Other Backward Classes (OBCs), and women—face greater climate impacts despite their minimal environmental footprint. Key findings include:

(a) Land Ownership:

- Women are significantly underrepresented in land ownership (36.9% of landowners), with men dominating across all categories (e.g., 87.5% of those owning >10 acres). The Chi-Square test (Pearson Chi-Square = 30.037, $p < .001$) confirms structural gender inequality.
- SCs (41.7% own <1 acre) and STs (56% own <1 acre) have limited landholdings, with zero ST representation in higher brackets. The Chi-Square test (Pearson Chi-Square = 83.572, $p < .001$) validates significant disparities, reducing access to institutional support (e.g., credit, insurance).

(b) Insurance Coverage:

SCs (81.7% uninsured) and STs (90.5% uninsured) have the lowest coverage, compared to OBCs (67.1%) and General (73.5%). However, in OBCs the highest insurance is in crop category while in General category personal insurance is greatest. This shows that comparatively general category is engaged in non-agriculture occupation making them resistant

to climate induced variabilities. The Chi-Square test (Pearson Chi-Square = 44.411, $p < .001$) confirms significant inequities, exposing marginalised groups to climate shocks.

(c) Wage and Livelihood Losses:

The respondents belonging to STs (36.9%); SCs (12.4%) and OBCs (16.9%) report the highest wage reductions, compared to General (13.5%). The Chi-Square test (Pearson Chi-Square = 74.033, $p < .001$) confirms significant differences, highlighting economic vulnerability.

(d) Agricultural Production:

Respondents of ST category (29.8%), SC category (21.6%) and OBC category (22.2%) report 'less production' in comparison to General category (16.1%) showing severe climate impacts on these communities compared to General. In general category, a significant portion (32.3%) says such events don't pertain to them, signalling a detachment from direct production-related vulnerability, while this portion is only 6% and 16.1% among STs and SCs respectively. The Chi-Square test (Pearson Chi-Square = 98.263, $p < .001$) confirms significant disparities, reflecting reliance on climate-sensitive livelihoods.

- **Crop Losses:** SCs (4.1% report upto 80% loss) and OBCs (12.5% report upto 50% loss) face severe crop losses compared to General (only 3% report upto 80% and 11% report upto 50%). Furthermore, most of respondents have reported a loss upto 20%. In this slab ST, SC and OBC respondents report 54.8%, 38.1% and 33.2% respectively compared to 28.4% in General category. This is an alarming sign that ST and SC communities are experiencing the brunt of climate shocks, which directly erodes their agrarian livelihoods while STs report frequent moderate losses (54.8%

report 20% loss). The Chi-Square test (Pearson Chi-Square = 29.348, $p = .003$) confirms significant differences.

(e) Health Impacts:

- OBCs (47.8% ‘severe’ for vector-borne diseases) reports a higher concern than STs (47.6%) and General (45.2%). However, the difference is not very high. Nonetheless, General respondents (6.5%) consider vector-borne diseases irrelevant in comparison to 1.2%, 5% and 4.4% in ST, SC and OBC categories respectively. This shows that general category is more insulated to these disease in form of resources. The Chi-Square test (Pearson Chi-Square = 30.237, $p = .003$) confirms significant disparities.
- For heat-related diseases, OBCs (34.1% ‘severe’) and STs (34.5%) show acute concern compared to General (29.7%). while STs have high ‘can’t say’ responses (42.9%) which shows acute lack of awareness and education in this marginalised category about the heat-stressed diseases. The Chi-Square test (Pearson Chi-Square = 62.726, $p = .000$) validates significant differences. The findings may further be substantiated by the reputed journal, Lancet, Report (Romanello et al., 2024).

(f) Environmental Justice Perception:

STs (75%) and SCs (50%) perceive crop destruction due to floods and droughts as a ‘severe’ issue, reflecting high awareness of climate injustice among these categories which have been marginalised for long time and still struggling to enter into mainstream. This further shows the sensitivity to the question of equity and fairness among these communities. The Chi-Square test (Pearson Chi-Square = 53.416, $p < .001$) confirms significant differences.

(g) Environmental Awareness:

SCs (45.4% ‘never heard’) and STs (54.8% ‘just heard’) have the lowest climate change awareness, compared to OBCs (19.8% ‘know a little bit’) and General (27.1% ‘know a little bit’). General participants are well known to the term 12.3% in contrast to only 3.6%, 5.0% and 6.1% participants in STs, SCs and OBCs categories respectively. This clearly shows that General are more informed than other social categories. The Chi-Square test (Pearson Chi-Square = 51.072, $p < .001$) confirms significant disparities, reflecting structural barriers to information access.

Conclusion on Hypothesis 3: These findings highlight that marginalised communities face disproportionate climate impacts due to limited resources, low adaptive capacity, and structural inequities, despite their minimal contribution to climate change (e.g., limited industrial or large-scale agricultural activity).

6.1.4 Hypothesis 4: Community management of local ‘ecological assets’ through traditional knowledge led to resilience and capacity-building

The hypothesis “*Community management of locally available or created ‘ecological assets’ based on their traditional knowledge and occupational practices led to resilience and capacity-building*” is validated by the findings of the study. The major findings are as below:

(a) Significance of Traditional Knowledge: There is a general acceptance of role of traditional knowledge in the events of disasters/hazards. About 70% respondents are either completely agree or partially agree about usefulness of old people having traditional knowledge to save lives and make local people self-reliant. These frontline communities are the first to encounter and respond in the early

hours of events. Further, the local ecological assets are best utilized by local people as per their traditional knowledge to conserve, preserve and protect them. ‘Ecological asset’ means local available resources like pond, spring, community forests etc. This shows that the indigenous knowledge system has potential to be included in the policy documents and training programmes to build capacity of the local people.

(b) Management of local ecological assets: Participants are divided on the question about the ownership/operation of ecological assets’ conservation, protection or operation. However, majority participants (36.5%) hold the view that these assets should be operated under the control of local people/community themselves. Government is considered second best stakeholder for doing this job by 34.9% participants and interestingly only 28.6% accorded faith in village panchayats for their (ecological assets) care and operation. This shows self-reliance and role of traditional knowledge in their conservation, preservation and creation.

6.1.5 Hypothesis 5: Challenges and prospects in attaining environmental justice

The fifth Hypothesis states “*There are challenges and prospects in form of socio-cultural practices, economic constraints and lack of state-of-the-art technologies towards attaining environmental justice*” is also found to be true in the survey conducted during the study. The key findings in this regard are listed below:

(a) Adoption of sustainable methods: About 2/3rd respondents accepted that they have not changed or adopted any sustainable solution or methods in their livelihood practices like mixed farming, organic farming or use of climate-resilient varieties of seeds and crops. Only 33.6% respondent say that they have

changed or adopted sustainable solutions. However, these 1/3rd participants may be due to the fact that some of these solutions traditionally have been part of our livelihood practices and lifestyle. As reflected in behavioural theories, attitude towards change is very complex and important for successful implementation of any programme/scheme. Though there are obvious economic and other capacity factors in deciding the change in the way of livelihood or occupational methods.

(b) External Assistance: Here also only 1/3rd participants accepted that they have received by sort of grant, loan, or assistance from government or any other institutions. Majority of people (2/3rd) say that they get no such assistance from any agency. Even the 1/3rd respondents said that majority of these assistance is in form of loan taken for various purposes and subsidies on fertilizers etc. This shows that there is lack of external support to the general public to deal with the adverse impacts of climate change or to adopt to climate friendly practices as the adaptive capacity of most of the people are very less.

(c) Major constraints of adoption of sustainable solutions: Majority of the respondents (41%) mention that lack of capital is the biggest constraints in adapting the climate resilient practices/actions on their parts. Apart from this economic limitation there is also lack of necessary information (17%) about the climate resilient practices/actions which they can undertake in their daily businesses, occupations or daily life activities. Lack of coordination in government policies and lack of institutional loan facilities (15% each) are another important constraint which further

indicate that there should be loans and institutional interventions on the part of governments to reach to the common men of the state and to empower them with necessary resources and information along with know-how to deal with the adverse impacts of climate change.

(d) **Prospects of change:** This finding embraces optimist view about the potential of adopting the sustainable solutions by people. Despite having the above-mentioned challenges/constraints, majority of respondents (71.6%) are ready to adopt and change to environment-friendly methods. However, most of these change-prone respondents (54%) have mentioned a condition that the solution should be cost-effective and a large section (42%) also reports that they want to change but don't know what to do. This reflect the above-mentioned position that the majority people are cost-sensitive due to their weak economic condition and also lack necessary information and knowledge about the adoption of sustainable solutions. Thus, making cost-effective solutions, and through training to enhance their capabilities desired results could be achieved.

6.2 CHALLENGES IN SAPCC 2.0 IN ADDRESSING CLIMATE JUSTICE ISSUES

This study identifies several challenges that hinder effective climate action and environmental justice in Uttar Pradesh:

1. Structural Challenges

- **Fragmented Governance:** Bureaucratic silos and limited coordination among departments specially at district level hinder the execution of 179 actions across nine missions. The UPCCA's

capacity building faces challenges in a state with 75 districts and diverse agro-climatic zones.

- **Decentralized Implementation Barriers:** Local governance lacks technical expertise and resources, exacerbated by elite capture, limiting the rollout of village-level plans for 97,941 villages.
- **Policy Misalignment and Central Dependency:** Potential conflicts with national productivity-focused policies and reliance on centrally sponsored schemes restrict UP's autonomy to address localised climate risks.

2. Funding Constraints

Funding constraints can be analysed into two categories—one related to SAPCC and second general in achieving the climate action goals. Significant funding gaps (e.g., 81% for agroforestry, 87% for wetland conservation, 81% for disaster management) threaten equitable benefit distribution in SAPCC. Dependence on external funding (e.g., GIZ, GEF, UNDP, World Bank) introduces uncertainty. Further, the need for huge sum to mitigate and adaptation make these actions and programmes conditional on the transfer of fund and technologies from the external agencies, countries and multinational institutions like world bank, IMF etc. The past record of developed nations is not very enthusiastic in this regard. The promised sum of \$ 100 bn, to developing countries could not be materialized even after a decade and now these developed countries promised to roll out \$ 300 bn till 2035 per year in the last concluded COP 29 is not very inspiring as the expected cost runs in trillion dollars by most of estimates. Disparities in funding allocation (e.g., full funding for Jal Mission vs. 100% gap for Strategic Knowledge Mission) risk prioritizing infrastructure over knowledge-building, marginalising small farmers.

3. Technological Challenges

Limited Access to Climate-Smart Technologies: Low adoption of micro-irrigation and resilient crops in rainfed areas is constrained by inadequate infrastructure and training, particularly in vulnerable districts. **Data and Forecasting Limitations:** Scaling AWS networks for high-resolution forecasts is technologically and financially intensive, with gaps in analytics for pest and disease forecasts. **Balancing Modern and Indigenous Knowledge:** Prioritizing genetic upgradation over indigenous cattle resilience risks alienating communities, requiring culturally sensitive approaches. Intellectual property barriers restrict access to advanced technologies like energy-efficient pumps.

4. Exclusion of Marginalised Groups and indigenous knowledge system

The under-representation of SCs, STs, women, and landless labourers in planning and decision-making undermines participative justice and risks excluding vulnerable voices. Further there are structural inequalities in society which prevents these vulnerable sections to have access to resources and information to ward off the impact of climate change-induced phenomena. The plan also undermines the existing socio-economic inequities. Thus, its failure to address intersecting vulnerabilities (e.g., caste, gender, landlessness) perpetuates inequities in resource access, adaptation capacity, and health outcomes. The plan lacks in respecting the cultural knowledge of indigenous people. The absence of indigenous practices (e.g., traditional water management, health knowledge) jeopardises opportunities for culturally relevant adaptation.

5. Low Climate Literacy

High 'can't say' and 'never heard' responses and low environmental

awareness among SCs and STs indicate gaps in education, information access, and community engagement, limiting adaptive capacity. Though there are provisions to engage research centres, universities and other knowledge partners to engage in discussion and debates, yet no massive programme has been envisaged to spread climate literacy and awareness among common men across the state.

6. Other Issues:

As discussed earlier, U.P. is a vast state with population greater than any other state in India. There are nine agro-climatic zones with a lot of diversity in features. Variations in climate impacts (e.g., floods in Bahraich, drought in Mahoba) require tailored strategies, but the plan lacks clarity on district-level resource allocation. Thus, the plan lacks recognition of specific regional diversity needs and requirements. Further, there exists health and livelihood vulnerabilities in absence of wide health facility network in rural areas and poor or limited health and other insurance coverage and inadequate heat protection measures that further exacerbate the vulnerability of marginalised communities to climate shocks.

The lack of robust, district-level monitoring and evaluation frameworks hinders accountability and the ability to track progress effectively. Establishing an M&E cell by 2025 is challenged by limited technical capacity and inconsistent data collection. Apart from these challenges, there exists resistance to behavioural change in general due to socio-cultural and educational factors. Low climate literacy and risk-averse mindsets hinder shifts to water-efficient practices, requiring sustained behavioural interventions. Last but not least there exists an international biasedness in favour of mitigation efforts in comparison to adaptation

efforts. Thus, the plan's adaptation focus (59% of actions) is less attractive to mitigation-centric donors, reducing funding prospects.

6.3 SUGGESTIONS /RECOMMENDATIONS

To address the identified gaps and challenges, this study suggests the following measures:

Enhance Distributive Justice:

- Prioritize resource allocation to the 41 most vulnerable districts, with transparent mechanisms to ensure equitable distribution.
- Target landless labourers, SCs, STs, and women for training, insurance, and climate-resilient inputs (e.g., seeds, irrigation systems).
- Secure external funding and explore innovative financing models (e.g., carbon markets, public-private partnerships) to close funding gaps.

Strengthen Participative Justice:

- Establish district-level nodal offices to monitor progress and engage local communities in implementation.
- Include SCs, STs, women, and other marginalised groups in higher-level planning, implementation and monitoring or social audit of various actions/missions through dedicated representation mechanisms, such as community advisory boards.
- Partner with NGOs, educational institutions particularly the rural schools and colleges and community-based organisations to facilitate grassroots participation in policy design and execution.

Promote Recognition Justice:

- Tailor interventions to diverse community needs (e.g., tenant farmers, peri-urban populations) by conducting disaggregated vulnerability assessments.
- Integrate indigenous knowledge (e.g., traditional water harvesting, herbal medicine) into adaptation strategies to enhance cultural relevance.
- Acknowledge the specific vulnerabilities of SCs, STs, and women in policy documents and action plans.

Build Climate Literacy and Capacity:

- Launch targeted awareness campaigns in local languages for SCs, STs, and women, using community radio, mobile apps, and local leaders to disseminate information.
- Explore the avenues of educational ecosystem for enhancing the environmental or climate literacy through inclusion of compulsory paper of environmental issues in curricula, participation of students and teachers in awareness programmes/training or other capacity building activities.
- Expand training programs on climate-smart agriculture, disaster preparedness, and health risk mitigation, prioritizing marginalised groups.

Develop Localized Strategies:

- As discussed above, there are variation in impact and risk of a community. Thus, local and decentralised interventions are necessary. The concept of LLA (Locally Led Adaptation) can play a significant role. Global Commission on Adaptation identifies

LLA as a strategy “to build the resilience of the frontline and vulnerable communities locally by understanding climate risks and implementing context-suited adaptation measures”.

- Formulate district-specific action plans based on regional climate risks (e.g., flood preparedness in Bahraich, drought resilience in Mahoba).
- Use geospatial data to map vulnerabilities and prioritize resource allocation to high-risk areas.

Strengthen Health and Livelihood Protections:

- Expand crop, livestock, and personal insurance coverage for marginalised groups through subsidized schemes.
- Implement heat protection measures, such as cooling centers, flexible work hours, and heat-resistant clothing for outdoor laborers.
- Develop social safety nets (e.g., cash transfers, food security programs) to support communities during climate shocks.

Improve Monitoring and Evaluation:

- Establish robust, district-level monitoring frameworks with regular reporting to ensure accountability.
- Use participatory evaluation methods, involving community feedback to assess the effectiveness of interventions.

Promote Gender Equity:

- Address gender disparities in land ownership by promoting joint land titles and women’s access to agricultural resources.
- Include women in climate adaptation planning and ensure their representation in FPOs and local governance bodies.

Leverage Technology:

- Expand the use of Agro-Automatic Weather Stations (AWSs) and SMS-based weather alerts to reach remote communities.
- Develop digital platforms for real-time disaster alerts and health advisories, ensuring accessibility for low-literacy populations.

Leverage Climate Diplomacy:

India must leverage its growing economic and political cult to acquire leadership of developing nations to protect and demand the due share of carbon budget for these nations. Further there should be diplomatic investment to get fund and technology transferred from the developed countries particularly the provisions of “loss and damage” in COPs (Conference of Parties). This fund either from multilateral institutions or governments must be in form of grants and not in form of loans. This fund is necessary for funding adaptation and mitigation efforts by local governments in their action plan on climate change.

6.4 LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY

Given the constraints of time and resources at the doctoral thesis level there are always limitations of the study. Further in social sciences studies, the limitation arises on several accounts in comparison to the studies in natural sciences where the scale of measurements has higher reliability. The present study has also some limitations that should be considered:

Though, this study has taken data of 800 respondents who hails from diverse backgrounds on accounts of their social, economic, educational, religious, gender and regional backgrounds. Yet the sample of 800 respondents from four districts may not fully represent Uttar Pradesh’s

diverse socio-economic and climatic conditions. Including more districts and a larger sample could enhance generalisability.

Second this study has reliance on self-reported data. Perceptions-based data introduces potential biases, as respondents' awareness levels, socio-cultural factors, and subjective experiences may influence responses. This margin of error exists in social science studies in general.

The study could not deeply explore the indigenous practices, which could provide valuable insights into community-based adaptation strategies due to the limitations of time and resources given the fact that this is a doctoral thesis only. To study such vast area and population a team of specialists is required to cover the different nuances of the scope.

The analysis of the SAPCC 2.0 relies on the document's content, with limited insights into implementation challenges or on-ground realities due to the study's scope and the roll out the plan is in its initial phases and no specific data is available regarding its implementation in a wholistic way either at district level or at state level.

6.5 BENEFITS/ RELEVANCE OF THE STUDY

Despite the limitations mentioned above, the study has relevance in social, academic, policy, administrative and community levels. This research yields significant societal benefits by addressing pressing environmental and equity challenges. The following sections elaborate on these benefits, building on the initial contributions and exploring additional dimensions of impact.

1. Raising Awareness of Climate Change Impacts

The confirmation of Hypothesis establishes that climate change manifests in Uttar Pradesh through extreme weather events (e.g., heatwaves,

floods), declining agricultural productivity, and health challenges (e.g., water borne, vector borne diseases, malnutrition). These impacts disrupt ecosystems, displace communities, and strain economic resources.

The research serves as a clarion call for public education campaigns, enabling citizens to understand climate risks and adopt adaptive behaviours (e.g., water conservation, sustainable farming). It also galvanizes local leaders and educators to integrate climate literacy into community programs, fostering a culture of preparedness and resilience.

2. Advocating for Environmental Justice

Hypothesis 3 validates that marginalised groups—such as rural farmers, women, and lower-caste communities—face heightened vulnerability due to limited access to resources, inadequate infrastructure, and systemic exclusion from decision-making processes.

By spotlighting these inequities, the research provides a compelling case for policies that prioritize vulnerable populations. It encourages the development of targeted interventions, such as subsidized climate-resilient crops, disaster relief funds, and gender-sensitive adaptation programs, ensuring that climate action reduces rather than exacerbates social disparities.

3. Evaluating and Improving State Climate Action Plans

The partial truth of Hypothesis 1 indicates that while Uttar Pradesh's State Action Plan on Climate Change (SAPCC) outlines ambitious goals, it falls short in equitable implementation, stakeholder engagement, and monitoring mechanisms.

The research offers a roadmap for policymakers to strengthen the SAPCC by incorporating participatory approaches, robust accountability

frameworks, and data-driven evaluations. This ensures that climate strategies are not only comprehensive but also responsive to the needs of all societal segments, particularly the most vulnerable.

4. Informing Policy and Governance

The evidence from study underscores the need for integrated policies that address health, livelihoods, and habitat preservation concurrently. For example, the research highlights the necessity of heat action plans, afforestation initiatives, and skill development programs to support climate-affected communities.

Policymakers can leverage these findings to align state budgets with climate priorities, streamline inter-departmental coordination, and secure funding for green infrastructure. This enhances governance efficiency and positions Uttar Pradesh as a model for climate-resilient development in India.

5. Empowering Communities and Stakeholders

The research's findings empower local communities by providing them with credible data to demand accountability from authorities. It also equips NGOs and grassroots organisations with evidence to advocate for inclusive climate policies and secure funding for community-led initiatives.

This empowerment fosters a sense of agency among residents, encouraging them to participate in local governance, adopt sustainable practices, and collaborate on resilience-building projects, such as community-managed water systems or cooperative farming models.

6. Contributing to Global Climate and Justice Discourses

Uttar Pradesh's socio-economic diversity and environmental challenges

make it a microcosm of global climate issues. The research's insights into disproportionate impacts and policy gaps resonate with challenges faced by other developing regions.

By contributing to international platforms like the UNFCCC COP conferences and academic journals, the study informs global climate strategies. It supports the advancement of frameworks like the Paris Agreement, emphasizing equity and localized action, and strengthens India's voice in global climate negotiations.

7. Supporting Long-Term Sustainability

The research advocates for a balanced approach to development that integrates environmental stewardship, social equity, and economic viability. It highlights the importance of preserving Uttar Pradesh's natural resources, such as its rivers and forests, while promoting inclusive growth.

This focus on sustainability ensures that future generations inherit a healthier environment and a more equitable society. It also attracts investment in green technologies and renewable energy, creating jobs and stimulating economic growth in the state.

8. Catalysing Interdisciplinary Research and Collaboration

The study's interdisciplinary approach—combining climate science, public health, sociology, and policy analysis—sets a precedent for holistic research on climate change.

It encourages collaboration among academics, scientists, and practitioners, fostering innovation in climate solutions. Universities and research institutions in Uttar Pradesh can use this model to launch similar studies, creating a knowledge hub for climate and justice research in the region.

9. Strengthening Public Health Systems

The adverse health impacts identified in Hypothesis, such as increased disease prevalence and mental health challenges due to climate stressors, highlight the need for climate-resilient healthcare systems. The research informs health policy by advocating for mobile clinics, early warning systems for heatwaves, and training for healthcare workers on climate-related illnesses. This strengthens public health infrastructure, reducing morbidity and mortality in vulnerable communities.

10. Promoting Economic Resilience

The livelihoods impacted by climate change, as confirmed by Hypothesis 2, include agriculture, fisheries, and small-scale enterprises. Hypothesis 3 further reveals that these losses disproportionately affect marginalised groups, exacerbating poverty. The research supports the development of economic diversification programs, such as training in climate-smart agriculture or microfinance for green enterprises. These initiatives enhance economic stability, reduce poverty, and create opportunities for sustainable livelihoods.

Thus, this doctoral research on *"Climate Action and Environmental Justice: A Study of Uttar Pradesh"* delivers far-reaching societal benefits by documenting climate impacts, exposing inequities, and critiquing state responses. It drives public awareness, informs policy, empowers communities, and contributes to global climate justice efforts. By addressing immediate challenges and laying the foundation for long-term sustainability, the study positions Uttar Pradesh as a leader in equitable climate action, with ripple effects for India and beyond.

6.6 CONCLUSION

The research “*Climate Action and Environmental Justice: A Study of Uttar Pradesh*” provides a comprehensive evaluation of the UPSAPCC 2.0 and the lived experiences of climate change in selected districts of Baihraich, Lakhimpur Kheri, Mahoba, and Sonbhadra in Uttar Pradesh. Climate change is no longer an academic discourse, but its impacts are getting apparent in day-to-day life with significant grave consequences for societies across the globe. However, the world suffers from “*Giddens’s Paradox*”. Further, climate change is happening in an unequal world infected with grave inequalities of resources, income and power as shown in celebrated work *Global Warming in An Unequal World: A Case of Environmental Colonialism*” that popularised the correlation between carbon emission and world’s poverty and prosperity with historical context of colonialism and extraction of resources of colonised areas for the benefits of colonial powers. Only a few countries, for instance, the USA, former Soviet Union countries, the UK, France, Poland, Germany, Japan, and Canada are responsible for about 75% of accumulated emissions as of 2019 and a majority of countries have contributed only 7% to the gross greenhouse gases (GHGs) in the atmosphere. Since the inception of the Industrial Revolution (IV), these extreme inequalities in carbon space utilization created gross economic inequalities rooted in the processes of ‘imperialism’ and ‘colonialism’; supported by ideologies of ‘capitalism’ and ‘liberalism’; accelerated by waves of ‘neo-liberalism’ and ‘globalization’. Today’s climate catastrophe is the product of these historical circumstances.

Nevertheless, the worldwide implications of climate change, the impacts of climate change are not borne equally by different sections of society.

The impacts differ to rich and poor, developed countries and developing world, old generations and young generations and one species to other species. There exists a question of justice that try to look the phenomenon of climate crisis through the rights of different sections of society, generations, species and nations. Scholars have explored the relationship between climate change and anthropogenic activities due to which this era is also known as ‘anthropocene’. However, some say that it is not fair to term ‘Anthropocene’ (an age of climate change caused by human activities) but better to term it ‘Capitalocene’ because they contend that it is not human activities but bourgeoisie capitalism that has caused this change in the climate of our planet.

Both liberal and conservative political scientists—often referred to as neo-classical environmentalists—think that established liberal democratic political systems can effectively address climate change issues and pursue substantive climate justice through current energy and economic regimes, global legal frameworks, and associated transnational institutions and mechanisms. However, some questions the efficacies of these measures and expose the international consensus on this urgent matter of existential threat to not only human race but to many species in our ecosystem as in the words of Antonio Guterres, UN Secretary-General, “failed climate leadership”. Scholars of this tradition put the notion that capitalism is posed to bring greater suffering and exploitation of communities and natural resources as it advances in the 21st century. The slogan goes: “Ecosocialism or Barbarism: there is no third way”.

The key question of how best to incorporate the concept of environmental justice in the climate action plan is the most vital in the developmental paradigm of state policies. The developmental paths are being redesigned

to make them compatible with environmental sustainability and socio-economic equity. The concept of 'low-carbon development pathways' has become traction among policymakers and academia as a viable option for sustainable development.

The concept of environmental justice evolved from the environmental movements that arose against unequal distribution of environmental harms especially in the habitats of people of colour and sections of disadvantaged groups of society. The literature on environmental justice consists of a pluralistic understanding of the concept. Many scholars have interpreted and analysed the concept of environmental justice differently in terms of distributional justice, procedural justice, recognition justice, and capability approach to justice. In the earlier years of environmental movements, the issues of "equity and "fairness" dominated the discourses of environmental justice, the demand for participation and having a say in the decision-making and recognition of their socio-cultural identity also became part of environmental justice discourse.

The thesis presents a study of interactions between climate actions and justice. The findings partially validate Hypothesis 1, confirming that the SAPCC 2.0 is comprehensive but falls short in inclusivity and justness due to gaps in addressing marginalised groups, centralized implementation, and neglect of cultural practices. Hypotheses 2 is robustly supported, demonstrating that climate change is a socio-economic crisis affecting livelihoods, health, and habitats. The study validates that agriculture output, labour income, loss of working hours, attack of pests on crops, due to abnormal weather conditions induced by climate change, are severely impacting the livelihood prospects of people. The sensitivity of agriculture is apparent to climate change-induced events in state of Uttar Pradesh

where a major portion of labour force is engaged in agriculture and allied sectors for their subsistence. These perspectives suggest that climate variability—through rising temperatures, altered rainfall patterns, and humidity—fostering flood, drought, heatwaves, storms, pest outbreaks on crops, vector generated diseases outbreaks, thereby reducing agriculture yields, compromising human health, and destabilizing local ecosystems. Such issues have profound implications for income security, food availability, and nutritional health and overall human development.

The marginalised communities—SCs, STs, OBCs, and women—face disproportionate impacts despite their minimal contribution to the problem. It is apparent from the above discussion that the phenomena of climate change, particularly through extreme weather disruptions, is significantly influencing people but their impacts are being faced disproportionately by the marginalised sections of the society. These sections not only have been marginalised in resource allocation/ownership but also in knowledge and information accessibility. Their poor resources make it difficult for them to cope up the adverse conditions induced by climate change. This undermines their adaptive capacity and enhanced the disparity between different sections of society. Despite having less power over land use and contributing marginally to large-scale emissions or unsustainable land practices, they face heightened exposure to the adverse effects of climate change. This underlines a critical dimension of climate injustice: those least responsible for ecological degradation, like landless labourer, tribes or semi-landholding women, are often the most affected and least equipped to adapt or to combat. The study highlights the urgency for climate-adaptive labour policies, heat protection measures, and social safety nets

to safeguard the working population from climate-driven economic vulnerability.

The study explores that the conservation and creation of ecological assets like ponds, river embankment, taking care of community forests, making boats with lighter plant stems in emergency has resilience and capacity building power. The young generation need to be made aware about the usefulness and effectiveness of our traditional knowledge system. The lived experiences and perceptions of the respondents clearly shows that there are certain challenges and prospects in climate action to make it more just and inclusive. Obviously, there are economic challenges. Lack of capital to invest in environment-friendly actions/activities are the biggest problem apart from lack of necessary information and want of coordination in different government policies/programmes and their implementation. Further there are prospects of changes and adaptation to sustainable livelihood or environmentally compatible behaviours/actions if people would be provided choices/solution that are affordable and with necessary training and capacity building measures.

Despite above-mentioned constraints, there are very proactive measures taken by Government of India and Government of Uttar Pradesh to ward off the impacts of climate change in every possible way given the resources available with the government. Apart from NAPCC at national level and SAPCC at state level, various policies interventions like Bio-Energy Policy, Green Hydrogen Policy, and making all developmental ecosystem compatible with climate action plan, capacity building measures are being taken at various level to engage major stakeholders. Judiciary is taking active measures in disposing the environmental cases and several important decisions have helped the poor and marginalised

sections of society in getting better compensation or protect them from the ill-effects of industrial activities e.g. discharge of effluents into streams, pollution and mining activities. Recently the NGT has ordered Northern Coalfield to pay compensation amounting Rs. 10 crores for violating environmental norms by dumping coal near the residential area at Bina, Sonbhadra. Similarly, on 19 May, 2023 NGT took suo moto action for illegal mining in Agori Khas, Obra, Sonbhadra district.

The study emphasises the urgent need for justice-oriented climate policies that prioritise equitable resource distribution, inclusive decision-making, and recognition of diverse community needs. The proposed suggestions—enhancing distributive, participative, and recognition justice, addressing funding gaps, building climate literacy, and developing localized strategies—offer a roadmap for strengthening the SAPCC 2.0 and supporting vulnerable populations. Despite its limitations, the study contributes valuable insights to the discourse on climate action and environmental justice, emphasizing the intersection of climate change with structural inequities.

Looking ahead, policymakers must adopt a holistic approach to climate action, integrating marginalised voices, leveraging indigenous knowledge, and addressing regional disparities. The findings underscore that climate change is not only an environmental challenge but also a socio-economic and ethical one, requiring concerted efforts to ensure that those least responsible for the crisis are not left to bear its heaviest burdens. By prioritizing environmental justice, Uttar Pradesh can pave the way for a resilient, inclusive, and sustainable future.

SELECTED BIBLIOGRAPHY

PRIMARY SOURCES:

- Primary data collected from the selected districts of Bahraich, Lakhimpur Khiri, Mahoba and Sonbhadra of Uttar Pradesh on the lived experiences and perception about climate related phenomena. The data was collected from January 2024 to June 2024.
- NAPCC (National Action Plan on Climate Change) (2008), Prime Minister's Council for Climate Change, Government of India, New Delhi. https://archivepmo.nic.in/drmanmohansingh/climate_change_english.pdf
- UP SAPCC 1.0 (2014). Uttar Pradesh State Action Plan on Climate Change. Department of Environment, Forest, and Climate Change, Government of Uttar Pradesh. Retrieved from https://moef.gov.in/uploads/2017/09/SAPCC_UP_final_version_0.pdf
- UP SAPCC 2.0 (2023). Uttar Pradesh State Action Plan on Climate Change 2021-2030. Department of Environment, Forest, and Climate Change, Government of Uttar Pradesh. Retrieved from https://upccce.org/public/UPLOADS/REPOSITORY/DOC/27_stateactionplan.pdf
- Interview with noted environmentalist Padam Shri Kalyan Singh Rawat, founder of Maitee Movement, that motivate young couple entering into married life to plant a sapling and take care of it till it turn into a tree on 19th Feb. 2024 at 12:00 PM.
- Interview with Sh. Prem Chand Swarankar, noted environment activist in Mahoba district on 3rd April 2024 at 6:30 PM.
- Interview with Smt. Kalpna Khare, Director of Grammonati Sansthan, a reputed NGO working in environmental issues in Bundelkhand region, Headquartered in Mahoba District, Uttar Pradesh on 4th April 2024 at 3:00 PM.
- Interview with Sh. Umesh Kumar Gupta, Regional Pollution Officer, Sonbhadra on 26th Feb. 2024 at 1:00 PM.
- Interview with Sh. Kenahi Gond, Village Pradhan and a local leader in Chopan, Sonbhadra on 25th Feb. 2024 at 4:45 PM.
- Interview with Sh. Sukkhan Pathari, a local Tribal leader of Kanohara, Sonbhadra on 25th Feb. 2024 at 9:45 AM.

SECONDARY SOURCES

REFERENCES

CHAPTER-1

- Adger, W. N., Dessai, S., Goulden, M., Hulme, M., Lorenzoni, I., Nelson, D. R., ... & Wreford, A. (2009). Are there social limits to adaptation to climate change? *Climatic change*, 93, 335-354. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10584-008-9520-z>
- Adger, W. N., Paavola, J., & Huq, S. (2006). Toward justice in adaptation to climate change, *Fairness in Adaptation to Climate Change*, MIT Press, USA. <https://doi.org/10.7551/mitpress/2957.003.0004>
- Agyeman, J., Bullard, R. D., & Evans, B. (Eds.). (2003). *Just sustainabilities: Development in an unequal world*. MIT Press.
- Albus, S. (2011). Strengthening Equity in Rural Drinking Water Supply in Uttar Pradesh-A Local Government Perspective. Retrieved from <https://lup.lub.lu.se/luur/download?func=downloadFile&recordOId=1967066&fileOId=1967068>
- Anguelovski, I., Shi, L., Chu, E., Gallagher, D., Goh, K., Lamb, Z., ... & Teicher, H. (2016). Equity impacts of urban land use planning for climate adaptation: Critical perspectives from the global north and south. *Journal of Planning Education and Research*, 36(3), 333-348. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0739456X16645166>
- Angus, I. (Ed.). (2010). *The Global Fight for Climate Justice: Anticapitalist Responses to Global Warming and Environmental Destruction*. Fernwood Publication.
- Aykut, S.C., Maertens, L. (2023). The Climatization of Global Politics: Introduction to the Special Issue. In: Aykut, S., Maertens, L. (eds) *The Climatization of Global Politics*. Palgrave Macmillan, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-17895-5_1
- Baer, H. A. (2021). *Global Capitalism And Climate Change: The Need for an Alternative World System* (2nd Ed.), Lexington Books, London.
- Balkan, S. (2022). *Rogues in the Post Colony: Narrating Extraction and Itinerancy in India* (First Edition). West Virginia University Press.

- Belcher, O., Bigger, P., Neimark, B., & Kennelly, C. (2020). Hidden carbon costs of the “everywhere war”: Logistics, geopolitical ecology, and the carbon boot - print of the US military. *Transactions of the Institute of British Geographers*, 45(1), 65-80.
- Bhargava, Y. (2021). "In 2020, World Added 3 Billionaires Every Two Days, India Added One Every Week.! The Hindu, 2 March. <https://www.thehindu.com/news/national/india-adds-40billionaires-in-pandemic-year-adani-ambani-see-rise-in-wealth-report/article33970268>. ece (accessed on 7 October 2024).
- Böhm, S., Misoczky, M. C., & Moog, S. (2012). Greening capitalism? A Marxist critique of carbon markets. *Organization Studies*, 33(11), 1617-1638. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0170840612463326>
- Bullard, R. D., & Johnson, G. S. (2000). Environmentalism and public policy: Environmental justice: Grassroots activism and its impact on public policy decision making. *Journal of Social Issues*, 56(3), 555-578.
- Bullard, R. D., & Wright, B. H. (1990). The quest for environmental equity: Mobilizing the African - American community for social change. *Society & Natural Resources*, 3(4), 301-311. <https://doi.org/10.1080/08941929009380728>
- Caney, S. (2020). “Climate Justice”, The Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophy (Summer 2020 Edition), E. N. Zalta (ed.). Retrieved on September 20, 2021, from <https://plato.stanford.edu/archives/sum2020/entries/justice-climate/>.
- Carlton, J. S., Perry-Hill, R., Huber, M., & Prokopy, L. S. (2015). The climate change consensus extends beyond climate scientists. *Environmental Research Letters*, 10(9), 094025. DOI 10.1088/1748-9326/10/9/094025
- Chancel, L. (2022). Global carbon inequality over 1990–2019. *Nature Sustainability*, 5(11), 931-938. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41893-022-00955-z>
- Cook, J., Nuccitelli, D., Green, S. A., Richardson, M., Winkler, B., Painting, R., ... & Skuce, A. (2013). Quantifying the consensus on anthropogenic global warming in the scientific literature. *Environmental research letters*, 8(2), 024024.
- Cook, J., Oreskes, N., Doran, P. T., Anderegg, W. R., Verheggen, B., Maibach, E. W., ... & Rice, K. (2016). Consensus on consensus: a synthesis of consensus

estimates on human-caused global warming. *Environmental research letters*, 11(4), 048002.

- Crawford, N. C. (2019). Pentagon fuel use, climate change, and the costs of war. <https://conspiracytheorieswithcoffeeandpot.com/wp-content/uploads/2023/12/pentagon-fuel-use-climate-change.pdf>
- Davis, J., Moulton, A. A., Van Sant, L., & Williams, B. (2019). Anthropocene, Capitalocene Plantationocene?: A manifesto for ecological justice in an age of global crises. *Geography Compass*, 13(5), e12438.
- de Freitas Netto, S. V., Sobral, M. F. F., Ribeiro, A. R. B., & Soares, G. R. D. L. (2020). Concepts and forms of greenwashing: A systematic review. *Environmental Sciences Europe*, 32, 1-12. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12302-020-0300-3>
- Desai, S., & Dubey, A. (2012). Caste in 21st century India: Competing narratives. *Economic and Political Weekly*, 46(11), 40.
- Down to Earth (2024). State of India's Environment 2024, A Down to Earth Annual, CSE, New Delhi.
- Earthjustice, (2024), How Climate Change Is Fueling Extreme Weather. Oct 1, 2024 <https://earthjustice.org/feature/how-climate-change-is-fueling-extreme-weather>
- Eckersley, R. (1992). *Environmentalism and Political Theory: Toward an Ecocentric Approach*, UCL (University College of London) Press, London.
- Ehrlich, P. R., & Ehrlich, A. H. (2013). Can a collapse of global civilization be avoided? *Proceedings of the Royal Society B: Biological Sciences*, 280(1754), 20122845. <https://doi.org/10.1098/rspb.2012.2845>
- Falkner, R. (2013). The crisis of environmental multilateralism: A liberal response. *The Green Book: New Directions for Liberals in Government*, p.347-358. Biteback Publishing.
- Falkner, R. (2017). *Business Power and Conflict in International Environmental Politics*. Springer.
- Fischer, F. (2017). *Climate Crisis and the Democratic Prospect: Participatory Governance in Sustainable Communities*. Oxford University Press. London.

- Füssel, H. M., & Klein, R. J. (2006). Climate Change Vulnerability Assessments: An Evolution of Conceptual Thinking. *Climatic Change*, 75(3), 301-329, Springer. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10584-006-0329-3>
- Ghosh, A. (2018). *The great derangement: Climate change and the unthinkable*. Penguin UK.
- Ghosh, A. (2021). The nutmeg's curse: Parables for a planet in crisis. In *The Nutmeg's Curse*. University of Chicago Press.
- Giddens, A. (2009). *The Politic of Climate Change*, Polity Press, Cambridge.
- Haider, S. (2021, December 19). Explained: Why did India reject UNSC draft on climate? *The Hindu*, New Delhi edition. <https://www.thehindu.com/sci-tech/energy-and-environment/explained-why-did-india-reject-unsc-draft-on-climate/article37988088.ece>
- Hansen, G., & Stone, D. (2016). Assessing the observed impact of anthropogenic climate change. *Nature Climate Change*, 6(5), 532-537.
- Haraway, D. (2015). Anthropocene, Capitalocene, Plantationocene, Chthulucene: Making in *Environmental Humanities*, 6(1), 159-165.
- Heffron, R.J. (2021). What is the “Just Transition”? In: *Achieving a Just Transition to a Low-Carbon Economy*. Palgrave Macmillan, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-89460-3_2
- Höök, M., & Tang, X. (2013). Depletion of fossil fuels and anthropogenic climate change—A review. *Energy policy*, 52, 797-809.
- HRC (Human Right Council) (2019), Resolution adopted by the Human Rights Council, 41/21, “Human Rights and Climate Change”, July 12, 2019, Agenda Item-3, United Nations General Assembly <https://documents.un.org/doc/undoc/gen/g19/223/65/pdf/g1922365.pdf>
- Hulme, M. (2009) *Why We Disagree about Climate Change: Understanding Controversy, Inaction and Opportunity*, Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Ikeme, J. (2003). Equity, environmental justice, and sustainability: incomplete approaches in climate change politics. *Global Environmental Change-Human and Policy Dimensions*, 13(3), 195–206. [https://doi.org/10.1016/s0959-3780\(03\)00047-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0959-3780(03)00047-5)

- IPCC (2007) Fourth Assessment Report, Working Group I, Glossary of Terms: [http://ipcc-wg1.ucar.edu/wg1/ Report/AR4WG1_Print_Annexes.pdf](http://ipcc-wg1.ucar.edu/wg1/Report/AR4WG1_Print_Annexes.pdf).
- Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) (2007). Historical Overview of Climate Change. In *Climate Change: The Physical Science Basis. Contribution of Working Group I to the Fourth Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change*.
- IPCC. (2014) *Climate Change 2014: Synthesis Report. Contribution of Working Groups I, II, and III to the Fifth Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change* [Core Writing Team, Pachauri, R.K. and Meyer LA. (eds.)]. IPCC, Geneva, Switzerland, 151 pp. Retrieved from https://www.ipcc.ch/site/assets/uploads/2018/05/SYR_AR5_FINAL_full_wcover.pdf
- Jeffery, R., Jeffrey, C., & Lerche, J. (2014). *Development Failure and Identity Politics in Uttar Pradesh*. Sage India Pvt. <https://doi.org/10.4135/9789351507895>
- Kashwan, P., (2022). *Climate Justice in India (vol.1)*, Cambridge University Press, London.
- Klein N. (2014). *This Changes Everything: Capitalism vs The Climate*. Simon & Schuster.
- Klein N. (2017). *No Is Not Enough: Resisting Trump's Shock Politics and Winning the World We Need*. Penguin Books.
- Ledley, T. S., Sundquist, E. T., Schwartz, S. E., Hall, D. K., Fellows, J. D., & Killeen, T. L. (1999). Climate change and greenhouse gases. *Eos, Transactions American Geophysical Union*, 80(39), 453-458.
- Lee, S., & Jamal, T. (2008). Environmental Justice and Environmental Equity in Tourism: Missing Links to Sustainability. *Journal of Ecotourism*, 7(1), 44–67. <https://doi.org/10.2167/joe191.0>
- Lobell, D. B., Burke, M. B., Tebaldi, C., Mastrandrea, M. D., Falcon, W. P., & Naylor, R. L. (2008). Prioritizing climate change adaptation needs for food security in 2030. *Science*, 319(5863), 607-610. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.1152339>

- Machin, A. (2013). *Negotiating climate change: Radical democracy and the illusion of consensus*. Bloomsbury Publishing.
- Mani, M.; Bandyopadhyay, S.; Chonabayashi, S.; Markandya, A.; Mosier, T. (2018). South Asia's Hotspots: Impacts of Temperature and Precipitation Changes on Living Standards. South Asia Development Matters; World Bank, Washington, DC <http://hdl.handle.net/10986/28723> License: CC BY 3.0 IGO.
- McCright, A. M., & Dunlap, R. E. (2011). The politicization of climate change and polarization in the American public's views of global warming, 2001–2010. *The Sociological Quarterly*, 52(2), 155-194. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1533-8525.2011.01198.x>
- Mikhaylov, A., Moiseev, N., Aleshin, K., & Burkhardt, T. (2020). Global climate change and greenhouse effect. *Entrepreneurship and Sustainability Issues*, 7(4), 2897.
- Mill, J. S. (1987). *Utilitarianism and other essays*. Penguin Books.
- Mohai, P., & Saha, R. (2006). Reassessing racial and socioeconomic disparities in environmental justice research. *Demography*, 43(2), 383-399.
- Moore, J.W. (2014). The Capitalocene. Part II: Abstract Social Nature and the Limits to Capital.
- Moore, J.W. (Ed.). (2016). *Anthropocene or Capitalocene?: Nature, History, and the Crisis of Capitalism*. Pm Press.
- Morgan, Gareth, and John McCrystal (2009). *Poles Apart: Beyond the Shouting and Who's Right about Climate Change?* Melbourne, Australia: Scribe.
- Neelam, & R. Sharma (2023). Geographical Landform Types of Uttar Pradesh, India. *International Journal For Multidisciplinary Research*, 5(5). <https://doi.org/10.36948/ijfmr.2023.v05i05.6739>
- Nelson, R., Kokic, P., Crimp, S., Martin, P., Meinke, H., Howden, S. M., ... & Nidumolu, U. (2010). The vulnerability of Australian rural communities to climate variability and change: Part II—Integrating impacts with adaptive capacity. *Environmental Science & Policy*, 13(1), 18-27. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsci.2009.09.007>

- Newell, P. (2020). The Business of Rapid Transition. *WIREs Climate Change*, 11(6), e670. <https://doi.org/10.1002/wcc.670>
- Newell, P., & Mulvaney, D. (2013). The political economy of the ‘just transition’. *The Geographical Journal*, 179(2), 132-140. <https://doi.org/10.1111/geoj.12008>
- Newell, P., & Paterson, M. (1998). A climate for business: global warming, the state and capital. *Review of International Political Economy*, 5(4), 679-703.
- Oreskes, N. (2018). *The scientific consensus on climate change: How do we know we’re not wrong?* (pp. 31-64). Springer International Publishing.
- Patel, J., & Shukla, S. (2023). Urban Development in Uttar Pradesh: A Historical Study. *International Journal For Multidisciplinary Research*, 5(5). <https://doi.org/10.36948/ijfmr.2023.v05i05.7438>
- Pellow, D. N. (2007). *Resisting global toxics: Transnational movements for environmental justice*. MIT Press.
- Piketty, T. (2020). *Capital and Ideology* (translated by Arthur Goldhammer, Belknap Press of Harvard University Press. Cambridge, Massachusetts, London.
- Poortinga, W., Whitmarsh, L., Steg, L., Böhm, G., & Fisher, S. (2019). Climate change perceptions and their individual-level determinants: A cross-European analysis. *Global environmental change*, 55, 25-35. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gloenvcha.2019.01.007>
- Powell, J. L. (2016). The consensus on anthropogenic global warming matters. *Bulletin of Science, Technology & Society*, 36(3), 157-163.
- Ram, K., & Yadav, S. (2024). The impact of COVID-19 on poverty estimates in India: a study across caste, class and religion. *Contemporary Voice of Dalit*, 16(1), 86-100. <https://doi.org/10.1177/2455328X211051432>
- Ranjan, A., Mandal, K. K., & Kumari, P. (2020). Impact of coal-fired thermal power plant on the drinking water quality of Anpara, Sonbhadra, Uttar Pradesh, India. *Groundwater for Sustainable Development*, 11, 100395.
- Rawls, J. (n.d.). *A Theory of Justice: Revised Edition*.
- Revi, A., Satterthwaite, D., Aragón-Durand, F., Corfee-Morlot, J., Kiunsi, R. B., Pelling, M., ... & Sverdlik, A. (2014). Towards transformative adaptation in

- cities: the IPCC's Fifth Assessment. *Environment and Urbanization*, 26(1), 11-28. Sage Publication. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0956247814523539>
- Ritchie, H., (2019) "Who has contributed most to global CO2 emissions?" Published online at OurWorldinData.org. Retrieved from: <https://ourworldindata.org/contributed-most-global-co2>
 - Rosa, R. V., Milhomem, T. L. M., Bertotti, G. de A. L. B., Alves, J. L., Lins, M. J. N. de O. L., & Bertotti, J. A. B. J. (2024). Recife Park City: the role of the Recife local climate action plan and the Pernambuco decarbonization plan. *Concilium*, 24(7), 401–416. <https://doi.org/10.53660/clm-3261-24g35>
 - Rosenzweig, C., Karoly, D., Vicarelli, M., Neofotis, P., Wu, Q., Casassa, G., ... & Imeson, A. (2008). Attributing physical and biological impacts to anthropogenic climate change. *Nature*, 453(7193), 353-357.
 - Sabarwal, S.; Sergio, V. M.; Marla, S.; Diego, A. (2024). *Choosing Our Future: Education for Climate Action*. © Washington, DC: World Bank. <http://hdl.handle.net/10986/42098>
 - Schlosberg, D. (2004). Reconceiving environmental justice: global movements and political theories. *Environmental Politics*, 13(3), 517-540. <https://doi.org/10.1080/0964401042000229025>
 - Schlosberg, D. (2012). Climate justice and capabilities: A framework for adaptation policy. *Ethics & International Affairs*, 26(4), 445-461.
 - Schlosberg, D., & Collins, L. B. (2014). From Environmental to Climate Justice: Climate Change and the Discourse of Environmental Justice. *WIREs Climate Change*, 5(3), 359-374. <https://doi.org/10.1002/wcc.275>
 - Schlosberg, David (2013) 'Theorising Environmental Justice: The Expanding Sphere of a Discourse'. 22(1) *Environmental Politics* 37,38
 - Sengupta, S. (2019). India's engagement in global climate negotiations from Rio to Paris in Dubas, N. K. (ed.) *India in a warming world: Integrating climate change and development*, 114-141. <https://pdfs.semanticscholar.org/8daa/b586bb9b0cdc236540a1d7a0c3c128bff9f1.pdf#page=143>
 - Shaw, C. (2023). *Liberalism and the Challenge of Climate Change*. Taylor & Francis.

- Singh, J., Sahany, S., Singh, K. K., Robock, A., & Xia, L. (2024). Future climate change impacts on rice in Uttar Pradesh, India's most populous agrarian state. *Earth's Future*, 12(5), e2023EF004009. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2023EF004009>
- Stocker, T. F., Qin, D., Plattner, G. K., Alexander, L. V., Allen, S. K., Bindoff, N. L., ... & Xie, S. P. (2013). Technical summary. In *Climate change 2013: the physical science basis. Contribution of Working Group I to the Fifth Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC)* (pp. 33-115). Cambridge University Press.
- Supreme Court of India, (2024), M K Ranjitsingh & Ors. V/s Union of India & Ors. In Writ Petition (Civil) NO. 838 of 2019, 2024 INSC 280. https://main.sci.gov.in/supremecourt/2019/20754/20754_2019_1_25_51677_Judgement_21-Mar-2024.pdf
- Szabo, S., & Webster, J. (2021). Perceived greenwashing: the effects of green marketing on environmental and product perceptions. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 171, 719-739. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10551-020-04461-0>
- Tari, V. S., Wahyuni, D. K., Siddiqui, N., & Rathi, D. (2024). Need for an Evolved Groundwater Justice in Rural Areas of Uttar Pradesh, India. *Nature Environment and Pollution Technology*, 23(1), 125–137. <https://doi.org/10.46488/nept.2024.v23i01.009>
- Tripathi, V., Ahuja, D. (2022). Poverty and Income Distribution Amid Covid-19: An Analysis of India. In: Subudhi, R.N., Mishra, S., Saleh, A., Khezrimotlagh, D. (eds) *Future of Work and Business in Covid-19 Era*. Springer Proceedings in Business and Economics. Springer, Singapore. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-19-0357-1_7
- UN (2023) Sustainable Development Goals 13- Climate Action, https://www.un.org/sustainabledevelopment/wp-content/uploads/2023/09/Goal-13_Fast-Facts.pdf Retrieved on 08.08.2024.
- UNEP (United Nations Environment Programme) (2015), *Climate Change and Human Rights*, December 2015. UNEP, in cooperation with Columbia Law School. https://wedocs.unep.org/bitstream/handle/20.500.11822/9530/Climate_

Change_and_Human_Rightsclimate-change.pdf.pdf?sequence=2
&%3BisAllowed=

- UNFCCC, (1992). Article 1, Definitions 2 https://unfccc.int/files/essential_background/background_publications_htmlpdf/application/pdf/conveng.pdf
- United Nations (2019). United Nations Portal. *Climate Justice*,
- United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP) (2021). Annual Report 2021, Planetary Action. UNEP. <https://www.unep.org/resources/annual-report-2021>
- Vanderheiden, S., (2016) Environmental and Climate Justice in T. Garbrielson, C. Hall, J. M. Meyer, & D. Schlosberg (eds.) *The Oxford Handbook of Environmental Political Theory*. pp. 321-332. Oxford University Press.
- Wainwright, J., & Mann, G. (2013). Climate leviathan. *Antipode*, 45(1), 1-22.
- Walker, B., & Salt, D. (2012). *Resilience thinking: sustaining ecosystems and people in a changing world*. Island press.
- Wheeler, T., & Von Braun, J. (2013). Climate change impacts on global food security. *Science*, 341(6145), 508-513. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.1239402>
- WMO (World Meteorological Organisation) (2024). *State of the Global Climate 2023*, WMO- No. 1347, Geneva, <https://library.wmo.int/idurl/4/68835>
- World Resource Institute (WRI) (2023, March 20). 10 Big findings from the 2023 IPCC report on climate change. Retrieved from <https://www.wri.org/insights/2023-ipcc-ar6-synthesis-report-climate-change-findings>
- Yuan, H., Zhou, P., Zhou, D. (2011), What is Low-Carbon Development? A Conceptual Analysis, *Energy Procedia*, Volume 5, p.1706-1712, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.egypro.2011.03.290>.
- Zhou, P. (2014). Low-Carbon Development. In: Michalos, A.C. (eds) *Encyclopedia of Quality of Life and Well-Being Research*. Springer, Dordrecht. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-94-007-0753-5_3382

CHAPTER-2

- Adger, W. N. (1999) Social Vulnerability to Climate Change and Extremes in Coastal Vietnam, *World Development*, 27 (2), 249-269.

- Adger, W. N. and Kelly, P. M. (1999) Social vulnerability to climate change and the architecture of entitlements, *Mitigation and Adaptation Strategies for Global Change*, 4, 253-266.
- Allen, K. (2003). Vulnerability reduction and the community-based approach: A Philippines study. In *Natural disaster and development in a globalizing world* (pp. 186-200). Routledge.
- Amaratunga, D., Baldry, D., Sarshar, M., & Newton, R. (2002). Quantitative and qualitative research in the built environment: application of “mixed” research approach. *Work study*, 51(1), 17-31.
- Brief Industrial Profile of Mahoba District, U.P. (2016) MSME-Development Institute, Kanpur (Ministry of MSME, Govt. of India), pp. 3-7.
- Brooks, N. (2003). Vulnerability, risk, and adaptation: A conceptual framework. *Tyndall Centre for climate change research working paper*, 38(38), 1-16. Retrieved from https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Nick-Brooks-3/publication/200032746_Vulnerability_Risk_and_Adaptation_A_Conceptual_Framework/links/0fcfd50ac169e15865000000/Vulnerability-Risk-and-Adaptation-A-Conceptual-Framework.pdf
- Burns, N., & Grove, S. K. (2009). *The practice of nursing research: appraisal, synthesis, and generation of evidence*. St. Louis, Mo: Saunders Elsevier.
- CEDA (2021) HDI: How States Fare in Human Development, Centre for Economic Data & Analysis, Ashoka University, <https://ceda.ashoka.edu.in/hdi-how-states-fare-in-human-development/>
- Census of India (2011). *Census of India- Uttar Pradesh*, Office of the Registrar General & Census Commissioner, India. Ministry of Home Affairs, Government of India. Retrieved from <https://censusindia.gov.in/census.website/>
- Central Ground Water Board (2013), *Ground Water Scenario of Lakhimpur Kheri District, U.P.,(A.A.P.: 2012-13)* by Dr. D.S. Pandey, Scientist D. Retrieved from https://www.cgwb.gov.in/old_website/District_Profile/UP/Lakhimpur-kheri.pdf

- Central Ground Water Board (2018). CGWB, Ministry of Jal Shakti, Government of India. Retrieved from https://www.cgwb.gov.in/old_website/Annual-Reports/ANNUAL%20REPORT%20CGWB%202018-19_final.pdf
- Central Ground Water Board(2019), Report on Aquifer mapping and Groundwater management plan, Mahoba district, Uttar Pradesh by Shri Pramod Kumar Tripathi, Scientist D. Retrieved from https://cgwb.gov.in/old_website/AQM/NAQUIM_REPORT/UP/Mahoba%20NAQUIM%20Report.pdf
- Central Ground Water Report (2019). CGWB, Ministry of Jal Shakti, Government of India. Retrieved from https://cgwb.gov.in/old_website/Annual-Reports/Modified_ANNUAL%20REPORT%20of%20CGWB%202019-20%20by%20SND_21052021.pdf
- De Vaus, D. A. (2002). *Analyzing social science data: 50 key problems in data analysis*. Sage Publication.
- District Census Handbook- Lakhimpur Kheri (2011). Census of India 2011. Uttar Pradesh. Series 10. Directorate of Census Operations Uttar Pradesh. Retrieved from https://censusindia.gov.in/nada/index.php/catalog/1245/download/3994/DH_2011_0922_PART_B_DCHB_KHERI.pdf
- District Sankhikiya Patrika-Baharaich. (2023). Directorate of Economics and Statistics, Government of Uttar Pradesh. Retrieved from <https://updes.up.nic.in/spiderreports/intialisePage.action;jsessionid=327A5D5AC8F2D7443201C358C1C58BB4>
- District Sankhyikiya Patrika (2021-22) Economics Data and Statistics Division, Directorate of Economics and Statistics, Govt. of Uttar Pradesh
- District Skill Development Plan (2020-21). District Program Management Unit, Mahoba, Uttar Pradesh Skill Development Mission, Uttar Pradesh. Retrieved from <https://www.upsdm.gov.in/Content/WebAssets/DSDP/MAHOBA.pdf>
- District Survey Report (2024), District Survey Report (DSR)- Kheri (River Bed Mining)- Year 2024. Retrieved from <https://cdn.s3waas.gov.in/s3a2557a7b2e94197ff767970b67041697/uploads/2024/07/2024073097.pdf>

- India Statistics District. (n. d.). District Level Information of Mahoba (Uttar Pradesh), Retrieved from <https://www.indiastatdistricts.com/uttarpradesh/mahoba-district>
- Indian Meteorological Department (IMD). Summary of Climate Hazards and Vulnerability Atlas of India, Office of Climate Research and Services. IMD, Ministry of Earth Science, GoI. Retrieved from https://imdpune.gov.in/hazardatlas/atlas_summary.html
- Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) (2019). Special Report Climate Change and Land Retrieved from <https://www.ipcc.ch/srccl/>
- Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) AR 5 (2014). AR 5 Climate Change 2014: Impacts, Adaptation, and Vulnerability. Retrieved from <https://www.ipcc.ch/report/ar5/wg2/>
- IPCC (2001) Climate change 2001: Impacts, Adaptation, and Vulnerability, Summary for Policymakers, WMO.
- Jones, R. and Boer, R. (2003) Assessing current climate risks Adaptation Policy Framework: A Guide for Policies to Facilitate Adaptation to Climate Change, UNDP, in review, see <http://www.undp.org/cc/apf-outline.htm>.
- Kaithal, A. K. (2021). Climate change and Uttar Pradesh: Issues, Challenges and way forward. *Journal of Emerging Technologies and Emerging Research*, 8(10), 783-789.
- Nicholls, R. J., Hoozemans, F. M., & Marchand, M. (1999). Increasing flood risk and wetland losses due to global sea-level rise: regional and global analyses. *Global Environmental Change*, 9, S69-S87.
- Parahoo, K. (2006). Nursing research: principles, process, and issues. Basingstoke, Hampshire, England; New York: Palgrave Macmillan.
- Reserve Bank of India (RBI) Handbook of Statistics on Indian States (2023a). RBI, Government of India, <https://m.rbi.org.in/scripts/PublicationsView.aspx?id=22128>
- Reserve Bank of India (RBI) Handbook of Statistics on Indian States (2023b). RBI, Government of India <https://m.rbi.org.in/scripts/PublicationsView.aspx?id=22156>

- Roy, M. (2020). Sampling Methods. in (ed.) Acharyya, R. & Bhattacharya, N. *Research Methodology for Social Science*, Routledge.
- Schneiderbauer, S., & Ehrlich, D. (2004). Risk, hazard, and people's vulnerability to natural hazards. *A review of definitions, concepts, and data. European Commission Joint Research Centre. EUR, 21410,40.*
https://www.researchgate.net/profile/SSchneiderbauer/publication/268149143_Risk_Hazard_and_People's_Vulnerability_to_Natural_Hazards_a_Review_of_Definitions_Concepts_and_Data/links/55e6916308aebdc0f58bb763/Risk-Hazard-and-Peoples-Vulnerability-to-Natural-Hazards-a-Review-of-Definitions-Concepts-and-Data.pdf
- Singh, P., Goyal, M., & Choudhary, B. B. (2021). Drivers of foodgrain productivity in Uttar Pradesh. *Economic & Political Weekly*, 38, 40-45. Retrieved from https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Bishwa-Choudhary/publication/354687071_Drivers_of_Foodgrain_Productivity_in_Uttar_Pradesh_Panel_Data_Analysis/links/6146cbe9519a1a381f6c1e93/Drivers-of-Foodgrain-Productivity-in-Uttar-Pradesh-Panel-Data-Analysis.pdf
- Statistical Diary Uttar Pradesh (2021). Economic & Statistics Divisions State Planning Institute Planning Department, Uttar Pradesh. Retrieved from https://updes.up.nic.in/esd/reports/diary%20eng%202021_merged.pdf
- Taherdoost, H. (2022). What are different research approaches? Comprehensive Review of Qualitative, quantitative, and mixed method research, their applications, types, and limitations. *Journal of Management Science & Engineering Research*, 5(1), 53-63.
- Tripathi, A. (2014). Socioeconomic Backwardness Increases Vulnerability to Climate Change: Evidence from Uttar Pradesh. IEG (Institute of Economic Growth) Working Paper No. 337. Retrieved from <https://iegindia.org/upload/publication/Workpap/wp337.pdf>
- United Nations International Strategy for Disaster Reduction (UNISDR) (2004). *Living With Risk. UNISDR.* Retrieved from https://www.unisdr.org/files/657_lwr1.pdf

- UP Bio-Energy Policy-2022. (2022). Invest UP. Government of Uttar Pradesh. Retrieved from https://invest.up.gov.in/wp-content/uploads/2022/11/State-Bio-Energy-Policy-2022English_101122.pdf
- Uttar Pradesh Arthik Samiksha, 2022-23 (2023). State Planning Department, Government of Uttar Pradesh. https://updes.up.nic.in/updes/data/arthik_samiksha/arthik%20samiksha_2022_23.pdf
- Uttar Pradesh Directorate of Economic and Statistics (UPDES). Important Data and Analysis Dashboards, Government of Uttar Pradesh. Retrieved from <https://updes.up.nic.in/>
- Uttar Pradesh State Water Policy- 2020 Draft (2020). Uttar Pradesh Water Management & Regulatory Commission (UPWaMReC). Food and Agriculture Organization. Retrieved from <https://faolex.fao.org/docs/pdf/ind214018.pdf>
- Wildlife Institute of India Uttar Pradesh. (n.d.). Wildlife Institute of India, An Autonomous Institution of the Ministry of Environment, Forest, and Climate Change, Government of India. <https://wii.gov.in/>
- Wisner, B. (2013). Assessment of capability and vulnerability. In *Mapping vulnerability* (pp. 183-193). Routledge.
- Yadav, D. S., & Chauhan, G.S., (2020). Water resource scarcity and its impact on masses in Bundelkhand region: A case study of Mahoba district (U.P.), India, *Journal of Global Resources*. 6 (01), August 2019- January 2020, pp. 31-37.

CHAPTER – 3

- Aggarwal, P. K. (2008). Global climate change and Indian agriculture: impacts, adaptation and mitigation. *Indian Journal of Agricultural Sciences*, 78(11), 911.
- Arent, D. J., Tol, R. S., Faust, E., Hella, J. P., Kumar, S., Strzepek, K. M., ... & Ngeh, J. (2015). Key economic sectors and services. In *Climate change 2014 impacts, adaptation and vulnerability: Part a: Global and sectoral aspects* (pp. 659-708). Cambridge University Press.
- Baer, H.A. (2021). *Global Capitalism and Climate Change: The Need for an Alternative World System* (2nd Ed.). Lexington Books.

- BEE (Bureau of Energy Efficiency) (n.d.). National Mission for Enhanced Energy Efficiency, Bureau of Energy Efficiency, Ministry of Power, Government of India, New Delhi. <https://beeindia.gov.in/en/programmes/nmeee>
- Bie, Z., (2023). October 24, 2023. Charting a Climate-Resilient Future: The New Delhi Summit's Commitments and Global Unity, G 20 Research Group, University of Toronto. <https://g20.utoronto.ca/analysis/231024-bie.html#top>
- Brundtland, G. H. (1987). *Our common future* world commission on environment and development.
- Carson, R. (1962). *Silent Spring*. Houghton Mifflin Harcourt.
- CDRI (Coalition for Disaster Resilient Infrastructure) (n.d.). [cdri.world](https://www.cdri.world/), Copernicus Marg, New Delhi, <https://www.cdri.world/>
- Delbeke, J., Runge-Metzger, A., Slingenberg, Y., & Werksman, J. (2019). The Paris Agreement. In *Towards a climate-neutral Europe* (pp. 24-45). Routledge.
- Dev, T., & Goswami, A., (2024) 16-30 September, 2024. *Trade On Emission, Down to Earth*, New Delhi.
- DST (Department of Science & Technology) (2010a). National Mission for Sustaining The Himalayan Ecosystem Under National Action Plan on Climate Change, DST, Ministry of Science & Technology, Government of India, New Delhi. https://dst.gov.in/sites/default/files/NMSHE_Mission_document.pdf
- DST (Department of Science & Technology) (2010b). National Mission on Strategic Knowledge for Climate Change Under National Action Plan on Climate Change, DST, Ministry of Science & Technology, Government of India, New Delhi. https://dst.gov.in/sites/default/files/NMSKCC_mission%20document%201.pdf
- European Commission (n.d.), The European Green Deal: Striving to be the first climate-neutral continent. https://commission.europa.eu/strategy-and-policy/priorities-2019-2024/european-green-deal_en
- Government of India (2008). National Action Plan on Climate Change (NAPCC), *PM's Council on Climate Change*, New Delhi
- Grubb, M., Vrolijk, C., & Brack, D. (1999). *The Kyoto Protocol: A Guide and Assessment*. Earthscan.

- Heynen, N., Perkins, H. A., & Roy, P. (2006). The political ecology of uneven urban green space: The impact of political economy on race and ethnicity in producing environmental inequality in Milwaukee. *Urban Affairs Review*, 42(1), 3-25.
- INDC (2022). India's Intended Nationally Determined Contribution: Working towards Climate Justice, Ministry of Environment, Forest and Climate Change, Government of India. Retrieved from <https://unfccc.int/sites/default/files/NDC/2022-06/INDIA%20INDC%20TO%20UNFCCC.pdf>
- Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC). (2023). Climate Change 2022- Impacts, Adaptation and Vulnerability: *Working Group II Contribution to the Sixth Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (1st ed.)*. Cambridge University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1017/9781009325844>
- International Energy Agency (IEA). (2023). World Energy Outlook 2023. IEA, Retrieved from <https://www.iea.org/reports/world-energy-outlook-2023>
- IPCC. (2021). Summary for Policymakers. In: *Climate Change 2021: The Physical Science Basis. Contribution of Working Group I to the Sixth Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change* [Masson-Delmotte, V., P. Zhai, A. Pirani, S.L. Connors, C. Péan, S. Berger, N. Caud, Y. Chen, L. Goldfarb, M.I. Gomis, M. Huang, K. Leitzell, E. Lonnoy, J.B.R. Matthews, T.K. Maycock, T. Waterfield, O. Yelekçi, R. Yu, and B. Zhou (eds.)]. Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, United Kingdom and New York, NY, USA, pp. 3–32, doi:10.1017/9781009157896.001.
- IPCC. (2013). *Climate Change 2013: The Physical Science Basis. Contribution of Working Group I to the Fifth Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change* [Stocker, T.F., D. Qin, G.-K. Plattner, M. Tignor, S.K. Allen, J. Boschung, A. Nauels, Y. Xia, V. Bex and P.M. Midgley (eds.)]. Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, United Kingdom and New York, NY, USA, 1535 pp.
- IPCC. (2014). *Climate Change 2014: Synthesis Report. Contribution of Working Groups I, II and III to the Fifth Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change* [Core Writing Team, R.K. Pachauri and L.A. Meyer (eds.)]. IPCC, Geneva, Switzerland,

- ISA (International Solar Alliance) (n.d.). About ISA, <https://isolaralliance.org/about/background>
- JJM (Jal Jeevan Mission- Har Ghar Jal), (2024). Dashboard, Jal Jeevan Mission, Ministry of Jal Shakti, GoI, <https://ejalshakti.gov.in/jjmreport/JJMIndia.aspx>
- Kabir, E., Kumar, P., Kumar, S., Adelodun, A. A., & Kim, K. H. (2018). Solar energy: Potential and future prospects. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, 82, 894-900. Elsevier.
- Kumar, G., Kumari, R., Kishore, B.S.P.C., Saikia, P., Kumar, A., Khan, M.L. (2020). Climate Change Impacts and Implications: An Indian Perspective. In: Roy, N., Roychoudhury, S., Nautiyal, S., Agarwal, S., Baksi, S. (eds) Socio-economic and Eco-biological Dimensions in Resource Use and Conservation. Environmental Science and Engineering. Springer, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-32463-6_2
- Leadit (Leadership Group for Industry Transition) (n.d.), <https://www.industrytransition.org/>
- Mann, M. (2021). *The New Climate War*, Public Affairs Hachette Book Group. New York
- McKinsey Global Institute, (2020). ‘Will India get too hot to work?’, November 25, 2020. McKinsey & Company. <https://www.mckinsey.com/capabilities/sustainability/our-insights/will-india-get-too-hot-to-work>
- Ministry of Home Affairs (MHA) & United Nations Development Programme (UNDP). (2019). *Disaster Score Card for States and Union Territories of India (vol I)*. New Delhi. 2018. Retrieved from <https://ndmindia.mha.gov.in/ndmi/viewUploadedDocument?uid=I103>
- MNRE (Ministry of New and Renewable Energy). National Green Hydrogen Mission. MNRE, Government of India, New Delhi <https://mnre.gov.in/national-green-hydrogen-mission/>
- MoAFW. (2020). *DEMANDS FOR GRANTS (2020-2021)*. New Delhi: Department of Agriculture, Co-operation and Farmers Welfare, Ministry of Agriculture and Farmers Welfare

- MoEA (Ministry of External Affairs) (2023). G-20 New Delhi Leaders' Declaration, 9-10 September, 2023. New Delhi, India. <https://www.mea.gov.in/Images/CPV/G20-New-Delhi-Leaders-Declaration.pdf>
- MoEA. (Ministry of External Affairs) (2021). Address by Prime Minister at the Leaders' Summit on Climate 2021. Ministry of External Affairs, Government of India. https://mea.gov.in/Speeches-Statements.htm?dtl/33820/Address_by_Prime_Minister_at_the_Leaders_Summit_on_Climate_2021
- MoEFCC. (2022). India's long-term low-carbon development strategy. Ministry of Environment, Forest and Climate Change, Government of India. <https://moef.gov.in/uploads/2022/11/Indias-LT-LEDS.pdf>
- MoHUA (Ministry of Housing and Urban Affairs) (n.d.). Schemes/Programme, *Atal Mission for Rejuvenation and Urban Transformation- AMRUT*, MoHUA, GoI, <https://mohua.gov.in/cms/amrut.php>
- MoHUA (Ministry of Housing and Urban Affairs) (n.d.). Schemes/Programme, *Smart Cities*, MoHUA, GoI, New Delhi. <https://mohua.gov.in/cms/smart-cities.php>
- MoPNG (Ministry of Petroleum and Natural Gas) (n.d.). About Global Biofuels Alliance (GBA) "New Phase of Leadership on Energy Transition." <https://mopng.gov.in/en/page/68>
- Murphy-Greene, C. (2022). *Environmental Justice and Resiliency in An Age of Uncertainty* (1st ed.). Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781003186076>
- NAPCC (National Action Plan on Climate Change) (2008), Prime Minister's Council for Climate Change, Government of India, New Delhi. https://archivepmo.nic.in/drmanmohansingh/climate_change_english.pdf
- Narain, S. (2015) 'Sunita Narain Analyses the Paris Agreement' Down to Earth, <https://www.downtoearth.org.in/climate-change/sunita-narain-analyses-the-paris-agreement-52129>
- NITI Ayog (2022). Mission LiFE, Lifestyle for Environment: An India-led global mass movement to nudge individual and community action to protect and preserve the environment. National Institution for Transforming India Ayog

- (NITI Ayog), New Delhi. https://www.niti.gov.in/sites/default/files/2022-11/Mission_LiFE_Brochure.pdf
- NMSA (National Mission for Sustainable Agriculture) (2014). National Mission for Sustainable Agriculture Operational Guidelines, Department of Agriculture & Cooperation, Ministry of Agriculture, Government of India, New Delhi. https://mpkrishi.mp.gov.in/hindisite_New/pdfs/NMSA.pdf
 - NMSH (National Mission on Sustainable Habitat 2021-2030) (2021). Ministry of Housing and Urban Affairs, Government of India, New Delhi. <https://mohua.gov.in/upload/uploadfiles/files/NMSH-2021.pdf>
 - NWM (National Water Mission), (n.d.). *Objective of National Water Mission*, National Water Mission, Ministry of Jal Shakti, Department of Water Resources, River Development & Ganga Rejuvenation, Government of India, New Delhi. <https://nwm.gov.in/objective-national-water-mission>
 - Pettifor, A., (2022). The Green New Deal, Climate Breakdown, and Power. In Tienhaara, K. & Robinson, J. (eds.) *Routledge Handbook on the Green New Deal*, Routledge Taylor & Francis Group.
 - PIB (Press Information Bureau, Government of India, (2021). 01 Nov. 2021, National Statement by Prime Minister Shri Narendra Modi at COP26 Summit in Glasgow, New Delhi <https://pib.gov.in/PressReleaseDetail.aspx?PRID=1768712®=3&lang=1>
 - PM Surya Ghar (n.d.). PM Surya Ghar: Muft Bijli Yojna, Government of India. <https://pmsuryaghar.org.in/>
 - Press Information Bureau. (2021, March 23). Automatic Weather Stations. Retrieved from Press Information Bureau, Government of India: <https://www.pib.gov.in/PressReleaseDetail.aspx?PRID=1706937>
 - Prime Minister Office (PMO). (2008). National Action Plan on Climate Change (NAPCC). Prime Minister's Council on Climate Change, Government of India. Retrieved from https://archivepmo.nic.in/drmanmohansingh/climate_change_english.pdf
 - Protocol, M. (1987). Montreal protocol on substances that deplete the ozone layer. *Washington, DC: US Government Printing Office*, 26, 128-136.

- Rosencranz, A., & Jamwal, K. (2021). Common but differentiated responsibilities and respective capabilities: did this principle ever exist? *Environmental Policy and Law*, 50(4-5), 291-297. DOI 10.3233/EPL-200231
- Sablok, A. (2023, September 14). Examining the Role of The Coalition for Disaster Resilient Infrastructure (CDRI). Indian Council of World Affairs Sapru House, New Delhi. Retrieved from https://www.icwa.in/show_content.php?lang=1&level=3&ls_id=9924&lid=6344
- Seyfang, G. (2003). Environmental mega-conferences—from Stockholm to Johannesburg and beyond. *Global Environmental Change*, 13(3), 223-228.
- Sharma, J., Upgupta, S., Jayaraman, M., Chaturvedi, R. K., Bala, G., & Ravindranath, N. H. (2017). Vulnerability of forests in India: a national scale assessment. *Environmental management*, 60, 544-553. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00267-017-0894-4>
- Singh, N., Singh, S., & Mall, R. K. (2020). Urban ecology and human health: implications of urban heat island, air pollution, and climate change nexus. In *Urban Ecology* (pp. 317-334). Elsevier.
- Smart Cities (n.d.). Vision of Smart Cities Mission, Ministry of Housing and Urban Affairs, GoI, New Delhi. <https://smartcities.gov.in/>
- Spangenberg, J. H., Pfahl, S., & Deller, K. (2002). Towards indicators for institutional sustainability: lessons from an analysis of Agenda 21. *Ecological indicators*, 2(1-2), 61-77. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S1470-160X\(02\)00050-X](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1470-160X(02)00050-X)
- Subramanian, N., Nilsson, U., Mossberg, M., & Bergh, J. (2019). Impacts of climate change, weather extremes and alternative strategies in managed forests. *Ecoscience*, 26(1), 53-70. Elsevier.
- Sullivan, E. T. (1972). The Stockholm conference: A step toward global environmental cooperation and involvement. *Ind. L. Rev.*, 6, 267.
- Sushmita (2024). What's missing from India's climate action plans? IDR (India Development Review), July 16, 2024. <https://idronline.org/article/climate-emergency/whats-missing-from-indias-climate-action-plans/>

- Swachh Bharat Mission-Grameen (n.d.). Swachh Bharat Mission: Driving India's Sanitation Renaissance, SBM-G, Department of Drinking Water & Sanitation, Ministry of Jal Shakti, GoI, <https://swachhbharatmission.ddws.gov.in/>
- Turner, S. W., Hejazi, M., Kim, S. H., Clarke, L., & Edmonds, J. (2017). Climate impacts on hydropower and consequences for global electricity supply investment needs. *Energy*, *141*, 2081-2090. Elsevier.
- UNCED (United Nations Conference on Environment and Development) (1992). <https://sdgs.un.org/publications/agenda21>
- UNCHE (United Nations Conference on Human Environment). (1972), 5-16 June 1972, Stockholm. <https://www.un.org/en/conferences/environment/stockholm1972>
- UNEP (2020). 16 Ways to Take Action on Climate, 10 Oct. 2020. United Nations Environment Programme. <https://www.unep.org/news-and-stories/story/16-ways-take-action-climate>
- UNEP (United Nations Environment Programme) (2016), *Frontiers 2016: Emerging Issues of Environmental Concern*, UNEP, Nairobi. <https://www.unep.org/resources/frontiers-2016-emerging-issues-environmental-concern>
- United Nations Climate Change (UN Climate Change) (n.d.), The UNFCCC secretariat, United Nations, <https://unfccc.int/about-us/about-the-secretariat>
- United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP). (1972). *The Stockholm Declaration and the Action Plan for the Human Environment*. <https://www.un.org/en/conferences/environment/stockholm1972>
- United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP). (1972). *The Stockholm Declaration and the Action Plan for the Human Environment*. <https://www.un.org/en/conferences/environment/stockholm1972>
- United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP). (2020). *About UNEP*. <https://www.unep.org/>
- United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (adopted 9 May 1992, entered into force 21 March 1994) 32 ILM 849 (1992) (UNFCCC), art. 3(1).

- UP State Water Policy (2020). Uttar Pradesh Water Management & Regulatory Commission (UP WaMReC), Government of Uttar Pradesh. <https://faolex.fao.org/docs/pdf/ind214018.pdf>
- Uttar Pradesh Bio-Energy Policy (2022), Invest UP, Government of Uttar Pradesh, https://invest.up.gov.in/wp-content/uploads/2022/11/State-Bio-Energy-Policy-2022English_101122.pdf
- Uttar Pradesh Hydrogen Policy (2024), Uttar Pradesh New and Renewable Energy Development Agency (UPNEDA), Government of Uttar Pradesh, <https://www.upneda.org.in/MediaGallery/GreenHPolicyEng.pdf>
- Uttar Pradesh Solar Energy Policy (2022), Uttar Pradesh New and Renewable Energy Development Agency (UPNEDA), Government of Uttar Pradesh, https://upneda.org.in/MediaGallery/Uttar_Pradesh_Solar_Energy_Policy2022_English_.pdf
- Velders, G. J., Andersen, S. O., Daniel, J. S., Fahey, D. W., & McFarland, M. (2007). The importance of the Montreal Protocol in protecting climate. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 104(12), 4814-4819. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.0610328104>
- Wall, D. (2010). *The Rise of the Green Left: Inside the Worldwide Ecosocialist Movement*. Pluto Press, London.
- Wall, D. (2010). *The Rise of the Green Left: Inside the Worldwide Ecosocialist Movement*. Pluto Press.
- World Commission on Environment and Development (WCED). (1987). *Our Common Future*. <https://www.un.org/en/academic-impact/sustainability>
- WRI (World Resources Institute) (2023), March 20, 2023. 10 Big Findings from the 2023 IPCC Report on Climate Change, <https://www.wri.org/insights/2023-ipcc-ar6-synthesis-report-climate-change-findings>

CHAPTER – 4

- Agyeman, J., Bullard, R. D., & Evans, B. (Eds.). (2003). *Just sustainabilities: Development in an unequal world*. MIT Press.

- Article 4.2 of UNFCCC (1992). United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change. United Nations, New York. https://unfccc.int/files/essential_background/background_publications_htmlpdf/application/pdf/conveng.pdf
- Baxter, B. (2005). *A Theory of ecological justice*. Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9780203458495>
- Biesta, A. (2007). Good environmental governance. *Ecological Economics* 61(4), 724-732.
- Bookchin, M. (1982). 2006. The Ecology of Freedom. *The Emergence And Dissolution Of Hierarchy*. A K Press.
- Brandstedt, E. (2017). The savings problem in the original position: assessing and revising a model. *Canadian Journal of Philosophy*, 47(2-3), 269-289. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00455091.2016.1250202>
- Bryant, B. (1995). *Environmental justice: Issues, policies, and solutions*. Island Press.
- Bullard R. D. (1993). *Confronting environmental racism: Voices from the Grassroots* (Boston: South End Press).
- Bullard, R. D. (1983). *Solid waste sites and the black Houston community*. *Sociological Inquiry*, 53(2 - 3), 273-288. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1475-682X.1983.tb00037.x>
- Bullard, R. D. (2000). *Dumping in Dixie: Race, class, and environmental quality* (2nd ed.). Verso Press.
- Caney, S. (2005). Cosmopolitan justice, responsibility, and global climate change. *Leiden Journal of International Law*, 18, 747-775. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0922156505002992>
- Caney, S. (2010). Climate change and duties of the advantaged. *Critical Review of International Social and Political Philosophy*, 13(1), 203-228.
- Caney, S. (2016). *The Struggle for climate justice in a non-ideal world*. Midwest Studies in Philosophy, volume XL 'Ethics and Global Climate Change' <https://philpapers.org/archive/CANTSF-2.pdf>
- Canfield, J. V. (2013). *The Justice of saving our world: Rawlsian theory applied to environmentalism and alternative energy*. Pepperdine University School of Law, Legal Studies Research Paper No. 2013-21.

- Day, R. (2018). A Capabilities Approach to Environmental Justice, in R. Holifield, J. Chakraborty, & G. Walker, (Eds.). *The Routledge Handbook of Environmental Justice* (pp. 126-135). Routledge, Taylor & Francis Group.
- Deneulin, S., & Shahani, L. (Eds.). (2009). *An introduction to the human development and capability approach: Freedom and agency*. Earthscan.
- Dobson, A. (1998). *Justice and the environment: Conceptions of environmental sustainability and theories of distributive justice*. Clarendon Press.
- Dobson, A. (2007). *Green political thought* (4th edition). Routledge, Taylor & Francis Group.
- Dryzek, J. S. (2013). *The politics of the earth: Environmental discourses* (Third edition). Oxford University Press.
- Eckersley R. (1992). *Environmentalism & political theory: Toward an ecocentric approach*. Routledge, <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781315072111>
- Eckersley, R. (2016). Responsibility for climate change as a structural injustice. in T. Garbrielson et al. (ed.) “*The Oxford Handbook of Environmental Political Theory*”. Oxford University Press, London, UK. pp. 346-361.
- Edwards, B. (1995), With liberty and environmental justice for all: The emergence and challenge of grassroots environmentalism in the United States. In B. Taylor (ed.) *Ecological Resistance Movements: The Global Emergence of Radical and Popular Environmentalism*, New York Suny Press.
- EPA (Environmental Protection Agency) (2019) About Environmental Justice. Retrieved From <https://www.epa.gov/environmentaljustice/about-environmental-justice>
- Fraser, N. (2000). Rethinking recognition. *New Left Review*, 3, 107.
- Fraser, N. (2008). Social justice in the age of identity politics: Redistribution, recognition, and participation. In *Geographic thought* (pp. 72-89). Routledge.
- Fraser, N. (2009). Feminism, capitalism and the cunning of history. *New Left Review*, 56(March-April), 97-117.
- Gajevic Sayegh, A. (2018). Justice in a non-ideal world: the case of climate change. *Critical review of international social and political philosophy*, 21(4), 407-432. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13698230.2016.1144367>

- Gardiner, S. M. (2011). *A perfect moral storm: The ethical tragedy of climate change*. Oxford University Press.
- Gumbs, A. P. (2016). *Undrowned: Black feminist lessons on organizing for liberation*. MIT Press.
- Gupta, A. (2008). Marxism, social movements, and environmental politics: is there space for green politics? *Organization & Environment*, 21 (4), 390-410.
- Harris, P. (2009). *World Ethics and climate change: From international to global justice*, Edinburgh University Press.
- Holifield, R., Chakraborty, J., & Walker, G. (Eds.). (2018). *The Routledge Handbook of Environmental Justice* (pp. 1-11). Routledge, Taylor & Francis Group.
- Holland, A. (2012). Environmental justice and capabilities: Exploring a new direction. *Environmental Justice*, 5(3), 149-155.
- Hunold, C., & Young, R. (1994). *The role of risk assessment in environmental policy and litigation*. *Yale Journal on Regulation*, 11(1), 107-145.
- Jamieson, D. (2014). *Reason in a dark time: Why the struggle against climate change failed—and what it means for our future*. Oxford University Press.
- Kenchan, S., & Katz, C. (Eds.). (2021). *Principles of justice and real-world climate politics*. Rowman & Littlefield Press.
- Krimsky, S. (2003). *Science and globalization: Rhetoric and reality*. Lanham, MD, Lexington Books.
- Lavelle, M., & Coyle, M. (1992). The federal government, in its cleanup of hazardous sites and its pursuit of polluters, favors white communities over minority communities under environmental laws meant to provide equal protection for all citizens. *National Law Journal*, 15(3). <https://environmentaljusticebook.org/wp-content/uploads/2020/10/unequal-protection-nlj-1992.pdf>
- Maltais, A. (2016). A climate of disorder: what to do about the obstacles to effective climate politics. In: C. Heyward and D. Roser, (eds.) *Climate justice in a non-ideal world*, 43(6), Oxford University Press,
- Martinez-Alier, J., & Röpke, I. (Eds.) (2008). *Recent Developments in Ecological Economics*. Edward Elgar Publishing.

- McGregor, D., Whitaker, S., & Sritharan, M. (2020). Indigenous environmental justice and sustainability. *Current Opinion in Environmental Sustainability*, 43, 35-40. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cosust.2020.01.007>
- Melosi, M. V. (2004). *Garbage in the cities: Refuse reform and the environment*. University of Pittsburgh Press.
- Meyer, A. (2000). *Contraction and convergence: The global solution to climate change*, Green Books.
- Meyer, L. H., & Roser, D. (2010). Climate justice and historical emissions. *Critical Review of International Social and Political Philosophy*, 13(1), 229-253
- Moellendorf, D. (2016). Taking UNFCCC norms seriously. In C. Heyward and D. Roser (eds.) *Climate justice in a non-ideal world*. Oxford: Oxford University Press, 104–121.
- Mohai P., Saha, R. (2015). Which came first, race or place? Examining environmental justice from an intersectional perspective. *Social Science Research*, 51, 34-47.
- Morris, A. (2008). The problem of administrative justice. *Hastings Law Journal*, 60(1) 41.
- Naess, A. (1973). The shallow and the deep, long-range ecology movement. A summary. *Inquiry: An Interdisciplinary Journal of Philosophy*, 16 (1-4), 95 – 100.
- Naess, A. (1995). The Shallow and the Deep, Long-Range Ecology Movement: A Summary. In A. Drengson and Y. Inoue, *The Deep Ecology Movement: An Introductory Anthology*, (pp.3-8). North Atlantic Book.
- Nussbaum, M. & A. Sen (Eds.), (1993). *The Quality of Life*. Oxford, Clarendon Press.
- Nussbaum, M. C. (2000). *Women and human development: The capabilities approach*. Cambridge University Press.
- Nussbaum, M.C. (2011). *Creating capabilities: The human development approach*. Harvard University Press.
- Page, E. (2012). Give it up for climate change: A Defence of the beneficiary pays principle. *International Theory*, 4(2), 300-330.

- Parks, B. C., & Roberts, J. T. (2010). Climate change, social theory and justice. *Theory, Culture & Society*, 27(2-3), 134-166. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0263276409359018>
- Pellow, D. N., & Park, L. K. (2002). *The Silicon valley of dreams: Environmental justice, housing policy, and sustainable development*, Oxford University Press.
- Pezzullo, P. C. (2021). Environmental justice and climate justice, in M. Grasso, & M. Giugni, (eds.). *The Routledge Handbook of Environmental Movement (1st ed.)* Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9780367855680>
- Pickering, J., & Barry, C. (2017). On the concept of climate debt: Its moral and political value. In *Global political justice* (pp. 147-165). Routledge.
- Powers, M., & Faden, R. R. (2006). *Social justice: The moral foundations of public health and health policy*. Oxford University Press, USA.
- Pulido, L. (1996). *Environmentalism and economic justice: Two Chicano struggles in the Southwest*. University of Arizona Press.
- Pulido, L. (2003). Environmental racism. *Annual Review of Sociology*, 29(1), 261-279.
- Rawls, J. (1971). *A theory of justice*. Harvard University Press.
- Robyns, I. (2005). The capability approach: a theoretical survey. *Journal of Human Development*, 6(1), 93-117. <https://doi.org/10.1080/146498805200034266>
- Roser, D. (2016). Reducing injustice within the bounds of motivation. In C. Heyward and D. Roser, (eds.). *Climate justice in a non-ideal world*. Oxford University Press, 83–103.
- Schlosberg D., & Carruthers D.V. (2010). Indigenous Struggles, Environmental Justice, and Community Capabilities. *Global Environmental Politics*, 10(4), 12-35.
- Schlosberg, D. (2007). Defining environmental justice: Theories, movements, and nature. *Environmental Politics*, 16(3), 377-398. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/263529056_Defining_Environmental_Justice_Theories_Movements_and_Nature_-_by_David_Schlosberg
- Schlosberg, D. (2009). Capacity and capabilities: A response to the greenhouse development rights framework. *Ethics Place and Environment*, 12(3), 287-290.

- Schlosberg, D. (2013). Theorising environmental justice: the expanding sphere of a discourse. *Environmental politics*, 22(1), 37-55. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09644016.2013.755387>
- Schlosberg, D. (2007). *Defining environmental justice: Theories, movements, and nature*. Oxford University Press.
- Sen, A. (1992). 1995. *Inequality Re-examined*. Harvard University Press.
- Sen, A. (2009). *On justice*. Oxford University Press.
- Sen, A. (1999). *Development as Freedom*. Oxford University Press.
- Shiva, V. (2015). *Earth democracy: Justice, sustainability, and peace*. North Atlantic Books.
- Shrader-Frechette, K. (2002). *Environmental justice: Creating equality, reclaiming democracy*. Oxford University Press.
- Shue, H. (1993). Subsistence emissions and luxury emissions. *Law & Policy*, 15(1), 39-60. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-9930.1993.tb00093.x>
- Shue, H. (1999). Global environment and international inequality. *International affairs*, 75(3), 531-545. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1468-2346.00092>
- Simmons, I. G. (2008). *Global environmental history: 10,000 BC to AD 2000*. Edinburgh University Press.
- Singer, P. (2002). One Atmosphere. In P. Singer, *One World: The Ethics of Globalization*. Yale University Press.
- USGAO (1983, June 01). US General Accounting Office Siting of Hazardous Waste Landfills and Their Correlation with Racial and Economic Status of Surrounding Communities, RCED-83-168. <https://www.gao.gov/assets/rced-83-168.pdf>
- Vanderheiden, S. (Ed.). (2008). *Political theory and global climate change*. MIT Press.
- Vanderheiden, S. (2008). *Atmospheric Justice: A Political Theory of climate change*, Oxford University Press.
- Vanderheiden, S. (2011). Globalisation Responsibility for Climate Change” *Ethics and International Affairs* 25(1): 65-84.

- Vanderheiden, Steve, (2016) ‘Environmental and Climate Justice’ in T. Gabrielson et al. (eds.) “*The Oxford Handbook of Environmental Political Theory*”. Oxford University Press, pp. 321-332
- Walker, M. (2006). Towards a capability - based theory of social justice for education policy - making. *Journal of Education Policy*, 21(2), 163–185. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02680930500500245>
- Young, I. M. (1990). 2011. *Justice & the Politics of Difference*. Princeton University Press. Princeton and Oxford.

CHAPTER – 5

- Acharuparambil, D. S. F. (2021). Insurance Cover Among SC/ST Community as Compared to General Community of Rural Population. Accessed from MPRA_paper_110431.pdf
- Chakravarty, P., & Gattupalli, S. (2024). Integration of Indigenous Traditional Knowledge and AI in Hurricane Resilience and Adaptation. In *Advances in Hurricane Risk in a Changing Climate* (pp. 125-158). Cham: Springer Nature Switzerland.
- Choudhury, M. U. I., Haque, C. E., Nishat, A., & Byrne, S. (2021). Social learning for building community resilience to cyclones: role of indigenous and local knowledge, power, and institutions in coastal Bangladesh. *Ecology & Society*, 26(1).
- Dehury, R. K., & DeHuRy, P. (2017). A Review of Measures against Increasing Temperature and Climate Change for the Safeguard of Workers in India. *Journal of Clinical & Diagnostic Research*, 11(10).
- Devkota, R. (2013). Indigenous knowledge for climate change induced flood adaptation in Nepal. *The International Journal of Climate Change: Impacts and Responses*, 5(1), 35.
- Down To Earth. (2022a, July 21). UP headed towards drought? Less than normal rainfall in 96% districts accessed from <https://www.downtoearth.org/in/agriculture/up-headed-towards-drought-less-than-normal-rainfall-in-96-districts-83838>

- Down To Earth. (2022b, Oct 11). North India rains: Crops ruined in Uttar Pradesh; over half a million affected by floods. accessed from <https://www.downtoearth.org.in/climate-change/north-india-rains-crops-ruined-in-uttar-pradesh-over-half-a-million-affected-by-floods-85403>
- Down To Earth. (2022c, September 07). Declare lumpy skin an epidemic, say Uttar Pradesh cattle owners; seek aid. Accessed from <https://www.downtoearth.org.in/wildlife-biodiversity/declare-lumpy-skin-an-epidemic-say-uttar-pradesh-cattle-owners-seek-aid-84778>
- Down to Earth. (2024a, Dec 31). 94% Indian youth feel impacted by climate change: Survey accessed from <https://www.downtoearth.org.in/climate-change/94-indian-youth-feels-impacted-by-climate-change-survey>
- Down To Earth. (2024b, Dec 31). India suffered record breaking health impacts due to climate change during last decade: Lancet report accessed from <https://www.downtoearth.org.in/climate-change/india-suffered-record-breaking-health-impacts-due-to-climate-change-during-last-decade-lancet-report>
- Imdad, K., Sahana, M., Krishnan, A., Das, U., & Mall, B. (2024). District Wise Heat Wave Threshold Determination for Uttar Pradesh. *Uttar Pradesh State Disaster Management Authority, Government of Uttar Pradesh*.
- Jatav, S. S. (2024). Farmers' perception of climate change and livelihood vulnerability: a comparative study of Bundelkhand and Central regions of Uttar Pradesh, India. *Discover Sustainability*, 5(1), 11.
- Malik, B. B. (2019). Poverty of social construction and landlessness: dignity for Dalits in eastern Uttar Pradesh. *Contemporary Voice of Dalit*, 11(2), 150-171.
- Mukhtar, Y., Shankar, U., & Wazir, Z. A. (2023). Prospects and challenges of emerging insect pest problems vis-à-vis climate change. *Indian Journal of Ecology*, 50(4), 1096-1103.
- NAPCC (2008). National Action Plan on Climate Change (NAPCC), *PM's Council on Climate Change*, Government of India, New Delhi
https://moef.gov.in/uploads/2017/09/SAPCC_UP_final_version_0.pdf
https://upccce.org/public/UPLOADS/REPOSITORY/DOC/27_stateactionplan.pdf

- Romanello, M., Walawender, M., Hsu, S. C., Moskeland, A., Palmeiro-Silva, Y., Scamman, D., ... & Costello, A. (2024). The 2024 report of the Lancet Countdown on health and climate change: facing record-breaking threats from delayed action. *The Lancet*, 404(10465), 1847-1896.
- Singh, Pragati & Yadav, Karuna & Upadhyay, Rajesh. (2018). Impact of Climate Change on Tendu Leaves Production of Sonbhadra abstract.
- The Business Standard (2024, Oct 31). India to Face 24.7% GDP loss by 2070 due to climate change: ADG report, Economy & Policy News, New Delhi. Accessed from https://www.businessstandard.com/economy/news/india-to-face-24-7-gdp-loss-by-2070-due-to-climate-change-adb-report-124103100902_1.html
- The Hindu (2016, March 24). Double Whammy for debt-hit U. P. Farmers. Bundelkhand. Accessed from <https://www.thehindu.com/news/national/other-states/double-whammy-for-debthit-up-farmers/article7937827.ece>
- The Hindustan (2020, August 18). 25 Villages surrounded by flood water, woes remain intact, accessed from <https://www.livehindustan.com/uttar-pradesh/bahraich/story-bahraich-25-villages-surrounded-by-flood-waters-woes-remain-intact-3427947.html>
- The Hindustan (2025, May 17). Heat wave causes surge in heat stroke patients in Bahraich. Accessed from <https://www.livehindustan.com/uttar-pradesh/bahraich/story-heatwave-causes-surge-in-heat-stroke-patients-in-bahraich-201747504587125.html>
- Tripathi, A. (2013). Farmers' vulnerability to climate change in Uttar Pradesh, India: measurement and correlates. *Institute of Economic Growth, New Delhi*. Retrieved from www.ecoinse.org/lib_docs.
- UNEP. 2023. *Adaptation Gap Report 2023: Underfinanced. Underprepared. Inadequate Investment and Planning on Climate Adaptation Leaves World Exposed*. Nairobi: UNEP.
- UP SAPCC 1.0 (2014). Uttar Pradesh State Action Plan on Climate Change. Department of Environment, Forest, and Climate Change, Government of Uttar Pradesh. Retrieved from

- UP SAPCC 2.0 (2023). Uttar Pradesh State Action Plan on Climate Change 2021-2030. Department of Environment, Forest, and Climate Change, Government of Uttar Pradesh. Retrieved from
- Zagma, B., J. Kowalzig, L. Walsh, A. Hattle, C. Roy, and H.P. Dejgaard. 2023. *Climate Finance Shadow Report 2023: Assessing the Delivery of the \$100 Billion Commitment*. Oxfam International

Uttar Pradesh Climate Change Action Plan and Environmental Action Research

Questionnaire/Schedule

(Solely for Academic purpose)

Village/city	Block	District
Personal background		
Q.1.1 Name	Q. 1.2 Father/Husband's Name	
Q.1.3 Age	Q.1.4 Gender- Female (), Male (), Other ()	
Q.1.5 Caste	Q.1.6 Category- General/OBC/SC/ST	
Q.1.7 Religion-		
Hindu ()	Muslim ()	Sikh ()
Christian ()	Others ()	
Q.1.8 Qualifications-		
Uneducated (),	Class 1-5(),	Class 5-10 (),
Graduate (),	Post-Graduate ()	Class 11-12 ()
Q.1.9 Occupation-		
Agriculture ()	Labour ()	Shopkeeper ()
Businessman ()	Private Job in Organised sector()	Private Job in unorganised sector ()
Govt. Job()	Unemployed ()	Student ()
Home-maker ()		
Q.2.1 Type of family –		
Single ()	Joint ()	Other ()
Q.2.2 Type of accommodation-		
kaccha ()	pakka ()	semi-pakka ()
other ()		
Q.2.3 There is a possibility of your house getting damaged due to rain, flood, storm, earthquake and natural calamities –		
Even at low intensity ()	at medium intensity ()	at a high intensity ()
can't say ()		
Q.2.4 Type of Ration card-		
B.P.L ()	A.P.L ()	Antyodaya ()
Other ()	None ()	
Q.3.1 If you, your father/mother/husband/wife own land. Then, your total land ownership is		
Less than 1 acre ()	1-5 acre ()	6-10 acre ()
more than 10 acre ()		

Q.3.2 What percentage of your total land is sown -

Q.3.3 What percentage of the total sown area is irrigated -

Q.3.4 Source of irrigation is –

Canal (), electric tube well (), diesel-powered tube well (),
pond (), other () does not belong ().

Q.4.0 Which insurance do you have to protect yourself from sudden disasters and minor accidents-

Personal Insurance (), Crop Insurance (), Livestock Insurance (), Income Insurance (), No Insurance ()

Q.5.1 Please provide your information about the words written below- Use 1-5 codes

1 - Never heard, 2 - Just heard, 3 - Know a little bit,
4 - Well known, 5 - Have specialized knowledge.

S No.	Environment related perspectives/concepts/ efforts/actions	Selected code 1-5
3.a	Climate change	
3.b	Global Warming	

Q.5.2 According to you, climate has changed in a few back years (20-30 years) like an Increase in untimely rain, flood, sudden heat, Loo, strong waves, etc-

Completely agree (), Agree (), Disagree (), Completely Disagree (), Can't say ()

Q.5.3 What is the impact of the above-mentioned changes in climate- (Rank them 1-5)

1-Critical change 2-Serious change 3-Important change
4-Moderate change 5-Irrelevant

S No.	Effect (Negative)	Tick	Rank(1-5)
5.3a	Sudden change in climate		
5.3b	Increase in frequency of drought and crop failure		
5.3c	Increase in frequency of flood and crop failure		
5.3d	Attack of pests on crop		
5.3e	Increase in the cost of agriculture/fishery/animal husbandry		

5.3f	Reduction in wages or other occupations		
5.3g	Decrease in working hours (wages/income) due to rising temperature		
5.3h	Displacement from the original village/place and moving to a new place.		

Q.5.4 How do abnormal climates like untimely rain, pre-summer season, Loo, drought flood, etc, affect production?

Less production (), Substantial reduction in production (),
 Normal production (), Increased production (),
 Can't say (), Doesn't pertain ()

Q.5.5 In the last 5 years adverse climate change has negatively affected your crop production? Yes () No ();

If yes then what's the % -

upto10% (), upto 20% (), upto50% (), upto80% (), can't say ()

Q.5.6 How do you feel about the following environmental and climate issues from the point of view of equity and justice (Please rank them 1-5)

1-Severe, 2-Important, 3-Normal, 4-Irrelevant, 5-Can't say

S No.	Key areas of environmental and climate equity and justice	Tick	Rank (1-5)
5.6a	Poisonous smoke from cars and factories of rich people effect innocent people breathing		
5.6b	Destruction of crops of poor farmers due to floods and droughts due to global warming.		

Q.6.1 The extreme weather conditions mentioned above such as heat waves, floods, cold waves, Cyclone can affect your health. (Please rank from 1-5)

1-Severe 2-Significant 3-Normal 4-Irrelevant 5-Can't say

S No.	Health Effects	Tick	Rank(1-5)
6.1a	Increase water-borne disease like cholera		
6.1b	Increase in vector-borne diseases like malaria		
6.1c	Excessive heat-related diseases increase.		

Q.6.2 How many people in your family have suffered from the diseases mentioned above in the last one year and how many times have they got ill –

Q.7.1 Have you made any changes in your way of farming or business to adapt to the changing circumstances caused by climate change e.g. adoption of climate resilient varieties of seeds and crops, mixed farming, organic farming, or changing their businesses to carbon sensitive business.??

Yes (), No (), Does not pertain ()

Q.7.2 Do you get any external assistance to deal with situations caused by climate change e.g. loan, grants, subsidies? –

Yes (), No ()

Q.7.3 Constraints for mitigation/adaptation efforts/actions to deal with conditions resulting from climate change -

Lack of capital for investment (),

Lack of coordination in government policies/practices ()

Lack of implementation of government policies/procedures ()

Lack of necessary information ()

Lack of institutional loan facilities ()

Q.8.0 According to you, the operation, conservation, and promotion of local ecological assets such as water sources, ponds, springs, and community forests are more efficient when they are owned/operated by-

The Government () Village Panchayat () Local people/Community ()

Q.9.0 In old Days, people or communities possessed traditional knowledge and traditional methods of carrying out their professional activities. The methods were like making boats during floods, water harvesting, etc. It is essential to save people and build capacity during natural disasters.

Completely agree () Partially agree () Disagree () Can't say ()

Q.10 If your economic activity or business (agriculture, animal husbandry, industry) or lifestyle is causing harm to the environment, then you may prefer to adopt environment-friendly methods/activities/lifestyle-

Yes () No ();

if yes

Yes, but don't know what to do (),

Yes, if it is cost-effective ()

Yes, even if it is costly ()

Any other information, if you want to provide-

Thanks for your kind cooperation and providing important information.

उत्तर प्रदेश जलवायु परिवर्तन कार्य योजना तथा पर्यावरण न्याय शोध हेतु

प्रश्नावली

(केवल अकादमिक उद्देश्य के लिए)

व्यक्तिगत पृष्ठभूमि

- Q.1.1 नाम- Q.1.2 पिता/पति का नाम -
- Q.1.3 उम्र- Q.1.4 लिंग - महिला, () पुरुष, () अन्य, ()
- Q.1.5 जाति- Q.1.6 वर्ग - सामान्य/ओबीसी/एससी/एसटी
- Q.1.7 धर्म- हिन्दू (), मुस्लिम (), सिख (), बौद्ध (), ईसाई (), अन्य ()
- Q.1.8 शिक्षा का स्तर - अशिक्षित (), कक्षा 1-5 (), कक्षा 6-10 (), कक्षा 11-12 (),
स्नातक (), परास्नातक (), तकनीकी/प्रॉफेशनल स्नातक ()
- Q.1.9 व्यवसाय- कृषक (), मजदूर (), दुकानदार (), व्यवसायी (), प्राइवेट
नौकरी संगठित क्षेत्र में (), प्राइवेट नौकरी असंगठित क्षेत्र में (),
सरकारी नौकरी (), बेरोजगार (),
- Q.2.1 परिवार का प्रकार - एकल (), संयुक्त (), अन्य ()
- Q.2.2 आवास का प्रकार - कच्चा (), पक्का (), अर्द्धपक्का (), अन्य ()
- Q.2.3 आपके घर (आवास) की बारिश बाढ़, तूफान, भूकंप आदि प्राकृतिक आपदाओं में दूटने (नष्ट) की
आशंका है-
- कम तीव्रता में भी (), मध्यम तीव्रता में (), अधिक तीव्रता में (),
अत्यधिक तीव्रता में (), कह नहीं सकते ()
- Q.2.4 राशन कार्ड का प्रकार - बी0 पी0 एल0 (), ए0 पी0 एल0 (), अंतयोदया (),
अन्य (), किसी प्रकार का नहीं ()
- Q.3.1 यदि आप अथवा आपके पिता जी/माताजी/पति/पत्नी भू-स्वामी हैं तो आपके परिवार के पास
कुल भूमि हैं-
- 1 एकड़ से कम (), 1-5 एकड़ (), 6-10 एकड़ (), 10 एकड़ से अधिक ()

Q.3.2 आपके पास कुल भूमि का कितने प्रतिशत बोया जाता है-

Q.3.3 कुल बोये गए क्षेत्रफल का कितने प्रतिशत सिंचित है-

Q.3.4 सिंचाई का साधन है - नहरें (), बिजली नलकूप (), डीजल चालित नलकूप (),
तालाब (), अन्य ()

Q.4.0 आपके पास आकस्मिक आपदाओं एवं दुर्घटनाओं से बचने के लिए कौन कौन से बीमा हैं?

व्यक्तिगत बीमा (), फसल बीमा (), पशुधन बीमा (), अन्य कोई बीमा (),
कोई बीमा नहीं है ()

Q.5.1 आप नीचे लिखे गए शब्दों के बारे में अपनी जानकारी दीजिए 1-5 कूट का प्रयोग करें। 1=

सुना ही नहीं, 2= केवल सुना है, 3= थोड़ा-बहुत जानता/जानती हूँ, 4=अच्छी तरह से जानता/जानती हूँ, 5= विशेष रुचि/ज्ञान है

क्रम संख्या	पर्यावरण संबंधी अवधारणा/संकल्पनाएं/प्रयास/कार्यवाही	चयनित कूट
3.a	जलवायु परिवर्तन	
3.b	वैश्विक तापन (ग्लोबल वार्मिंग)	

Q 5.2 आपके अनुसार पिछले कुछ वर्षों (लगभग 2030 वर्षों) में मौसम में परिवर्तन आया है जैसे

असमय बारिश, बाढ़, अचानक गर्मी आना, तेज बारिश, लू, शीत लहर आदि में बढ़ोतरी होना -

पूरी तरह से सहमत (), सहमत (), असहमत (), पूरी तरह से असहमत (),

कुछ कह नहीं सकते ()

Q.5.3 जलवायु में हुए उपरोक्त परिवर्तनों के परिणामस्वरूप क्या प्रभाव पड़े है (कृपया 1-5 तक रैंक दें)

रैंक: 1 = अत्यधिक गंभीर (विनाशकारी), 2 = गंभीर, 3 = महत्वपूर्ण, 4 = सामान्य, 5 =

अप्रासांगिक 6= कुछ कह नहीं सकते

क्रम संख्या	प्रभाव (नकारात्मक)	✓ चयनित कारक	रैंक (गंभीरता के क्रम में)
5.3a	मौसम में अचानक बदलाव		
5.3b	सूखा और फसल की बर्बादी बार-बार (पुनरावृत्ति) बढ़ना		

5.3C	बाढ़ में खेत और फसल की बर्बादी बार-बार (पुनरावृत्ति) बढ़ना		
5.3d	फसलों पर कीटों का आक्रमण बढ़ना		
5.3e	कृषि मछली पालन / पशुपालन की लागत में वृद्धि		
5.3f	मजदूरी अथवा अन्य वयवसाय में कमी		
5.3g	बढ़ते तापमान के कारण काम के घंटों (मजदूरी/आय) में कमी		
5.3h	अपने मूल गाँव/स्थान को छोड़कर नए स्थान पर विस्थापित होना		

Q.5.4 असामान्य मौसम जैसे असमय बारिश, जल्दी गर्मी आना, लू, सूखा, एवं बाढ़ के कारण आपके उत्पादन पर क्या प्रभाव पड़ा है?

उत्पादन कम हुआ है (), उत्पादन में काफी कमी आई है (), उत्पादन सामान्य रहा है ()
उत्पादन में बढ़ोतरी हुई है (), कुछ कह नहीं सकते (), संबंधित नहीं है () .

Q.5.5 पिछले पांच वर्षों में आपकी फसल के उत्पादन में असामान्य मौसम आपदाओं के कारण नुकसान हुआ है

हाँ (), नहीं (), यदि हाँ तो कितने प्रतिशत

10 % तक (), 20 % तक (), 50 % तक (), 80 % तक (), कुछ कह नहीं सकते ()

Q.6.1 उपरोक्त वर्णित विषम मौसम परिस्थितियों जैसे लू बाढ़, शीत लहर, तूफान आपके स्वास्थ्य को प्रभावित करते हैं। (कृपया 1-5 तक रैंक दें)

रैंक: 1 = गंभीर, 2 = महत्वपूर्ण, 3 = सामान्य, 4 = बहुत कम / अप्रासांगिक 5 = कुछ कह नहीं सकते

क्रम संख्या	स्वास्थ्य प्रभाव	✓ चयनित कारक	रैंक (गंभीरता के क्रम में)
3.6a	दूषित जल जनित बीमारियाँ बढ़ती हैं जैसे हैजा,		
3.6b	वेक्टर (मच्छर आदि) जनित बीमारियाँ बढ़ती हैं जैसे मलेरिया		
3.6c	अत्यधिक गर्मी/लू लगने संबंधी बीमारियाँ बढ़ती हैं		

Q6.2 पिछले एक वर्ष में आपके परिवार में उपरोक्त जलवायु परिवर्तन जनित रोगों से कितने लोग

कितनी बार बीमार हुए हैं-

Q7.1 जलवायु परिवर्तन से उपजी परिस्थितियों से निपटने अथवा अनुकूलन करने के लिए क्या आपने

अपने कृषि के तरीके अथवा व्यवसाय आदि में बदलाव किया है जैसे अलग अलग प्रजातियों तथा अलग अलग फसलों को बोना, मिश्रित खेती करना, जैविक खेती अपनाना, अपने व्यवसाय को दूसरे पर्यावरण - संवेदनशील व्यवसाय में बदलना, ---

हाँ (), नहीं (), संबंधित नहीं है () .

Q.7.2 क्या आपको जलवायु परिवर्तन से उपजी परिस्थितियों से निपटने के लिए किसी प्रकार की बाह्य

सहायता जैसे ऋण मिलना, अनुदान प्राप्त होना, सब्सिडी आदि प्राप्त होती है -

हाँ (), नहीं ()

Q7.3 जलवायु परिवर्तन से उपजी परिस्थितियों से निपटने के लिए न्यूनीकरण/ अनुकूलन हेतु

प्रयास/ कार्यवाही में बाधक तत्व -

निवेश के लिए पूंजी की कमी ()

सरकारी नीतियों/ प्रयासों में समन्वय की कमी ()

सरकारी नीतियों/ प्रयासों के क्रियान्वयन में कमी ()

आवश्यक जानकारी का अभाव ()

संस्थागत कर्ज लेने की सुविधा का अभाव ()

Q.8.0 आपके अनुसार स्थानीय पारिस्थितिकी संघटितियाँ जैसे पानी के स्रोत- तालाब, झरने, सामुदायिक

वन का परिचालन, संरक्षण, संवर्धन अधिक कुशलतापूर्वक होता था है जब उनका स्वामित्व एवं

संचालन होता है -

सरकार के पास () ग्राम पंचायत के पास () स्थानीय लोगों / समुदाय के पास ()

Q.9.0 पुराने लोगों या समुदाय के पास जो परंपरागत ज्ञान तथा अपने व्यवसायिक कार्यों को करने के

पारंपरिक तरीके थे जैसे बाढ़ के समय नाव बनाना आयुर्वेदिक ज्ञान, सूखे के समय जल का संचयन

आदि करना, वे प्राकृतिक आपदाओं में लोगों को बचाने एवं क्षमता निर्माण के लिए बहुत आवश्यक है-

पूरी तरह सहमत है (), थोड़ा बहुत सहमत है (), असहमत है (), कुछ कह नहीं सकते ()

Q.10 यदि आपकी आर्थिक गतिविधि या व्यवसाय (कृषि पशुपालन, उद्योग) या जीवन स्तर पर्यावरण को हानि पहुंचा रहे है, तब आप अपने व्यावसायिक तरीकों/क्रियाकलापों/जीवन स्तर को पर्यावरण अनुकूल बनाना चाहेंगे-

हाँ (), नहीं ()

यदि हाँ

हाँ, लेकिन यह नहीं जानते कि क्या करना है ()

हाँ, लेकिन वो लागत प्रभावी (किफ़ायती) हों (),

हाँ, यदि वो महंगा भी हो ()।

क्या आप कुछ और कहना चाहेंगे --

धन्यवाद आपके सहयोग और महत्वपूर्ण जानकारी देने के लिए ।